

This study addresses the need for improved risk assessment during explosive ordnance disposal (EOD) at sea by highlighting the environmental and operational complexities of handling unexploded ordnance (UXO) in the marine environment. It discusses the increasing demand for offshore EOD due to the construction of offshore wind parks and initiatives proactively addressing UXO dump sites. In an effort to understand the RA tools that are available to EOD experts, this work reviews ten RA methods and identifies a methodological gap, thereby revealing the need for a new EOD RA method. Consequently, it introduces a novel method named the Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded underwater Military Munitions (RUMMs). This model, which can be used during early EOD planning states or immediately before UXO handling, calculates the probability of an undesired detonation, the consequence of an undesired detonation, and the complexity of the EOD operation. Its consistent and reproducible results, unaffected by fatigue or time pressure, add a new layer of reliability to EOD decision-making.

FREY — A NEW RISK ASSESSMENT MODEL FOR UNEXPLODED UNDERWATER MILITARY MUNITIONS

A NEW RISK ASSESSMENT MODEL FOR UNEXPLODED UNDERWATER MILITARY MUNITIONS

Torsten Frey

UNIVERSITÄT
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Torsten Frey (M.A.)

born on 6 March 1989, in Nordhausen

Reviewers:

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Robert Holländer, Prof. Dr. Jens Greinert

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Abstract

This work focuses on risk assessment (RA) during the execution of explosive ordnance disposal (EOD) at sea. Its purpose is to improve decision-making during the management of unexploded ordnance (UXO) in marine environments. To this end, it identifies the existing methodological gap and closes it by developing, presenting, testing, and applying a novel method for EOD RA.

For a focused and meaningful investigation of EOD risk, it is first necessary to define the scope of this study. It is limited to UXO that was submerged in the years from 1914 to 1949. Objects from this period constitute the vast majority of UXO in Germany. UXO that is contained in wrecks or that is filled with chemical warfare agents is not discussed. Both of these matters would add more layers of complexity to an already complicated subject matter. The study focuses on German waters, including its inland waters, territorial sea, and exclusive economic zone. This decision mainly impacts the environmental conditions that must be considered to perform RA during an EOD operation.

UXO can be characterised by a number of properties, many of which determine how hazardous their presence is and how challenging their handling during EOD will be. These properties include the individual object's mass, dimensions, casing material and thickness, the time it has been submerged, the type and condition of its fuse (if present), as well as the mass and type of the explosive material it contains. This explosive content is characterised by its impact sensitivity and relative effectiveness. In addition, numerous environmental factors must be considered. The most relevant ones that are implemented into the EOD RA model are the sedimentation rate (which is mainly responsible for object burial), corrosion rate, current velocity, water depth, wave height, and visibility under water. Considering all this, the complexity of handling UXO in the marine environment becomes evident.

UXO detonations can lead to dire consequences in the case of accidents. In addition, the leakage of hazardous carcinogenic explosive substances contaminates the marine environment. Given the negative effects of the presence of UXO, it is undeniable that, under certain circumstances, EOD is an essential activity. In Germany, these circumstances are mainly twofold. Firstly, the vast and rapid construction of offshore wind parks will be a critical driver for EOD in the upcoming years. Secondly, a recent initiative to execute an immediate action programme to deal with UXO dump sites in the German Baltic Sea demonstrates the political will to approach the issue on a greater scale. With these developments in mind, it can be predicted that more offshore EOD work than ever before

will take place in the upcoming years. Handling more UXO increases the chance of accidents and the occurrence of negative effects. Conducting EOD work professionally and diligently is of paramount importance.

Next to studying UXO, it is also vital to understand the means and methods for managing them. To account for the complexity of the task, the EOD industry and its stakeholders have developed numerous frameworks and guidelines. This study introduces and investigates six EOD frameworks and selects the most comprehensive one as a frame of reference for the way forward. In this instance, it also identifies three key processes during which the handling of UXO takes place. Hence, they constitute the riskiest part of any EOD campaign. These key processes are *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*.

The goal of this study is to better understand the risk to which the EOD personnel and their equipment are exposed. The existing literature offers a number of RA methods that deal with UXO or EOD in the marine environment. Ten of them were reviewed here. To find out whether these RA methods are relevant for the scope of this study, a categorisation tool is introduced. It classifies each method by using the following five categories: study type (qualitative vs. quantitative), level of decision-making (strategic vs. applied), risk assessment component (probability vs. consequence), spatial scale (large vs. small), and temporal scale (long-term vs. short-term). With this tool, it is possible to identify the requirements for the EOD RA method and determine that it should be rather quantitative, applied, rather probability-focused, and operate on small local and short-term temporal scales. Neither of the pre-existing RA methods fulfils these requirements of an EOD RA. They hardly address the work during which the actual handling of UXO takes place. They rather address and manage UXO risk in the larger context of an offshore development project. This is remarkable when considering that the handling and removal of UXO is the ultimate goal and the most crucial part of any EOD activity. These gaps indicate the need for a new EOD RA method. Accordingly, the development and demonstration of such a method are the main missions of this study.

The principle achievement of this work is the design of the Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded underwater Military Munitions (RUMMs). This was accomplished via an extensive and iterative literature review and a series of expert workshops. RUMMs is an RA model that is based on a directed graph. It expresses how the properties (called factors) of the UXO object, the environment, and the EOD procedure affect the risk during the EOD operation. The model's scope is the risk of an undesired detonation (the undesired event) for the personnel and equipment at the EOD site (the risk receptor). Taking the current state of knowledge and expert opinions into account was a key principle during the development process of RUMMs. To account for different RA requirements at different stages of the EOD procedure, two modal layouts were established—the planning layout and the confirmed layout. The former relies heavily on existing environmental data and therefore allows performing RA well in advance of the execution of *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, or *recovery*. On the downside, its results are inherently more uncertain than those of the confirmed layout. The latter was designed to allow RA immediately before

the key processes take place. This means that input data will be more reliable, but also that greater effort is required to obtain them. The planning layout consists of 34 factors, and the confirmed layout consists of 23 factors. The study describes each individual model factor and how RUMMs uses it to calculate the three model outputs *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. To transform the tangible model factors into the abstract model outputs, RUMMs uses normalisation and weighting. Expert workshops were conducted to define how to implement these operations into the model.

Before a model as complex as RUMMs can be brought to application, it is first necessary to explore it. Two methodologies for exploration are used. The local sensitivity analysis is an approach that helps understand how strongly the model outputs react to changes in model inputs. The planning layout is very responsive to the factors impact sensitivity of the explosive material, casing thickness, time sunk, and water depth. The response of the confirmed layout is strongest for changes in the condition of the casing, the fuse corrosion state, other fuse properties, and again, the impact sensitivity. For RUMMs users, this means two things: Firstly, they should be particularly alert if the values of these factors change. Secondly, these are the factors for which input data quality and reliability should be highest. The other exploratory method, the Monte Carlo simulation, is used to determine the model outputs' distribution functions over a total of 9000 model runs for two input distribution types and both model layouts. The distributions of the model outputs allow understanding how a given UXO object and EOD operation compare to the population of all model runs and, thus, which output values must be considered low, medium, or high risk.

Finally, RUMMs is applied to 20 UXO objects and their EOD operations. This exercise reveals how challenging the identification of UXO objects and the research in historic documents are. At times, the consulted references contradict each other or information is missing. Hence, often, conservative assessments or best estimates have to be applied. Nevertheless, the application of RUMMs demonstrates that the model works as intended. Given thorough and diligent research of the model's input data, it reliably calculates plausible values for the three model outputs. Particularly, the application of the confirmed layout demonstrates that the outputs of RUMMs' match with the decisions of a professional EOD company. This is proof of the reliability of the RA that is performed by the model. After the successful application of RUMMs, it can be stated that it fulfils the requirements of an EOD RA method.

Offshore EOD has been an ongoing activity and will continue to do so. EOD experts are highly skilled professionals. Some have decades of experience and have handled hundreds of UXO objects. However, for a high-risk activity, an over-reliance on routine may lead to accidents. Every single object must be thoroughly assessed before a decision on the next steps can be taken. RUMMs is not affected by fatigue, repetitiveness, lack of focus, or personal mood. For a given set of input values, it will always produce the same output values. Its results are reproducible and can be reviewed in post to learn from past EOD actions. RUMMs cannot take a decision and relieve experts from their responsibility.

Instead, structured RA with RUMMs adds a solid additional layer of reliability to every expert's personal assessment and can therefore significantly improve EOD decision-making. It is suggested that the next step be a real-world application, either in preparation of an EOD campaign or during its execution.

Graphical abstract.

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Acronyms, Abbreviations and Initialisms

AB 500	Abwurfbehälter (container)
AHP	analytic hierarchy process
ALARP	As Low As Reasonably Practicable
AUV	autonomous underwater vehicle
AXO	abandoned explosive ordnance
BASTA	‘ <u>B</u> oost <u>A</u> ppplied munition detection through <u>S</u> mart data <u>i</u> n <u>T</u> egration and <u>A</u> I workflows’
Bdz.	Bodenzünder (ground fuse)
BFR KMR	Baufachliche Richtlinien Kampfmittelräumung
BGS	British Geological Survey
BMA	Bombenmine (bomb mine) A
BSH	Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
CONMAR	‘ <u>C</u> ONcepts for conventional <u>M</u> ARine Munition Remediation in the German North and Baltic Sea’
CWA	chemical warfare agent
DAIMON	‘ <u>D</u> ecision <u>A</u> id for Marine <u>M</u> unition <u>O</u> Ns’
DDT	deflagration to detonation transition
DGUV	Deutsche Gesetzliche Unfallversicherung
DMM	discarded military munitions
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
EED	estimated exposure dose
EEZ	exclusive economic zone
EMC	Einheitsmine (standardised mine) C
EOD	explosive ordnance disposal
EPS	European Protected Species
ERA	ecological risk assessment
ERW	explosive remnants of war
EU	European Union

FINO	Forschungsplattformen in Nord- und Ostsee
Fp.	Füllpulver (filling powder)
FRATSAD	First Risk Assessment Tool for Subaquatic Ammunition Dumpsites
GDR	German Democratic Republic
GEOMAR	GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
GICHD	Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining
GP	general purpose
HMX	High-Molecular-weight rdX
HRA	human health risk assessment
IOW	Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (German: Leibniz-Institut für Ostseeforschung Warnemünde)
LCA	life cycle assessment
LLUR	Landesamt für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und ländliche Räume
LoU	limitation of use
MBES	multi-beam echosounder
MCS	Monte Carlo simulation
Mk V	Mark V
MOE	margin of exposure
MUDAB	Meeresumweltdatenbank
NEQ	net explosive quantity
OAT	one-factor-at-a-time
PC 1,400	Panzerbombe, Cylindrisch, 1400 kg (cylindrical armour piercing bomb)
PDF	probability density function
PETN	pentaerythritol tetranitrate
ProBaNNt	' <u>P</u> rofessional intelligent munitions assessment using 3D reconstructions and <u>B</u> ayesian <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etworks'
RA	risk assessment
RC	review criterion
RDX	research department explosive/royal demolition explosive
RE	relative effectiveness

RoBEMM	‘Robotic underwater salvage and disposal process including technology for dismantling ammunition in the sea’ (German: ‘ <u>R</u> obotisches <u>U</u> nterwasser- <u>B</u> ergungs- und <u>E</u> ntsorgungsverfahren inklusive Technik zur Delaborierung von <u>M</u> unition im <u>M</u> eer’)
ROV	remotely operated underwater vehicle
RUMMs	<u>R</u> isk Assessment Model for <u>U</u> nexploded underwater <u>M</u> ilitary <u>M</u> unitions
SAR	sediment accumulation rate
SPRC	source-pathway-receptor-consequence
SprengG	Sprengstoffgesetz
SprengV	Verordnung zum Sprengstoffgesetz
SSS	side-scan sonar
TMC	Torpedomine (torpedo mine) C
TNT	2,4,6-trinitrotoluene
UE	undesired event
UK	United Kingdom
UM	unit of measure
UMA	U-Bootmine (submarine mine) A
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
US	United States
UXO	unexploded ordnance
Wgr. Zdr.	Wurfgranatenzünder (mortar fuse)
WROV	Work-Class ROV
WWI	World War I
WWII	World War II

List of Symbols

This list contains the symbols that are used in this dissertation. Those that are capitalised throughout their description are RUMMs model factors.

B	Burial State
C	Consequence of an Undesired Detonation
CC	Condition of Casing
CM	Casing Material
CR	Corrosion Rate
CR_b	Corrosion Rate – Buried
CR_u	Corrosion Rate – Unburied
CT	Original Casing Thickness
Δ	Change of the output value during the sensitivity analysis
D	Water Depth
d	Great-circle distance between to points on a sphere
E	Complexity of the EOD Operation
$f(A)$	Actual frequency
$f(E)$	Expected frequency
FC	Fuse Corrosion Sate
F^C	A factor's version in the planning layout
F^l	A factor's limitation of use
F^{max}	Upper value range boundary of a factor
F^{min}	Upper value range boundary of a factor
F^n	Normalized factor
F_1^n	Normalized factor (positive linear)
F_{-1}^n	Normalized factor (negative linear)
F_2^n	Normalized factor (positive exponential)
F_{-2}^n	Normalized factor (negative exponential)
F_3^n	Normalized factor (positive root)
F_{-3}^n	Normalized factor (negative root)
F_4^n	Normalized factor (positive incremental)
F_{-4}^n	Normalized factor (negative incremental)

F^{nC}	Normalized factor contributing to the <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>
F^{nE}	Normalized factor contributing to the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>
F^{nP}	Normalized factor contributing to the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>
FP	Fuse Properties
F^P	A factor's version in the planning layout
fp_1	Fuse property 1 - Fuse Present
fp_2	Fuse property 2 - Fuse Armed
fp_3	Fuse property 3 - Fuse without Battery
fp_4	Fuse property 4 - Electrolyte in Vial
fp_5	Fuse property 5 - Spring Loaded/Cocked Striker, Diaphragm
fp_6	Fuse property 6 - Chemical Long Delay Fuse
fp_7	Fuse property 7 - More than one Fuse
fp_8	Fuse property 8 - More than one Fuse Type
fp_n	One of the eight Fuse Properties
FT	Fuse Type
F^w	Weighted factor
F^{wC}	Weighted factor contributing to the <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>
F^{wE}	Weighted factor contributing to the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>
F^{wP}	Weighted factor contributing to the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>
$H_{1/3}$	Significant Wave Height
$H_{1/10}$	significant wave height (median of highest tenth)
H_{m0}	significant wave height (estimate from wave spectrum)
I	Impact Sensitivity
i	Input variable of the sensitivity analysis
I_b	Impact Sensitivity Base Value
I_c	Current Impact Sensitivity
IC_c	Current Impact Sensitivity Classification
I_o	Original Impact Sensitivity
λ	Lambda, which is required to test for correlation of logarithmic functions
λ_{EOD}	Longitude (of the EOD location)
λ_F	Longitude of a factor value in the haversine formula
l_l	UXO Longest Dimension
l_s	UXO Shortest Dimension
M	Main Charge Type
m_c	Charge Mass
m_u	UXO Mass
n	sample size (not to be confused with n and n)

O	Model Output
o	Output variable of the sensitivity analysis
ϕ_{EOD}	Latitude (of the EOD location)
ϕ_F	Latitude of a factor value in the haversine formula
P	Probability of an Undesired Detonation
PD	Planned EOD Date
$P(E)$	Expected probability
$Q1$	First quartile
$Q2$	Second quartile
$Q3$	Third quartile
$Q4$	Fourth quartile
Q_n	n %-quantile
R	Visual Range Under Water
r	Radius of a sphere
RE	Relative Effectiveness
S	Sediment Type
s	Sample standard deviation
SAR	Sediment Accumulation Rate
SC	Sensitivity coefficient
SF	Shock Factor
SR	Slant range between a detonation and a risk receptor
θ	Depression angle between the horizontal plane at the location of a risk receptor and the direction of SR
T	Year Sunk
t_b	Time Buried
t_s	Time Sunk
t_u	Time Unburied
U	UXO Type
u	east-west vector of currents
v	north-south vector of currents
v_c	Current Velocity
v_w	Wind Speed
W	Weight
$X_{(1)}$	Sample minimum

$X_{(n)}$	Sample maximum
\bar{x}	Sample mean
\tilde{x}	Median
z	Z-score of a confidence interval

List of Units

a	year
ft	foot
kn	knot
lbs	pound
M	nautical mile
ML	Richter local magnitude
N	newton
psu	practical salinity unit
UM	unit of measure

Chapter 1

Introduction

When media and publications address the issue of unexploded ordnance (UXO) in German waters, they commonly mention one number: 1 600 000 t. Upon entering the German translation (“1,6 Millionen Tonnen”) into web search engines, offshore UXO appears among the top search results, even though no context for the number is given in the search term. This is the result of a remarkable effort by representatives of authorities and researchers to bring this matter to the attention of the public and politicians and to develop solutions for its management. It appears that a number of 1 500 000 t was first published in a report in 1990 [1 in 2]. The larger number of 1 600 000 t then appeared in a keystone report on UXO in the German Sea, which collected a vast amount of relevant information that was available at the time of its publication in 2011 [3]. Unfortunately, the former reference has been lost, and the latter one does not provide an explanation of how the research led to this number.

Despite the lack of a precise number, there is a general consensus that the amount of UXO in German waters continues to be a concern for the maritime economy and marine ecosystems. For more than a decade, it has been demanded to address this issue on a national level [e.g., 4]. The preparation of this dissertation was accompanied by a gradual paradigm shift that responds to these calls for a greater solution. This study is a result of these recent developments and can hopefully be a contribution to a future without UXO in the German Seas. Even though the issue of UXO is very complex, a wealthy industrial nation like Germany can solve it with existing technologies if sufficient effort and resources are dedicated to it.

1.1 Offshore UXO in a Multi-Use and Multiple Stressor Environment

In 2030, the global ocean economy’s gross world product is predicted to more than double compared to 2010. By the same year, over 40 million people are projected to be employed by the maritime industry. [5] Operational expenditure in the sector will likely increase by almost one-fifth between 2018 and 2050. With a contribution of roughly 50 % the offshore wind industry will be the main driver of investment in the years to come.

The spatial requirements of the blue economy will be roughly sevenfold (50 000 km² in 2018 vs. 350 000 km² in 2050), and wind farms will take up the greatest part of this space. [6] The European Union (EU) recognised this development and prepared a ‘Blue Growth Strategy’ to collect the anticipated economic benefits [7]. Germany acted similarly by establishing an economic ‘Maritime Agenda’ [8]. Due to this development, marine space, especially in coastal areas, is predicted to become an increasingly limited resource that will be frequented by multiple actors and industries simultaneously. At the same time, technical developments allow for the exploitation of marine resources and space in an unprecedented manner. However, gaining safe access to them requires facing the multifaceted challenge of UXO in the sea, as it presents an obstacle to the desired blue growth.

UXO causes two types of environmental problems. First, many explosive materials are carcinogenic and genotoxic [9]. Second, detonations underwater can cause serious harm to marine faunae, especially cetaceans [10]. However, these UXO-related issues do not exist in isolation. Globally, the oceans and seas are affected by multiple anthropogenic stressors simultaneously. These include (but are not limited to) warming of the oceans, nutrient pollution, ocean acidification, freshwater influxes through ice melting, the accumulation of atmospheric pollutants, commercial fishing, and acoustic energy input [11, 12]. Coastal ecosystems in industrialised European waters are strongly affected and remain in a dire state. In 2015, a report by the European Environment Agency indicated that not even one of sixteen marine ecosystem types and pressures showed a good or improving status [13]. The prospect of removing one of the many stressors without having to limit any actor’s access to marine resources is very attractive. Calls to remove UXO from the sea have been accompanying research on the matter for years. A new immediate action programme in Germany [14] appears to be the first serious attempt at responding to these demands.

The EU wishes to organise the efficient, safe, and sustainable use of its seas. A framework for maritime spatial planning was established to take advantage of the economic potential of the European Seas and protect the environment at the same time. [15] The presence of UXO impedes both the ambitions to make use of the sea’s economic potential as well as the aim of doing so in a sustainable and ecosystem-friendly way. Understanding the challenges that are related to explosive ordnance disposal (EOD) and developing new tools to solve them are therefore desirable research goals. This dissertation is a contribution to the greater effort of reaching them.

1.2 Focus, Scope, and Purpose of this Dissertation

Research related to offshore UXO has intensified over the years. Figure 1.1 presents the number of publications that appear as search results when entering “Offshore UXO” as a term into Google Scholar for the years from 2008 until 2022. The graph shows a fairly linear increase in research output for the period. While this is not a comprehensive investigation of the history of offshore UXO research, it indicates a growing interest in the issue.

FIGURE 1.1: Results for the term “Offshore UXO” in the search engine Google Scholar for the years 2008 to 2022.

Research on offshore UXO is being performed in many different fields of science, ranging from historical reviews of entry paths of UXO into the sea [e.g., 16] to chemical measurements of explosive compounds in water, sediment, and biota [e.g., 17]. Some of the papers report on biological and toxicological effect studies of explosive compounds in faunae [e.g., 18]. Others address physical experiments, e.g., the migration of UXO objects [e.g., 19] or the effects of detonations on vessels or marine mammals [e.g., 20]. All of these publications are extremely valuable in describing the problem of offshore UXO and creating awareness. Accordingly, many of these studies are consulted throughout this dissertation. The results presented here would not have been possible without them. These studies often recommend that clearance begin sooner rather than later. They can be used to inform high-level management decisions, such as the establishment of a monitoring scheme or to prioritise contamination hot spots. Yet, only rarely do they improve the EOD procedure. To solve the problem of offshore UXO, other types of research must be consulted.

Some studies that address the management of UXO in general and EOD in particular focus on technical or organisational ways to improve specific tools and processes. This concerns aspects such as the monitoring of contamination hotspots [e.g., 21] or the provision of decision support systems to determine how to deal with offshore UXO on a strategic level [e.g., 22]. However, EOD requires great attention to detail. It is a procedure that is executed when a very specific point or limited area should be cleared of UXO. It consists of a preliminary survey, including a site-specific historical site assessment, a technical survey of an area, an investigation of target points, and ultimately the clearance and removal of UXO [23]. Academic literature strongly focuses on the technical survey and investigation phases of EOD [e.g., 24]. Ways to improve the capacity to find objects, discriminate between UXO and other objects, and identify UXO types and conditions are often addressed in articles and reports. Only a few publications discuss what to do with the UXO afterwards. An important reason for this imbalance may lie in the fact that searching for and investigating objects is a capability that many scientific organisations have. The handling of explosive materials, on the other hand, is a skill that is far less common.

As EOD is an ongoing activity, method statements and other grey literature are valuable resources to understand the state of technology and methodology. While descriptions of site-specific historic surveys are more commonplace than in the academic world, focus is again placed on technical survey approaches. This is reflected in EOD guidelines, which heavily deal with finding UXO and less with handling it. During a survey, terabytes of data are collected and analysed with elaborate and sophisticated technologies and approaches [25]. For the handling of objects (once they are found), such data-driven efforts are unheard of. In summary, clearance and disposal are to a much lesser degree represented and discussed at conferences, in articles, guidelines, and grey literature. This dissertation faces this shortcoming by focusing heavily on the final phase of EOD. Its purpose is to contribute to the closing of this research gap. While not all experts may agree with each of the author’s observations, interpretations, and decisions, the work can hopefully lead to a better understanding of the challenges during UXO clearance and provide support during EOD decision-making.

This study cannot fully close the mentioned research gap but must focus on very specific aspects. It proposes a new tool that supports experts who are responsible for UXO handling. The method that is developed here is a quantitative and probabilistic risk assessment (RA) approach that focuses on applied decision-making on a small spatial and short-term temporal scale. The three processes for which risk is assessed are *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. The method was designed to assess the risk of an ‘undesired detonation’ that the ‘personnel and equipment at the EOD site’ are exposed to during these three processes. The dissertation focuses on UXO, which was submerged in German waters from 1914 until 1949. Detailed rationales for all this scoping are provided in the upcoming chapters.

The RA tool that is developed and presented here does not propose a decision for the EOD process. Instead, its outputs are three indicative values for the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. The dissertation offers insights into the interpretation of these outputs. They were designed in such a way that the decision on how to perform EOD remains with the responsible expert on site. The RA method can inform this decision, and model outputs can be used to verify a decision or raise a red flag. A mathematical model cannot replace an expert with years of experience who has an in situ impression of the UXO object that shall be handled and the environmental conditions. However, it can assist the expert since its results will be reproducible and independent of fatigue, repetitiveness, lack of focus, and personal mood. This is, in a nutshell, why this dissertation proposes a novel method for EOD RA.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

To explore the aspects that were introduced in the previous section in a scientific manner, it is necessary to formulate and test a relevant main research hypothesis (H_M). Offshore EOD takes place in Germany and around the world on a regular basis. The

hypothesis claims that it is beneficial to develop and use a structured RA method to support EOD decision-making. Benefits could, e.g., lie in the inclusion of information that is currently not usually considered or in improving the traceability and reproducibility of the process leading up to a decision. Confirming H_M , therefore, requires an informed and intelligent methodological design that is based on the current state of knowledge on UXO and EOD and fits the scope that was presented in 1.2. It also means that the new method must be tested for real-world scenarios.

H_M : Structured RA improves the decision-making of specialists during EOD.

H_M implies and presupposes several conditions that must be tested through three minor research hypotheses (H_i , H_{ii} , and H_{iii}). The first is that UXO cannot be handled by non-skilled workers and that even trained professionals require a dedicated workflow to perform EOD. While this statement may be intuitive, it should be substantiated by a review that proves the complexity and hazards of UXO. After all, the same objects were used as explosive ordnance by millions of soldiers, many of whom only received a few weeks or even days of training. It is necessary to understand why objects that were once used by the millions can only be handled by specialised experts today. H_i addresses this question.

H_i : UXO requires handling by specialists who execute a professional EOD workflow.

If H_i can be proven, the next aspect that has to be examined is whether performing structured RA is necessary to understand the risk that EOD personnel and their equipment are exposed to. Accidents during EOD are rare, so it could be assumed that current practices are sufficient to deal with offshore UXO until all of it has been removed. However, if the number of EOD decisions were to rapidly increase, if new challenges were to arise, or if fewer personnel were available, this assumption could become obsolete. In any case, to warrant the effort of performing structured RA during EOD, it is necessary to prove H_{ii} .

H_{ii} : EOD requires structured RA to understand the risk to which EOD personnel and their equipment are subjected.

In case H_{ii} turns out to be true, it is still necessary to examine whether existing approaches are suitable to assess EOD risk. This means that relevant methods must first be identified and then reviewed for their potential to aid decision-making during EOD. If they are not sufficient to understand the risk that is associated with handling offshore UXO, a new EOD RA method is required. H_{iii} is stated to investigate this aspect.

H_{iii} : Existing methods are insufficient to assess EOD risk.

Once H_i , H_{ii} , and H_{iii} have been tested and accepted individually, it is possible to answer H_M . This dissertation is organised in such a manner that these hypotheses are investigated one by one. The following section provides an overview of the structure of this study.

1.4 Structure of the Dissertation

To introduce the reader to the issue of offshore UXO and to address H_i , Chapter 2 contains a great deal of background knowledge on the matter. On the one hand, the purpose of all this information is to provide context and review the existing literature. While not every single source that discusses offshore UXO could be read for this dissertation, the field is sufficiently niche that a great portion of the available articles and grey literature could be reviewed. On the other hand, the chapter uses the collected information to define the scope of the dissertation (see 1.2). This concerns the historical, geographic, and legal context. Subsequently, the chapter informs the reader about numerous UXO properties and how they contribute to the challenges and risk during EOD operations. These properties will be picked up as risk factors at a later stage to develop the titular RA method.

Chapter 3 discusses the practice of managing UXO in German waters by means of EOD. The chapter compares six EOD frameworks that describe how the treatment of UXO should be conducted and selects the most suitable one as a frame of reference for this study. Next, it presents the selected framework in detail. The activities *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery* are identified as the key processes during which the actual handling of UXO takes place, which adds further scope to this study. Subsequently, Chapter 3 describes technical methods for EOD operations and how decision-making with regard to the three key processes is currently done without a structured RA approach. All of this information is used to test H_{ii} . The chapter also includes a description of environmental properties that affect UXO objects or EOD operations and demonstrates how they add even more complexity to the matter. Again, these properties will be used for the RA.

Before the method can be developed, Chapter 4 deals with H_{iii} by reviewing existing RA methods that address offshore UXO. For this purpose, it provides some general conceptual background on the academic discourse on risk and the assessment thereof. Next, the chapter presents a novel framework for the review of RA methods. The framework is also used to determine the requirements of an EOD RA method. Existing approaches are tested against these requirements. The review allows for the precise identification of the methodological gap that existed before this study.

Chapter 5 is the central chapter of this dissertation. Based on the information that is provided in the three preceding chapters, it develops an RA model, which is called Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded underwater Military Munitions (RUMMs). Its purpose is to improve decision-making during EOD. The chapter describes the literature research and expert involvement process that was executed to design two different versions of RUMMs: a planning and a confirmed layout. The former relies heavily on predictions (which introduces some uncertainties) but allows for RA at an early stage in the EOD procedure. The latter is more precise but requires more on-site data. Thus, it can only be used immediately before UXO handling takes place. Chapter 5 also defines two very important aspects of the RA—the risk receptor and the undesired event (UE) that should be investigated. The risk receptor is the ‘personnel and equipment at the EOD site’. The UE is the ‘undesired detonation’. Next, the chapter provides information

on a total of 34 risk factors, each of which contributes to the EOD risk. The factors are introduced in isolation and in connection with other factors that affect them or that they have an impact on. Through a process of normalisation and weighting, these factors are then converged to three model outputs: *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. For the reader's information, some omitted risk factors as well as model limitations are stressed as well.

RUMMs is a very complex model, which is why Chapter 6 explores the model before applying it to test H_M . First, a sensitivity analysis is executed. The purpose of this analysis is to test how strongly changes in the input data influence the model output values. Next, six thousand model runs are executed during an Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) by applying different input data distributions to understand the distribution of model output values. The findings from these analyses allow for interpreting the results of the model application. Chapter 6 assesses ten EOD operations each for the planning and confirmed layouts each. Planning model inputs are based on UXO objects that were detected by the GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel (GEOMAR) during research cruises. Confirmed model inputs are based on EOD operations that were performed by the EOD company SeaTerra in the past. Finally, the chapter tests whether the methodological gaps that were introduced in Chapter 4 have been closed.

Chapter 7 concludes this study. First, it revisits the research hypotheses. Afterwards, it proposes ways to improve RUMMs and options for how to tailor it for use in other fields of application. In its final section, the chapter provides an outlook on the future of EOD and the role that RUMMs may play in it.

Chapter 2

The Issue of Offshore Unexploded Ordnance

The title of this chapter suggests that UXO is an issue, i.e., a problem. This claim is quite intuitive; after all, this dissertation addresses weapons that were meant to cause serious damage during the most violent and catastrophic military conflicts in human history. Nevertheless, it is necessary to substantiate this notion. Thus, this chapter provides background information on UXO in the sea and introduces some of its properties and potential effects. In short, it establishes why UXO needs to be dealt with.

2.1 Background and Context

UXO is a multifaceted issue that many scientists from many different disciplines are researching. Among them are historians, hydrographers, geophysicists, and legal scholars. These fields provide the knowledge that is necessary to manage the issue of offshore UXO. To provide the reader with some background knowledge, this section reviews this work. It begins with an investigation into the term ‘UXO’. Next, it describes the historical, geographic, and legal context of the offshore UXO issue. Following each of these descriptions, it offers some conclusions that are relevant for the further course of this study.

2.1.1 Terminology

The literature contains a variety of terms to label what can generally be described as legacy or leftover weapons and munitions that are not safely stored but are present at an undesired location. These terms have been defined in different ways by different institutions, partially leading to slightly contradictory meanings. This subsection quotes some of these definitions and evaluates their usefulness within the scope of this dissertation. It is limited to definitions that apply globally or to Germany. As there are no European normative or guiding documents on the matter (see 2.1.4), the European level is not represented here. The aim of this subsection is the development of definitions that fit the scope of this dissertation.

The *Protocol on Explosive Remnants of War* is an international treaty that defines the term ‘explosive ordnance’ as “conventional munitions containing explosives, with the exception of mines, booby traps and other devices.” [26] Since this is Protocol V to the *Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons* the definition focuses on conventional explosive weapons and omits nuclear, biological, and chemical arms. It continues with the definition of ‘UXO’ as “explosive ordnance that has been primed, fused, armed, or otherwise prepared for use and used in an armed conflict. It may have been fired, dropped, launched or projected and should have detonated but failed to do so.” [26] It furthermore defines ‘abandoned explosive ordnance (AXO)’ as “explosive ordnance that was not used during an armed conflict, that has been left behind or dumped by a party to an armed conflict, and which is no longer under control of the party that left it behind or dumped it. Abandoned explosive ordnance may or may not have been primed, fused, armed or otherwise prepared for use.” [26] These definitions include most of the relevant entry paths for munitions in the sea (see 2.1.2). However, the UXO definition fails to consider live ammunition that has been used during military exercises and manoeuvres and was therefore not used in armed conflict. Similarly, the AXO definition does not recognise that the majority of dumping within the study area took place not during but after the conclusion of World War II (WWII) (see 2.1.2). This means that not all dumping was conducted by actors that can be labelled as parties to an armed conflict. These definitions are therefore inapplicable to the case examined here and are rejected. Hence, the definition of ‘explosive remnants of war (ERW)’ as “unexploded ordnance and abandoned explosive ordnance” must also be rejected. [26]

Three years before the publication of Protocol V, the non-profit organisation Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining (GICHD) published its own set of definitions. GICHD is mandated to be the Secretariat of the *International Mine Action Standards* by the United Nations (UN) [27]. It is apparent that the Protocol V definitions that were reviewed in the previous paragraph were derived from the GICHD document. According to GICHD, ‘explosive ordnance’ is “all munitions containing explosives, nuclear fission or fusion materials and biological and chemical agents” [28]. The second sentence specifically lists types of explosive ordnance and includes “all mines” [28]. The weakness of this definition is that it is too inclusive, with all sorts of non-explosive substances mentioned. It is thus rejected. ‘UXO’ is defined as “explosive ordnance that has been primed, fused, armed or otherwise prepared for use or used. It may have been fired, dropped, launched or projected yet remains unexploded either through malfunction or design or for any other reason” [28]. This definition does not specify the use of explosive ordnance in armed conflict, thereby including UXO from military exercises and manoeuvres. However, neither this nor any other definition provided by GICHD includes the entry path of dumping or otherwise leaving behind explosive ordnance. It is therefore rejected for further use here. In the more recent GICHD document *A Guide to Mine Action*, the definitions of AXO and ERW from Protocol V were adopted [29].

The ‘Explosives Act’ (*Sprengstoffgesetz (SprengG)*) is the legal basis for handling explosive substances and blasting accessories in Germany. This law defines munitions as “projectiles, propelling charges, practice munition for small arms, other firearms, artillery, and other technical equipment” [30]. Furthermore, the term ‘discovered munition’ is introduced. It is defined as “munitions or explosive military weapons that were not uninterruptedly stored, monitored, or administered.” [30] These definitions are rejected since they implicitly include potentially inert (i.e., non-explosive) practise munitions. Section 2.1.4 discusses the law in greater detail.

During EOD on real estate owned by the German state, it is mandatory to follow the *Baufachliche Richtlinien Kampfmittelräumung (BFR KMR)*, ‘Technical Construction Guidelines for Explosive Ordnance Disposal’. They are commonly used for EOD in Germany in general. Since the document is only available in German, the following definitions are translations by the author. ‘Ordnance’ is defined as “objects without ownership that are of military origin, that are intended for warfare, and that contain explosives, chemical warfare agents, smoke-producing substances, incendiary substances, irritants or residues of these substances, or that are military weapons or parts of these weapons.” [31] Again, this definition is rejected since it includes non-explosive ordnance and even weapons that are not munitions. The document’s definition of ‘UXO’ is the same as the one provided by the GICHD, and the definition of ‘discovered munitions’ is the same as the one provided in *SprengG* [31]. Both were already rejected above.

Deutsche Gesetzliche Unfallversicherung (DGUV) is the German Statutory Accident Insurance Associations’ umbrella organisation. Numerous documents it has published are relevant to EOD. However, only one document contains definitions for ‘munition and munition parts’ and for ‘discovered munition’. It is the *DGUV Regel 113-003 - Regeln für Sicherheit und Gesundheitsschutz beim Zerlegen von Gegenständen mit Explosivstoff oder beim Vernichten von Explosivstoff oder Gegenständen mit Explosivstoff*, which translates to ‘Rules for Safety and Health during Disassembly of Objects with Explosive Substances or Disposal of Explosive Substances or Objects with Explosive Substances’. According to the document, ‘munition and munition parts’ are “objects with explosives, such as shells, cartridges, warheads, hand grenades, mines, bombs, torpedoes as well as rockets for military use, including propelling charges and pyrotechnical munition. Munition may also contain incendiary substances, smoke-producing substances, irritants, or chemical warfare agents.” [32] Like many other definitions, it is too inclusive for this study. Especially the second sentence mainly covers substances that are out of scope. The definition of ‘discovered munition’ is essentially the same as the one in *SprengG*, except for not mentioning explosive military weapons [32]. It is rejected for the same reason as above.

In the *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* UXO is defined as “Objects or parts of objects of military origin without ownership, intended for warfare, that contain explosives or residues of these substances.” [23] While it is not very specific, this definition can be accepted, as it does not include any aspects that are out of the scope of this dissertation, nor does it exclude relevant types of munitions or entry paths. The quality guideline does not contain any further definitions that are relevant to this chapter.

Finally, the specialist terminology database of the German Federal Defence contains some relevant definitions. The primary sources for these definitions are not readily available. Accordingly, these definitions are quoted from the database. The definition of ‘ordnance’ follows GICHD’s definition of ‘explosive ordnance’, but is even more comprehensive as it adds “objects and components containing explosives, nuclear fission or fusion materials and biological and chemical agents” [33]. It is therefore again rejected as being too inclusive. A definition of ‘discovered munition’ that is provided in the database is incomprehensible and therefore ignored. In addition, a definition of ‘munitions discovery’ is provided: “detected object that is identified as munition or is regarded as munition due to its shape, label, location, etc.” This is an idem per idem definition and can thus not be accepted. The database defines ‘UXO’ as “self-propelled munition, dropped munition or projectiles, whose explosive, expelling or bursting charge did not or did not fully come into effect after drop, shooting, throw or launch of the munition.” [33] The definition does not include mines or explosive ordnance that was dumped or otherwise left behind, and no suitable definitions for these objects are provided in the database. It is therefore not suitable for this dissertation.

On top of the above, other terms are less frequently found in the literature. Among them is ‘discarded military munitions (DMM)’. According to United States (US) law, it refers to “military munitions that have been abandoned without proper disposal or removed from storage” and does not include UXO (Title 10 U.S.C. §2710(e)(2)) [34]. The definition is akin to AXO and too narrow for this study.

To devise definitions that are suitable for this study, the terms that will be used throughout this dissertation need to be selected. From the above definitions, numerous terms are available: ‘ordnance’, ‘explosive ordnance’, ‘munitions’, ‘discovered munitions’, ‘munitions discovery’, ‘UXO’, ‘AXO’ and ‘ERW’. The terms ‘ordnance’ and ‘munitions’ are considered too broad. The term ‘explosive ordnance’ may both refer to objects that have not been dumped or in some way deployed (i.e., that are still ready for future use) and to objects that have been in some way deployed, dumped, or otherwise left behind. The following definition is used in this study:

Explosive ordnance means all conventional munitions containing explosives, explosive military weapons, and objects containing explosives that are of military origin and that are intended for warfare, except for those containing smoke-producing substances, irritants, nuclear fission or fusion material, biological agents, or chemical warfare agents (CWAs).

The terms ‘discovered munitions’, ‘munitions discovery’, ‘UXO’, and ‘ERW’ all describe explosive ordnance that was deployed in some way. ‘Discovered munitions’ and ‘munitions discovery’ are disregarded. They suggest that only once an object is found does it become relevant, when in reality it exists independently of being discovered. According to the definition of the UN, ‘ERW’ is the most comprehensive term [26]. The Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal directly contradicts this with its ‘UXO’ definition [23]. A comparative quantitative search of the exact ‘explosive remnants of war’ and ‘unexploded ordnance’ was conducted in the electronic databases *Google Scholar*,

TABLE 2.1: Comparative quantitative search of the terms ERW and UXO in the years 2005 till 2022 in various publication databases (results from April 13, 2023).

Database name	Number of Results for Search Term	
	Explosive Remnants of War	Unexploded Ordnance
Google Scholar	3720*	14 300*
EbscoHost	96	910
Wiley Online Library	53	442
Springer Link	213	714
ScienceDirect	60	571

* Approximate numbers as given by the database.

EbscoHost, *Wiley Online Library*, *Springer Link*, and *ScienceDirect*, to identify which term appears more often in the publications listed in each of them. The underlying notion is that the scientific and expert communities use the term they perceive as most appropriate more frequently. It would thus lead to a higher number of search results. The acronyms were not included in the search to avoid including search results in which they may have different meanings than the ones required here. For all databases, only search results from 2005, the first full year after the publication of the *Protocol on Explosive Remnants of War* [26], until 2022, the latest full year before conducting the search, were included. Table 2.1 shows the results of this search. In all of the consulted databases, the term ‘unexploded ordnance’ is more widely used than ‘explosive remnants of war’. To ensure that it is logically consistent with the definition of ‘explosive ordnance’ above, the term ‘unexploded ordnance’ is therefore used in the following way:

UXO means all explosive ordnance without ownership that was in some way deployed, dumped, or otherwise left behind and which remains unexploded for any reason.

The terms ‘AXO’ and ‘DMM’ are not defined here and are not used any further. They can be considered a subcategory of ‘UXO’ and their definition has no merit. Since the marine environment is the exclusive domain that is addressed in this study, the term ‘UXO’ always refers to ‘offshore UXO’.

Another term that will constantly be used throughout this study is that of ‘EOD’. While the UN do not offer a definition, GICHD defines EOD as “the detection, identification, evaluation, render safe, recovery and disposal of UXO” [28]. The German definition that is given in BFR KMR lists the same activities. Other terms, such as ‘UXO Clearance’, can be found in the literature, but they are not defined in the regulating documents that were reviewed here. As there are no competing definitions for EOD, the one from GICHD is used for this dissertation:

EOD means the detection, identification, evaluation, render safe, recovery and disposal of UXO.

2.1.2 Historical Context

Why and how UXO ended up in the sea is far more than mere historical background knowledge. Historical surveying has great practical value during the execution of comprehensive EOD work, as its results drive subsequent processes and work steps (see 3.2.1) [23]. Hence, a brief historical review of UXO in general also aids in the development of the scope for the study at hand. While UXO in the sea is a global phenomenon [35], this subsection focuses on Germany (i.e., the study area; see 2.1.3). It is not a full account of UXO's entry into German waters. It rather focuses on providing sufficient information to allow for informed scoping.

In the historical description, no primary sources are consulted, as this would have required extensive visits to historical archives. For this chapter, a review of contemporary accounts on the historical context is considered sufficient. A lack of diligence and scientific professionalism in terms of historical research when addressing the issue of UXO was criticised in the literature [36]. Indeed, reports and research on the subject usually lack references to primary sources to substantiate the numbers of submerged objects and tonnages of dumped material. It is, however, not the purpose of this study to address this shortcoming. Instead, the reader is herewith made aware of this structural problem in the field.

The exact time frame that is relevant for research on UXO is subject to debate. It has been claimed to encompass the time from 1870 until the present day [3]. The explosive substance 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene (TNT), which makes up a great share of the material in conventional ordnance (see 2.2.6), was invented seven years prior in 1863 [37]. Only in 1902 was it adapted for military use [38]. Either way, since the late 19th century, major scientific and technological advancements have driven explosive ordnance development. Over time, new types of weapons, such as grenades and bombs, were introduced. [3] Design often disregarded requirements for safe demilitarisation [39]. Many of these types of explosive ordnance ended up as submerged UXO in the sea via different entry paths.

The following passages are concerned with the different entry paths of UXO into the marine environment. In essence, they describe how the explosive ordnance became UXO. Subsequently, deductions for scoping are made.

Dumping

As a consequence of the fast-paced technological development in weapons technology, the challenge of having to dispose of obsolete explosive ordnance occurred regularly. In an attempt to address this problem, dumping was performed regularly. [3] Explosive ordnance was i.a. dumped when it became unsafe to handle or transport due to deterioration. The times after World War I (WWI) and WWII marked the most significant periods in terms of explosive ordnance dumping. [39]

Two types of explosive ordnance dumping activities were performed. Either it was cast overboard or the transporting ships were scuttled (i.e., deliberately sunk by allowing water to enter the hull), and the explosive ordnance sank with them. In addition, there is

the possibility of transport losses or emergency dumping [3]. The amount dumped during individual actions ranges from a few to thousands of objects. [39] Since most dumping activities were planned operations, the great majority of dumped explosive ordnance was not fused or armed (see 2.2.10). [3, 40] An exception are dispensers with cluster munitions, which may be fused. [3]

After the end of WWI [41], dumping and scuttling were performed with chemical and conventional ordnance alike, both separately and in combination [17, 41]. The scuttling of ships was especially favoured for chemical ordnance disposal [42]. CWAs that remained after WWI were both dumped [43] and destroyed onshore. Agents were again produced before and during WWII. They were not widely used, which resulted in a great CWA stock that had to be dealt with after the war's conclusion. In 1946, after WWII had ended, the Allies again opted for dumping. As a consequence, around 170 000 t of chemical ordnance was dumped into the North Sea and up to 65 000 t into the Baltic Sea. Of these, about 90 t and 5000 t, respectively, ended up in German waters [3].

In Germany, the largest share of currently present UXO originates from dumping. Some dumping of explosive ordnance was executed by German troops during the final stage of WWII. [3] Later, in 1945, the Potsdam Agreement decreed to demilitarise Germany and to distribute the warfare materials among the Allies or destroy them. Once the war had ended, the victorious Allies continued the practice and dumped both captured and their own explosive ordnance. The vast majority of explosive ordnance dumping took place in the war's aftermath. [3, 44] For the American military, it was considered a preferred method of disposing of explosive ordnance [39]. Demilitarisation through dumping occurred because no apparent alternative existed [10]. Other methods, such as onshore detonation, burning, or emptying of ordnance, were time-consuming and hazardous for the executing personnel. In opposition to these methods, dumping was regarded as an efficient, safe, and permanent way of disposal.

Overall estimates say that up to 1 800 000 t of conventional ordnance was introduced into German waters, of which up to 1 600 000 t remain there to this day. The German North Sea was contaminated with around 1 300 000 t and the German Baltic Sea with around 300 000 t. According to official nautical charts, the UXO is distributed throughout 14 dump sites in the North Sea and 16 in the Baltic Sea. [3, 45] In addition, the victorious powers dumped their own surplus ordnance as UXO in other areas. The British Army, for example, dumped up to 1 200 000 t of ordnance, which was however not disposed of in German waters. [46] One estimate suggests that an overall amount of 360 000 t to 385 000 t of ordnance was dumped in the Baltic Sea, which includes 40 000 t of chemical ordnance. This would mean that the overwhelming majority of conventional explosive ordnance dumping in the Baltic Sea took place in the study area (see 2.1.3) [39]. In Italy, dumping of previously cleared UXO from bombed harbours occurred [47]. There is no evidence that this was also practiced in Germany. Post-WWII-dumping activities were meant to be finished in December 1946 but continued until 1949. Americans stopped dumping in 1946 as they realised that dismantling the valuable metals was commercially viable. The practice was

continued by the British. [44] A legal ban on dumping was only partially introduced in 1975 and fully in 1996 (see 2.1.4). It is, however, widely accepted to assume that most nations omitted it by around 1970 to 1974 [e.g. 39, 41].

Even though rough estimates exist, it is impossible to provide a precise and conclusive number of dumped explosive ordnance, let alone for specific UXO types, either in Germany or overall, for several reasons. Especially in the later stages of WWII, not all of the explosive ordnance disposal activities were documented, and it is unknown whether certain charges of explosive ordnance were dumped or otherwise disposed of. The same is true for some of the explosive ordnance that was captured by the Allies. Possibly, activities were documented, but the respective archival documents have not yet been scrutinised. [3] Other records have been destroyed [41]. In general, documentation on the dumping of chemical ordnance is more readily available than that on the dumping of conventional ordnance [17]. As a result, it has to be expected that all types of explosive ordnance that existed at the time of dumping may now be present as UXO. This is in contrast to other entry paths, which are specific to the type of explosive ordnance.

Naval Mining

While dumping is an entry path that was mainly used to dispose of obsolete and unwanted explosive ordnance, the majority of entry paths are more directly related to actual warfare. Naval mining is one of these.

Both during WWI and WWII, naval mines were deployed by German and Allied forces alike [3]. Global naval mine-laying by all factions amounted to 235 000 mines during WWI [48] and to 550 000 mines during WWII [49]. In the entire Baltic Sea, this resulted in the overall laying of 100 000 to 150 000 naval mines [50]. In the entire North Sea, 190 000 naval mines were laid during WWI alone, making it at the time the marginal sea that was most affected by naval mines globally [48]. In Germany, mining occurred in both the North and Baltic Seas, with a focus on the North Sea [3]. During WWI, naval mines were mainly laid for defensive purposes by surface vessels. In WWII, technical possibilities increased, and mining was performed by ship, aircraft, and submarine, thereby enabling the use of mines for offensive purposes. [51] The deployment of mines by aircraft in German waters was to a great degree carried out by the British Royal Air Force. Between 1940 and 1945, its bomber command deployed over 40 000 naval mines in so-called ‘gardening’ operations. [52]

Classifying mines by their position in the water allows for an understanding of how they became UXO. According to this classification, three types of mines were used: moored mines, bottom mines, and drifting mines [53]. Moored mines were heavily used during both World Wars. Ground mines, on the other hand, while already existing towards the end of WWI, were mainly deployed during WWII. Finally, drifting mines were only rarely utilised, due to their lack of efficiency. [54]

Efforts to remove bottom and moored mines were initiated during and immediately after each of the wars. The operation continued until 1972. The sweeping of moored mines often took place in the following manner. First, the mooring that attached the mine

to the seabed was severed. Due to their air-filled floating bodies, the mines rose to the surface, where a vessel fired at them. As a consequence, the mines would either detonate or the damage to the floating body would allow water to enter the hollow mine. In the latter scenario, the mine sank to the seabed, where it remained unless properly cleared at a later point in time. Actually, a safety feature of moored mines was meant to ensure the automated sinking of the mine to the seabed. If the feature functioned as intended, this would again lead to the presence of an uncleared UXO object. If it did not function and the afloat mine was not recognised during the demining efforts, it may have freely drifted to a current-determined location. [3] Due to these uncertainties, this operation is better labelled ‘sweeping’ than ‘clearance’. Sweeping essentially resulted in the elimination of the imminent threat to surface vessels and submarines but created a legacy on the seabed. Clearance, on the other hand, is the complete removal of the UXO (see 3.2.2). After WWII, sweeping techniques were improved to initiate ground mines. However, these efforts also remained rather ineffective, and an indeterminate number of ground mines were left on the seabed. [54]

In addition to the above, there were other ways in which naval mines became UXO. Some moored mines completely broke loose from their anchors even before sweeping took place. In this case, either automated sinking or free drifting, as described above, was the consequence. [3] Other moored mines had already malfunctioned during deployment. They failed to be released from their anchor, remained attached to it, and sank with it to the seabed. [50] In this case, they may not have been found during mine sweeping [54]. Drifting mines, on the other hand, became UXO by design if they did not detonate. When deployed, it freely floated around to an undetermined location [53]. Unless cleared, both drifting mines and loose moored mines may have floated to the coast, or otherwise, they may have eventually sunk [3, 54].

One source suggested that only 15% to 30% of WWII mines around the United Kingdom (UK) were fully cleared after the war. Due to the absence of records for WWI, the same source suggests that the ratio of cleared mines from that war may be even lower. [55] Another report states that 85% of naval mines around the British Isles could not be found during the sweeping operations following WWI [54]. It is, however, unclear whether these numbers are transferable to Germany. Still, it is a strong hint towards the wide presence of naval mines as UXO. There is no indication that any mines were laid in Germany after WWII.

Naval Combat

During both world wars, but especially during WWII, naval engagements took place regularly to attack and, in turn, defend facilities on land or at sea. Such naval combat certainly led to the entry of explosive ordnance into German waters in the North and Baltic Seas. Naval combat included weapons such as artillery shells, torpedoes, and depth charges. It is difficult to quantify the number of UXO objects originating from this entry path. [3]

The entry of UXO as a consequence of combat is in part due to the ratio of misfired explosive ordnance, which refers to UXO that failed to detonate as intended. A conservative estimate suggests a misfire rate of 10 % for modern explosive ordnance but a misfire rate closer to 30 % during the world wars. [56] Other estimates suggest that a ratio of more than 10 % of most types of explosive ordnance failed to function [55]. Yet another estimate suggests that one firing range in Denmark had a 2 % to 10 % ratio of shells that did not detonate on impact with the target [52]. Whatever the exact numbers, it is apparent that a certain portion of the explosive ordnance did not function as intended, regardless of whether it hit the target or not. This insight does not only apply to the entry path of naval combat but also to aerial warfare and exercise (see below). As a consequence, all sizes and types of artillery shells may be found as UXO, with larger calibres mainly originating from WWI. Where all these objects are now is challenging to predict, as not all naval engagements were recorded [54]

Torpedoes were mainly used in naval combat during WWII. Especially during the first years of the war, German torpedoes were unreliable and often failed to detonate, either because they ran out of propellant or because their fuses did not work. Yet others simply missed their target. In all of these cases, they sank to the seabed and became UXO. [54, 55]

Naval warfare changed drastically with the introduction of submarines. During WWII, Germany relied heavily on these vessels, which the Allies often countered with depth charges, an anti-submarine weapon that was delivered by plane or by surface vessel [51, 54]. It is unclear what percentage of depth charges failed to function when they reached the determined depth for detonation. [55]

Bombing and Aerial Warfare

Bombs were only rarely used during WWI. During WWII, the number of air raids on sea- and land-based targets close to the coastline increased. [55] Bombs gradually grew in terms of net explosive quantity (NEQ) (see 2.2.7) and in importance alike, and their massive use brought about their presence as UXO in the German North and Baltic Seas. [3] Germany committed to a strategy of close integration of the air force with land and naval units. On the other hand, Britain and the US relied heavily on strategic bombing, constantly deploying long-range bombers across the sea to reach targets in Germany. [51] Numerous bombs missed their targets at sea, while others fell short during attacks on land targets, some of which landed in the sea. Since they were actively deployed, they must have been fused. [54] On top of that, numerous events required bombers to jettison the bombs they had on board. This includes bombers being attacked or damaged, as well as heavy weather. [52, 55] British bombers were also required to jettison leftover bombs that had not been deployed on their return flight [51]. It could be argued that all jettisoned bombs belong to the entry path dumping. There are, however, some properties that distinguish these bombs from otherwise dumped explosive ordnance. Jettisoned bombs may or may not have detonated upon impact on the water surface, which is a function of the drop

height. Furthermore, it is not always certain whether these jettisoned bombs were fused or not. [52] Dumped explosive ordnance, on the other hand, did not detonate but sank to the seabed as a UXO.

Next to bombs, the increase in aerial warfare resulted in an increased entry of missiles and shells that were deployed by planes. On top of that, in response to air raids, anti-aircraft guns on land and aboard ships attacked the planes. If these did not hit their target, they ended up at an undetermined location in the sea and sank to the seabed, similar to the explosive ordnance that was used during naval combat. [3, 51]

Finally, beginning in 1944, the German land-to-land weapons systems Fieseler Fi 103, also known as ‘Vergeltungswaffe 1’ (V-1), which translates to ‘Vengeance Weapon 1’, and ‘Aggregat 4’, also known as V-2, were used. These imprecise weapons may have diverged into the open sea, where they became UXO if they did not detonate. [55]

Exercise and Testing

Since 2.1.1 determined that only munitions containing explosive material are considered UXO, this description does not address full-jacketed practice munition, i.e., ordnance that is not filled with explosive material. However, even when discussing practice munitions, they often contained hazardous substances [33], which may include explosive compounds.

Military exercises in defined geographic areas were often conducted with live explosive ordnance such as naval artillery shells, torpedoes, and mines. Other drill grounds were dedicated to exercises with live bombs. [3] In addition to these stationary grounds, it is likely that short-term exercises took place in other areas [54]. Some of the sites are still used as training areas by the German Navy. [3] Considering the shooting ranges that were operated by the National People’s Army of the German Democratic Republic (GDR) and the Soviet Armed Forces, it becomes apparent that a great part of the German Baltic Sea has at some point in time been in the range of firing practice. [57, 58].

Furthermore, testing of all types of explosive ordnance was required as part of their research and development process. Over the years, this has led to the entry of prototypes and test ordnance at specific testing grounds. [3] These do not exclusively originate from the period of the World Wars but were also established more recently [59].

To this day, the German armed forces operate shooting ranges at sea. Two overlapping impact areas are located in the Baltic Sea, west of the island of Fehmarn. Another one is operated by the air force and spans a larger stretch of the North Sea from the German-Danish border all the way south towards the latitude of Heligoland. [60]

Wrecks

Wrecks are another entry path for UXO. This description does not refer to vessels that were scuttled during dumping activities, which are considered to be part of the entry path dumping. When warships were sunk in naval combat, the explosive ordnance aboard sank with them [3]. The same is true for submarines and midget submarines [61]. Even greater amounts of explosive ordnance were aboard transport vessels. A well-known example is the ‘SS Richard Montgomery’ in the Thames estuary, which is presumed to hold 3173 t

of UXO [55]. If a vessel was sunk by gunfire, mines, or torpedoes, additional objects of that type of UXO may be present in the vicinity of the wreck. It is also possible that part of the explosive ordnance carried by a ship became exposed if the ship broke apart while it was sunk. [54]

On top of UXO, wrecks will often contain other hazardous substances, usually in the form of the fuel that was used to propel them [40]. They may also hold human remains [56]. It should also be noted that the issue of wrecks is not limited to ships, as crashed and shot-down planes may also contain UXO, specifically bombs [55].

It is estimated that around 1000 shipwrecks are present in the German North Sea and 500 in the Baltic Sea. A precise number cannot be given, as new wrecks are detected regularly. The number of 1500 includes all types of ships, not only those that sank during the World Wars and contain UXO. [62] In the entire North Sea, around 680 wrecks from WWI and WWII are assumed to contain UXO, at least 120 of which are located in German waters. It is, however, unclear how many tonnes of UXO they contain. [63]

Conclusions from the Historical Context

Now that the historical context of UXO and the different entry paths into the sea have been laid out, it is possible to further specify the scope of this study. The historical review demonstrates that the large majority of UXO that can be found in the study area (see 2.1.3) originates from combat during WWI and WWII and from dumping activities during the wars and thereafter. It is, therefore, feasible to define that this study addresses UXO that entered German waters between 1914, which marks the beginning of WWI, and 1949, which marks the reported termination of explosive ordnance dumping in Germany. With dumping ceased and no further armed conflict in the study area taking place, the only significant remaining entry path was exercise and training. It is therefore considered needlessly excessive to include UXO that entered the sea after 1949 in the study. Defining the historical scope in such a manner determines two aspects.

- It limits the types of UXO to those that were submerged in the years from 1914 to 1949. This in turn determines which fuses, explosive materials, and casing materials may be present in the UXO.
- It controls the period during which the UXO has been submerged and therefore has been subjected to environmental effects. This influences the condition that the UXO objects are in.

With the information from the historical review in mind, it is useful to further scope the population of UXO. This will allow for a focused and meaningful study. Certain types of UXO are disregarded for the remainder of this dissertation.

- UXO that is contained in wrecks: this is relevant for plane, ship, and submarine wrecks both scuttled and sunk during naval combat. If UXO in wrecks was included, this would add an entire layer of assessment to the study, as different additional and different

hazardous substances are aboard these wrecks, and therefore other salvage technologies are employed. As 3.3 demonstrates, numerous readily available technologies for EOD are applied constantly, which is something that cannot be said about wreck removal.

- UXO containing CWAs: adding CWAs to the scope would largely inflate many aspects that need to be considered in this dissertation, including its legal context and the potential negative impacts that need to be investigated. At the same time, the overall amount of CWAs in the study area (see 2.1.3) is minor when compared to conventional UXO.

2.1.3 Geographic Context

Next to the historical context, it is relevant to assess the geographic context in which this study is conducted. A geographic site description is required during the initial phase of EOD (see 3.2.1). Again, this step is a prerequisite for subsequent work. [23] Therefore, this study requires a geographic summary. This subsection does not concern the environmental conditions in the geographic area. These are scrutinised in 3.4.

UXO is a global phenomenon [35]. For a scope definition, it is warranted to define a study area and describe how UXO is distributed and redistributed in it. This subsection, therefore, addresses these issues. It closes with the geographic scoping of the study, this time from a geographic point of view.

Study Area

National sovereignty over maritime waters is addressed in the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)*, which came into force in 1994 [64]. *UNCLOS* was already signed by the GDR in 1982. The convention's accession by reunified Germany took place in 1994, just before coming into force. In 1998, *UNCLOS* was also formally confirmed by the EU. Today, the convention has 157 signatories and 168 parties. [65]

According to *UNCLOS*, a coastal state has the right to declare a territorial sea along its shore. The territorial sea of a country may reach out to 12 M from a baseline. The baseline is defined by the low-water line, i.e., the water surface level at the lowest tide. All waters landward of the baseline are treated as internal waters. On the other side of the baseline (i.e., seaward) up to a maximum of 12 M is the nation's territorial sea. In internal waters and the territorial sea, the coastal state is sovereign and, as long as it does "not hamper with the innocent passage of foreign ships" (Art. 24(1)), free to define laws in the same manner as on its onshore territory. In addition to establishing a territorial sea, a country may declare an exclusive economic zone (EEZ) of up to 200 M from the baseline. In this zone, the nation has sole exploratory rights to existing natural resources. *UNCLOS* defines additional areas that may be declared by a country. [64] These are not explained here, as the above are sufficient to attain an understanding of the study area. The existence of the widely accepted *UNCLOS* lends itself to the definition of the study area.

It is assumed that the internal waters, territorial sea, and EEZ are the areas in which a coastal state's main maritime economic interests are located. As section 2.3 will demonstrate, the presence of UXO is an obstacle to the pursuit of these interests.

FIGURE 2.1: The German internal waters, territorial sea, and EEZ.

As 2.1.2 explained, German waters suffered a heavy entry of UXO. At the same time, Germany's economic interests require safe access to large areas of the seabed. Its internal waters, territorial sea, and EEZ are therefore defined as the study area of this dissertation. Germany's territorial sea, with reference to the baseline definition, is specifically determined in the *Proklamation der Bundesregierung über die Ausweitung des deutschen Küstenmeeres* [66] (i.e., the 'Proclamation of the Federal Government concerning the expansion of the German territorial sea'). The German EEZ is defined in the *Proklamation der Bundesrepublik Deutschland über die Errichtung einer ausschließlichen Wirtschaftszone der Bundesrepublik Deutschland in der Nordsee und in der Ostsee* [67] (i.e., the 'Proclamation of the Federal Republic of Germany concerning the establishment of an exclusive economic zone of the Federal Republic of Germany in the North Sea and in the Baltic Sea'). Throughout the text, the terms 'German waters' and 'study area' are used interchangeably.

Figure 2.1 shows the areas that jointly make up the study area. It depicts no baseline as defined in *UNCLOS*. Accordingly, the area between the blue and yellow lines comprises both the German territorial sea and internal waters. The area demarcated by the yellow line is the German EEZ.

Distribution and Redistribution of UXO in the German Sea

As outlined in 2.1.2, it is estimated that around 1 600 000 t of UXO remain in the study area. It is not clear whether this number refers to the dumped amount alone or whether all the other entry paths are included. Independently from this point of uncertainty, it is appropriate to assume that the 30 dump sites are among the contamination hot spots in the study area [68]. The practice of repeatedly heading for the same contained geographic area and dumping tonnes of ordnance has led to concentrations of UXO that could otherwise only be found in a sunk ordnance cargo vessel. Within the dump sites, the distribution

depends on whether explosive ordnance was thrown overboard or released from a barge. While the former leads to a wider spread of individual objects, the latter results in the creation of piles [69].

Other areas with an elevated amount of UXO are the routes to the dump sites (since ordnance was also dumped en route), impact zones of shooting ranges, and anti-aircraft positions [3, 70]. Historical research also suggests a heightened presence of UXO in the vicinity of training areas and close to bombing hotspots, where the allied forces attacked areas of high military significance during WWII [70].

Apart from these hotspots, the presence of UXO in the study area is difficult to predict and, to a certain degree, random. Naval combat, mining, aerial warfare, and exercise led to background contamination, which must be expected throughout German waters. The distribution is not uniform but rather irregular. Historical research can help identify areas of naval combat or mining where the probability of encountering UXO is higher than in the surrounding region. The state of technology during explosive ordnance entry, navigational and other errors, as well as the chaotic nature of warfare, compromise the level of precision that can be expected from historic documents [3].

To further increase the complexity of the situation, UXO may be mobilised either by anthropogenic or natural mechanisms. A great deal of literature investigates the mobilisation of UXO by natural processes, specifically in coastal areas. Objects may be moved naturally in areas and depths of high current velocity, and if the object is sufficiently light and favourably shaped [71, 72]. In very shallow waters, wave action can mobilise UXO [73]. Another mechanism is the burial of objects by dunes, which may drag the objects with them as they migrate along the seabed [71].

Anthropogenic mobilisation processes are known, but their magnitude is not well understood. There is evidence that bottom-trawling activities redistribute UXO even over large distances of many nautical miles [51]. Areas of en-route dumping are considered particularly affected by this mobilisation mechanism [3]. There is also a potential for redistribution by large machinery, such as pipeline and cable-laying equipment [73]. Finally, it is known that in numerous cases, small UXO was accidentally brought ashore during measures of coastal protection. Sand was dredged from anti-aircraft batteries' impact zones and moved to a recreational beach. [58]

Conclusions from the Geographic Context

The description above demonstrates the complexity of the distribution of UXO in German waters. It is therefore rational to limit the geographic scope to German waters. Adding further geographic areas would not only add further contamination hotspots. The description above provides numerous reasons why a great variety of UXO must be expected throughout the study area, albeit not with an evenly distributed probability of encounter. With a look at the historical context, a greater geographic scope would even further increase the number of relevant types of UXO. While any type of explosive ordnance that was used in the European theatre must be expected in the study area, for

example, French or Polish UXO is less likely to be encountered than German or British UXO. Weapon systems that were used in the Pacific theatre or elsewhere across the globe can be excluded altogether from the scope of this dissertation.

Note that when referring to the German Baltic Sea or German North Sea throughout this dissertation, it always includes inland waters, the territorial sea, and the EEZ. If either of these regions is referred to, this is explicitly stated.

2.1.4 Legal Context

The degree to which the international community and individual countries demonstrate a willingness to establish a legal framework for a particular issue can be regarded as evidence of the seriousness with which this matter is perceived by the regulating actors. Tailored to the UXO challenge, this means that the higher the number and the greater the explicitness of legal provisions on the matter of entering explosive ordnance into the sea and on EOD (i.e., removing UXO from it), the more relevant the topic appears to those who provided said provisions. Consequently, this subsection reviews the overall legal context addressing the UXO issue. It presents the existing legal provisions on a global, regional, European, German, and state level that are binding in German waters. Unless otherwise stated, the documents introduced are currently in force. The subsection does not address norms, standards, and technical rules, as these are the focus of 3.1.

The subsection distinguishes between the legal context of the entry of explosive ordnance and the legal context of EOD. Subsequently, conclusions from this juxtaposition are drawn, and derivations for this study are made.

Legal Context of the Entry of Explosive Ordnance

Several documents that address the entry of explosive ordnance into the marine environment focus on dumping. As it is an activity that serves the disposal of UXO, it is regarded as waste in the context of these documents.

The 1972 *Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter*, commonly called the ‘London Convention’, was the first international convention to address the issue of dumping at sea. It specifically blacklisted the dumping of materials “produced for biological and chemical warfare” (Annex I, 7), i.e., CWAs, globally, but explosive ordnance was not addressed. It came into force in 1975. [74] The GDR ratified the convention in 1976, and the Federal Republic of Germany did so in 1977 [75]. Only with the *1996 Protocol to the Convention* was the dumping of conventional explosive ordnance prohibited. The protocol replaced the blacklist of prohibited substances with a whitelist of substances eligible for dumping. As explosive ordnance is not on this whitelist, it is hence prohibited from being dumped. [76] This protocol was ratified by Germany in 2006 [75].

Regional conventions were passed for the North Sea and the Baltic Sea, the two marginal seas that German waters are part of. Dumping in the North Sea was specifically addressed in the *Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping from Ships and Aircraft*, also referred to as the ‘Oslo Convention’. It was adopted in 1972

and came into force in 1974. However, it does not address ordnance dumping at all. [77] In 1998, it was replaced by the *Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic*, which was adopted in 1992 in Paris. It includes the North Sea as part of the North-East Atlantic. This ‘OSPAR Convention’ again uses a narrowly defined whitelist of materials eligible for dumping, thereby prohibiting the dumping of all ordnance. [78] Before coming into effect, the OSPAR Convention was ratified by Germany in 1994 and by the European Community (a predecessor of the EU) in 1997 [79].

The Baltic Sea counterpart to the Oslo Convention was the *Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area of 1974 (Helsinki Convention)*. It entered into force in 1980, and like the other early environmental marine conventions, it did not specifically address the issue of explosive ordnance dumping. [80] Again, this activity was later prohibited in the updated version of the convention, which carries the same name. It was signed in 1992, ratified by Germany and the European Economic Community (another predecessor of the EU) in 1994, and came into force in 2000. [81]

According to all of the currently effective documents that are presented above, emergencies involving human life, vessels, or offshore structures are exempt from the prohibition of dumping.

The EU addresses the release of waste into the sea in the directive 2008/98/EC on waste. In the directive’s preamble, it is noted that these activities are regulated by the London Convention and its 1996 Protocol (21). As a consequence, it does not explicitly prohibit dumping. It does, however, clearly state that all waste management, including disposal, must be carried out without endangering human life, harming the environment, or posing a risk to water, soil, plants, or animals (Art. 13). [82] Therefore, it is a valid interpretation that the directive considers all dumping of UXO unacceptable.

On a national level, Germany regulates the management of waste and therefore disposal and dumping in the *Gesetz zur Förderung der Kreislaufwirtschaft und Sicherung der umweltverträglichen Bewirtschaftung von Abfällen (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz)*, which translates to ‘Law for the Advancement of the Circular Economy and for Securing Environmentally Compatible Waste Management’. It states that all disposal must take place in approved facilities (§ 28(1)). As no such facility exists offshore, disposal at sea is practically not permitted. For waste that is exclusive to the military, the law is put into effect by the Federal Ministry of Defence, which may introduce exceptions, but only if imperative reasons render this necessary (§ 66). Dumping by the Federal Defence is therefore illegal unless defence purposes or intergovernmental obligations demand it. [83]

Dumping in the German EEZ is prohibited by the *Gesetz über das Verbot der Einbringung von Abfällen und anderen Stoffen und Gegenständen in die Hohe See (Hohe-See-Einbringungsgesetz)*, which is the ‘Law on the Prohibition of the Entry of Waste and Other Substances and Objects into the Open Sea’. With a few exceptions, the law prohibits disposal activities of any type of material (§ 4). However, it does not apply to vessels and aircraft of the German Federal Defence (§ 2(3)). Furthermore, it exempts emergencies (§ 7), which is in line with international conventions. The law’s declared purpose is the intro-

duction of the provisions made by the *International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships*, 1973, as modified by the *1978 Protocol* ('MARPOL 73/78'). [84] However, its content also happens to address the subject of dumping as prohibited by the London, OSPAR, and Helsinki Conventions.

In addition to the matter of dumping, other legal provisions deal with some of the other entry paths. Due to the international dimension of armed conflict, most of these provisions are provided in documents that are valid internationally. However, they do not cover all entry paths.

Mine laying at sea and the use of torpedoes in times of war are governed by the *Convention relative to the Laying of Automatic Submarine Contact Mines (Hague, VIII)* of 1907, which was ratified by Germany in 1909 and entered into force in 1910 [85]. The word 'submarine' does not refer to submarines but to the fact that mines were deployed underwater. The convention addresses 'automatic contact mines' and torpedoes. Even though there are numerous limitations, the use of all of these weapons is generally legal under the convention. The mines are required to become harmless when they are unanchored or come loose from their moorings. The same applies to torpedoes if they miss their targets. (Art. 1) From the description of demining given in 2.1.2, it is apparent that the understanding of what 'harmless' means was limited to reducing the most imminent threat. [86] The convention is, however, only applicable in times of war [87]. The convention was not updated, and other naval weapons or types of mines are regulated by it.

Numerous other conventions of the Hague Conventions of 1907 regulate aspects of warfare that inevitably result in the generation of UXO [88]. Apparently, this was considered an acceptable side effect of war. As no other international convention on maritime warfare has been developed to this day, it appears that this view remains in place globally.

The *San Remo Manual on International Law Applicable to Armed Conflicts at Sea* is a comprehensive manual on the legal aspects of naval warfare that are part of customary international law. It is not a legal document but a manual summarising the overall legal situation on the issue. The 1994 document does not mention significant regulations specifically addressing the deployment of torpedoes and mines beyond those made in Hague VIII (Art. 79.-91.). It does, however, add that "due regard for the natural environment" shall be taken during acts of war and that environmental destruction is only allowed in cases of military necessity (Part III, Section I, 44). [89]

The issue of laying naval mines during peacetime is not explicitly addressed by any international treaty. There is expert agreement that a state has the right to lay mines in its own territorial and internal waters, provided it does "not hamper with the innocent passage of foreign ships" (UNCLOS Art. 24(1)) [64]. Furthermore, laying naval mines in the territorial or internal waters of another state without that state's consent is illegal. There is also general agreement that the laying of naval mines is prohibited in the EEZ of other states and international waters. [87]

The 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine is the most recent example of the disregard of the above provisions. According to US intelligence, the Russian Federation laid mines in Ukrainian waters [e.g. 90], even though no official declaration of war had been issued when mining was executed. Thus, the operation was not legal under Hague VIII, to which Russia is, however, not a signatory.

The entry path of exercise is regulated at the German national level by the *Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift des Bundesministeriums der Verteidigung zum Waffengesetz (WaffVwV-BMVg)* ('Regulatory Provision by the Federal Ministry of Defence for the Weapons Law'). It states that firing exercises may only be performed on shooting and firing ranges (§ 14(2)) [91]. According to the *Zentrale Dienstvorschrift 40/11 - Übungsplätze und Schießanlagen am Standort* (Joint Service Regulation - Training Grounds and Shooting Ranges on Site) of the German Federal Defence, which is not a legal document, German waters are currently affected by the air defence shooting range Todendorf and the military training area Putlos (Chapter 2, V (235.)), both of which are located close to Schleswig-Holstein's Baltic Sea coast [92].

Legal Context of EOD

There are far fewer international legal provisions on EOD than there are on the avoidance of the entry of explosive ordnance into the sea. These are introduced here.

The *Protocol on Explosive Remnants of War* was already discussed in 2.1.1. Its definitions were rejected, as they were not considered to be sufficiently comprehensive. Nonetheless, it regulates clear liability for the clearance of all UXO (and AXO) that it includes in its definitions. Parties are required to clear all UXO in their territory (Art. 3(2)), i.e., also the territorial sea and inland waters, and to "provide where feasible, inter alia, technical, financial, material, or human resource assistance [...] to facilitate the [...] clearance [26]" of UXO in a territory they do not control but where they have used explosive ordnance (Art. 3(1)). However, this provision is technically inapplicable to UXO originating from post-war dumping, exercise, and testing. The largest issue with the protocol is its limitation to UXO, which originates from conflicts after it entered into force (Art. 1(4)). [26] For Germany, this occurred in 2005 when it declared its consent to be bound to the Protocol [93], which means that it does not affect the UXO originating from 1914 to 1947.

Further regulation on the global level can be found in Hague VIII. Next to the laying of naval mines, the convention also addresses the issue of the removal of mines after the conclusion of the war. Each nation is required to remove its own mines and the automatic contact mines in its own waters (Art. 5). [86] According to the contemporary understanding of what 'removal' entails (see 3.2.2), this provision has been violated with the inadequate clearance efforts that took place in the aftermath of both World Wars (see 2.1.2).

There is no national legislation that concerns the EEZ. According to the 'Federal Maritime Responsibilities Act' (*Gesetz über die Aufgaben des Bundes auf dem Gebiet der Seeschifffahrt* [sic] (*Seeaufgabengesetz - SeeAufgG*)) the federal government is responsible for the safety and ease of naval traffic (§ 1 2.). This means that EOD needs to be applied at a given location if either of these cannot be maintained. This is, however, only relevant

TABLE 2.2: German coastal federal states and relevant legal documents on EOD.

Federal State	Name of the Legal Document	English Translation of the Name
Bremen	<i>Gesetz zur Verhütung von Schäden durch Kampfmittel</i> [99]	‘Law on the Prevention of Harm Arising from Munitions’
Hamburg	<i>Verordnung zur Verhütung von Schäden durch Kampfmittel</i> [100]	‘Regulation on the Prevention of Harm Arising from Munitions’
Lower Saxony	<i>Kampfmittelbeseitigung in Niedersachsen</i> [101]	‘Explosive Ordnance Disposal in Lower Saxony’
Mecklenburg–Western Pomerania	<i>Landesverordnung zur Verhütung von Schäden durch Kampfmittel</i> [102]	‘State Regulation on the Prevention of Harm Arising from Munitions’
Schleswig-Holstein	<i>Landesverordnung zur Abwehr von Gefahren für die öffentliche Sicherheit durch Kampfmittel</i> [103]	‘State Regulation on the Prevention of Public Hazards Arising from Munitions’

if the UXO object is present along a naval waterway. According to § 1 3. b) of the same law, the federal government is furthermore responsible for hazard control and the elimination of interferences with public order in the EEZ. Therefore, UXO in the EEZ must be dealt with if it is a hazard or interferes with public order. [94] Within the German territorial sea, the majority of the responsibility in terms of EOD lies with the German federal states, as they are responsible for overall hazard control. This issue is regulated in the German *Grundgesetz* (Art. 30, 70 ff., 83). Should UXO present a hazard, the federal state that is responsible for the respective section of the territorial sea is required to handle it. [95] Matters regarding the handling of explosive substances are regulated by the German ‘Explosives Act’ (*SprengG* [30], see 2.1.1) and its three regulations (*1. Verordnung zum Sprengstoffgesetz (SprengV)* [96], *2. SprengV* [97], and *3. SprengV* [98]).

The coastal federal states of Germany all have state laws and regulations that regulate EOD in their territory, which includes their territorial sea. These describe the responsibilities of authorities and landowners with the overall purpose of preventing harm and public hazards from UXO. They do not require comprehensive EOD for the entire area of the federal state. Each of the documents regulates that a responsible state department for EOD exists, sometimes referred to as ‘state EOD squads’ (German: ‘Räumdienste der Länder’) [31]. Table 2.2 provides an overview of Germany’s five coastal federal states as well as the relevant legal documents that regulate EOD.

Conclusions from the Discussion of the Legal Context

The above distinction between legal documents on the entry of explosive ordnance and EOD (i.e., removal of UXO) seeks to juxtapose the level of activity on the opposing ends of the same issue. The regulation of the entry of explosive ordnance addresses the

TABLE 2.3: Number of legal provisions related to the entry of UXO and EOD on different administrative levels.

Regulatory Level	Number of Legal Provisions	
	Entry of Explosive Ordnance	EOD
Global	3	2
European	1	0
Regional	1*	0
German	2	1 [†]
State	0	1 [‡]

* The OSPAR and Helsinki Conventions are counted as one document.

[†] The regulations pertaining to the ‘Explosives Act’ are not counted as individual documents.

[‡] The coastal federal states’ legal documents on EOD are counted as one document.

prevention of addition to the UXO legacy and thus the avoidance of further contamination. The regulation of EOD, on the other hand, addresses the management and resolution of the already existing UXO challenge.

Overall, there are numerous legal provisions that deal with either side of the UXO challenge. Table 2.3 summarises the number of identified legal documents that are currently in force and that directly address the entry of explosive ordnance and EOD. The documents are sorted into five levels of geographic scope. These levels are global, European, regional (i.e., the Baltic Sea or the North Sea), German, and state (i.e., the five coastal federal states). Documents on the same regulatory level that regulate the same overall issues for different geographic entities are counted as one document. This is true for the OSPAR and Helsinki Conventions, as well as the five state-level documents on EOD shown in 2.2. The *1. SprengV*, *2. SprengV*, and *3. SprengV* are not counted as individual documents since all of them are direct regulations of the *SprengG*.

The majority of documents are concerned with the limitation of the entry of explosive ordnance into the sea. In the introduction to this subsection, it was assumed that the higher the number and the greater the explicitness of legal provisions on a matter, the higher the relevance of that issue in the eyes of lawmakers. It can therefore be stated that the prevention of the entry of explosive ordnance appears more relevant to the global (three documents), European (one document), and regional (one document) communities than the execution of EOD. Germany (two documents), as a signatory to the various conventions and a member of the EU, has followed suit and developed legislation on the prevention of the entry of explosive ordnance. This demonstrates a general preference for the prevention of pollution over clearance.

Dumping and naval mining are the focus of the regulatory scheme. There appears to be a failure to recognise the diversity of entry paths, which is reflected in the lack of regulation. Furthermore, dumping in the study area had already ceased in 1949, meaning that its prohibition came belatedly. Those provisions, which deal with naval mining, are derived from martial law and maritime law. Accordingly, the limitation on the entry of

explosive ordnance is a mere side effect. In summary, the additional entry of explosive ordnance into German waters has mainly been prevented by the absence of armed conflict and not by the existence of powerful legislation.

Fewer documents deal with EOD. The global community (two documents) has provided ambitious specifications that have either been violated or do not apply to conflicts preceding their commencement. Germany (one document) and its federal states (one document each) have focused on regulating responsibilities during EOD, introducing practice-oriented legislation, but national and state legislation fails to tackle the challenge of EOD strategically. EOD in German waters has been driven more by the offshore economy than by legislation [104]. The necessities of using the seabed have required EOD to take place.

From the discussion above, some conclusions can be drawn. These are exclusively derived from the legislation that regards EOD. The legislation on the entry of explosive ordnance and the prevention thereof is not relevant for the remainder of this study.

- There are no legal provisions that immediately impact the decision-making process on how to execute EOD. For this study, it is therefore irrelevant whether an operation takes place in the German territorial sea or the German EEZ.
- The state-level regulations determine that the responsible state department for EOD or a company commissioned by that department may perform EOD in the territory of that state [e.g., 99]. In the EEZ, there is no responsible body for EOD, as state departments for EOD hold no competence beyond their state's territory. Hence, EOD is often conducted by private companies (see 3.1). Beyond that, EOD may be performed by the German Federal Defence. [105] The results that are generated here are therefore valid for all those who have the technical resources and personnel capacities to perform EOD.

2.2 UXO Properties

UXO has many properties, some of which are relevant for EOD. To understand these UXO properties and how they are interrelated, the following subsections thoroughly describe them. The information that is provided here is the result of a comprehensive literature review, which always consisted of the search terms “offshore” and “UXO” or “unexploded ordnance” as well as other relevant search terms in line with the content of the respective subsection. The latter included terms like “casing”, “impact sensitivity”, “fuse”, “ignition chain”, and “main charge”. There are additional properties of UXO, for example, its origin, that are not addressed in this section. Instead, it focuses on properties that are relevant for the assessment of UXO objects that takes place later in this dissertation. Some of the information that is provided here was already published in a separate scientific paper by the author [106].

For the description and analysis in the subsections on the mass of the UXO (see 2.2.2), its dimensions (see 2.2.3), and the mass of the explosive material (see 2.2.6), a dataset was consulted. It contains data on UXO objects for which EOD was performed [107]. This dataset was provided courtesy of SeaTerra GmbH, a German company specialising in onshore and offshore EOD [108]. Data were provided in an anonymised fashion, so it was

impossible for the author to infer any information on contracting parties or other matters beyond the EOD operations proper. Data transfer took place as part of the research project ‘Professional intelligent munitions assessment using 3D reconstructions and Bayesian Neural Networks’ (ProBaNNt). The aim of this project is to improve decision-making during EOD operations [109]. This dissertation is part of this effort. For more information, see the acknowledgement section in the front matter. The dataset contains 230 entries of UXO objects for which an EOD decision was taken. Eight of the objects are not located in the study area defined in 2.1.3. These were not deleted to maintain the largest possible dataset. Some EOD operations were located in the Polish EEZ, one object was found in the Polish territorial sea (all close to the study area), and one operation was conducted in the Main River. For the description of UXO properties, this minor deviation from the study area is considered irrelevant. The dataset contains EOD operations from thirteen EOD projects ranging from 2010 until 2021.

The database contains 34 data columns. Some contain information that is relevant to this dissertation, while others (e.g., the sensor that was used to detect the object or the name of the vessel that was used during the EOD activity) are not of interest¹. None of the entries contain information in all columns. Hence, for the analysis of the data in the following subsections, subsets of entries that contain the required information were used. The following descriptions focus on some UXO-related information in the dataset. An analysis of the EOD information in the dataset is given in 3.3.1. For reasons of corporate secrecy, this dataset cannot be disclosed as an annex or otherwise in the context of this dissertation.

2.2.1 Time Sunk

As defined in 2.1.2, this study considers UXO that were submerged between 1914 and 1949. Accordingly, any given UXO object in scope may have been submerged 74 years to 109 years by 2023. This constitutes a period of 36 years.

The duration of a UXO object’s presence in the marine environment has an overall effect on its condition. The longer UXO is submerged, the longer its casing is subjected to chemical and physical corrosion (see 3.4.2). The same is true for the fuses. Over time, the properties of the explosive material change (see 2.2.9). The degree to which this happens depends not only on the explosive compounds themselves but also on the conditions of the surrounding environment [110].

¹Some information is duplicated in the database and thus not repeated here. The following columns exist in the database: project number, target point number, data source, sensor, cartesian coordinates, coordinate system, WGS 84 polar coordinates, water depth, modelled burial depth, modelled mass, magnetic moment, anomaly minimum, anomaly maximum, dipole width, dipole p-value, altitude, notes, clearance data, time, vessel, actual mass, length, width, or diameter, height, actual burial depth, sediment type, clearance process, uxo type, mass of explosive material, calibre, origin, detailed description, and comment.

2.2.2 Mass of UXO

Explosive ordnance is developed for many different operational purposes and is thus produced in a great variety of weights. In simple terms, it usually consists of a metal casing that is filled with explosive material, propellants, and pyrotechnics [42]. The weight of UXO mainly depends on the weight of the casing and the explosive main charge. Both are configured for the specific purpose of the object (for the latter, see 2.2.7). Other parts, such as the fuse, contribute to a lesser degree.

The mass of an individual UXO object can range from less than 1 kg to several tonnes. One UXO type that must be expected to be present in the study area is the British bomb D.P. 12,000-lb. Mk I, otherwise known as ‘Tallboy’. One of these bombs was destroyed in situ in the river Świna near Szczecin, Poland, in 2020. [111] The same type of bomb was also used to attack targets in Hamburg and on Heligoland [112] and thus may still be present in German waters. It has a mass of 11 885 lbs, i.e., 5391 kg [113].

To understand how mass is distributed over the population of UXO, it is possible to look at the EOD dataset. UXO mass values were available for 225 data entries—a subset that is now called n_{m_u} . For 112 objects, the UXO mass values were looked up in databases and other documents by the data provider after the EOD operation was conducted. For 159 objects, the entered values originated from magnetic modelling that is part of the technical survey of EOD (see 3.2.1). Finally, for five objects, the mass could be derived from the description of the UXO. A total of 52 objects had both looked-up and modelled values. In this case, the looked-up value was used, leaving 107 data entries with modelled values.

The median of n_{m_u} lies at 87.5 kg. The mean, which is strongly impacted by the few high mass values that are included in the dataset, lies at 202.5 kg. The histogram in Figure 2.2 shows the distribution of mass values for individual EOD objects. It clearly displays that many objects (52.8%) weigh less than 100 kg. In addition, 80% of data entries lie under 300 kg (to be precise, $Q_{80} = 311.6$ kg). The symbol Q_n refers to a quantile of the distribution below which $n\%$ of all cases are distributed.

Among other properties, the mass of the objects determines which EOD method can be used [23]. Given the distribution of mass values in Figure 2.2, it can be said that any institution that performs EOD services should be prepared to handle objects of up to 300 kg on a regular basis. Heavier objects occur much less frequently and are thus not handled routinely.

The maximum values in n_{m_u} were modelled 6371 kg, 1139 kg, 963 kg and 810 kg. The smallest values were looked up: 0.2 kg, 2.5 kg and 4.3 kg. The dataset thus covers the full range of possible UXO mass values. Remarkably, the highest values were all modelled based on the results of the technical survey, while small values were looked up. It is possible to look at the distribution of looked-up versus modelled UXO mass values in the quartiles of n_{m_u} . The distribution is as follows: in $Q1 = 36.4$ kg, 73% of values are looked up; in $Q2 = 87.5$ kg, 58% of values are looked up; in $Q3 = 229.8$ kg, 38% of values are looked up;

FIGURE 2.2: Distribution of the UXO mass of objects in subset n_{m_u} of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

TABLE 2.4: EOD procedures applied to objects in quartiles of subset n_{m_u} of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

EOD Process	Number of Objects					Ratio of Objects			
	n_{m_u}	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
In situ destruction	48*	2	9*	18	19	4%	19%	38%	40%
Left	3	0	0	0	3	0%	0%	0%	100%
Underwater transfer	18*	1	1*	10	6	6%	6%	56%	33%
Recovery	134	53	44	17	20	40%	33%	13%	15%
No entry	23	1	3	11	8	4%	13%	48%	35%

* One object was initially transferred under water and subsequently detonated. It is shown in rows for both EOD procedures.

and in $Q4 = 6371.0$ kg, 32% of values are looked up. The remainder for each quartile were modelled values. In summary, the ratio of looked-up to modelled values is decreasing with UXO mass.

This could be because heavier objects tend not to be recovered but to be left or detonated on site. In this case, no weighing would have been possible, which might explain the absence of looked-up mass values for these objects. Table 2.4 was produced to investigate this assumption. It shows how many UXO objects were treated by which EOD procedure. This information was included in the EOD dataset. The original data included descriptions of EOD procedures such as ‘recovered and handed over’ or ‘transported to beach’. Hence, in a preparatory step, categories were simplified, and all objects were sorted into the categories shown in column 1 of Table 2.4. For explanations on these processes, see 3.2.2. For 23 objects, no data on the EOD procedure were entered. The table shows absolute numbers for the entire sample (column 2) and for each quartile of UXO mass (columns 3 to 6). It also shows the ratios of objects in quartiles per EOD procedure (columns 7 to 10). Of 134 objects for which ‘recovery’ was performed, 97 (73%) fall into $Q1$ and $Q2$, i.e., weigh ≤ 88.7 kg. For each of the other EOD procedures (‘left’, ‘underwater transfer’, and ‘in situ destruction’) the majority of objects fall into $Q3$ and $Q4$. This means that objects that were treated this way have a larger mass. Of all 56 objects that fall

FIGURE 2.3: Distribution of the relative error of the modelled UXO mass of objects in subset n_{m_u} of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

into Q_4 , only 20 recovered, while 28 were not, and no information was available for another 8 objects. On the other hand, in Q_1 , 53 of 57 objects were recovered. In summary, the heavier an object, the more likely it is that it will not be recovered. Thus, no mass measurements were possible for a higher ratio of heavier objects, and hence only the values from the magnetic modelling are available in n_{m_u} . Further insights into the EOD information in the dataset are provided in 3.3.1.

To better understand the modelled data, it is possible to review the 52 objects, for which both a looked-up and a modelled mass value were available. To do so, the looked-up value (which is considered to be the ‘real’ value) was deducted from the modelled value, i.e., the absolute modelling error was calculated. This comparison showed that in 32 cases, the modelled values overestimated the UXO mass, and in 20 cases, they underestimated it. The mean (\bar{x}) of the error is 84 kg and the median (\tilde{x}) is 22 kg. The fact that both values are positive leads to the assumption that the modelled values rather overestimate the weight. The fact that $\bar{x} > \tilde{x}$ shows that overestimations are greater than underestimations. Next, the relative error of the modelling was calculated. A relative error of 0 means that the modelled mass was equal to the looked-up mass. A relative error of 1 means that the model predicted the weight to be exactly double the looked-up value, and so on. Some of the errors are remarkable: for one object, the modelled weight was 235 times the actual weight of the object. In another case, the relative error was 102. However, for the majority of objects, i.e., 44 out of 52, the maximum relative error lies between -1 to 2 as is displayed in Figure 2.3. It should be noted that the largest negative error is > -1 since -1 would mean that the modelled mass is 0 kg and an error < -1 would mean that a negative weight was modelled. Note that the error is not an indication of poor modelling. Instead, it demonstrates how challenging and complex magnetic modelling is. Factors such as the shape of the object [114], the degree of induced and remanent magnetization [31] and the burial depth [114] of the object influence the measurements and cannot be predicted from the data that are acquired during regular UXO surveys.

Looking at these modelling results, it would be possible to argue for their dismissal in further UXO mass discussions (which are continued in 5.7.4). However, this is not done for two reasons: firstly, objects with larger masses would be underrepresented in

FIGURE 2.4: Distributions of looked-up (above) and modelled (below) UXO masses of objects in subset n_{m_u} of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

the resulting subsample. Secondly, looked-up and modelled mass values are similarly distributed, as shown in Figure 2.4. The graph on the left is a histogram of all looked-up UXO mass values, and the graph on the right is the same for all modelled values. The distributions in both graphs look similar. They have a correlation coefficient of 0.82, which underlines their similarity. Notable differences are the steep decrease in objects from the first to the second bin in the left graph (looked-up data), while a similarly steep drop only occurs from bins two to three in the right graph (modelled data). Furthermore, the right histogram has a notable number of objects in the bin > 700 kg, while the left one does not.

2.2.3 Dimensions of UXO

UXO exists in many shapes and a great range of sizes. The dimensions (i.e., length, width, and height) of explosive ordnance are a consequence of its purpose and design. While some UXO objects are very small with dimensions below 100 mm, the previously mentioned ‘Tallboy’ bomb has a length of 6400 mm [111]. The shape and dimensions of UXO may change over time due to corrosion, biofouling, abrasion, and, in shallow waters, even wave impact [115].

FIGURE 2.5: Distributions of the longest (above) and shortest (below) dimensions of objects in subset n_l of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

Similar to the UXO mass, it is possible to look at the EOD dataset for information on the distribution of the longest and shortest dimensions of EOD objects. In the original data table, each dimension was entered as an individual column. An additional column for the UXO calibre existed, which should be equal to two of the dimensions of an object but often was not. Overall, 123 data entries (subset n_l) included a value for at least one of the dimensions or the calibre. For each of these, the longest and shortest dimensions were determined. The calibre was only used for objects that did not have values for width and height since the dimensions were measured after clearance and thus represent the actual state of the objects after clearance. The calibre, on the other hand, describes the dimensions of the objects as they were produced. Of all entries, 17 contained a value for only one dimension, 102 for two dimensions, and 5 for all three dimensions. These seemingly incomplete data entries can likely be explained by the fact that many UXO objects (such as all ordnance that is fired and most bombs) have a rather cylindrical or conical shape, i.e., they possess at least one circular plane. For these objects, two dimensions are equal. Others, such as some types of mines, are (almost) spherical, and therefore all dimensions are equal. Hence, it is not problematic that the great majority of data entries do not contain all three dimensions.

TABLE 2.5: Longest and shortest dimensions of objects in subset n_l of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

Dimension	\bar{x} (mm)	\tilde{x} (mm)	Q_{80} (mm)	$X_{(1)}$ (mm)	$X_{(n)}$ (mm)
Longest	898	970	1088	100	3000
Shortest	318	200	552	20	1000

Table 2.5 contains some statistical measures to characterise the dataset. It shows the mean (\bar{x}), median (\tilde{x}), the 80th percentile (Q_{80}), the minimum ($X_{(1)}$), and the maximum ($X_{(n)}$) for the longest and shortest dimensions of EOD objects in subset n_l . All values are rounded to integers. Even though objects with a longest dimension of 3000 mm were included in n_l (these were two British ground mines), this is rather uncommon, as indicated by \bar{x} , \tilde{x} , and Q_{80} , all of which lie well below that value. Most objects are considerably smaller, with only one fifth having a longest dimension > 1088 mm.

Table 2.5 also informs about the shortest dimension of EOD objects in subset n_l . Only 20 % of objects have a shortest dimension > 552 mm and none > 1000 mm. Instead, a look at the right histogram in Figure 2.5 reveals that about half of the objects lie in the range of 100 mm to 200 mm.

Similar to the mass of a UXO object, its dimensions determine which EOD method can be used [31, 23]. After a look at the distribution in the left histogram in Figure 2.5, it can be said that UXO with longest dimensions of up to 1200 mm is frequently treated, while larger objects occur only rarely. The graph also shows that one third of objects have a largest dimension in the range from 900 mm to 1000 mm, making this the most frequently occurring value range.

2.2.4 Casing Materials

Casings of explosive ordnance were produced from different metals and alloys. They contain the explosive material (see 2.2.6) and the ignition chain (see 2.2.10). The casing is not the only metal part of UXO, but it is its greatest one. It is noteworthy that a study focusing on the dump site in the Eastern Scheldt (The Netherlands) calculated that metal makes up 70 % of conventional UXO's weight. Of the metal parts, steel makes up 76 %, lead makes up 12 % brass (copper and zinc) accounts for 9 % and aluminium for 3 %. [42] Steel, aluminium [116], brass (with varying fractions of copper), copper, zinc [117] and different alloys [3] were used as casing materials [43]. Lead can be ignored when discussing casings, as it was used in fuses [3]. Other metals that were used in munitions include tungsten and tin [44]. These were, however, not used as casing materials.

The used casing materials were not uniform in their properties. The steel that was used for casings varied in quality [3] and carbon content [42]. After all, this study considers UXO from a period of 36 years that was manufactured using various production techniques in different countries in Europe and North America.

Some casings were not made from a single element or alloy. The piston rings of some artillery shells were made from copper [118]. Copper and zinc were used for driving bands of WWI artillery munitions [117]. Also, aluminium mines featured steel straps [52]. Other types of UXO include other components such as the tail of bombs or the moorings of mines, which could be made from other materials than the casing.

2.2.5 Casing Thickness and Condition of Casings

Similar to other UXO properties, the thickness of the casing of UXO varies greatly. The original casing thickness of the explosive ordnance when it was submerged ranged from a few millimetres to a few decimetres [3]. In one corrosion study, a casing thickness of 3 mm for bombs and of 5 mm to 7 mm for artillery shells was assumed [119]. Another study reported casing thicknesses of 8.8 mm to 13.1 mm for artillery shells, 6 mm for bombs, and 1.5 mm for smoke grenades [120]. The ‘Tallboy’ had an original casing thickness ranging from 32 mm to 115 mm [111]. If even a single UXO does not have a consistently thick casing, it is considered inappropriate to make flat assumptions for all UXO types in one group.

Unlike other UXO properties, it was not possible to determine typical casing thickness values for UXO, neither upon being submerged nor now. The property is not documented in the EOD dataset, nor was it possible to collect values from a literature review. Numerous publicly available UXO databases were consulted [121, 122, 123], but the casing thickness is not a parameter that is documented there. For further investigations of individual UXO objects, the parameter must therefore be researched on an item-by-item basis.

The main mechanism affecting UXO objects’ casing condition is corrosion (see 3.4.2). UXO exists in all conditions, ranging from fully intact to fully corroded [35]. In the period from 1999 to 2008, a total of 1,879 UXO encounters were reported to OSPAR by its contracting parties. On 768 occasions (42 %) the reported objects were in various states of corrosion, and only in 14 instances (1 %) the objects were in good condition. For the remainder, the state was unknown or not reported. [41] It is not clear why the share of corroded objects is so high. One explanation may be that encounters occur more often with unburied than with buried UXO, which affects the corrosion rate (see 3.4.2). UXO with a thin original casing that was recovered as early as 1953 already showed corrosion to the point that the casing was breached [2]. On the other hand, artillery shells washed ashore and found on tidal flats in Lower Saxony were reported to usually show only little corrosion in 2002 [44]. According to one report, naval mines in German waters were found in a variety of conditions, ranging from good to severely corroded. It also states that UXO that is located in the same general geographic area must not be expected to exhibit the same condition. [3] Another study reports on the condition of UXO in wrecks in Skagerrak. It confirms the self-evident assumption that UXO with thicker casings is in better condition than UXO with thinner ones. In this case, only aerial bombs were documented to be corroded to the point at which the payload interfaced with water, while artillery shells were intact. [124] The casing of UXO that is buried in the sediment or that was dumped in boxes can be expected to be in very good condition [3].

It should be mentioned that casings may also be breached by other processes than corrosion [125]. This includes abrasion from bottom sediments [42, 126]. A breach in the casing of moored mines may also be a result of the post-war demining technique of severing the mooring and firing at the floating mine (see 2.1.2).

The condition of the casing is a relevant UXO factor to consider in preparation for an EOD operation [23]. This is because UXO may break apart upon recovery, which may lead to the leakage of substances. [124, 127]. As 2.2.9 and 2.2.11 will explain, the condition of the casing also affects the sensitivity of explosive materials and the functionality of the fuse.

2.2.6 Explosive Materials in UXO

Explosive materials are energetic substances. When stimulated, they undergo a strong exothermic reaction (i.e., they release energy) in a very short time. The reaction that follows the initial stimulus is self-sustaining. It leads to the release of expanding gas and kinetic as well as thermal energy. [70] Many different materials are explosive. One encyclopaedia lists 93 different compounds [128]. Each of these compounds has different properties that determine how it works and, thus, how it can be used in explosive ordnance. In addition, there exist countless explosive mixtures, all with their own distinct properties. The same encyclopaedia lists around 180 mixtures from German production alone [128]. While not all of these are likely to be found in UXO, the number demonstrates the great variety. The other warring factions used some of the same blends but also had their own. A non-academic compilation that is available online lists 394 fillings for UXO, in 2022. While this also includes CWAs and other non-explosive payloads, the register underlines how many different fillings exist that may be relevant for the preparation of EOD. [129]

In a UXO object, two types of explosives or explosive mixtures will often be present: primary explosives and secondary explosives. Primary or initiating explosives can be brought to detonation even by small mechanical stresses or by a spark. Their purpose is to be the first element of the ignition chain, i.e., a sequence of explosive materials that detonate the main charge [32, 130]. The ignition chain may feature a booster that has the purpose of transferring the detonation from the primary charge to the main charge. Whether such a booster charge exists depends on the type of UXO. The main charge contains a so-called secondary explosive. [130] It is the payload of most UXO. It is less sensitive than the primary explosive but more powerful, with a higher detonation velocity and working capacity [70].

Main charges are usually explosive mixtures, such as Schießwolle 39 ('gun cotton'), to name just one example from Germany. During WWII, it consisted of 61.8% TNT, 23% Hexanitrodiphenylamine, and 15.2% aluminium powder [131 in 128]. This substance was specifically developed for use under water [70, 130]. There is extensive literature on the many explosive mixtures. It is relevant for any EOD expert who seeks to understand what type of substance they are dealing with.

The previously mentioned study on the Eastern Scheldt dump site (see 2.2.4) documents the weight proportion of the explosive TNT to be 90 %, followed by research department explosive/royal demolition explosive (RDX) (5 %), Tetryl (3 %) and pentaerythritol tetranitrate (PETN) (2 %). [42] Such ratios of the unmixed compounds may be relevant for the assessment of possible environmental hazards, but less so if one wants to understand their properties because mixing different compounds changes their properties [132]. Some of these properties are described in the subsequent subsections.

2.2.7 Mass of Explosive Materials

The mass of explosive material is also referred to as the NEQ. According to the definition in *2. SprengV*, the NEQ includes stabilisers [97]. In a UXO object, this refers to all explosive substances as well as mixtures and is not limited to the main charge. The following text therefore uses the term ‘charge mass’ instead of ‘NEQ’, when only referring to the weight of the main charge.

The amount of explosive material in UXO depends on its original purpose. Explosive material makes up 11 % of the weight of UXO at the Eastern Scheldt dump site in the Netherlands. The share of propellants is specified at 16 %. The latter group contains 70 % of nitrocellulose and 15 % of nitroglycerine, both of which are explosive substances. [42] It is important to note that the explosive properties of nitrocellulose and nitroglycerine may be lost due to mixing with other substances. However, following the above definition, stabilisers are included in the NEQ. Accordingly, the overall mass ratio of explosive material in the investigated UXO sample can be given as 27 %. It can be speculated that the number of 11 % refers to the weight of the main charge. Another claim that was found in the literature is that for projectiles, the charge mass usually contributes less than 10 % to the UXO mass [54].

In absolute terms, the charge mass of a single UXO object in the study area can be up to an approximate 5200 lbs (2359 kg) as is the case with the ‘Tallboy’ bomb [113]. One study reports that bombs can have a charge mass ranging from 5 kg to 2000 kg [54]. Mines may also have charges with a mass of up to 1000 kg. As the following discussion reveals, such large charges are the exception.

As for other properties, it is interesting to look at the distribution of the charge mass of EOD objects. In the EOD dataset, 62 entries (subset n_{m_c}) contained a value for the charge mass. Eight of these contained value ranges (e.g., 14 kg to 24 kg) instead of a single value. For these, the upper end of the value range was used for further analysis. The values were likely obtained by researching the charge mass based on the UXO type. In n_{m_c} the charge mass values range from < 1 kg to 340 kg, with a mean of 109 kg and a median of 120 kg. This already shows that the data are skewed to the left, i.e., towards the minimum. Figure 2.6 confirms this assumption. It displays the distribution of the charge mass of EOD objects in bins of 20 kg. One third of the objects contained an explosive charge < 60 kg. This group mainly consisted of artillery shells, grenades, and small mines. Another third of the objects contained charges weighing 80 kg to 140 kg. Of the remainder, 14 objects fall in the range 140 kg to 200 kg. These objects were aerial bombs and mines. Only 7 objects

FIGURE 2.6: Distribution of the charge mass of objects in subset n_{m_c} of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

(one torpedo and six large mines) contain charges > 220 kg, with none weighing > 340 kg. The distribution shows a global maximum in the bin < 20 kg and local maxima in the bins 100 kg to 120 kg and 140 kg to 160 kg. This multimodal distribution may be related to the operational purposes of the different types of explosive ordnance. It allows for an understanding of which types of explosive ordnance were produced and used frequently. It can be speculated that, for example, ordnance with a charge weight ranging from 40 kg to 80 kg or from 120 kg to 140 kg was rarely produced and deployed.

It appears that documentation of the charge mass appeared especially important when a detonation was planned by the data provider. Only 11 out of the 63 objects of n_{m_c} (i.e., 17%) were recovered, while 41 (i.e., 65%) were detonated. For the UXO mass (n_{m_u}), see 2.2.2, the ratios were 60% for recovery and 21% for detonation. Given that n_{m_u} is a subset that is considerably larger than n_{m_c} , it can be assumed that cleared objects are under-represented in n_{m_c} . From the analysis above, it is known that the lower the UXO mass of an object, the more likely it is to be cleared instead of detonated. Hence, a fair representation of cleared objects in n_{m_c} is expected to change the distribution shown in Figure 2.6. It would likely show higher numbers of occurrences in the lower bins.

A study that investigated the impacts of 88 underwater detonations on the Dutch Continental Shelf in 2010 and 2011 provides information on the reported charge sizes for the detonated UXO objects. It describes charge masses ranging from 10 kg to 1000 kg with the majority covering 125 kg to 250 kg. The dataset does not include any objects cleared by other means than detonation. It claims that most UXO found on the Dutch Continental Shelf at the time was detonated. [20] Hence, the study is not representative of other EOD methods. However, it supports the notion that charge masses that are larger than 340 kg (i.e., the maximum value of n_{m_c}) are the exception.

2.2.8 Relative Effectiveness of Explosive Materials

There are numerous ways to measure the performance of an explosive material during a detonation. One of these is the relative effectiveness (RE), also referred to as the ‘TNT equivalency’. Its precise definition varies in the consulted references, but they agree that it is not a physical property of the explosive material but an index factor that compares

a material's performance to that of TNT. The RE of TNT is, therefore, 1.0. A review paper offers a very general definition according to which RE is the “ratio of the explosive to that of a known quantity of TNT that have the same effect” [133]. The effect is determined by the energy release of the detonation. The review paper also presents ten methods to measure or calculate RE, some of which are supported by more detailed definitions. According to one definition, RE is the product of the heat of the detonation and the volume of its detonation products (the power index [134]). Another method uses the pressure of the detonation wave and relates it to the material's brisance. The brisance is the shattering effect that a charge has on its surroundings and, in turn, depends on the heat of the detonation, the detonation velocity, and the density of the explosive [130]. It is by itself a performance indicator of explosive materials. Yet another RE method focuses on the ability of an explosive to accelerate materials. [133] It is also possible to determine RE purely based on the heat of the detonation [134] or to measure the pressure of a detonation in an air blast test. Depending on whether the peak pressure or the impulse (i.e., the integrated pressure over time [135]) are measured during the test, different RE values are obtained with such a test. [136] Another method calculates the hydrodynamic work of a detonation using the density of the explosive material and the detonation's peak pressure [137].

Due to the multitude of methods and definitions, not even the question of whether kinetic energy, thermal energy, or both should be considered for RE has been fully clarified. Given the variety in definitions and testing methods, the values for TNT equivalency for the same explosive material can vary significantly, regularly producing errors of 20 % to 30 % and sometimes of up to 50 % [138 in 134]. When considering kinetic energy, the pressure that is generated by a detonation depends on many conditions, such as the size and shape of the used charge or the reflection off of obstructions, making it very difficult to reliably reproduce results [133]. RE values furthermore do not scale constantly with charge weight [138 in 134]. Due to all of these uncertainties, renaming RE to ‘approximate explosive equivalence’ was proposed [133].

It should also be noted that RE was not developed to express the performance of explosives under water. All testing procedures described in the literature are performed in air. No research on the effect of ageing on RE was found.

2.2.9 Sensitivity of Explosive Materials

Heat, friction, and impact sensitivity describe the behaviour of explosive materials when thermally or mechanically stressed. These properties characterise an explosive by how much energy is required to lead to a detonation of the material. The ageing of explosives can lead to changes—usually an increase—in their sensitivity [132, 139]. This is true both for the primary explosive materials in the fuse [43, 140] and the explosive materials of the main charge [139, 140]. A decrease in sensitivity is considered possible but unlikely, as this would require the complete degradation of the energetic groups in the material [139]. Accordingly, the *BFR KMR* (see 2.1.1) asks to avoid putting any mechanical stress on UXO during EOD [31].

On the one hand, some compounds that were commonly used during both World Wars, such as TNT, are chemically very stable [141]. One source reports that wet explosives tend to be less sensitive than dry ones [142 in 143]. On the other hand, prolonged exposure of explosive materials to seawater contributes to changes in properties. Chemical reactions in materials may lead to the formation of impact- or friction-sensitive compounds. Compounds of the main charge may react with one another, with metals from the casing, or with substances that are present in the surrounding seawater or the sediment [144]. Properties also change when explosive material is metabolised into other compounds by bacteria, fungi, and algae. Furthermore, environmental factors such as currents may lead to mechanical changes by grinding or washing materials out, which leads to an enlargement of the surface area. [145] Explosive mixtures change their composition when some of the included compounds are very soluble in water and others are not [146]. High salinity and dissolved organic matter were identified as factors favouring the photochemical degradation of some compounds (i.e., when subjected to ultraviolet radiation) [147], which may change their properties. Finally, impact sensitivity may also increase or decrease [148] significantly when materials dry. [132] It should be noted that there is literature available that does not unreservedly substantiate the claim of changing properties for explosive material on shore [149], i.e., not subjected to seawater, or even offshore [71].

In addition to changing properties, the use of impure TNT during ordnance production may have instantaneously led to a higher impact sensitivity ex-factory than intended [139]. Tests of historical TNT and Teteryl samples showed higher impact sensitivities than what is considered acceptable when these materials are produced today [132].

Impact sensitivity, or shock sensitivity, can be measured with several methods. For impact sensitivity, the EU requires the use of a specifically designed fall hammer apparatus or a similar method. According to the respective regulation, a material is considered ‘explosive’ at an impact sensitivity of 40 N m [150]. The limit of quantification of the fall hammer method is 49 N m [139]. Note that a lower value means that less impact energy is required to lead to a detonation of the material, i.e., a lower value means that the impact sensitivity is higher.

Similarly to impact sensitivity, several methods exist for determining the friction sensitivity of a material. The EU prescribes the use of a friction apparatus or a similar method. If a material has a higher friction sensitivity than 360 N it is considered explosive [150]. The limit of quantification with the friction apparatus lies at 353 N and thus below the threshold for determining a material’s status as explosive. Again, a lower value refers to a higher sensitivity.

The sensitivity to heat can be measured by filling the material into small metal tubes of different diameters and using four burners to heat them. Based on the critical diameter of the tube in which the material breaks into three or more fragments, the heat sensitivity value is determined. [145, 150] Thermal stability (yet another related parameter) can be measured via another test, such as a 48 h heating to 75 °C [144]. It has also been reported that explosive materials can be sensitive to static electricity [54].

2.2.10 Types of Fuses

A fuse is an element that initiates the function of explosive ordnance. It does so by initiating a detonator, which is filled with a sensitive primary explosive. Its purpose is to transfer energy to the main charge and initiate it. In addition, some types of explosive ordnance contain a booster between the detonator and the main charge, which is also filled with explosive material. In this case, the detonator initiates the booster, which forwards the energy to the main charge. [54] The sequence of explosive elements that detonate the main charge is referred to as an ignition chain [32, 130].

If a fuse is present, the UXO is referred to as being fused. However, the presence of a fuse in a UXO object does not necessarily mean that it is armed. UXO may have been dumped, jettisoned, or used with the fuse in place but not armed. The process of arming can mean that safety features that prevent the fuse from working were removed. [51] It can also refer to the removal of safety mechanisms that separated the detonator from the main charge, which prevented the explosive chain from working [54]. The arming procedure varied among the different types of explosive ordnance. For some types of aerial bombs, the arming took place immediately before [3], during, and after they were dropped [51]. Whether this automatic arming mechanism functioned as intended depended on the drop height. Fuses of some mines were armed with a delay [52]. In some parachute mines, arming was delayed by a clockwork mechanism [71]. If the delay mechanism seized working, the UXO object is fused but not armed. While dumped UXO is usually not fused (see 2.1.2), UXO that was used in combat is always armed fused and usually armed.

If they are functional, fuses are usually triggered by an external effect, which may be mechanical, acoustic, magnetic, or electromagnetic. The sensitivity of the fuse to these effects greatly determines whether a UXO object detonates. [51, 52] Mechanical fuses include hydrostatic and contact fuses. The former type was designed to be triggered by ambient water pressure at a defined depth. As the name suggests, the latter were supposed to be triggered by the physical impact of a bomb on a surface. Magnetic fuses are triggered by changes in the ambient magnetic field that are caused by a large ferromagnetic anomaly, for example, from a passing vessel. [71] Acoustic fuses use hydrophones to detect underwater noise that is caused by nearby vessels [3]. Depending on the functionality, fuses may either protrude from UXO [151] or be fully integrated into it.

In opposition to a delay mechanism for the fusing process, some fuses have features that delay the initiation of the detonator for a few seconds. Others contain mechanisms that ensure their functionality for a long time after they were armed. Long-term functionality was assured by chemical long-delay fuses in aerial bombs [111]. These are highly sensitive to acceleration and mechanical impact on UXO. [51] Other options to ensure long-term functionality were retainer spring-loaded fuses, cocked strikers, and diaphragms. These types are considered sensitive to accelerations. [51] If fuses used a clockwork mechanism, it is possible that this mechanism failed, and thus no initiation of the primary explosive took place. Such a clockwork mechanism may restart. [54]

Some UXO has special mechanisms (so-called anti-handling devices) to prevent defusing [51, 52]. These mechanisms use batteries, clockwork mechanisms, or operate upon mechanical impact [54].

Hague VIII Art. 1 provisions that mines are required to become harmless when they are unanchored or come loose from their moorings. The same applies to torpedoes if they miss their targets. [86] However, it was commonplace that this self-deactivation did not work as intended [52].

Once triggered, a fuse can use mechanical, electrical, chemical, or heat energy to initiate the ignition chain. This means it leads to the detonation of an explosive material—the detonator [54, 71]. In a mechanical fuse, a spike or pistol produces a mechanical impact on the primary explosive. In an electrical fuse, a spark initiates the detonation. [51, 54]

The many different types of UXO that were submerged between 1914 and 1949 were equipped with a great variety of fuses. The following paragraphs provide an overview of the fuses used during this period. It is non-comprehensive but describes those fuses that are most commonly mentioned in the literature on offshore UXO.

Based on the fuse type, mines can be classified as contact mines or influence mines. Contact mines were commonly equipped with numerous chemical (Hertz) or switch horns. The former type contains a glass vial that is filled with an electrolyte liquid. When impacted by a vessel, the vial is intended to break, releasing the liquid to energise a battery. [51, 54] In other mines, two vials contain separate liquids. When the vials break, the liquids mix and either produce an electrical charge or combustion [71]. Switch horns, on the other hand, are directly connected to a switch that is in turn connected to a battery [3]. For yet other contact mines (so-called antenna mines), a copper wire is attached to a floating device extended above the mine. When in contact with the hull of a ship, the contact between two different types of metal causes a voltage change, leading to the initiation of the primary explosive [51]. Influence mines may be equipped with magnetic [51, 152] or acoustic [71, 152] fuses. Some ground mines also contain barometric fuses that do not react to water depth but to pressure changes that can be attributed to passing vessels. In rare cases, fusing cables were attached to mines, which allowed triggering them remotely, for example, from land. More than one type of fuse can be present in a mine. [3]

Depth charges are commonly equipped with a hydrostatic [54] or barometric fuse [55]. Here, a bellows is compressed by the water pressure. This compression initiates a spring-loaded retainer spike that triggers the primary explosive. Later WWII depth charges have magnetic fuses [51]. Others may contain impact fuses [3, 54], yet other types contain clockwork or pyrotechnic delay mechanisms [3].

Many bombs contain impact fuses. In other cases, aerial bombs are equipped with magnetic or acoustic mechanisms [54]. Working principles to initiate the detonator may be pyrotechnical, electrical, or mechanical, including tearing wires, retainer springs, diaphragms, and cocked strikers [151]. Bombs can have numerous fuses at different locations,

for example, at the front, at the tail end, and along the side [52, 71]. A single bomb may contain different types of fuses [54]. Bombs intended for use against submarines were equipped with hydrostatic fuses [71].

Fuses in artillery shells were often armed while being fired [3]. The shells are usually equipped with impact fuses [42] and sometimes with barometric fuses [71]. The working principles are the same ones as for bombs [151]. Some artillery shells were equipped with time-delay fuses [71]. Finally, torpedoes were regularly equipped with impact fuses [3, 51] or magnetic fuses [3, 54].

Given the above explanations, it is apparent that knowledge of fuse types is important for any EOD operation [23]. In addition, some information on the condition of the fuse should be noted. These are introduced in the following subsection.

2.2.11 Condition of Fuses

Due to fuses and ignition chains being submerged between 1914 and 1949, it must be expected that they are in a very different condition than when the explosive ordnance was deployed or dumped.

On the one hand, detonators may become more sensitive with time (see 2.2.9). It is possible that chemical reactions led to the creation of substances such as potassium chlorate and others. These are even more sensitive than the explosives that are regularly used in detonators. [140] Primary explosives in detonators may have deteriorated and leached towards the surface of the UXO object or into the fusing mechanism. In this case, the high friction and impact sensitivity of the primary explosive can easily lead to its initiation. [71] In addition, the metal parts in fuses are subject to corrosion. Fuses with heavy metal parts (such as mercury(II) fulminate or lead(II) azide) are often strongly corroded, which makes their handling particularly challenging. [3]

On the other hand, if a fuse was originally present and armed, it can be corroded to such a degree that it does not function at all [52] or not as intended, for example, because corrosion caused mechanical parts to merge [153].

It is also possible that the functionality does not change. Even ground mines from WWI were found with fuses in very good condition [54].

In the case of some mines and torpedoes, fuses were equipped with an energy source. If a fuse was equipped with a battery that is now empty, it cannot work as originally intended [3, 154]. Magnetic [51] or acoustic [71] fuses in influence mines are presumed to have become inoperative by today. The same is true for aerial bombs that are fitted with similar mechanisms. On the other hand, if the energy is provided by an electrolyte (such as in the Hertz horns of some contact mines), the fuse will work indefinitely as long as the wire to the detonator remains intact. [54, 140] Lastly, it is also possible that safety mechanisms that prevented the arming of fuses have corroded and do not perform their intended function anymore [3].

2.2.12 Network of UXO Properties

Based on the UXO properties that are described in the subsections above, it is possible to design a network, as shown in Figure 2.7. From left to right, it depicts which property influences which other property. Each property is shown in a node that is connected to other nodes with edges. The colours of the nodes group the properties. The colour of the edges always originates from the colour of the parent node. The fact that nodes are vertically located above or below each other, thereby giving the impression of columns, has no meaning.

The network shown here contains those properties that are later used in the design of the RA model, which will be at the core of this dissertation. Other properties that were described above are not included (e.g., heat and friction sensitivity). A rationale for the decision on which properties to omit from the model is given in 5.8. Since they are not used in the model later on, they are, to avoid confusion, also not displayed in Figure 2.7. Connections that one may expect to see in this network (e.g., between *Casing Material* and *Condition of Casing*) are not shown here if they depend on environmental properties (e.g., corrosion, see 3.4). They are included in a more advanced version of the model in Figure 3.13. The significance of the node *Shock Factor* was not explained above but is outlined in 2.3.1.

2.3 Potential Effects of the Presence of UXO

The previous sections provided a great deal of background knowledge on the issue of offshore UXO. The description of the properties of UXO already suggests that it has the potential to negatively affect humans and the environment. Understanding these properties is a prerequisite to comprehending the effects. In general, there are two main types of hazards associated with UXO in the marine environment. These are the detonations and the spread of the explosive substances. Both can arise during EOD activities or completely independently.

This section is a general description of the two hazards and their potential negative effects. It focuses on the effects and consequences that may arise if EOD or other means of managing UXO, such as the establishment of restricted zones, do not take place. The review is not a comprehensive description of all the negative consequences for all potentially affected subjects of protection.

2.3.1 Mechanism and Effects of Detonations

A detonation is a chemical reaction of an explosive material that is coupled with the generation of a shock wave. The reaction runs through the material at a velocity that is faster than the speed of sound in water (i.e., 1500 m s^{-1}). [130] When a UXO object detonates under water, numerous effects occur in parallel. These are independent of whether the detonation is intentional (see 3.2.2) or not (see 2.2.9).

FIGURE 2.7: Network of UXO properties.

One major effect is the shock wave. A detonation propagates through the explosive material and transmits into the surrounding medium, in this case, water. Since the detonation is characterised by its extremely fast reaction, it results in a supersonic shock wave. [43] Because water is essentially incompressible, the shock wave can travel over large distances with little loss of energy [155 in 43]. However, the duration of peak pressure is shorter than in air [71].

Another effect is the formation of a gas bubble and a bubble pulse. The detonation results in the production of gas. Since the event takes place under water, the gas forms a bubble, which initially expands. Upon maximum expansion, it propagates energy into the water and creates a bubble pulse, which is an additional, albeit much smaller, pressure wave. This occurs at a slower pace than shock wave creation. [43] Subsequently, the bubble collapses under the pressure of the surrounding water and starts rising to the surface. The lower water depth leads to lower pressure, which allows the bubble to expand again. Numerous expansions and compressions of the bubble may occur, resulting in the formation of several increasingly weaker pressure waves. Once it reaches the surface, the bubble collapses, thereby elevating water into the air and creating the so-called bubble jet. [71]

In addition to the shock wave, a detonation under water and the resulting bubble pulse [156] both form sound waves. They are the strongest anthropogenic point source of noise in the sea. [10]

The magnitude of all of these effects mainly depends on the mass, RE, and detonation velocity [157] of the explosive material. In other words, it depends on the initial energy that is released by the detonation. Another relevant factor is whether an object is buried or not, or whether it is floating in the water column. [71] The severity of the effects also depends on the type of sediment an unburied UXO object is located on. If buried, the covering layer of sediment has a dampening effect on the detonation. When on top of the sediment, the part of the energy that is directed towards the seabed is immediately reflected and returned into the water column. Hard sediments and bedrock maintain the shock wave's velocity. [158] In shallow waters and on rock bottom, much of the energy is directly transmitted upward into the air, which means that less energy remains in the water [159]. The energy is also transmitted into the sediment, resulting in a seismic shock [158].

Whether a detonation has negative consequences for a vessel mainly depends on the distance and angle between the detonation and the vessel. In cases of direct contact, a detonation can lead to severe damage [55]. It is similar to that which would occur if the detonation took place in air and may lead to fragmentation, for example, of a vessel's hull [71]. However, in deeper waters, fragmentation is considered to be of less concern than the other effects of the detonation [54, 71]. The fragmentation of the hull is not to be confused with the fact that UXO itself will fragment during a detonation. Under water, these fragments will quickly lose kinetic energy [51]. In shallow waters, where fragments (as well as gravel) could be catapulted into the air, they have a greater potential to cause harm if no sufficient safety distance is maintained [158].

To determine the potential consequences of the shock wave, it is possible to calculate the shock factor. This is not a physical property of the explosive material but a value that estimates how strongly a vessel or other object in the water is affected, based on the mass and RE of the explosive material, the slant range between the UXO and the vessel, and the depression angle (between vessel and charge) [160]. The larger the shock factor, the higher the expected damage.

A detonation underneath a vessel's hull can lead to great destruction due to the pressure from the bubble pulse [55] and the bubble jet. Hull damage is problematic since it may cause the compartments of a ship to fill with water. [71] Furthermore, the vessel may be lifted and fall back on the water surface, leading to additional damage [54]. If the vessel is not right above the detonation, it may still be impacted by the shock wave. A large enough detonation and thus shock wave will cause the entire ship to shake, which can lead to many small leaks in the ship's hull and the dislodging of structures from the vessel. [71] If the detonation occurs below the vessel, these effects will occur in combination with the damage from the bubble pulse [54].

Due to the shock wave, divers may be killed instantly or suffer injuries [71]. Depending on the distance, equipment such as a remotely operated underwater vehicle (ROV) or an autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) at the surface or in the water column would be affected by detonations as well. Detonations of less than 10 kg are considered to have only a small effect at the surface when occurring at more than 10 m water depth. Even for equipment and personnel under water, only local damages are expected to occur in such situations. [155 in 43].

The detonation of UXO can affect every industry branch that is working at sea. This is mostly applicable to those actors that are interacting with the seabed and may accidentally detonate an object, such as fisheries [3] and dredgers [161]. A detonation may also take place aboard a vessel, if UXO is accidentally lifted aboard [51]. Less frequently mentioned sectors are military bases and different forms of resource exploitation, which may include sea mining [154].

Underwater detonations can also have severe effects on marine fauna, especially marine mammals. Effects of the pressure wave include haemorrhages, physical injuries to the ear, and air or fat embolisms that result from damage to the gas-containing organs (such as the lungs and the gastrointestinal tract) or the acoustic jaw fats, respectively. [10] In addition, marine mammals may be affected by the noise, i.e., the sound wave, which can lead to permanent or temporary hearing loss or deterioration [162]. Unsurprisingly, pressure waves from detonations may also be lethal or harmful to aquatic birds [163], fish [164], eggs, larvae [156], and invertebrates [165]. Fish and sea turtles may also be affected by the noise of the detonation [156]. In addition, a detonation can mobilise sediment [166], which can have adverse environmental effects when the sediment is contaminated [167].

Detonations can also affect underwater infrastructure. This is not limited to the pressure wave that runs through the water column. The seismic shock in the ground can cause damage as well. In general, pipelines are considered to be more vulnerable than cables. [158]

2.3.2 Spread and Effects of Explosive Compounds

Subsection 2.2.5 mentioned that UXO casings have been reported in all sorts of conditions, ranging from very intact to severely corroded, i.e., breached. From the moment the explosive material interfaces with the surrounding water, it can be distributed if the compounds are soluble in salt water. The solubility depends on various factors, such as the

type of compound [17], the exposed surface area, and environmental factors such as current velocity and water mixing [168 in 17]. Consequently, explosive materials such as TNT and its metabolites were detected throughout the German Baltic Sea and in sediments from UXO dump sites [21].

The spread of explosive materials can also occur without corrosion. Firstly, some explosive materials were dumped without a casing [70]. This has become evident at the German dump site Kolberger Heide, where a dumped pile of UXO is intermixed with large chunks of loose, unencased explosive material [68]. It is extremely unlikely that this large amount of material was exposed due to corrosion. Secondly, detonations or other modes of in situ destruction (see 3.3.3) can result in an incomplete reaction of the explosive material. This can lead to the spread of solid-phase particles of explosive compounds in the nearby water column and sediment [132, 169]. It can also mean that chunks of explosives remain openly on the seabed [170]. In both cases, the material is likely to be dissolved in the water.

Once dissolved or lying openly on the seabed, explosive compounds are available for uptake by marine biota. TNT, its metabolites, RDX, and High-Molecular-weight rdX (HMX), also called Octogen, can accumulate in fish dab [171]. The former two were also detected in the fillet [172]. The same is true for blue mussels. In specimens that were placed immediately next to loose chunks of explosive material, concentrations were so high that the mussels were not fit for human consumption. [9] Birds may also feed on mussels and, therefore, take up explosive compounds. Marine mammals, as top predators, may consume contaminated prey, leading to the biomagnification of explosive compounds. However, knowledge on this matter is sparse. [70]

Explosive compounds have various adverse effects on receptors that are exposed to them. Inter alia, it was found that TNT and its metabolites are genotoxic for fish [173]. A prevalence of liver tumours was detected in flatfish in the vicinity of a dump site [171]. For birds, TNT exposure can be lethal and has numerous sub-lethal effects, such as weight loss and tremors. It can also negatively affect their digestive and central nervous systems. [174] So far, there is no evidence that hazardous amounts of explosive compounds from UXO have reached human seafood. Nevertheless, it is important to be aware that, for example, TNT is classified as suspected to be carcinogenic to humans in Germany [175]. It has furthermore been found to be mutagenic [176]. Other explosive compounds may have other consequences. An additional scenario of humans unsuspectingly interacting with explosive compounds is that, similar to entire UXO objects (see 2.1.3), they can be mobilised and washed ashore. Chunks of explosives may be confused with different stones (such as pyrite and marcasite), fossils, and flotsam [177]. In such cases, direct contact with skin and eyes may occur, and children may ingest the substances, which may induce numerous other health effects and can even be lethal [106].

2.4 Conclusion—The Case for Explosive Ordnance Disposal

Chapter 2 provides the reader with a great deal of background knowledge on the issue of UXO in the German Seas. The large amount of relevant information has made it necessary to start scoping, especially in terms of the historical and geographic contexts that are discussed throughout the remainder of this study. Chapter 2 subsequently describes UXO properties, many of which indicate how hazardous an object's presence is and how challenging its handling during EOD is. Based on these descriptions, it was possible to develop a network of UXO properties that helps understand their interconnectedness. Finally, Chapter 2 describes the potential effects of UXO. It is this final section (2.3) that serves as the basis for the main conclusion of this chapter, which is provided below.

Given the negative effects of the presence of UXO, it is undeniable that, under certain circumstances, EOD is a necessary activity. UXO detonations can lead to dire consequences in the case of accidents, and the leakage of substances causes contamination of the marine environment. It is not the purpose of this dissertation to assess the severity of these effects beyond the description in 2.3, but their existence is indisputable. Both of these effects can also occur during EOD (see 5.3), which is a high-cost and high-risk activity [42]. However, EOD takes place under somewhat controlled circumstances, which sets it apart from detonation accidents and current- and corrosion-induced leakage. Deciding under which circumstances EOD is required is the topic of debates that accompany offshore construction projects. The vast and rapid construction of offshore wind parks in the German EEZ [178], will be a driver for EOD in the upcoming years. Debates on when, where, and how to conduct EOD are furthermore inevitable for the aspired treatment of German dump sites since EOD is the only way to actually solve the UXO problem [42] and eliminate the hazards. A recent initiative to conduct a feasibility study and initiate an immediate action programme to deal with UXO dump sites in the Baltic Sea demonstrates the political will to approach the issue on a greater scale [14].

H_i: UXO requires handling by specialists who execute a professional EOD workflow.

With these developments in mind, more EOD work than ever before is expected to take place in the upcoming years. Handling more UXO increases the chance of accidents and the materialisation of negative effects. Conducting this work professionally and diligently is of paramount importance. Hence, *H_i* can be accepted. It is, therefore, necessary to understand how EOD is conducted and under what circumstances it takes place. Chapter 3 informs about these issues and identifies future requirements.

Chapter 3

Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal

Chapter 2 proved that UXO requires handling by a professionally executed EOD workflow. This chapter, therefore, investigates EOD in detail. First of all, it describes and juxtaposes six EOD frameworks and identifies one that offers the most comprehensive insights into the EOD procedure for further use throughout this dissertation. It then describes the organisational concepts of EOD as provided in the selected framework. This description identifies the aspects of handling UXO that will be the scope of this study. Furthermore, it investigates and characterises EOD in the study area and the technical and methodological approaches that are commonly used to perform it. Finally, the chapter explores the context in which EOD takes place, i.e., the properties of the marine environment.

3.1 EOD frameworks

There have been numerous attempts at structuring the EOD procedure within an organised framework that supports practitioners. This section provides information on available EOD frameworks. To avoid defining a new procedural framework for EOD in this dissertation, this subsection identifies a pre-existing one to support this study. This review includes frameworks from those sources that were readily available at the time of research and is not conclusive in terms of the number of existing frameworks. No inquiries were made to authorities or to companies offering EOD as a service as to whether they have developed their own framework or which one they prefer to use internally. This exercise aims to determine which of the individual processes of EOD are concerned with the actual handling of UXO and therefore pose the greatest risk. This way, the subsection clarifies which processes have to be completed and, thus, which information needs to be available by the time immediate interaction with UXO occurs.

Procedural frameworks that were generated for onshore EOD or that are mainly concerned with the EOD of UXO containing CWAs were not considered in the review. The first subsection presents a total of six available frameworks. One such framework is selected for continued use in the scope of this study, and the selection rationale is presented.

It is assumed that the contexts in which these frameworks were developed vary. Thus, the selection does not constitute a judgement regarding the quality of the frameworks. It merely means that the selected one is most fitting for this study. A description of the content of the selected framework is presented in the subsequent section (3.2).

3.1.1 Overview of Available Procedural Frameworks

This subsection contains a comparative description of six different EOD frameworks. It is supported by Figure 3.1, in which these frameworks are labelled Framework 1 through 6. In the text, these are abbreviated hereafter as F1 through F6. After the comparison, this subsection selects F1 as the framework of reference.

Two main publications that organise the EOD procedure were developed in an integrative manner, taking into account the expertise of professionals from potentially affected actors. These are the *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* with its ‘Phases of offshore EOD’ (Framework 1 (F1)) [23] and a document called *Assessment and management of unexploded ordnance (UXO) risk in the marine environment* with its ‘Phases of the UXO risk management framework’ (F2) [46]. These are the most comprehensive documents on the subject of EOD.

Method statements and project reports are prepared before or after the execution of EOD projects. They are another type of document that organises the EOD procedure. One example is a report on how to perform EOD that was released by pipeline operator Nord Stream AG as part of the Environmental Impact Assessment of the construction of the pipeline Nord Stream 1. The procedure described in the document is mainly concerned with the historical survey and the technical survey, both with the aim of detecting the location of UXO. Thus, it is appropriately dubbed the ‘survey strategy’ (F3). [50] Another document presents a desk study on the Borssele wind farm zone, a different framework that is labelled the ‘UXO risk management phases’ (F4) [51].

Frameworks for the EOD procedure are also presented by businesses that offer consulting and other services for the planning and execution of EOD. Two of these are briefly introduced here. The UXO risk management and EOD company 6 Alpha Associates Ltd. labels their procedure ‘UXO risk management’ (F5). [55] Finally, the ‘risk management framework’ for marine-based projects is applied by Ordtek Ltd. (F6) [179].

From this brief description, it becomes apparent that the frameworks vary greatly in terms of the contexts in which they were developed. Accordingly, they also vary in scope and scale. F3, F4, F5, and F6 are not accompanied by an insightful descriptive text. This is justified by very different reasons. When F3 was released, the EOD procedure was still in planning, and for F4, the framework was just supporting information contextualising the content of a report. In the cases of F5 and F6, the frameworks’ underlying information is part of the intellectual property of the publishers, which they may be reluctant to share.

After the analysis that is given in the following two subsections had been finalised, other frameworks came to the attention of the author (e.g. [180]). Subsequent chapters in this dissertation rely on decisions that are made in this section. Therefore, it was not possible to return to the section and perform a reassessment by adding additional frameworks.

3.1.2 The Frameworks and Their Phases

To select one of the existing EOD framework for the way forward, a comparison is warranted. Figure 3.1 is a comparative graph of the identified EOD frameworks. At the top of the figure, they are numbered consecutively Framework 1 through 6, as introduced in 3.1.1. Below, in the grey box, the names of the frameworks are presented, as they are labelled in the respective documents. In the large white box labelled ‘Processes in phases’ below, the procedures are shown as they are presented in the references. The smaller boxes inside the large white one each represent one work step, and they are numbered for each framework individually. Disregarding their labelling in the source documents, these are henceforth referred to as ‘phases’. Numbers in parentheses indicate the number of processes that phases are subdivided into. In the text, these are henceforth abbreviated by the number of their framework in combination with the order number in that framework (e.g., the first phase of Framework 1 is labelled F1P1). For the extent of the box ‘Procedures of frameworks’, the causal progression of phases is displayed vertically, from top to bottom, as the black arrow on the left indicates. The arrow is scaleless, and thus the size of each of the boxes gives no linear indication regarding the extent, effort, or required time of any of these phases. Instead, large boxes indicate that the phase overlaps with several phases of other frameworks. The vertical space between two phases is the transition between phases.

The content of the box ‘Phases in frameworks’, was generated by using F1 as a baseline framework. F2 was added by comparing the phases of F2 to those of F1 and then placing the boxes of both phases according to the correspondence or discrepancy between each other. For the addition of F3, this placement was done in alignment with the F1 and F2 processes, and so forth for the remaining frameworks. This meant that adding new frameworks became increasingly complicated, and diligent comparison between the phases of each of the frameworks was necessary to avoid errors. In a final check, several pairs of two random overlapping or nearly overlapping phases of two different frameworks were chosen and reassessed to double-check that their vertical positioning according to each other was correct.

There are, however, some limitations to this kind of figure. As addressed for F3, F4, F5, and F6, there is a lack of detailed information on the exact meaning of each of the phases. For Figure 3.1, the boxes were placed, and their size was determined based on the title and, in the case of F6, very brief descriptions. When the scope of work for phases was not entirely clear, their placement and the determination of their extent were subject to generous interpretation. An example may clarify this situation. F1P2 is initiated by a process called *definition of the measurement methods*. While F2, F3, and F6 address

* These phases were combined in the original references, so it was not possible to identify the transition.
[†] These phases were performed once for the construction site and once for anchor points.
[‡] In reality, this 'phase' would take place instead of F4P4. Since the reference listed it individually, it was included in the figure but is excluded from the discussion.

FIGURE 3.1: Comparison of available EOD frameworks.

the issue of defining methods to find UXO, there is no equivalent action in F4 and F5. It must, however, be assumed that this action is implied in the phases F4P4 and F5P4, as a continuation of EOD work and execution of succeeding work processes would otherwise not be possible. Furthermore, the extent of the phases was determined based the work they start and end with. Phases of one framework that are skipped by another framework are not represented by adding gaps within a phase if the latter overlaps with many phases of the former. There is, for example, no equivalent to F3P6 in any of the other frameworks. However, for reasons of comprehensible presentation, no gap was inserted into the respective

phases of the other frameworks that overlap with F3P6. The consequence of both the generous interpretation and the omission to add gaps within phases leads to a certain fuzziness in the figure.

There are numerous findings to be made from assessing Figure 3.1. It allows comparing the structure of the frameworks. Only rarely are two of the overall 33 phases fully overlapping. These pairs are limited to $F2P3 \cong F6P3$, $F2P4 \cong F3P3/7$ and $F4P2 \cong F5P3$. There are also two incidents in which two or more phases of a framework correspond to one phase of another framework. These are $F4P4 \cong F6P4 \wedge P5 \wedge P6$ and $F4P5 \cong F6P7 \wedge P8$. Finally, it is noteworthy that all frameworks except F5 have a transition between phases at the moment when fieldwork is planned or initiated, which is the transition before F1P2, F2P3, F3P3/7, F4P4, and F6P4. Overall, it can be stated that the frameworks are very different in their structure. The vertical overlap indicates where one phase of a framework covers content of a phase of another framework. These overlaps are completely random throughout the graph, even though the generation of the graph followed an approach by which the addition of new frameworks to the graph was always aligned with those frameworks that had already been entered. This outcome was unexpected and shows that graphs such as Figure 3.1 are a useful tool for comparative studies of procedural frameworks.

Another notable detail is the fact that not all frameworks start and end at the same points at the top and bottom. F1P1 and F6P1+2 start earlier than the initiating phases of the other frameworks. This is because F1P1 and F6P1+2 explicitly consider the surrounding conditions of the EOD. These include, inter alia, the natural environment and the larger project context (such as those of a construction project). For the other frameworks, these are either not explicitly mentioned (F3) or deliberately placed outside the procedural context of EOD (F2, F4, and F5). On the other hand, there are three different points at which the frameworks end. F3 is concluded after a so-called *post detonation survey* during which the success of a clearance operation is investigated. F1 and F5 (disregarding F5P6 in accordance with footnote [‡] in Figure 3.1) conclude with certifications of and reports on the completed EOD work. For more information on these two types of finalising processes, see Figure 3.2. Finally, the remaining frameworks conclude with assessments of residual risk (for a definition, see 5.4) that may remain after EOD (F2), monitoring activities (F4), or both (F6). In summary, while the structures of EOD procedures vary greatly, there is some agreement on how to initiate and conclude them.

Next, it is reasonable to address the transitions along the frameworks, i.e., the spaces between two consecutive phases. An example of the standard space is the transition between F1P2 and F1P3. All gaps larger than the standard space are noteworthy. This is especially true given that a generous interpretation for the determination of the extent of phases was applied. Like the size of the boxes, the size of the gaps presented is not a linear indication of the lack of content in that framework.

All the gaps are briefly discussed here. There are gaps in all frameworks except F2. In F1, the gap between F1P1 and F1P2 originates from the absence of a phase for the development of a UXO risk management strategy. In the framework, a decision on the need to continue EOD work is taken based on a threat assessment. If continued, risk management

TABLE 3.1: Level of detail of available EOD frameworks.

Structural element	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
No. of phases	4	5	<u>7</u>	5	5	<u>7</u>
No. of phases with processes	4	4	2	1	3	0
No. of phases without processes	0	1	5	4	2	7
No. of processes	30	16	8	5	12	0
Level of Detail*	<u>30</u>	17	13	9	14	7

* The number of phases without processes plus the number of processes.

strategies such as the avoidance of UXO are discussed towards the end of F1P2. There are two gaps in F3. The gap between F3P1 and F3P2 is a consequence of the absence of archive research to gain historic information on UXO for a geographic site. The gap between F3P2 and F3P3 originates from the fact that there are no provisions for an assessment of hazards or risks or the development of a risk management strategy at this stage in the framework. F4 also contains two gaps. The one between F4P1 and F4P2 derives from the absence of an evaluation of prior surveys. Another gap exists between F4P4 and F4P5, which exactly matches the gap between F6P6 and F6P7. Neither F4 nor F6 mention a survey after the execution of clearance efforts. The gap in F5 between F5P5 and F5P6 is disregarded as per footnote † in Figure 3.1. In summary, most of the frameworks contain some gaps. However, Figure 3.1 shows that none of the gaps are directly related to the handling of UXO. Accordingly, the gaps are not considered during the selection of the framework to move forward with.

In Figure 3.1, numbers in brackets that are stated after the names of the phases indicate the number of ‘processes’ that phases are subdivided into. Processes are structural elements of a framework that are hierarchically placed below phases. Of the total 33 phases depicted in Figure 3.1 eleven are further subdivided into processes. Table 3.1 provides an overview of the number of phases and processes of each framework. F3 and F6 are divided into the most phases, with seven each (underlined). F1 is the only framework in which each phase is subdivided into processes, and F6 is the only one in which no further subdivision is present. The overall number of phases and processes in each of the frameworks indicates their respective level of detail. Therefore, the bottom row contains the sum of the number of phases that are not subdivided, which essentially means that they are acting as a phase and a process alike, and the number of processes. This number is labelled ‘level of detail’. With a level of detail of 30, F1 presents by far the highest level of detail in its framework. At the bottom of the spectrum, F4 has a level of detail of 9, and F6 has the lowest level of detail of 7.

The purple boxes in Figure 3.1 are those phases that are relevant for the actual handling of UXO. It can be noted that the phases in question vary greatly in the extent of the framework they cover. The greatest extent is covered by F2P5 and F5P5, while the most narrow focus on UXO clearance is present in F3P9. Even though the relevant phases differ in their overall focus, they overlap vertically, indicating that some of the processes they include must correspond.

Following the above description of the level of detail and based on the findings that were generated thus far, it is possible to exclude F4 and F6 from the continuation of the investigation. The rationale is that the relevant phases, F4P5 and F6P6, are not further subdivided into processes. At the same time, the phases are rather extensive when compared to other frameworks. They are therefore considered too crude for a good understanding of the implications of UXO handling. This is further amplified by a lack of descriptive text, which may have outweighed the low level of detail in the framework. Incidentally, F4 and F6 are also those frameworks with the lowest level of detail, according to Table 3.1.

3.1.3 The Frameworks and Their Processes

In order to move ahead, the remaining frameworks (F1, F2, F3, and F4) are further scrutinised by facilitating a similar comparison as the one described above. Figure 3.2 was developed to compare those phases that are related to UXO handling. These were displayed as purple boxes in Figure 3.1. Figure 3.2 shows them at the top. They contain the names of the phases. Below, the large white box ‘Processes in phases’ contains the sequence of processes as they are described in the original documents. The content of this box was again generated by using F1 as a baseline framework. The other frameworks’ processes were then placed in correspondence. The term ‘process’ is used in disregard of the labelling in the references. In the text, the processes are henceforth abbreviated by the number of their framework in combination with their order number in that framework (e.g., the first process of Framework 1 is labelled F1p1).

Figure 3.2 reveals that the structure of the phases that are relevant to UXO handling is more similar than the overall structure of phases that was compared in 3.1.2. Full overlaps between processes, which indicate identical content, are commonplace. Especially the alignment $F1p1 \cong F3p3 \cong F4p4$ is a remarkable point in the procedures, as the workflow of the three frameworks appears to align at this point. Subsequently, further processes are equivalent to each other ($F1p2 \wedge p3 \wedge p4 \wedge p5 \cong F2p2 \wedge p3 \cong F4p5$). These are the processes during which the actual handling of UXO takes place. F3 does not align, as it does not stipulate any EOD methods other than ‘disposal’, which it describes as detonating an object. The greater structural similarities in the phases when compared to the overall frameworks might be related to the fact that subdividing a larger workflow into phases is more arbitrary than the subdivision and description of concrete work steps, i.e., processes.

Greater differences become noticeable when comparing the starting and end points of the phases. This is not surprising when comparing the unaligned phases in Figure 3.1. F2 and F4 are considerably less focused on the handling of UXO itself than F1 and F3. The former start at earlier points in the EOD procedure and have a wider scope, which overlaps with numerous phases of the latter. Both F2 and F4 include the technical survey, that is, the work that aims at detecting UXO, in the phases presented in Figure 3.2. F1 and F3, on the other hand, only begin when this detection has been finalised and the investigation of individual objects is initiated. The end points of the phases also vary greatly. In F1, F2, and F3, the phases presented here are the final ones. In F4, an additional

FIGURE 3.2: Comparison of relevant UXO handling phases.

phase follows. It is therefore plausible that F4p4 ends at an earlier point than the other frameworks' phases. Particularly, F1 and F2 describe numerous, predominantly administrative processes after the actual handling of UXO is completed.

Processes that deal with the handling of UXO under water are highlighted in green. Gaps between processes other than the highlighted ones are not relevant for this assessment. The only gaps that concern the highlighted processes exist between F3p3 and F3p4 as well as between F3p4 and F3p5. They originate in the framework's disregard for EOD methods other than detonations. The framework was released in 2009, while the others were all released at least five years later. This may be a reason why differentiation between different EOD methods is not included in F3. The framework is therefore not fit for further use in this study. Of the remaining ones, the reference that presents F4 does not include a comprehensive description of the processes. Therefore, it is also regarded as unfit. Finally, the comparison between F1 and F2 shows that the former offers a slightly higher level of granularity in terms of the processes that concern the handling of UXO. F1 was therefore selected as the framework of reference to support and inform the remainder of this study.

3.2 EOD procedure According to the Selected Framework

In 3.1.3, it was established that the EOD framework F1 provided in the *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* [23] will be utilised as a frame of reference throughout this dissertation. It serves as the principal source for this section and all of its subsections. The quality guideline was developed by the author of this dissertation as part of the research project 'Robotic underwater salvage and disposal process including technology for dismantling ammunition in the sea' (German: 'Robotisches Unterwasser-Bergungs- und Entsorgungsverfahren inklusive Technik zur Delaborierung von M_unition im M_eer') (RoBEMM). It is possible that individual process steps or details are handled differently from the description given in the quality guideline during real-world EOD clearance. However, as the document is the result of an extensive stakeholder process (see Appendix 1), it is regarded as sufficiently representative of how EOD should be conducted.

To further understand how EOD is executed, the framework is described in this section. For a description of the generation of the framework, the reader is referred to Appendix 1. In this section, the overall content of the framework is outlined first. The subsequent subsection describes the relevant processes of phase F1P4 *clearance and disposal* in more detail. The final subsection further underlines the complexity of EOD by describing relevant actors and personnel resources in the study area (see 2.1.3).

3.2.1 Content Overview of the Quality Guideline

This subsection provides an overview of the content of the quality guideline. The *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* is composed of six chapters: a general chapter, one chapter each for the four phases of EOD, and a chapter defining and describing quality factors.

The first and general chapter establishes the background and purpose of the document. Even though it can in principle be applied to the work at dump sites, it was originally developed for the EOD campaigns in preparation of offshore projects such as wind park construction, cable laying, or dredging. The first chapter also establishes that the EOD procedure is subdivided into four phases. It further determines the geographical scope of the document, which coincides with the study area of this dissertation (see 2.1.3). The general chapter also includes sections with definitions of technical terms and a non-exhaustive list of applicable legal documents, standards, and other guidelines. The penultimate section of the first chapter introduces the actors involved in EOD. For each actor, the section describes their role during EOD, the competencies they are required to have, the verification documents they must have readily available, and the personnel they must employ. Actors who are relevant for this study are introduced in 3.2.3. The final section covers the requirements for the personnel that are employed by those actors. The personnel who are relevant for this study are introduced in 3.2.4.

Next, the four phases of EOD are described in one chapter each. Each phase is further broken down into processes.

- Phase I: Preliminary survey (5 processes)
- Phase II: Technical survey (8 processes)
- Phase III: Investigation of target points (9 processes)
- Phase IV: Clearance and disposal (8 processes)

While phases I and II address the entire area that is surveyed during the EOD procedure, phases III and IV have a more narrow spatial focus. They address individual target points where UXO may be present in the study area. Phases I, II, and III are briefly introduced here without addressing the specificities of their individual processes.

Phase I covers the preliminary survey, which is desk research on the area in which EOD shall be executed. This includes the definition of the coordinates of the survey area. The location and size of the area are determined by the purpose of the EOD campaign. It may be performed as part of an offshore construction project, for reasons of hazard prevention, or to reduce environmental burdens. Phase I is executed to generate a threat assessment for the area. If this threat assessment concludes that additional measures have to be executed, recommendations for the subsequent phases are given; if not, the EOD workflow ends after this phase. However, due to the heavy contamination of German waters with UXO, this is very unlikely. During phase I, five processes are executed.

- General site description
- Documentation of the site conditions
- Historical survey
- Threat assessment
- Creation of the final report on the preliminary survey

If the conclusion of phase I is that additional EOD measures are necessary, phase II, the technical survey, commences. The first aim of phase II is to find out if and where target points exist in the area of interest. For this purpose, a list of these points, i.e., a tar-

get list, is generated. The phase's second aim is to sign off all target-free sections of the survey area as safe, considering the limitations of the sensors used during the technical survey. This survey is executed by using geophysical and hydroacoustic methods to acquire field data. All available survey methods have advantages and disadvantages, and their selection and precise application are based on the results of phase I and the purpose of the EOD campaign. To generate the target list and be able to sign off areas, the data need to be processed and interpreted. It is possible that no target points are identified during phase II. In this case, no further actions are required. Otherwise, the EOD procedure continues. Overall, phase II consists of eight processes.

- Definition of the measurement methods
- Call for tender and contract award for phase II
- Definition of the method statement for phase II
- Survey process
- Data processing
- Data interpretation
- Creation of the final report on the technical survey
- UXO safety sign-off of target-free areas

The first objective of phase III is to investigate the target points one by one and check for the presence of UXO objects. The second objective is to sign off all target points at which no UXO has been found as safe. These are referred to as 'unconfirmed target points'. Like in phase II, the sign-off is limited by the capacity of the used sensors. The investigation is performed with sensors (such as magnetic and electromagnetic systems) and imaging techniques (such as cameras and forward-looking sonar). Phase III is subdivided into nine processes.

- Definition of the technologies
- Call for tender and contract award for phases III and IV
- Definition of the method statement for phases III and IV
- As-found survey
- Object uncovering
- Object identification
- Debris removal
- As-left survey of phase III
- UXO safety sign-off of the unconfirmed target point

The initial three processes of phase III also apply to phase IV. They apply to all target points in the area of interest, while the subsequent processes deal with individual target points. These processes are not directly linked to the handling of UXO. The process *object uncovering* only takes place if the object is fully or partially buried. The result of the process *object identification* determines which processes follow. If no UXO object is found, the consecutively listed processes are executed. If one or more UXO objects are discovered, the EOD procedure continues with phase IV. Since it concerns the actual handling of UXO, the following subsection introduces the final phase in more detail.

3.2.2 Overview of Phase IV: Clearance and Disposal

Phase IV of the quality guideline covers the clearance and disposal of UXO. The phase aims to sign off all target points in the study area, at which UXO has been found during phase III, as safe. Phase IV consists of eight processes, which are listed and described in more detail below. Figure 3.3 displays the workflow of phase IV with its processes and decision points according to the quality guideline. The figure addresses the fact that all processes from *UXO identification* to *UXO safety sign-off of the cleared target point* concern an individual target point, while the processes *storage and transport* and *creation of the final report on EOD* concern all target points in the area of interest.

- UXO identification
- Underwater transfer
- In situ destruction
- Recovery
- As-left survey of phase IV
- UXO safety sign-off of the cleared target point
- Storage and transport
- Creation of the final report on EOD

Phase IV is initiated by the process of *UXO identification*. This process aims to determine whether a UXO object is safe to handle, safe to transport, or neither. For this purpose, the UXO object is investigated and characterised. During this characterisation, numerous properties of the UXO object are documented (see 3.3.2). These properties determine how phase IV continues. Depending on the characterisation of the UXO object, different steps toward its clearance are taken. If the UXO object is safe to handle and safe to transport, *recovery* takes place. If the UXO object is not safe to handle, *in situ destruction* is executed. If the UXO object is safe to handle but not safe to transport, the next process depends on whether a transfer of the UXO object is necessary. If not, the UXO object is destroyed in situ. However, if it is necessary to relocate the UXO object, *underwater transfer* takes place, followed by destruction in situ.

These three processes are those during which the handling and proper clearance work of UXO take place. They are thus the ‘key processes’ that are the scope of this dissertation. In Figure 3.3 they are highlighted in green. Technical and methodological options for performing these processes are described in 3.3. The process *storage and transport* also involves the handling of UXO. It is, however, not within the scope of this study since the handling of UXO aboard a ship is akin to the handling of UXO onshore.

The key process *underwater transfer* deals with the relocation of UXO, if warranted. According to the quality guideline, there may be three reasons why the *underwater transfer* is necessary, all of which take place in preparation for *in situ destruction*.

1. It is planned to detonate several UXO objects at once. These must therefore be transferred to the same location.
2. For reasons of species or environmental protection, the detonation is to be carried out on a mudflat bar, i.e., in air, during low tide.

3. It is not possible to execute *in situ destruction* at the target point because the anticipated consequences (see 2.3.1) are considered unacceptable.

While the quality guideline acknowledges that scenarios exist in which UXO is not completely cleared, it does not further specify these. *Underwater transfer* of UXO may take place to remove it from an area of interest. In this case, EOD ends with the *underwater transfer*. The rationale can be to leave the UXO at a location where it can remain until more sophisticated EOD technologies are available, which may make the *recovery* of items possible that are not currently considered safe to handle and safe to transport [181]. This scenario is not incorporated in Figure 3.3, as it is not described in the quality guideline.

In situ destruction is the key process that deals with the deliberate initiation of the explosive material (most prominently its main charge, see 2.2.6) in the UXO. This process aims to destroy one or several UXO objects that are not safe to transport and thus cannot be recovered. Before the *in situ destruction* itself takes place, a protection concept is prepared and implemented. This concept includes a comprehensive methodological description and schedule of the planned *in situ destruction*, as well as planned measures for the deterrence of wildlife, the deployment of a shock and sound wave-reducing bubble curtain, and the establishment and maintenance of a safety distance. Only after these measures have been carried out successfully is it possible to initiate the explosive material to execute the *in situ destruction*. Afterwards, the success of the operation is verified. If this verification reveals that the UXO object or parts thereof are still not safe to transport, the *in situ destruction* needs to be repeated. In the opposite case, the process was successful and is considered completed.

The key process *recovery* covers the lifting of UXO that is safe to transport aboard a clearance vessel. If the process takes place after the *in situ destruction*, the recovered items are likely remnants of UXO. For ease of reading, the lifted objects are nonetheless always addressed as UXO.

It should be mentioned that some older publications recommend always performing *in situ destruction* [e.g. 182]. In light of the negative effects that each detonation can have on the marine environment (see 2.3), this notion has been largely dismissed.

All UXO that is recovered has to be stored and transported safely so it can be handed over to the competent authority (see 3.2.3). This authority subsequently delivers the UXO to land-based destruction. Transport is not tied to the individual target point and may instead take place at pre-determined intervals or whenever the storage capacity of the dedicated vessel is exhausted.

Once all UXO that has been found at a target point has been removed through *recovery*, *in situ destruction*, or *underwater transfer*, an *as-left survey* is executed. As-left surveys also take place during phase III in cases where objects at target points turn out to be hazard-free debris. The purpose of this process is to either find additional objects that may be UXO or otherwise confirm that no more UXO is present at the target point. If the

FIGURE 3.3: Procedure of phase IV: Clearance and disposal.

as-left survey reveals that another object may be present, the procedure moves back to phase III to potentially uncover and identify it. If no object is found, a clearance report is prepared for the target point.

Next, the *UXO safety sign-off of the cleared target point* is executed. A qualified EOD expert (see 3.2.4) verifies that no more UXO is present at the target point. Similar to phase II, the sign-off certificate acknowledges the limitations of the sensors used during the as-left survey. Once the target point is signed off, the next target point can be investigated. Instead of performing this process for each target point individually, it is possible to sign off several target points at once.

Once all target points have been cleared and all recovered UXO have been transported to their destination, the *creation of the final report on EOD* takes place. This final report covers all measures that took place during phases III and IV. It contains, inter alia, information on the methods applied during all steps of phases III and IV, the documentation of all investigated target points, and cleared UXO. This marks the final process in the quality guideline and therefore concludes the EOD procedure.

3.2.3 Description of Involved Actors

To define the organisations that are involved in carrying out the work of the phases and processes covered in 3.2.1 and 3.2.2, the quality guideline names numerous actors. This subsection includes only those actors that are involved in the key processes: the EOD service provider, the client, the consultant, and relevant authorities.

The EOD service provider performs the great majority of the work that takes place during the key processes. This actor performs the processes of *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. During the *in situ destruction*, they also prepare and implement the protection concept and check whether the detonation was successful. Depending on the arrangement with the client, the EOD service provider may also register the *in situ destruction* with competent authorities beforehand and report about the process afterwards. All these services are executed according to the provisions made in a method statement, which is prepared during phase III. The EOD service provider is required to possess skills in good engineering practice and knowledge of the legal requirements regarding EOD, diving work, underwater work, and relevant aspects of occupational health and safety. To assure their suitability to perform the key processes, the EOD service provider needs to provide several verifications. These comprise functioning safety, quality, and environmental management systems, references from completed offshore EOD projects, and sufficient public liability insurance that covers UXO risks for personal, property, and pecuniary damage. To legally deal with explosive substances in the study area, the EOD service provider furthermore needs permission per § 7 SprengG (see 2.1.4). This provision only applies to the German territorial sea and to ships flying the German flag in the EEZ [183 in 184]. However, the quality guideline recommends demanding this verification when working in the EEZ as well. The quality guideline states that, per Regulation (EC) No 765/2008, equivalent permission can also be obtained from an accredited conformity assessment body in another EU country [185]. Since numerous authorities, including

state bomb disposal teams of the federal states, are exempt from SprengG, the quality guideline implies that EOD service providers are private companies (§ 1a (1) SprengG) [30]. The EOD service provider needs to employ a technical supervisor for EOD and, depending on the applied EOD methods, divers, ROV operators, and operators for other machinery. The next subsection provides descriptions of all of these personnel resources.

All EOD services are commissioned and therefore initiated by a client. The extent of the client's direct involvement in the key processes, and thus the required level of knowledge, depends on whether or not a consulting actor is involved. If this is not the case, the client performs continuous quality control during the *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. Depending on the agreement with the EOD service provider, the client may also conduct registration of and reporting about the *in situ destruction* to competent authorities. If no consulting actor is involved, the client furthermore requires knowledge of good engineering practice, legal requirements in EOD, and relevant aspects of occupational health and safety. The work of the client needs to be managed and coordinated by a sufficiently experienced representative.

If a consultant is involved in the key processes, part or all of the responsibilities and related requirements described in the previous paragraph may be fulfilled by this actor instead of the client. To verify suitability for their role in the key processes, a consultant needs to provide documentation of sufficient public liability insurance that covers UXO risks for personal, property, and pecuniary damage, a functioning quality management system, and references from completed offshore EOD consultancy services. The tasks that are transferred to the consultant need to be coordinated by a representative with a sufficient level of experience and expertise. It should be noted that, while it is possible to involve more than one consultant throughout the EOD procedure and distribute responsibilities among those, this scenario appears impracticable for the key processes unless consultants are distributed among target points.

Finally, numerous authorities need to be involved or informed during the key processes. The authorities that need to be involved are partially determined by the location of the target point in the study area. As was established in 2.1.4, each of the German coastal federal states has state laws and regulations, introducing a state bomb disposal team. Table 3.2 provides an overview of Germany's five coastal federal states and the names of their respective state bomb disposal teams. Bremen was not previously included in the quality guideline and was added here [99]. According to the quality guideline, these authorities may assess the work aboard the clearance vessel during *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. Such monitoring is especially recommended if a previously unknown EOD service provider performs the work or if new technologies are deployed. Independently of this type of supervision, each detonation taking place in the German territorial waters needs to be registered with the responsible body, according to Table 3.2. Furthermore, these authorities need to be notified of all UXO objects that were cleared in the territorial sea of their respective federal states. In their area of jurisdiction, a state bomb disposal team may also take charge of the clearance site during the process *UXO identification* and

TABLE 3.2: German coastal federal states and their state bomb disposal teams.

Federal State	Name of State Bomb Disposal Team (German)	Name of State Bomb Disposal Team (English Translation)
Bremen	Kampfmittelräumdienst	‘Explosive ordnance disposal service’
Hamburg	Kampfmittelräumdienst der Feuerwehr Hamburg	‘Explosive ordnance disposal service of Hamburg fire department’
Lower Saxony	Kampfmittelbeseitigungsdienst	‘Explosive ordnance recovery service’
Mecklenburg–Western Pomerania	Munitionsbergungsdienst	‘Munitions recovery service’
Schleswig-Holstein	Kampfmittelräumdienst	‘Explosive ordnance disposal service’

thus perform the key processes in place of the EOD service provider. In the German EEZ, there is no equivalent authority that may take over the assessment of the work aboard the clearance vessel or even perform EOD work itself.

Before the *in situ destruction* process can take place, the protection concept needs to be submitted to the German Federal ‘Maritime and Hydrographic Agency’ (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH)) for prior assessment. It is sufficient to hand in one holistic protection concept that applies to all sites where the *in situ destruction* is planned. BSH is not responsible for the approval of the *in situ destruction* of UXO, but it works towards the consideration of nature conservation requirements by the client or the EOD service provider. However, it only does so for offshore procedures [186], i.e., wind farm development, offshore-platform construction, and offshore-cable routing [e.g. 187]. It may then review the protection concept, and it may also require revisions and resubmission. In addition, BSH maintains Germany’s national noise register in the North and Baltic Seas. Accordingly, each detonation needs to be registered with BSH in post. Finally, independently of the mode of clearance, the clearance work (or omission thereof) performed with each UXO object must be reported to BSH. If left underwater, UXO may constitute an underwater obstacle and must thus be reported via the dedicated reporting procedure. All this involvement of BSH needs to take place irrespective of the location of UXO in the study area.

The ‘Reporting and Coordinating Centre of the Waterways Police of the German coastal states in the Maritime Safety and Security Centre’ (German: Leitstelle der Wasserschutzpolizeien der Küstenländer im Maritimen Sicherheitszentrum) operates a central office for the reporting of offshore UXO in the entire study area. *In situ destruction* needs to be reported to this authority in advance. Information on the clearance operation of every UXO object needs to be reported to the office as well.

Lastly, whenever the process *in situ destruction* is executed, the bodies listed by the Electronic Waterway Information Service of the ‘Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration’ (German: Wasser- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes) [188] need

to be informed in advance for the waters under their jurisdiction. This is necessary for the publication of a notice to mariners, providing them with key information on pending detonations.

3.2.4 Description of Involved Personnel

The descriptions of the EOD service provider, the client, and the consultant in 3.2.3 mentioned specific personnel that they are required to employ. The roles described in the quality guideline only cover a fraction of the personnel in the actors' organisations. Others are, however, not immediately related to EOD. For most roles, the quality guideline focuses on the personnel managing the work or bearing responsibility for proper execution. These managing individuals may be supported by additional employees. While it recommends keeping personnel turnover to a minimum, the quality guideline acknowledges that, in the context of the overall EOD procedure, each role may be filled by several individuals. It is thus possible that assigned people change between processes or target points. It is, however, impractical to perform such a change during a process.

This subsection describes the roles of personnel directly involved in the key processes. These are required to be present on the clearance vessel at the clearance site. All of the following roles concern non-nautical personnel, which means that they do not operate the clearance vessel. Nevertheless, they need to verify their physical and mental capability for offshore work. Furthermore, a sufficient number of first responders need to be aboard the vessel at any given point in time. The roles and their minimum requirements are briefly introduced here.

The central role during the key processes is that of the technical supervisor for EOD. This person supervises all work during phase IV, including the key processes. At least one technical supervisor for EOD must be appointed at the clearance site per § 19 and § 21 SprengG. Each technical supervisor for EOD needs to hold a certificate of competence per § 20 SprengG and have at least three years of practical experience in dealing with offshore UXO.

Operators for machines that are used during the key processes (the quality guideline specifies cranes, excavators, and excavator pumps) need to participate in an educational programme on the fundamentals of EOD, the threats originating from UXO, and relevant safety regulations for 16 hours before they can be employed during EOD. Furthermore, they must hold operating licences for the machines they are handling. If ROVs are deployed, they are operated by an ROV pilot, who must have completed a relevant course for qualification.

Divers are only employed if site conditions do not allow carrying out work by deploying an ROV or other means (see 3.3.2). They need to provide a professional diving certification. Just like the technical supervisor for EOD, they must hold a certificate of competence § 20 SprengG and have a minimum of three years of practical experience in offshore EOD.

Depending on the degree of involvement of consultants during the key processes, either a competent representative of the client or the consultant needs to be involved. Independently from the affiliation, this representative is required to have a minimum of five years of professional experience in the offshore sector and be in possession of an academic degree that is relevant to the work.

3.3 EOD in Practice

So far, the reader has been made aware of the issue of offshore UXO (Chapter 2) and of the EOD procedure that can be used to approach this challenge (3.2). As a next step, this section explores EOD from a more technical perspective. Initially, it provides an overview of EOD activities in German waters. Secondly, it describes decision-making in preparation for and during the three key processes *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. Lastly, it introduces the technologies and approaches that can be used to execute all or either of the key processes.

3.3.1 EOD in German Waters

In German waters, i.e., the study area (see 2.1.3), EOD constitutes a very regular activity. It is, therefore, possible to analyse which key processes are executed, or, in more general terms, what happens to UXO when it is encountered. To do so, both publicly available information and the EOD dataset (see 2.2) are reviewed.

Table 3.3 shows an overview of EOD operations that took place in the study area for years 2013 through 2018. The numbers were released in a series of annual reports on the developments and progress regarding the issue of UXO in German waters [189, 190, 191, 192, 193, 194]. The numbers in these publications are based on the mandatory notifications that were submitted to the Reporting and Coordinating Centre of the German Waterways Police of the German coastal states in the Maritime Safety and Security Centre (see 3.2.3). The original lists also included some UXO that was encountered on beaches. These were removed for Table 3.3. In column 2, the table shows the number of objects for each year, which is not equal to the number of EOD operations listed in the remaining columns. On top of the key processes, they contain additional options. The combination of *under water transfer* and *in situ destruction* contains cases in which both processes were executed. Therefore, it is not the sum of both processes individually. There were no cases during which *under water transfer* was combined with *recovery*. The table also contains the column ‘Remains in Place’. This demonstrates that the option to not treat UXO exists, even though it is chosen very rarely. Operations that are ‘In Progress’, were not solved by the time the numbers were prepared for the respective report. Hence, they are likely included in the following years in another column. The ‘Other’ column includes cases such as UXO that was only investigated without an indication of subsequent steps. The upper half of Table 3.3 shows absolute numbers of operations, and the lower half shows relative contributions of processes. Therefore, no number of objects is included in the lower half.

TABLE 3.3: Annual overview of notifications on UXO and EOD to the Maritime Safety and Security Centre for the years 2013-2018 [189, 190, 191, 192, 193, 194].

Year	No. of Objects	<i>Underwater</i>	<i>In Situ</i>	<i>Underwater Transfer</i>	<i>Recovery</i>	Remains in Place	In Progress	Other	Sum	
		<i>Transfer</i>	<i>Destruction</i>	and <i>In Situ</i> <i>Destruction</i>						
No. of EOD Operations										
2013	101	4	8	0	11	1	2	4	30	
2014	5390	8	35	7	41	0	18	0	109	
2015	8098	30	72	2	75	5	22	0	206	
2016	660	7	23	46	103	0	73	1	254	
2017	2429	4	22	0	114	5	9	3	155	
2018	3755	1	22	7	240	0	89	1	360	
All	20 433	54	182	62	582	11	213	9		
EOD Operations (% of annual total)*										
2013		13	27	0	37	3	7	13	100	
2014		7	32	6	38	0	17	0	100	
2015		15	35	1	36	2	11	0	100	
2016		3	9	18	41	0	29	0	100	
2017		3	14	0	72	3	6	2	100	
2018		0	6	2	67	0	25	0	100	
All		5	16	6	52	1	19	1	100	

* Rounded to integers.

Before the data are discussed, some limitations must be addressed. The report from 2012 included reported numbers as well. However, in that year, the notification procedure was tested, which means that the numbers are incomplete [195]. It was decided not to include these here. Each of the subsequent reports contains a list of all EOD activities that were submitted for the respective year. However, the table in the 2013 issue only lists 32 activities, while the report states that 148 notifications were received. In the years thereafter, the reported numbers of notifications fit the respective lists, which indicates that the report's authors were still working on a sensible and comprehensive publication for 2013. This is also indicated by the steep increase in handled objects from 2013 to 2014. In addition, the 2014 report contains 16 operations with dates from earlier years. Furthermore, the decision on what constitutes an individual notification appears to vary throughout the years. Especially in 2016, many artillery shells were reported individually, for which *recovery* took place on the same day in the same geographic area. In other reports, such clusters were often treated as a single operation. The numbers for 2016 may therefore be overestimated. As stated above, some operations were removed due to them being UXO on beaches. For the years 2013 and 2014, this removal could not be connected to the number of objects since the list did not contain information on the number of objects per operation. This information was only introduced in 2015. The number of objects for 2013 and 2014 is thus likely too high. Finally, while the publication of reports ceased after 2018, the notification procedure to the Maritime Safety and Security Centre remains in place.

Nevertheless, the content of Table 3.3 is insightful. Firstly, it can be noticed that the number of overall EOD operations increases over time. Initially, this may have been due to the establishment of the notification process. In later years, the technological progress of technical survey methods or the more rigorous execution of such surveys could be an explanation. A general increase in offshore activity is another option. It is also remarkable that the number of objects does not correlate with the number of operations. The decision during EOD commonly seems to be taken for a cluster of objects. Either all or most of them are deemed 'safe to transport' and thus *recovery* takes place, or not, which means that *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, or both are executed.

The lower half of the table shows that the execution of *in situ destruction* declined. In the first four years, it constituted one-quarter to one-third of operations, in the last two years, a maximum of 14% is not surpassed. At the same time, the number of *recovery* operations increased from below 40% in the first three years to over two-thirds in 2017 and 2018. In 2016, there was a peak of operations that involved *underwater transfer* and subsequent *in situ destruction*. A look at the individual operations in the respective report reveals that this was a project-specific procedure for a particular cable route [192]. Leaving objects in place has been extremely rare throughout the years. The share of operations that remained in progress was very volatile throughout the years. It was higher in years with an overall high number of operations. This could indicate that some bottleneck exists, which becomes apparent in years with high EOD activity. Insufficient personnel at EOD companies or the lack of capacity at authorities to process requests may be such bottlenecks. In summary, all three key processes are regularly conducted in German waters.

TABLE 3.4: EOD operations and mean values of selected UXO properties of objects in the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

EOD Process	EOD Objects		Mean (\bar{x}) of UXO Properties*		
	Absolute	Relative (%) [*]	UXO Mass (kg)	Charge Mass (kg)	UXO Longest Dimension (mm)
<i>Underwater Transfer</i>	16	7	272	88	987
<i>In Situ Destruction</i>	46	21	291	134	1245
<i>Recovery</i>	133	60	67	20	797
Remains in Place	3	1	-	150	-
No process	23	10	-	106	283
All	221	100	125	112	870

* Rounded to integers.

Of the five state bomb disposal teams of the coastal federal states (see 3.2.3) only Lower Saxony publishes numbers on offshore UXO. The authority reports on the tonnage of UXO detected, supposedly in its own territorial waters. Numbers were first gathered for 2014. They fluctuate between 0.76 t in 2019 and 9.27 t in 2016. There is no indication of the operations that were executed to deal with the UXO. [196]

The EOD dataset that was introduced in 2.2 provides additional information on EOD in the study area. For this purpose, all EOD objects that were located in the study area were deleted from the dataset, leaving a subset of 221 objects. Subsequently, Table 3.4 was produced. It shows the EOD processes in column 1 and the absolute and relative number of EOD objects that were treated with these processes in columns 2 and 3, respectively. In columns 4, 5, and 6, the table contains the mean (\bar{x}) values of weight, charge weight, and longest dimension of the UXO objects. As described in 2.2.3, only rarely were all three dimensions entered into the table. The largest of the available dimensions was used for this table. Note that only rarely was information for all of columns 2 through 6 available for an EOD object. For example, of the 133 recovered objects, UXO mass was only entered for 77, charge mass for 9, and a dimension for 90. The statistical representativeness of the \bar{x} values is limited. One line contains information on objects for which no process was executed. It is not clear why these exist in the dataset. Potentially, the information was not included in the original project documentation, or EOD was conducted by an actor other than the data provider. Since all data originated from finalised projects, these are likely not objects for which the decision on how to handle them continues to be in progress.

Table 3.4 can be used to get a general idea of the EOD processes that were conducted for the EOD objects in the dataset. First and foremost, the distribution of EOD operations among the key processes is roughly in line with the shares shown for the entire study area in Table 3.3. *Recovery* makes up the largest portion of operations, followed by *in situ destruction* and *underwater transfer*. Another important piece of information in Table 3.4 is that on average, objects for which *in situ destruction* was executed are heavier (both in total and in terms of the explosive charge) and larger than objects that were transferred under

water. The latter were, in turn, heavier and larger than the objects that were recovered. This is an indication that the size and weight of objects are important information when considering whether to bring them aboard a clearance vessel and transport them to the shore.

In summary, this subsection showed that all three key processes are regularly conducted in the study area. There appears to be a trend to recover objects more often than was the case in earlier years, while reducing the share of *in situ destruction* processes. At the same time, larger and heavier objects are detonated more commonly than smaller and lighter objects. It is not clear whether the number of small objects increased over the years (and with them the share of *recovery* operations) or whether an overall gradual shift in the selected key processes took place.

3.3.2 Decision Making in Preparation of the Key Processes

The previous subsections presented the share of EOD operations in the study that the key processes make up. It also showed what kind of objects they were executed for. With all this knowledge in mind, it is necessary to understand how decision-making during EOD takes place, which leads to the key processes being executed.

The decision-making process on which of the key processes to perform and how to do so strongly depends on the result of the phase IV process *UXO identification*. During this process, the UXO object is scrutinised, and if possible, certain UXO parameters that are relevant to the EOD decision are examined and documented. These include factors such as the object's mass, dimensions, type of explosive material, and fuse, as well as the state of the object and its fuse [23]. All of these were addressed in 2.2. Some environmental conditions, such as the water depth and the burial state of the object, are also considered [197]. The investigation and identification culminate in a decision, which leads to one of three results.

- The UXO is safe to transport.
- The UXO is safe to handle.
- The UXO is not safe to handle.

The terms 'safe to transport' and 'safe to handle' are defined as decision outcomes by the technical supervisor for EOD [198]. What exactly each of these statuses implies is not clear, even though the terms are used in pertinent rules and regulations [e.g. 32]. The continuation of the EOD workflow and the execution of the key processes depend on the status that is assigned to a UXO object (see Figure 3.3) [23]. Given the great importance of the decision, it is remarkable that no clear definition of 'safe to transport' or 'safe to handle' exists.

According to the EOD framework, *UXO identification* is always part of the EOD procedure with all its four phases. Therefore, once the identification takes place, a great deal of information that was gathered throughout the previous phases is available. During the phase I process *threat assessment*, the hazards and risks to all potentially affected subjects of protection (including future use of the area) are assessed and described [23]. A subject

of protection is something that shall be protected from harm due to its intrinsic or material value [199]. These results are therefore relevant information for decision-making in preparation of the key processes, especially regarding the question of whether *underwater transfer* is necessary.

Larger EOD campaigns are currently exclusively conducted in connection with offshore projects. In opposition to such planned EOD campaigns, it is also possible that an object is accidentally encountered. This is only briefly addressed by the EOD framework. In such cases, additional factors are included to determine how to proceed. Similar to the *threat assessment*, the risk for all potentially affected subjects of protection must be assessed as part of the *UXO identification*. If a subject of protection is immediately threatened by the existence of a UXO object, the decision on how to deal with the object may differ from a situation in which the same object is located far away from any human activity. This shows that urgency or acuteness play a role in decision-making as well. [197] Considering the planned extension of German offshore wind parks and the possible initiation of EOD efforts in dump sites (see 2.4), the relative share of this type of accidental encounter, with its requirement for ad-hoc decision-making, will shrink in the future. It is therefore not considered to be a representative case of regular EOD and will not be taken into account throughout the remainder of this study.

Decision-making is not limited to the selection of the key processes but also concerns the methods and tools that shall be used to conduct them. The following section addresses the technical and methodological options for the execution of the key processes. Each option has its advantages and disadvantages and will be more suitable in some situations than in others. It needs to be understood that the selection of equipment and method is subject to factors beyond the ideal solution for each UXO object. An EOD campaign in preparation for an offshore wind park requires the involved actors to bring an appropriate set of equipment and personnel onto the vessel. If a situation is encountered in which the ideal piece of equipment is not available on the vessel, the decision may still be to proceed with the tools at disposal at the time, provided they are appropriate alternatives to the ideal approach. Waiting for a specific piece of equipment and the personnel that is trained to handle it to arrive at an offshore site can take days or longer if it has not been mobilised, which is economically infeasible. It is also possible that one technical supervisor for EOD prefers different means for a process than another. Preferences for equipment and procedures depend, inter alia, on the experience that experts have gathered in the past. This demonstrates that economic and practical considerations play a role when deciding on the procedure for handling individual UXO objects. While ideal solutions for a problem may exist, the decision on which approach to choose is not dogmatic.

3.3.3 Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal Methods

This subsection provides a general overview of the methods and technical options for the key processes. The description is not exhaustive, and individual EOD service providers may offer solutions that are tailored towards very narrow and niche scenarios and cases. These very specific services and pieces of equipment may not be mentioned in the literature,

and the author does not have access to the many method statements that were prepared for EOD campaigns over the past years. It is noteworthy that the vast majority of academic literature on offshore EOD deals with the *technical survey* (see 1.2), i.e., phase II of the EOD procedure. Aspects of phases I (*preliminary survey*) and III (*investigation of target points*) are addressed to a lesser degree. Phase IV, with the key processes, is virtually absent from the literature. Hence, in similar fashion as in numerous sections of Chapter 2, grey literature and even marketing material of EOD companies were consulted to prepare the descriptions below. A reason for this uneven distribution of publications may lie in the nature of the phases. During phase II, the survey processes generate large amounts of data that can be assessed to identify opportunities for improvement in technology and methodology. This is very attractive for researchers. Phase IV, on the other hand, relies heavily on engineering and practical, experience-driven decision-making. Data that are generated tend to be disclosed only to partners involved in EOD campaigns. In addition, while many scientific institutions have the capability to survey and monitor UXO, they do not meet the prerequisites that would allow them to handle them. In Germany, the latter is limited to private EOD service providers and the responsible state bomb disposal teams.

The pressing nature of offshore wind park construction has the potential to accelerate innovation in the sector in the same way it has done in the past [104]. The German immediate action programme may further contribute to such a development. The following account is therefore only a snapshot of generally accepted engineering practice and some novel concepts that are in development. The technology will undoubtedly be advanced in the future.

ROVs

ROVs are a commonly used platform to investigate and clear UXO [68]. They can be utilised during all three key processes. As the name suggests, ROVs are remotely controlled by one or more pilots from aboard the clearance vessel, which is why they require an umbilical cable [200]. Accordingly, they have a virtually endless power supply, which cannot be said for untethered systems [24]. Usually, they are diving in the water column and are propelled by thrusters. Due to the vast number of possible applications, they exist in various sizes. During EOD, usually a Work-Class ROV (WROV) is used. Such ROVs regularly weigh above 1000 kg and can carry a payload of more than 200 kg. [201 in 202] ROVs can be equipped with a great variety of sensors, cameras, grabs, manipulators, and other tools. Provided an ROV's thrusters and manipulators have sufficient capacity, even rather heavy UXO can be lifted and moved. [68]

When dealing with UXO, an ROV can only be utilised when a technical supervisor for EOD and an ROV pilot are present. Compared to divers, longer working times are possible. There are no time restrictions for the duration of a dive, and crew changes aboard a vessel can be done easily [68]. Thrusters or suction/dredging pumps [116] on an ROV can be used to remove sediment from a UXO object. However, it is also possible that thrusters accidentally mobilise sediments, leading to a temporal reduction in visibility. [68] Similar to any device that is operated underwater, a positioning uncertainty exists [23], a challenge

that mainly affects the process of approaching a previously detected UXO object or when performing *underwater transfer* to a very specific point. Once the object is in sight, the position of the ROV relative to the UXO object becomes more important than the absolute position of the ROV in the water.

Crawlers

Crawlers are a specific type of ROV that moves on the seabed. Since there is no need to maintain a given water depth with thrusters, they can be heavier than diving ROVs. As a consequence, they are less affected by waves or currents and can be built to operate heavier equipment and lift larger objects. [68] They have been found to work stably in challenging environments [203]. On the other hand, permanent contact with the seabed can be disadvantageous. Soft sediments limit the serviceability of crawlers if they cannot remain atop [68]. The limitation of moving on the seabed reduces the flexibility of the operation when compared to divers or ROVs, which can simply move above an object. A crawler was used successfully during one EOD campaign in Germany [104]. Competing crawler concepts for handling UXO underwater were presented in the past [e.g., 204].

Divers

Divers are another option to handle UXO. To do so, a diver must hold a certificate of competence per § 20 SprengG. They are more versatile than crawlers and ROVs since a trained expert is located immediately next to the UXO [205]. A diving team is usually equipped with survey gear such as a camera and is in contact with the vessel at the surface [23, 166]. An umbilical cable allows the supporting staff at the surface to communicate with the diver via video, audio, and cable pull [206]. When safe for transport, divers can recover low-weight UXO to the surface.

To reduce human risk, diving is avoided whenever possible [115, 207]. It is a hazardous activity, even in a non-EOD context. Numerous limitations to environmental factors, such as the sea state and the current velocity (see 3.4), need to be considered. On top of that, the operating time of a diving team is limited by the air supply and the physical limitations of the human body. However, there are cases in which a diver is superior to the use of an ROV or crawler. In cases of poor visibility or if it is required to reach into soft sediments without dredging [115], divers can haptically determine the properties of an object. This would be impossible for a machine. Furthermore, divers can communicate with each other and, hence, coordinate their work relatively seamlessly. [68]

Underwater Transfer

Underwater transfer is the relocation of UXO that is safe to handle but not safe to transport. The process always involves lifting an object from the seabed and never dragging it across. The two main options for transfer are subsea baskets and lifting bags [23, 166]. Placement into a basket and attachment of a lifting bag can be achieved by an ROV, crawler, or diver. Lifting bags can be remote-controlled or initiated by a diver [206]. Enclosed mine lifting bags can reduce fragmentation in the case of an accidental detonation [166].

Detonation and Deflagration

It is possible to distinguish between high-order detonation, low-order detonation, deflagration, and combustion of explosive compounds, all of which are chemical transitioning processes. The difference between them lies in the velocity at which the chemical reaction propagates through the material. The velocity is in the order of mms^{-1} for combustions, ms^{-1} for deflagrations, and kms^{-1} for detonations [208 in 209]. Another source states that a detonation is reached at 1500 ms^{-1} [130]. The threshold between a low-order and a high-order detonation is given at 5000 ms^{-1} [210 in 209].

Controlled detonations and deflagrations are the two options for the *in situ destruction* process. They are considered a last resort for cases in which no *recovery* is possible, which means that an object is not safe to transport. The negative effects that planned detonations have are essentially the same as those of an unintended detonation (see 2.3.1). The difference lies in the fact that deterring measures for marine mammals are implemented and that civilian shipping will be prohibited from a safety zone around the detonation site. [23] Deflagrations emit considerably less noise than detonations [211]. However, they are associated with a higher level of environmental contamination. Performing a reliable and complete deflagration of an aged and unknown explosive charge underwater is considered very challenging. [197]

The purpose of attempting a low-order detonation or a deflagration, is to avoid all the negative consequences for the marine environment that result from a high-order detonation. Most prominently, the resulting sound pressure and shock waves can seriously harm marine mammals, particularly their auditory senses [10]. However, the other methods have their own disadvantages. According to one study, an average 25 % of the explosive material remained when deflagrations were performed [212]. Hence, the method requires an additional handling of explosive material, thereby essentially transforming a single EOD operation in two.

To perform either of these *in situ destruction* methods, a donor charge is used to initiate the UXO. The charge is usually a commercially available plastic explosive and can be placed on or next to the UXO by a diver or an ROV [166, 207]. The weight of the charge varies, and the literature provides values of up to 10 kg. Once placed, it can be initiated acoustically, mechanically (with a shock tube), or with a detonation cord. For the *in situ destruction* to commence, all equipment and personnel must be removed from the water, and all vessels must leave the area and adhere to a safety radius. [166]

To avoid numerous detonations and the consequential creation of several shock and sound waves (see 2.3.1), it is also possible to detonate several objects at once [23, 166]. Even though the aim is to reduce the number of detonations, an upper threshold for the NEQ, for example, 250 kg [166], is maintained. Unless the UXO objects are already located at the same location, *underwater transfer* is required in preparation for this method.

Disarming

Disarming is the process of separating the fuse from the main charge, i.e., interrupting the ignition chain. Accordingly, this is not a relevant method for unfused UXO. There are numerous options for performing this operation. A diver or ROV can manually remove (usually unscrew) the fuse [197]. There also exist rocket wrench systems that mechanically unscrew fuses, for example, by unwinding a wire rope from a coil at high velocity. The torque that is produced is supposed to be sufficient to remove fuses that are jammed in their thread. [213] No evidence was found that any of the above are performed regularly during offshore EOD in Germany.

Alternatively, a water jet can be used to cut the connection between the fuse and the main charge [3, 197]. It was also proposed to use a water jet to cut holes into the casing of UXO, flush out the explosive material, and capture it for further treatment. This method was tested in air, and the demonstration under water is pending. Reliably capturing the emulsion of water and explosive material, preventing the object from moving under the force of the water jet, and limited visibility were identified as challenges that require further attention. [214] Another approach that was suggested and tested in a laboratory is chemical drilling of the casing and subsequent electrochemical treatment of the explosive compounds to transform them into stable materials [215].

Certain UXO can be disarmed through a small detonation. The idea is to apply small explosive charges to interrupt the ignition chain. The aim is to avoid a detonation or deflagration of the main charge. Given the property changes that explosive materials undergo over time (see 2.2.9), it is impossible to guarantee that this goal can be achieved. This method is sometimes referred to as a ‘low-order method’, which must be distinguished from the ‘low-order detonation’ mentioned above. [197] It was reported as being regularly applied by the state bomb disposal team of Schleswig-Holstein. A low-order method, for example, with a cutting charge, does not remove any of the explosive material but interrupts the ignition chain (see 2.2.10) [181].

Another approach is the use of lasers to disarm UXO objects. The proposition is to weaken the casing of an object with a laser and thereafter initiate a small amount of the explosive material so the fuse gets separated from the remainder of the main charge. [216]

Recovery

Baskets can not only be used for *underwater transfer* but also for the *recovery* of UXO [217], i.e., bringing it to the surface. As mentioned above, divers and ROVs can do so too. An additional option for the *recovery* of individual objects are tools such as an orange-peel grab [23] or a clam shell [205]. These are attached to an excavator that is located on a vessel, ponton, or jack-up platform. The length of the excavator’s arm limits the operating depth of such tools. Recently, commercial EOD companies began marketing the use of so-called ‘multi-tools’. These can be used to uncover and identify objects before

recovering them with an orange-peel grab. [218] There is no evidence that they can be used to perform additional tasks that require more precise and delicate handling of objects, such as disarming or the placement of a donor charge.

To remove large quantities of small UXO objects, other options exist. Firstly, underwater magnets can be used to pull UXO out of the water. Secondly, clam shells can be used to dredge large volumes of sediment. Thirdly, a suction dredger may remove sediment from the seabed while a mesh sieves it for UXO. A problem with all three methods is the uncontrolled movement of objects that may or may not have been identified before the use of the equipment. [31] As this dissertation rests on the assumption that *UXO identification* is finished before the three key processes begin, these practices are not regarded any further.

After *in situ destruction*, the *recovery* of residues in the surrounding area is necessary [23]. The same is true for disarmed UXO. This may be conducted by an ROV or a diver [207] after a safety period has passed. During this type of *recovery* operation, visibility may be reduced due to sediment that was mobilised by the detonation [166].

3.4 Environmental Properties Affecting EOD

Offshore EOD (and more specifically, the key processes) takes place in the diverse and dynamic marine environment. To comprehend the challenges during EOD, it is therefore beneficial to understand the environment of the study area (see 2.1.3). Numerous properties of the offshore environment are relevant for EOD since they either directly impact how EOD work can be conducted or have influenced the UXO while it has been submerged. The following subsections thoroughly describe these environmental properties and how they interrelate with each other and the UXO properties (see 2.2). Some of the information that is provided here was already published in a separate scientific paper by the author [106]. Subsequently, the network of UXO properties (see 2.2.12) is expanded by adding the environmental properties.

3.4.1 Sedimentation and Burial

Sediment is the fine-grain loose material on the sea floor [23]. There, it is vertically and horizontally distributed and is thus a determinant of the bathymetry and fundamental to the shape of the benthic environment [219]. Sediment types can be categorised according to grain size. A commonly used scale distinguishes sand (2.000 mm to 0.063 mm), silt (0.063 mm to 0.002 mm), and clay (< 0.002 mm) [220].

Some properties of the sediment, such as grain sizes, may affect EOD. This includes the capacity of a dredger to pick up sediment or the sediment's potential to reduce visibility when mobilised. [31] However, the main point of interest concerning EOD is whether an object is buried or not. If it is fully or partially buried, it needs to be uncovered during phase III (see 3.2.1) or, if it is already identified, during phase IV. Furthermore, whether an object is buried or not influences its corrosion (see 3.4.2). It is therefore helpful to

understand how much sediment accumulates at a given location. It should also be noted that explosive compounds can accumulate in the sediment [21]. The treatment of such contaminated sediments is, however, not part of the EOD procedure.

Many geographic areas are subject both to sedimentation and erosion. Whether the former or the latter is dominant determines whether a location or an area will have a positive or negative sediment accumulation rate. [219] All sediment movement that is induced by water movements, including tidal activities, is referred to as hydrodynamic mixing. [221] In addition to these mechanisms, sediment is moved by biogenic mixing and anthropogenic processes. The latter includes activities such as anchoring, construction, and bottom trawling. Especially trawling impacts large areas of the seabed. [221]

Only one-third of the Baltic Sea floor is considered to be a sediment accumulation area [222 in 219]. The remainder is considered an erosion or transport area. This includes part of the study area in the Baltic Sea [219]. In one study, the sediment accumulation rate in the Baltic Sea was calculated to range from 0.3 mm a^{-1} to 24.0 mm a^{-1} (i.e., mm per year). None of the stations that were used for these measurements were located in the study area, but the numbers give an indication of the sediment accumulation rate that can be expected in the German Baltic Sea. [223] A machine learning-based algorithm that used discrete Baltic Sea sediment accumulation rate measurements since 1986 predicted sediment accumulation rates ranging from 0.2 mm a^{-1} to 14.7 mm a^{-1} for the area to the north and east of Rügen [219, 224]. The dataset was generated by using discrete Baltic Sea sediment accumulation rate measurements since 1986. Furthermore, several predictor variables (bathymetry, distance from rivers, substrate class, amount of inorganic suspended particulate matter in the water column, impact of wave action on the seabed, and current speed), all of which influence sediment accumulation rate, were collected. The sediment accumulation rate measurements as well as predictor variables were used to train a random forest machine learning algorithm to make continuous spatial sediment accumulation rate predictions for the Baltic Sea at a 95 m resolution. [219]

In the North Sea, morphological changes are considerably larger than in the Baltic Sea. Coastal erosion and accumulation in shallow coastal areas with depths $< 20 \text{ m}$ can reach values way below -50.0 mm a^{-1} and above 50.0 mm a^{-1} , respectively [225]. For the deeper parts of the North Sea that are further offshore, no data were available.

High sediment mobility in an area increases the likelihood that objects are buried [52]. The higher the sediment accumulation rate, the faster an object will be buried. In addition, underwater dunes can move several metres annually and thereby bury UXO [51, 71]. In areas with sandy sediment, a main driver of burial tends to be the erosion of the sediment around a UXO object [226]. The presence of the object on the sea floor accelerates the bottom current flow, which can increase sediment mobility. The consequence can be the development of a scour, into which the object may slowly descend. Successive sediment accumulation can easily bury an object. [72] How quickly a scour forms depends on factors such as the current velocity, wave action, sediment grain size, and the object's dimensions [226]. It is also possible that UXO is unburied and reburied [227].

FIGURE 3.4: Distribution of the burial depth of objects in subset n_b of the EOD dataset [adapted from 107].

In addition, UXO may have penetrated the sediment immediately upon entering the sea. This is referred to as impact burial and is more prevalent in muddy sediments [72, 226]. While also possible for dumped UXO, this mechanism is considered more relevant for ordnance that was used in combat [161]. The penetration depth depends on many factors. These are the impact velocity and angle of the munition when hitting the sea surface, the water depth and the drag coefficient of the ordnance object, and finally the shear strength, bearing strength, and density of the sediment. [228] At water depths of 2.5 m, impact burial of up to 6 m into very soft mud is considered possible [161]. Some ordnance, such as air-delivered mines, was designed not to penetrate the seabed [71].

It is possible to use the EOD dataset, which was already investigated to explore numerous UXO properties in 2.2, to obtain insights into the typical burial depth of UXO that was cleared. In this case, the subsample size of objects that contained a value for burial depth is $n_b = 199$. Figure 3.4 shows the distribution of burial depths for n_b . Of the first bin, 62 objects were not buried at all, i.e., showed a value of 0 m. This amounts to roughly one-third of the objects. The remainder is commonly buried at a depth of less than 1 m. They require dredging and uncovering before the key processes can be executed. The mean and median of n_b lie at 0.56 m and 0.50 m depth, respectively. These numbers are supported by the literature [54]. A potential bias is introduced by the fact that, due to the limitations of technical survey methods, UXO at greater depth may not have been found during phase II.

3.4.2 Corrosion

Corrosion significantly controls the state of the different metal parts of UXO at any given point in time. Both the casing and the ignition chain are impacted by corrosion, which starts the moment an object is submerged. [126] As a side effect, corrosion also leads to the disappearance of markings on UXO casings, making identification more difficult. [126] The same is true if corrosion leads to a significant change in the UXO object's shape. Past research on corrosion has often addressed UXO or other containers holding CWAs. The aim

was usually to understand how many years after dumping and at what rate a release of the content of these UXO is to be expected. Since the casing materials used for chemical and conventional UXO were often the same [118], it is useful to review this literature here.

Several environmental factors affect corrosion. These are the oxygenation, pH value, salinity, and temperature of seawater, as well as the current velocity. Many of these are, in turn, a function of water depth [42, 118]. Corrosion is promoted by high temperatures, oxygenation, and salinity, as well as a low pH value [229]. Water depth is also a relevant factor for tension corrosion, as it is affected by pressure [118]. On the other hand, deeper waters are less affected by weather impacts, which are considered to favour corrosion [230]. Tidal activities are relevant as well since UXO may be exposed to air during low tide [231].

Different studies consider different environmental factors to be particularly relevant for the corrosion rate. Among them is the oxygenation of seawater since anoxic conditions do not allow for corrosion to take place at all [118]. However, such conditions cannot be found in German waters [232]. Anoxic conditions may instead be present in sediments. This means that UXO that is buried in anoxic sediments can be expected to be in a better state than UXO that lies on the seabed. [52, 233] The ratio of corroded to intact UXO may therefore roughly match the ratio of proud to buried objects. Based on interviews and a review of press reports, one study could confirm that UXO objects on the seabed of the Bornholm Basin were completely corroded. The state of buried objects, on the other hand, could not be confirmed. [233] Another study predicts an acceleration of corrosion when shifts between oxic and anoxic conditions occur [234 in 230].

Current velocity was identified as the main factor responsible for varying corrosion rates [120]. In addition, storm events and abrasion from bottom sediments contribute to the loss of material integrity of wrecks and, thus, also of UXO [42, 126].

Other relevant factors impacting corrosion are inherent to the UXO casing itself. The thicker a casing, the longer it will take to corrode to the point at which the content interfaces with seawater [124, 235]. Other factors are the material composition and carbon content of the casing and the production processes applied, especially corrosion inhibition processes. [42, 118] Metal used for German WWII ordnance decreased in quality over the course of the war [235]. Historic research on these matters is challenging as they were poorly documented due to production confidentiality. For a precise understanding that goes beyond assumption-based modelling, attempts were made to reconstruct the chemical composition of German UXO casings from before 1946. [118] Unlike vessels, ordnance was not specifically designed to last in the marine environment for an extended period. Instead, it was intended that it would ultimately fail to function. [126] Numerous studies also point towards galvanic corrosion as a consequence of different metals used in the same UXO object being in contact with each other [42, 118, 127] or if two objects made from different materials are touching [124]. The corrosion of UXO with an aluminium casing is very limited, as aluminium corrosion stops once all of its atoms have bonded with oxygen [52]. Real-world observations show that UXO is present in all conditions, ranging from fully

TABLE 3.5: Predictions of corrosion time until content of UXO or CWA containers interfaces with seawater.

UXO Type	Duration (a)	Corrosion Rate (mm a ⁻¹)*	Location	Ref.
Jgr. 18 AB shell	200	0.05	Baltic Sea	[118]
CWA container (non-alloy steel)	25	0.05	Baltic Sea	[118]
Dumped UXO	50 to 100	0.10	Baltic Sea	[229]
Bombshells, munition shells	25 to 265	0.05 to 0.58 [†]	Baltic Sea	[120 in 236]
Large calibre shell	300	-	Not specified	[237]
Mustard gas barrels	23	-	Polish EEZ	[238]
Mustard gas bombs	46	-	Polish EEZ	[238]
Mustard gas shells	69	-	Polish EEZ	[238]
Mustard gas containers	50	-	Russian Baltic Sea	[239]

* Rounded to the second decimal place.

[†] The original reference was obtained by the author after the submission of the dissertation. It reports a greater variety of durations ranging from 8 years for ‘cans’ to 100 years for 150 mm artillery shells [120].

intact to fully corroded. The effects of corrosion on EOD are not explained here, as the challenges of deteriorated casings and fuses were already addressed in 2.2.5 and 2.2.11, respectively.

In the literature, there are numerous predictions on the amount of time required for UXO casings to corrode to the point at which an object’s content leaks out. This is a point in time that is of special interest. It is the moment at which the content of a UXO object (the main charge and the ignition chain) interfaces with and is affected by seawater. It is assumed that the size of the breach in a casing grows as corrosion proceeds [125]. Several predictions on how long it takes for the initial breach of casings to occur are listed in Table 3.5. The first column states the UXO type as it is named in the respective publications. Even though all references except one [i.e., 237] make predictions for the Baltic Sea, there is a considerable spread in the time that is expected to pass until a casing is breached. None of the studies specifies that UXO is assumed to be buried in the sediment for any amount of time. The time it takes to corrode to the point at which the content of an object interfaces with seawater ranges from 23 to 50 years for barrels containing CWAs (i.e., not UXO). For bombs, it is given as 46 years; for shells, it ranges from 69 to 300 years. The predictions are plausible to a degree, as it is expected to take longer for thicker casings to breach.

3.4.3 Current Velocity

Currents in general and current velocity, in particular, were already mentioned as controlling factors for sedimentation and corrosion. On top of that, currents also affect the EOD key processes more immediately. All of the commonly used methods for EOD—divers, ROVs, and crawlers (see 3.3.3)—are affected by currents. However, the extent of the

effect differs significantly. In simple terms, divers are more negatively affected by currents than ROVs, which are usually influenced more strongly than crawlers. For ROVs and crawlers, the limitations of use that are provided by manufacturers are the information that needs to be considered for their deployment. Especially for divers, strong currents are a limitation, which may require the use of a special current shield [31]. High current velocities are a cost driver for diving operations as they limit the time windows during which work can be executed. Maximum acceptable current velocities for divers ranging from 0.25 m s^{-1} [240] to 0.5 m s^{-1} [23] were found in the literature. A non-comprehensive search for operational limits of work-class ROVs (see 3.3.3) resulted in values ranging from 2.6 kn ($\approx 1.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) [241] up to 3 kn ($\approx 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) [242].

Currents may lead to UXO or payload material migration. High current velocities and a low UXO mass increase the potential for mobilisation. [72] Other influencing factors are the direction of currents, the shape of the UXO object, and protrusions from the UXO object. The local seabed topography also plays a role, and UXO that is mobilised may gather in depressions. Strong tidal currents in the North Sea may mobilise smaller UXO objects. It is, however, considered unlikely that larger bombs or mines will be moved over large distances by current mechanisms. [71] At dump sites, bottom currents are considered insufficient to move the heavy, partially buried UXO [3]. Nevertheless, the fact that UXO may not remain at one location places a certain amount of time pressure on the EOD process [115], which essentially means that the time between the completion of phase II and the execution of phase IV (see 3.2.1) should be minimised.

Winds, waves, and tides influence currents. Since EOD takes place at the seabed, it is more important to understand the bottom currents than those at the surface. The degree to which, for example, wave action has an impact on the seabed depends on the water depth. The greater the wavelength and the shallower the water, the stronger the wave's interaction with the seabed. [46] Near-shore locations, which are usually less deep, are therefore considered a challenging working environment [203] (see 3.4.5).

Current velocities throughout the study area vary significantly. In the North Sea, tidal currents reach velocities of up to 1.5 m s^{-1} . They can be intensified by wind-induced currents of an additional 0.3 m s^{-1} . [243] These combined effects make the deployment of divers and ROVs impossible, and thus crawlers remain the only suitable option in areas with current velocities this high.

To better understand how strongly EOD would be affected at a given location, data from oceanographic models were consulted, courtesy of Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (German: Leibniz-Institut für Ostseeforschung Warnemünde) (IOW). Dedicated models for the Western Baltic Sea [244, 245] and the German Bight [246] were used to extract hourly u and v vectors of the bottom currents in grid cells for the years 2017 until 2019. The u vector provides east-west information, with a positive number signifying a westerly and a negative one representing easterly currents. The v values express the same for currents from the northern and southern directions, respectively. The magnitude of the vector indicates the current velocity. For each grid cell, a current velocity (v_c) was calculated with equation (1). Note that, in truth, the data do not represent an area but

FIGURE 3.5: Median current velocities in German waters [adapted from 244, 245, 246].

a volume since the current velocity was calculated for the bottom water layer. Subsequently, an overall median and seasonal medians were calculated. Meteorological seasons were used, for which spring is assumed to begin on March 1, summer on June 1, autumn on September 1, and winter on December 1. All this was executed and provided by IOW.

$$v_c = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} \quad (1)$$

The resulting grids were provided as netCDF files. QGIS could not read the coordinate reference system of the data. Hence, they were shifted to the correct location with the Georeferencer tool in QGIS using 43 reference points for the North Sea and 28 for the Baltic Sea. After the grids were shifted with the Georeferencer, grid cell size was $510 \text{ m} * 870 \text{ m} = 0.44 \text{ km}^2$. The resulting map is shown in Figure 3.5. Firstly, it should be noted that no data were provided for the outermost northwestern area of the German EEZ in the North Sea. The map furthermore demonstrates that the current velocity in the German North Sea is overall lower than in the Baltic Sea, where it approaches 0.00 m s^{-1} in most areas. In the North Sea, values that are close to 1.30 m s^{-1} can be found in the tidal areas between the individual Eastern and Northern Frisian Islands. The maxima occur at the entrance to Jade Bay.

Figure 3.5 displays median values for each 0.44 km^2 raster cell. Accordingly, the real current velocities are each higher and lower than the values displayed here for 50% of the time. This means that the deployment of divers is not possible, and even the possibility of using ROVs is very limited in some areas of the North Sea. The situation is entirely different in the Baltic Sea, where current velocities are overall low, so ROVs and divers can be used most of the time. The values of each raster cell were used to calculate some statistical measures that are listed in Table 3.6. For this purpose, the raster was transformed into a point vector layer using QGIS' *Raster pixels to points* function. It calculates the centre coordinate for each raster cell and adds the cell's value as an attribute to the

TABLE 3.6: Median current velocities in the German North and Baltic Seas [adapted from 244, 245, 246].

Season	\bar{x} (m s ⁻¹)	\tilde{x} (m s ⁻¹)	Q_{90} (m s ⁻¹)	$X_{(1)}$ (m s ⁻¹)	$X_{(n)}$ (m s ⁻¹)
North Sea					
Spring	0.27	0.25	0.40	0.01	1.28
Summer	0.28	0.25	0.41	0.01	1.31
Autumn	0.27	0.25	0.39	0.01	1.26
Winter	0.27	0.25	0.38	0.01	1.22
Annual	0.27	0.25	0.40	0.01	1.27
Baltic Sea					
Spring	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.19
Summer	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.18
Autumn	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.15
Winter	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.00	0.10
Annual	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.15

FIGURE 3.6: Distributions of the median current velocities in the German North and Baltic Seas [adapted from 244, 245, 246].

point. The resulting attribute table can be used to perform statistical analysis. Table 3.6 underlines the fact that current velocity data are considerably lower in the Baltic than in the North Sea. All of the statistical measures (mean (\bar{x}), median (\tilde{x}), the 90th quantile (Q_{90}) and the minimum ($X_{(1)}$) and maximum ($X_{(n)}$)) were derived from the local medians of each grid cell. The table reveals that there are no overall significant seasonal variations for both seas. Q_{90} shows that even in the North Sea, current velocity is lower than 0.41 m s^{-1} for 90% of the area for at least 50% of the time all year long. This does, however, not eliminate the possibility that there can be areas in which seasonal variability is higher. Finally, it is also noteworthy that in both seas, maxima are lower during winter than during the other seasons.

Figure 3.6 shows the distribution of the median current velocity values throughout the area of the German North and Baltic Seas. The area does not correspond to the study area as the German EEZ in the North Sea is not fully covered by the data. Since

the current velocity decreases towards the northwestern direction, it can be assumed that the addition of this area would contribute to the low-velocity intervals. From the available data, it becomes apparent that the median current velocity is below 0.10 m s^{-1} for almost the entire Baltic Sea. Grid cells in bins with higher value ranges are so rare that they are not visible in Figure 3.6. North Sea currents are stronger, but as was already stated above, only at a minor fraction of the area do medians surpass 0.40 m s^{-1} .

3.4.4 Sea State

The sea state is another environmental property that influences the ability to perform offshore work in general and EOD in particular [23]. It is the oscillation of the sea surface and consists of wind waves and swell. The height of wind waves depends on the wind speed, wind duration, and fetch, i.e., the contact distance of the wind with the sea surface. Swell, on the other hand, are waves originating from larger-scale non-regional events, such as distant storms. [247]. The sea state can be quantified statistically by determining the significant wave height, a parameter for which numerous definitions exist. BSH uses a definition according to which the significant wave height is the mean of the highest third of waves ($H_{1/3}$) [247]. Other definitions use the median of the highest tenth ($H_{1/10}$) or estimate the significant wave height from the wave spectrum (H_{m0}) [248]. Since BSH is the competent authority for maritime issues in German waters, its definition will be used throughout this dissertation, whenever possible.

The sea state is considered a cost and performance driver in EOD, as higher waves will require a larger vessel to support operations [212]. Specifications for maximum wave heights for the deployment of divers and ROVs can be found in the literature. They demonstrate the sea state's potential to limit offshore operations. For divers, maximum wave height values for deployment of 1.2 m [249], 1.5 m [23], and 2.0 m [250] were found. For ROVs, maximum launch and recovery wave heights range from 2.5 m to 4.5 m [251].

In the German EEZ, there are three ‘Research Platforms in the North Sea and Baltic’ (German: Forschungsplattformen in Nord- und Ostsee (FINO)). They are continuously measuring numerous environmental properties that are relevant for offshore wind park construction. Among them are wind speed and wave height. [252] According to these measurements, the monthly average significant wave height never surpassed 3 m at any of the FINO measurement stations from 2004 until 2018. At FINO 2, which is located 33 km north of the island of Rügen in the Baltic Sea, the most frequently occurring significant wave height was around 0.5 m. FINO 1 and 3 are located 45 km north of Borkum and 80 km west of Sylt, respectively (both in the German North Sea). For both stations, the most frequently measured significant wave height was around 1 m. [253]

The German Environmental Agency (German: Umweltbundesamt) converges environmental monitoring data that are acquired by German federal, state, and scientific institutions. These are published in the Sea Environmental Database (German: *Meeresumweltdatenbank (MUDAB)*). From this database, a dataset was downloaded and analysed to understand the sea state in the study area. At the time of access, data included measurements from 2013 until 2019 for both seas and additionally for 2020 for the North Sea. [255]

TABLE 3.7: LLUR sea state scale [254].

Description	Scale Value	Wave Height (m)
Smooth	0	0.0
Very calm	1	0.0 to 0.3
Calm	2	0.3 to 0.8
Slightly moved	3	0.8 to 1.5
Moderately moved	4	1.5 to 2.5
Quite rough	5	2.5 to 4.0
Rough	6	4.0 to 6.0
High	7	6.0 to 10.0
Very high	8	10.0 to 12.0
Extremely heavy	9	> 12.0

Many values of the dataset are given as sea states on a scale that is used by the main provider of the data, the Agency for Agriculture, the Environment, and Rural Areas of the State of Schleswig-Holstein (German: Landesamt für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und ländliche Räume (LLUR)). The institution measures the absolute wave height [254] and converts it into their own scale. The LLUR scale, which is shown in Table 3.7, does not correspond to other more commonly used systems, such as the Douglas or Beaufort scales (see 5.7.28). Other agencies provide their data in m. For this study, they were all translated to the LLUR scale to enable analysing the full dataset. Values that fell into two subsequent values of the scale (e.g., 0.3 m could fall into categories 1 and 2), were sorted into the higher scale value. This eliminated conversion to the scale value 0. This was not problematic since wave height measurements of 0 m were only included in the dataset by LLUR and not by any other data provider. Converting data from the scale to m would have also been possible. However, this would have required a conversion from a range to a distinct value, which would have introduced uncertainties.

Table 3.8 provides an overview of descriptive statistical measures for the sea state for each season in the German North and Baltic Seas. From the table, it becomes apparent that the lowest possible sea state of 0 was measured as minima ($X_{(1)}$) in both seas through all seasons. The highest maxima ($X_{(n)}$) were measured in spring and autumn in the North Sea. These correspond to wave heights of at least 2.5 m and 4 m, respectively. This indicates that the North Sea is more prone to extreme sea states. There were 20.6 % fewer measurements taken in the North Sea than in the Baltic Sea. Still, sea states 4 to 6 (i.e., wave heights ranging from 1.5 m to 6.0 m) were all measured more often in the former (see Figure 3.7). Other sources point out that during extreme storm events, single North Sea waves (i.e., 100-year maxima) may reach 16 m [256]. Seasonal medians (\tilde{x}) are identical for both seas, except for spring, where Baltic Sea measurements indicate a higher sea state. The deviation corresponds to a delta of no more than 0.8 m. Over 50 % of the time, wave heights are below 0.8 m. Mean values (\bar{x}) are larger in the North Sea during spring and summer while being higher in the Baltic Sea during the other half of the year.

TABLE 3.8: Sea states in the German North and Baltic Seas [adapted from 255].

Season	n	\bar{x} (scale)	\tilde{x} (scale)	Q_{90} (scale)	$X_{(1)}$ (scale)	$X_{(n)}$ (scale)
North Sea						
Spring	353	1.7	1	3	0	6
Summer	682	1.6	1	3	0	4
Autumn	384	1.7	2	3	0	5
Winter	96	1.8	2	3	0	4
Annual	1515	1.7	1	3	0	6
Baltic Sea						
Spring	467	1.5	2	2	0	3
Summer	424	1.5	1	2	0	4
Autumn	577	1.9	2	3	0	4
Winter	440	1.8	2	3	0	3
Annual	1908	1.7	2	3	0	4

To understand how all this impacts the ability to perform EOD throughout the year, it should be noted that the 90th quantile (Q_{90}) lies at 3 for all seasons in both seas, save for the Baltic Sea during spring and summer. This means that at least 90% of measurements are smaller than or equal to a scale value of 3 or a maximum of 1.5 m. Hence, EOD work is permissible almost at all times when considering the sea state. Since sea state 4 (wave height of up to 2.5 m) prohibits the use of divers, their work is affected more often than the deployment and use of ROVs or crawlers. As discussed above, the North Sea's sea state is prone to more extreme values than the Baltic Sea's. Limitations on work time are therefore to be expected more frequently in the former. On the other hand, the latter displays a significantly higher share of sea state 2. While EOD work in the Baltic Sea is essentially possible at all times, it tends to be affected by waves of up to 0.8 m more frequently than in the North Sea, where sea state 1 occurs most frequently.

All the above conclusions need to be put into perspective by commenting on the number of measurements per season. In the North Sea, the sample size (n) for winter does not even reach 30% of n for any other season in either sea. It can be speculated that this is a consequence of the occurrence of heavy weather, during which no sampling would be executed since no cruises could take place. Accordingly, the North Sea would be underrepresented from December 1 until February 28 due to a high sea state, which could in turn not be measured. Note that, as a consequence of climate change, average wind speeds and wave heights are expected to increase [258]. Offshore work in some decades is therefore expected to be more challenging than it is today.

Figure 3.8 shows the geographic locations of the measurement locations that are mentioned in the text above. The FINO stations are performing continuous measurements. The MUDAB datasets on wave height were obtained from discrete measurements. Sea state values were obtained at 64 stations (blue dots) within the study area (i.e., German inland waters, territorial sea, and EEZ; see 2.1.3), most of which are located in the German

FIGURE 3.7: Distributions of the sea states in the German North Sea (above) and Baltic Sea (below) [adapted from 255].

territorial sea and thus close to the coast. Three additional stations (pink dots) are located within 5 km of the study area, or, more precisely, of the German territorial sea. From this observation, it can be concluded that the great majority of the study area is not covered by sea-state measurements.

Figure 3.8 also shows all stations at which wind speed measurements could be obtained from MUDAB. All stations at which sea state was measured doubled as stations for wind speed. Overall, 493 stations for wind speed measurements were included in the MUDAB dataset. However, all datasets that were located more than 5 km outside the study area were excluded as they were not considered relevant for this assessment. Thus, 337 stations (green dots) that were located throughout the entire study area and another 14 stations (red dots) within 5 km outside the EEZ were included in the analysis. These stations were included as some of them are placed in areas that are not otherwise represented in the data, for example, to the far northwest of the study area. Figure 3.8 displays a stark contrast between the number of sea state and wind speed measurement locations. The coverage of the latter is considerably higher. Therefore, if one seeks to understand the typical sea state at a given location in the study area, it would be sensible to use wind speed as a parameter and make inferences regarding the sea state.

FIGURE 3.8: Geographic locations of wind speed and wave height measurements in German waters [adapted from 255, 257].

Therefore, a dataset of wind speed measurements was obtained from MUDAB. It covers the years from 1986 to 2020. Again, a table was generated to understand how statistical measures for the wind speed differ throughout the year and between both seas (Table 3.9). Beforehand, the data were cleaned, and all values above 50 m s^{-1} were deleted. They were considered erroneous as that value is considered to be the maximum sustained wind speed in the southern North Sea region [259]. While there are variations in n for seasons and regions, there is no outlying number, that would be similar to the sea state in the North Sea during winter. Thus, a lack of representation of any given season can be ruled out.

Table 3.9 shows statistical measures for wind speed. The values for \bar{x} and \tilde{x} are higher for the North Sea during all seasons and annually. They are highest during the winter. A look at Q_{90} reveals that 90% of North and Baltic Sea measurements fall under 14.4 m s^{-1} and 12.0 m s^{-1} , respectively. When translating these values into Beaufort numbers (see 5.7.28) [260] and significant wave height, values of 7 corresponding to 4 m for the North and 6 equating to 3 m for the Baltic Sea could be reached. Under such conditions, the use of divers would not be admissible, but certain ROVs could be deployed.

With some limitations, it is possible to compare these wind speed data to the sea state data that are presented in Table 3.8 and in Figure 3.7. Using the Beaufort scale, wind speed can be converted into significant wave height. For example, the annual median (\tilde{x}) wind speed values are 7.4 m s^{-1} (North Sea) and 6.0 m s^{-1} (Baltic Sea). This translates to \tilde{x} significant wave heights of 1.0 m for the entire study area, which corresponds to value 3 on the LLUR scale. The \tilde{x} values in Table 3.8 indicate LLUR wave height values of only 1 for the North Sea and 2 for the Baltic Sea. This means that for the North Sea, a median weight height of less than 0.3 m was measured, while a median weight height of up to 1.0 m is expected according to the wind speed measurements. A reasonable assumption would be

TABLE 3.9: Wind speeds in the German North and Baltic Seas [adapted from 255].

Season	n	\bar{x} (m s^{-1})	\tilde{x} (m s^{-1})	Q_{90} (m s^{-1})	$X_{(1)}$ (m s^{-1})	$X_{(n)}$ (m s^{-1})
North Sea						
Spring	2380	7.9	7.2	12.9	0.0	50.0
Summer	2598	7.2	6.7	12.9	0.0	38.8
Autumn	1877	8.2	7.7	13.4	0.0	42.6
Winter	2250	8.9	8.0	15.4	0.0	50.0
Annual	9105	8.0	7.2	13.5	0.0	50.0
Baltic Sea						
Spring	3977	6.5	6.0	11.4	0.0	50.0
Summer	4050	5.8	5.1	10.3	0.0	50.0
Autumn	3581	7.1	7.0	12.0	0.0	23.2
Winter	2521	7.2	7.0	12.0	0.0	50.0
Annual	14 129	6.6	6.0	12.0	0.0	50.0

FIGURE 3.9: Distributions of the wind speeds in the German North Sea (above) and Baltic Sea (below) [adapted from 255].

that this is related to the underrepresentation of wave height measurements in the EEZ, where wind speeds and thus the resulting waves could be higher. All measurement locations are tagged according to their position in the study area, for example, whether they are located in the EEZ or the territorial sea. Assessing the wind speeds for these different locations surprisingly shows a deviation of only 0.7 m s^{-1} . Hence, distance to shore is not an indicator of higher wind speeds. In conclusion, the wave height assumptions based on wind speed are likely overestimated in comparison to direct wave height measurements.

Minima of 0.0 m s^{-1} occurs in all combinations of seasons and regions. Maxima of 50.0 m s^{-1} are possible in both regions but rarely occur, as both Q_{90} and the histogram in Figure 3.9 demonstrate. Figure 3.9 furthermore shows that wind speeds ranging from 5.0 m s^{-1} to 7.5 m s^{-1} are most prevalent in the North Sea, while 2.5 m s^{-1} to 5.0 m s^{-1} are the most commonly occurring values in the Baltic Sea. Such wind speeds would lead to a significant wave height of no more than 1 m, and, thus, to conditions that allow for EOD work without weather restrictions.

3.4.5 Water Depth

Since UXO is located on the seabed, the water depth is a factor that should be considered during EOD. The water depth at a location can change over time, either due to long-term sedimentation (see 3.4.1) or short-term tidal activities. While the tidal range in the Baltic Sea is low, it can reach over 4 m in the German North Sea [261]. Depending on the duration of an EOD operation, it is thus possible that there is a significant change in water depth.

Similar to other environmental properties, there are operational limits for water depth for the deployment of divers and ROVs. The operational limit of divers is considered to lie in the range of 40 m to 50 m [42, 262]. Furthermore, dive times decrease with depth, making the use of divers less efficient in deeper waters [115]. According to GICHD, EOD diving beyond depths of 20 m requires special skills and increases technological demands [56]. For ROVs, the depth limitations are less of a concern. One review of 119 studies on ROV-based visual biota surveys found that all of the used WROVs were able to reach at least 100 m of water depth [263]. As described in 3.3.3, the use of robotic systems is commonly preferred over divers to mitigate human risk. However, in shallow environments, divers are by some considered the only option [205], due to the lower depth limits of most ROVs [264]. Crawlers are less affected by the wave action of the shallow water environment and thus present a reasonable alternative [200, 264].

Numerous challenges during EOD are related to water depth. Lifting UXO changes the ambient pressure that it is subjected to. Reports of chemical UXO exist, according to which the inner pressure of objects led to them bursting open. Ongoing corrosion may increase the likelihood of such events. [3, 132] It is possible that this is an issue for conventional UXO as well. Challenges do, however, not only increase with depth. Shallow waters, such as the surf zone (with depths ranging from 5 m to 10 m), are considered to be especially challenging working environments [115]. The difficulties are mainly attributed to near-shore wave action [200].

FIGURE 3.10: Distributions of the water depths in the German North Sea (above) and Baltic Sea (below) [adapted from 257].

In addition to the challenges during EOD, the water depth influences the potential impacts of an underwater detonation on EOD personnel and equipment. Due to the increasing pressure, deeper waters attenuate the blast and fragmentation effects of UXO detonations at the surface [71]. In deeper waters, small amounts of explosive material are expected to cause only minor damage, even to equipment and personnel under water [155 in 43]. At more than 10 m depth, fragments are not considered a hazard for vessels at the surface [54]. Furthermore, the seismic magnitude of an underwater detonation decreases with depth [265]. Other effects, such as the shock wave and the bubble jet effect, are probably less mitigated by depth [71]. The severity of a shock wave is controlled by the distance between the detonation and the affected object. A ground mine, for example, must be close enough to its target to cause the intended damage. [54] Since greater depth also means a greater distance to a vessel, a detonation at a deeper location will lead to less shock than a detonation with otherwise identical properties in shallow waters. Consequently, shallower depths are considered more risky work environments during offshore EOD. [71, 54] This was explored in more detail in the subsection on possible effects of detonations (see 2.3.1).

The water depth in the study area ranges from 0 m to 71 m. The deepest point is located in the very north-western corner of the German EEZ in the North Sea. The deepest location in the Baltic Sea is at 47 m. The histograms in Figure 3.10 show the distribution

of the water depth in the German North and Baltic Seas. All values relate to marine chart zero. The grid that was used for the generation of these histograms is the same that was used to display the bathymetry in the maps in Figures 3.8 and 3.11 [257]. Some grid cells contained values above marine chart zero. These were deleted as they were not considered relevant. The histograms show that depths beneath 50 m are very rare in the study area. Even though any company offering EOD services in Germany should generally be prepared to work in depths of up to 71 m, no more than 1 % of the study area lies beneath 50 m.

3.4.6 Visibility and Turbidity

The fact that visibility is limited impedes underwater work. One contributing factor is the decreasing amount of natural light as the water depth increases. This can be compensated for with artificial illumination. Another factor is turbidity. The *Cambridge Dictionary* defines ‘turbidity’ as the property of a liquid “of being cloudy because a lot of small pieces of matter are held in it” [266]. It is caused by suspended matter, including sediment particles, organic matter, and microscopic organisms [267]. There are different ways of measuring turbidity. One way is to measure how a light beam of known intensity is attenuated in a liquid. Another way is to measure the degree to which light scatters in the medium. [268]

Turbidity levels are higher near river estuaries and after storm events [269]. Furthermore, turbidity is often high in port areas [270]. It can also increase due to EOD operations if they lead to the mobilisation of sediments. The relevance of turbidity during EOD is underlined by the fact that the use of underwater magnets is discouraged. This is, *inter alia*, due to them strongly dispersing sediment and rendering visual surveillance of work impossible. [10, 31]

Turbidity is inversely correlated with the ability to obtain visual information under water. High turbidity makes the EOD process more challenging since an accurate *UXO identification* (e.g., with cameras) is difficult [271]. This is especially relevant when considering that this identification includes evaluating the state of a UXO object and its fuse. In addition, lower visibility is a challenge during the execution of the key processes. It limits the ability to see what is happening to the UXO object and the EOD equipment and divers. One source indicates that high turbidity may be a limitation for divers [31]. This notion is reasonable given the higher uncertainty when less visual information is available. On the other hand, if underwater visibility is constantly poor, a diver haptically collecting information on an object may be the only option to identify it [23]. Consequently, EOD divers routinely work in dark and turbid conditions [270].

To distinguish between UXO and non-UXO, methods for chemical sensing of explosive compounds could be used, for example, by collecting water samples with divers [271] or Niskin bottles [21]. Another option to obtain additional information for the identification of objects and UXO is the use of so-called acoustic cameras [272]. It is also possible to equip ROVs with thrusters that blow off suspended sediment to increase visual clarity [273].

FIGURE 3.11: Geographic locations of Secchi depth measurements in German waters [adapted from 255, 257].

Since no representative dataset for the near-bottom turbidity of the study area exists, Secchi disc measurements were used as a substitute measure to understand the underwater visual range in the German North and Baltic Seas. Note that visibility in surface waters does not necessarily match visibility in deeper layers. Details are given in section 5.11.7. A Secchi disc is a standardised round plate that is printed with alternating black and white quadrants. It is lowered from the vessel into the water, and the depth at which it disappears from view is referred to as the Secchi depth. [274] This allows for a turbidity assessment [268]. A dataset was downloaded from *MUDAB* (see 3.4.4.) and analysed to gain a rough understanding of the visual conditions in the study area. The dataset includes Secchi depth measurements from 2002 until 2021. [255] The data included some values that were larger than 100 m, which were deleted since these were considered erroneous, as this is deeper than the water depth in the study area.

The Secchi depth measurement locations, both inside and outside the study area, are shown on the map in Figure 3.11. There are 109 stations in the Baltic Sea. In the North Sea, there are only 78 stations. The further the distance from the shore, the fewer stations exist, and thus the north-western part of the North Sea is not well represented in the data.

Table 3.10 contains some descriptive measures of the dataset. The Baltic Sea was sampled and reported to the database more frequently. Thus, the dataset is six times larger for the Baltic than the North Sea, even though the geographic area in the North Sea is larger. Data points exist for both regions for every year (except for the year 2003 for the Baltic Sea). Secchi depths as low as 0.1 m and 0.0 m were measured for the North and Baltic Seas, respectively. However, mean (\bar{x}) and median (\tilde{x}) values indicate that the visual range from the surface into the depth is often larger. The 10th quantile (Q_{10}) over the entire year lies at 0.5 m in both regions. Accordingly, 90 % of measurements resulted

TABLE 3.10: Visual ranges in the German North and Baltic Seas [adapted from 255].

Season	n	\bar{x} (m)	\tilde{x} (m)	Q_{10} (m)	$X_{(1)}$ (m)	$X_{(n)}$ (m)
North Sea						
Spring	75	4.6	3.7	1.5	0.9	11.0
Summer	688	4.2	3.5	1.0	0.1	19.0
Autumn	240	2.5	1.2	0.4	0.1	18.0
Winter	512	2.7	1.5	0.3	0.1	20.0
Annual	1515	3.4	2.5	0.5	0.1	20.0
Baltic Sea						
Spring	2564	3.4	3.5	0.5	0.1	14.0
Summer	2261	2.9	2.7	0.5	0.0	10.6
Autumn	2036	3.5	3.5	0.7	0.0	9.5
Winter	2155	3.8	3.8	0.8	0.0	14.0
Annual	9016	3.4	3.5	0.5	0.0	14.0

FIGURE 3.12: Distributions of the visual ranges in the German North Sea (above) and Baltic Sea (below) [adapted from 255].

in greater values than 0.5 m. The histograms in Figure 3.12 show the distribution of visual range measurements in both seas. They support the notion that the Secchi depth is very often sufficient to work underwater and allows for visually recognising the surroundings. Even values above 10 m are possible, but only account for 0.002 % and 5 % of measurements in the Baltic and North Seas, respectively.

Seasonal variations are more prevalent in the North Sea. \tilde{x} drops to 1.2 m in autumn, while being at 4.0 m during summer. Q_{10} is at 0.3 m in winter and at 1.5 m in spring. However, 72 out of 75 spring data points were sampled in 2004. This limits the data's representativeness for the season. The Secchi depth in the North Sea during spring may be grossly exaggerated, an impression that is strongly supported by the minimum value ($X_{(1)}$) of 0.9 m, which is large when compared to the other seasons. Seasonal values in the Baltic Sea vary much less and are usually close to annual numbers, with the notable exception of \tilde{x} and \bar{x} for summer, which could be related to the seasonal algae bloom. Autumn or winter in the North Sea are the times and area that are most likely limiting visual range. High uncertainty remains for spring in the North Sea.

3.4.7 Network of UXO and Environmental Properties

Based on the descriptions of the environmental properties in the previous subsections, it is possible to update the network of UXO properties that was presented in Figure 2.7. As shown in Figure 3.13, it is now a network of UXO and environmental properties. It can be read in the same way as the previous version. It adds two new types of nodes: the *Environment* nodes and the *EOD* nodes. The latter contain some information on where and when the EOD operation is going to take place. Their introduction is necessary since the descriptions of environmental properties above demonstrated that sedimentation, corrosion rate, current velocity, visual range under water, wind speed, and water depth all depend on the location. Current velocity, visual range under water, and wind speed additionally underlie seasonal variations. Rates of corrosion and sedimentation have a direct impact on UXO properties, such as the condition of the casing and therefore the fuse corrosion state and the current impact sensitivity of the main charge. The other environmental properties (water depth, current velocity, visual range under water, and wind speed) influence the EOD operation but not the condition of the UXO.

In theory, it would also be possible to use the location to derive information on UXO properties. For example, an object that is located outside a dump site can be assumed to be fused. However, the collection of such information is the task of the technical supervisor for EOD (see 3.2.4). The location-based deduction of UXO properties is not as straightforward as the relationship between a location and prevalent environmental properties. Therefore, UXO properties first and foremost depend on the UXO type. Researching them is an integral part of processes such as the *historical survey* and the *UXO identification*.

FIGURE 3.13: Network of UXO and environmental properties.

3.5 Conclusion—The Case for EOD Risk Assessment

After Chapter 2 laid the foundation of knowledge on UXO, this chapter continued by characterising EOD. Initially, Chapter 3 introduced numerous EOD frameworks and selected the most comprehensive one as a frame of reference for this dissertation. It described the selected framework in detail and identified the processes during which the handling of UXO takes place as ‘key processes’. These are *underwater transfer, in situ destruction,*

and *recovery*. Chapter 3 then introduced methods and equipment that are commonly used to conduct EOD. Finally, it described the environmental properties that affect EOD and must therefore be considered during their execution.

Throughout this chapter, the complexity of handling UXO in a challenging and dynamic environment became evident. To account for the complexity, the EOD industry and its stakeholders have developed numerous frameworks and guidelines. However, adhering to a procedural framework does not necessarily address the risk that is undoubtedly connected to EOD. Several EOD frameworks have the term ‘risk’ in their titles. However, this refers to the fact that these frameworks are executed to manage UXO risk in the larger context of an offshore development project. They hardly address the work during which the actual handling of UXO takes place. This is remarkable when considering that the removal of UXO is the ultimate goal and the most crucial part of any EOD activity. In light of these findings, H_{ii} can be accepted.

H_{ii} : EOD requires structured RA to understand the risk to which EOD personnel and their equipment are subjected.

Chapter 2 concluded that in light of an increased number of EOD projects, it is necessary to understand how this kind of work is conducted and under which circumstances it takes place. Following the same argument and with the challenging environmental conditions in mind, it is also necessary to better understand the risk to which the EOD personnel and their equipment are subjected. However, before the risk can be understood or even quantified, a basic understanding of the principles of risk and its assessment must be gained. Chapter 4 is dedicated to the provision of this understanding and to answering the question of whether existing methods suffice to comprehensively understand EOD risk.

Chapter 4

Review of Risk Assessment Methodologies

The previous chapter concluded that to understand the risk that EOD personnel and their equipment are subjected to, it is necessary to understand the basic concepts of risk and RA. Accordingly, Chapter 4 begins with an introduction to the concept of risk and a definition of some central terminology. The majority of the chapter is dedicated to the formulation of requirements for RA during the key processes and a review of ten existing methods that assess risk in connection with UXO in general or EOD in particular. To this end, a specific review concept was developed. The purpose of this exercise was to identify whether existing methods could be used to assess risk during the key processes. This sought-after method is henceforth referred to as the EOD RA.

4.1 Risk—A Brief Overview

The literature on risk and risk assessments is extensive. The ability to predict the future by assessing UEs with limited information that are available in the present is universally attractive to many disciplines of science, fields of business, and aspects of daily life. Entire books could be filled by reviewing concepts of risk, definitions of risk-related terminology, and the accompanying philosophical discourse. One review discusses multiple different historically developed concepts of risk (risk is an expected value, risk is the probability of an event, risk is uncertainty, risk is the potential for loss, risk is probability and consequence, risk is a consequence, risk is consequence and uncertainty, and risk is the effect of uncertainty) [275]. The purpose of this dissertation is to understand how RA can be utilised to support EOD decision-making, not to offer a discussion on the countless conflicting views on risk. This section is therefore limited to the bare minimum of the methodological foundation that is required.

To avoid an excessive discussion on the definitions of ‘risk’ and ‘risk assessment’ it is helpful to refer to a ground-breaking article by Kaplan and Garrick from 1981. With over 4000 citations, it is considered a reliable and sufficiently respected source. In their paper, the authors suggest that, to analyse risk, three questions must be answered.

1. What can happen (i.e., what can go wrong)?
2. How likely is it that this will happen?
3. If it does happen, what are the consequences?

The answers to these questions are expected to be a scenario identification, a probability of the scenario, and a measure of damage, respectively. [276] Hence, to analyse risk, it must first be clear what exactly is the subject of investigation. This is usually an initiating undesirable event [277] (see 5.3). Once clearly identified, the assessment of the probability and potential consequences of this event can begin. Note that the terms ‘risk assessment’ and ‘risk analysis’ are used interchangeably here. The developers of the three questions above do not make any distinction at all. This conflicts, for example, with the definition in ISO 31000, according to which the analysis is a part of the assessment [278]. Another source claims that the assessment is part of the analysis [277]. For this dissertation, RA is considered the process of answering the three questions.

Assuming that risk assessment is not being done without a purpose, it is usually part of ‘risk management’, which are “coordinated activities to direct and control an organisation with regard to risk” [278]. Risk management is usually part of a process that involves not only risk assessment but also monitoring and consultation activities and, most importantly, decision-making on how to deal with risk [278]. It is possible to distinguish four different strategies to address risk. These are to tolerate (do not take any measures and accept that risk exists), to treat (perform measures to reduce risk), to transfer (insure against risk), and to terminate (do not perform the risky activity). [279]

4.2 Preparation of the Offshore UXO and EOD Risk Assessment Review

As section 4.1 demonstrates, there is no uniform understanding of what exactly constitutes ‘risk’ and how it should be defined [275]. As it is not the purpose of this dissertation to add to that discussion, the diversity of definitions is regarded as an opportunity rather than an obstacle. Due to the existence of so many definitions, many methodologies are available. To understand which specific problems can be addressed by using the different RA methods, it is necessary to define criteria for their review.

To do so, the first subsection looks at some theoretical literature that covers different aspects of RA methods. First, it defines five review criteria (RCs) to understand how RAs can be reviewed and subsequently categorised. The second subsection uses these RCs in an RA categorisation tool to visualise which criteria an EOD RA should fulfil and to understand whether existing RA methods meet these criteria.

4.2.1 Risk Assessment Review Criteria

The theoretical literature on risk has produced many ways to categorise RA methods. Some of these are provided in textbooks, while others are the research output of meta-analyses. This subsection is not a comprehensive literature review, but it will provide

sufficient reference to existing literature to understand how RA methods can be categorised along five RCs. It focuses on the textbooks and meta-analyses and does not seek out the individual studies in which RA was applied.

Each of the RCs is characterised by a pair of opposing poles. They are the study type (*qualitative* vs. *quantitative*), the level of decision-making (*strategic* vs. *applied*), the risk assessment component (*probability* vs. *consequence*), the spatial scale (*global* vs. *local*), and the temporal scale (*long-term* vs. *short-term*). Once identified, they were used to define the requirements of an RA method for this dissertation and to explore the variety of RAs related to EOD and UXO.

Review Criterion 1—Study Type

One distinction between methods is between qualitative, semi-quantitative, and quantitative ones. When trying to express a given situation in a model, reality can be reconstructed qualitatively or quantitatively (or in a combination of the two). That means that either statements can be made to qualitatively describe the situation and, thus, the risk associated with it. Or it can be modelled numerically and thus quantified. [280] Qualitative methods resort to characterising probability, consequence, and therefore risk in linguistic ways, for example, by classifying them as ‘high’ or ‘low’. Quantitative analyses, on the other hand, use numerical values in specific measurable units to express risk. Semi-quantitative approaches use numerical values on rating scales. [281] In practice, this often means that semi-quantitative methods only allow expressing risk as discrete values, while quantitative methods permit continuous ones.

Accordingly, for this review, a distinction is made between quantitative and qualitative RA methods. These are suitable for different situations, and in some cases, applying a combination of both types of methods may be the best option. It may even be argued that no fully quantitative RAs exist. This is due to the assumption that even though a risk value may be calculated mathematically, the assessment of that value always takes place by an assessor who possesses a given, i.e., limited, amount of knowledge. [275]

In summary, RC1 describes the study type. Its spectrum is defined by the opposing pair of *qualitative* and *quantitative* approaches. For RC1, the semi-quantitative methods are the logical midpoint between the two opposing poles.

Review Criterion 2—Level of Decision-Making

RA can be used to support decision-making ranging from high levels of strategic consideration to detailed applied examinations. The level of decision-making can be described as negatively correlated to the level of detail that an RA provides as output. RA may, for instance, be used for the prioritisation of contaminated sites. However, the output of such an RA may be insufficiently detailed to support decision-making about how to address a specific site. [282] While the former can be considered a high-level strategic decision, the latter is more applied. This does not mean that a prioritisation RA would be of lower quality than an RA discussing different approaches for the management of a specific contaminated site. These are different questions, requiring different methods.

RC2 expresses the level of decision-making. It distinguishes between *strategic* and *applied* RA methods. Table 4.1 provides additional examples for levels of decision-making between these two opposing poles.

Review Criterion 3—Risk Assessment Component

Historically, the use of nuclear power for the generation of energy and the growing use of synthetic chemicals drove the development of new ways to quantitatively assess risk. However, the very different nature of the two technological trends cultivated distinct RA methods. For the assessment of nuclear power plants, it was necessary to study events that would lead to catastrophic consequences. Accordingly, focus was placed on determining the probability that such an event would materialise. In contrast, for chemical contaminants, it was relevant to understand how likely certain effects would be at a given level of exposure. Therefore, it was essential to be able to assess both probability and possible consequences. [282]

Section 4.1 highlighted that RA is often considered to be comprised of the two components probability and consequence. However, during an assessment, one may focus on or lean towards studying either of the two aspects. Under certain conditions, assessing the consequences may be considered less relevant. The consequences of nuclear accidents, for example, are considered unacceptable. Hence, RA that informs the design and construction of a nuclear power plant focuses on preventing such an accident by understanding the probability of the occurrence of certain events. This allows for inhibiting them by implementing specific avoidance measures. That does not mean that the consequences are entirely irrelevant. Understanding them is necessary for devising a contingency plan, i.e., “a plan that is made for dealing with an emergency [...]” [283]. However, developing such a plan requires a different type of RA. This example demonstrates that RC3 is connected to the temporal aspect of RA (RC5). Choosing to focus on probability, consequence, or both is, to a certain degree, a function of whether one is interested in understanding what happens before, after, or before and after a risk materialises.

Leaning towards either of the RA components may also result from an uneven distribution of knowledge. Consider a situation in which the mechanisms determining the likelihood of an event are well known but there is limited data on its consequence. This may lead to a tendency to use a method focusing on probability. [284] This challenge could be addressed by assessing the probability aspect quantitatively and the consequence aspect qualitatively (RC1).

In essence, RC3 describes how strongly an RA leans towards either of the two RA components *probability* or *consequence*, that were already identified in the definition by Kaplan and Garrick from 1981 [276] (see 4.1). A study that is placed at the centre of the two components addresses both to a similar degree.

Review Criterion 4—Spatial Scale

Identifying the proper spatial and temporal scales of an RA is important. Assessing both dimensions is considered an integral part of disaster risk management. The two scales are, to a certain extent, interrelated with one another. The consequences of an event may have a different spatial extent at two different points in time. The spatial scale that can be addressed by an RA ranges from global to local. Spatial aspects are relevant when assessing both geographic patterns and limits of events. [285] It can be assumed that there is a certain correlation between the spatial scale and the decision-making level (RC2). A prioritisation RA of different sites will, by nature, have a larger spatial scale than a site-specific RA.

For this study, one side of the scale refers to the literal meaning of global (*large*), while the opposite side refers to very *small* local assessments, dealing with a single object and its immediate geographic vicinity. The middle ground, which may be labelled ‘regional’ can refer to an area, the size of an individual bay, or an offshore infrastructure development site, such as a wind park. Such an area will vary from project to project, but the scale should suffice to provide a general understanding of the rating.

Review Criterion 5—Temporal Scale

It is uncertain when a risk will materialise and when its consequences will ensue. Numerous aspects of risk may change over time, most prominently the condition and vulnerability of a potentially affected risk receptor (see 5.5). It may therefore be insufficient to assess the current state of a given system and assess risk. Instead, change processes need to be included in the analysis. Overall, no steady state of the relevant systems should be assumed, and thus the extent of the risk of the seemingly same event may vary significantly over time. [285] Consequently, an RA that is executed one day may be faulty or misleading another day. In addition, depending on the temporal scale of an RA, the longevity of its results may vary.

Many temporal aspects of RA can be exemplified by discussing human health risk assessment (HRA) and ecological risk assessment (ERA), where exposure levels and the resulting consequences play a significant role. Both for humans and for organisms in an ecosystem, exposure to a stressor may be acute or chronic. The same overall exposure to this stressor may result in different effects (i.e., the consequence). Acute exposure to a given concentration may be life-threatening. On the other hand, if the exposure is spread out over the entire life span of an individual, an organism may be able to cope with it. Especially for acute exposure, another relevant aspect is the latency between exposure and consequence, i.e., whether the effects are immediate or delayed. For chronic exposure, the effects of exposure may accumulate over time. Finally, the effects of exposure may be acute or chronic as well. [286] These aspects can be transferred to other types of RA, as risk factors may be immediate and intense or continuous and persistent. For example, when assessing the financial risk of a bond, this may be impacted by the long-term economic performance of a country or by highly disruptive events, such as a pandemic.

TABLE 4.1: Overview of review criteria for the categorisation of RA methods.

Review Criterion	Pole 1	Categories					Pole 2
		1	2	3	4	5	
RC1: Study type	Qualitative	Purely qualitative	Rather qualitative	Semi-quantitative	Rather quantitative	Purely quantitative	Quantitative
RC2: Level of decision-making	Strategic	National strategy	Site prioritisation	Site management	Clearance decision	Object handling	Applied
RC3: Risk component	Probability	Solely probability	Mainly probability	Balanced	Mainly consequence	Solely consequence	Consequence
RC4: Spatial scale	Large	Global	National	Bay	Development project	UXO object	Small
RC5: Temporal scale	Long-term	Decades	Years	Months	Weeks	Days and hours	Short-term

The aspects discussed in the previous paragraphs demonstrate how important the definition of the temporal scale of an RA is. Consequently, RC5 describes the temporal scale of the predictive capacity of an RA on a range from *long-term* to *short-term*. The predictive capacity is the amount of time that the RA is targeting to predict the probability and resulting consequence. When discussing a natural disaster, one may seek to predict the risk for many decades into the future, which would be a long-term RA. On the other hand, when assessing the accident risk of a given EOD operation, one would be interested in the very immediate probability and consequence. RC5 does not refer to time as an input parameter for risk. For example, the fact that some UXO objects have been submerged since 1914 while others were dumped as late as 1949 is one of many input parameters when assessing the immediate risk during EOD. On the other hand, the continuous degradation of UXO shells over more than a century, leading to the leakage of explosive compounds and their long-term effects on an ecosystem, requires a long-term RA. In other words, the temporal scale expresses to what extent future system changes need to be considered in the RA.

Summary on the Review Criteria

The description of the RCs shows how diverse RA methods can be. To compare and evaluate RA methods concerning their suitability for EOD RA, five categories were introduced for each RC. The categorisation of methods is, to some degree, open to interpretation. Nevertheless, it allows understanding the requirements of the EOD RA and categorising existing RA methodologies.

Table 4.1 shows the five RCs and the categories that were used to subdivide them. The RCs are shown in column 1. The second and last columns contain the two opposing poles of each RC. For example, for RC4, these are a large and small spatial scale. The remaining columns contain the categories that help sort the methods.

4.2.2 Requirements of the EOD Risk Assessment

With the RCs that were developed and described in the previous subsection, it is now possible to categorise existing or potentially needed RA methods. This subsection defines the requirements for the needed EOD RA and discusses how to categorise it with the help of the RCs. Below, the five RCs are revisited one by one, and a category as per Table 4.1 is selected for each.

RC1—Study Type: The accident rate in EOD is very low, which means that data on the materialisation of risk is virtually nonexistent. However, EOD is a regular activity in German waters (see 3.3.1), which implies that all of the three key processes *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction* and *recovery* are executed regularly. Consequently, data on these EOD activities exist (see 2.2). Furthermore, expert knowledge makes the use of rating scales (as used in semi-quantitative methods) feasible in cases where no data are available. While not strictly performing RA, EOD experts execute a qualitative assessment every time they judge whether UXO is safe to handle, safe to transport, or neither (see 3.3.2). In summary,

it should be possible to design an EOD RA that leans towards the quantitative side of RC1. However, due to the lack of data on accidents, it must resort to expert judgement where necessary. Therefore, category 4, *rather quantitative*, is selected.

RC2—Level of Decision-Making: The EOD RA is required to focus on the risk during the execution of the key processes. It is necessary to analyse the particularities of the given UXO object and the surrounding environment to assess risk and inform the technical supervisor’s (see 3.2.4) decision on the way forward. The EOD RA is not meant to be a tool for the prioritisation of dump sites or the planning of offshore construction projects in light of UXO. It must, hence, be a method for applied and not strategic decision-making. Therefore, category 5, *object handling*, is selected.

RC3—Risk Assessment Component: As described in 2.3.1, the consequences of unintended detonations may be dire. This applies even more if a detonation occurs during EOD, as personnel or valuable technical equipment are in the vicinity of the UXO. Assuming that these consequences are generally considered unacceptable and must therefore be avoided, it can be argued that the method for RA should only focus on the probability component of risk. However, an understanding of the potential consequences in light of water depth and the type and mass of explosive materials may be beneficial as well. Therefore, category 2, *mainly probability*, is selected.

RC4—Spatial Scale: The key processes of EOD are spatially limited activities. The geographic extent includes the UXO object, the surrounding environment, and the EOD personnel and equipment on site (see 5.5). While the surrounding environment certainly influences EOD through macro-scale natural processes such as regional currents and regional weather conditions, the relevant conditions during the key processes are those on site. The EOD RA therefore deals with a small spatial scale. Hence, category 5, *UXO object*, is selected. It should be noted that, were the RA focusing on the consequences for marine mammals, it would have required a larger spatial scale (see 2.3.1).

RC5—Temporal Scale: There are two dimensions to the temporal scale of the EOD RA. Firstly, the idea is that, given all available information, the risk related to the key processes should be assessed. This should be possible right before executing them. Secondly, the materialisation of risk may be the immediate result of a certain action, which may lead to an immediate consequence. Considering both of these aspects, the temporal scale that needs to be covered by the EOD RA is very short. The fact that UXO objects were submerged between 1914 and 1949 is reflected in the UXO properties (see 2.2.12) and is independent from the temporal scale of the RA. Therefore, category 5, *days and hours*, is selected. Again, the requirements would change if consequences such as the chronic effects of explosive compounds accumulating in biota (see 2.3.2) were under investigation.

Figure 4.1 shows the categorisation of the EOD RA. In each line, one of the five RCs is defined by its pair of opposing poles. The space in between represents five horizontal axes on which the RA can be placed. The placement of nodes in each line (i.e., one for each RC) was done as a best estimate, considering the requirements of the EOD RA. This simple RA categorisation tool does not allow for a quantitative evaluation. Instead, it allows for

FIGURE 4.1: Methodological categorisation of the EOD RA.

clarification of the overall functionality and area of application of any RA and permits a comparative assessment of multiple RA methods. Connecting the nodes of the EOD RA from top to bottom produced a characteristic curve. A review and categorisation of pre-existing RAs allows checking whether they would result in the same or a similar curve. If yes, this would be an indication that a suitable RA method for EOD RA already existed.

4.3 Offshore UXO Risk Assessment Review

For a well-informed application of RA to the key processes, this section provides a review of existing offshore UXO and EOD RA methods. To give a comprehensive overview, the literature review was not limited to the key processes. The section provides the required amount of theoretical and methodological background to understand how the methods work and how they were applied to offshore UXO and EOD. It also covers several self-proclaimed RA methods, even though it is debatable whether they qualify as such.

Each of the following subsections describes one methodological approach from the literature and the studies that apply it to offshore UXO or EOD RA. These studies are consecutively numbered RA1 through RA10. Where possible, subsections assign the methods to the processes in the EOD framework (see 3.2.1 and 3.2.2). Furthermore, all RAs are entered in the RA categorisation tool, which allows comparing them to the EOD RA's requirements. The subsections do not report on the results of the referenced studies, as these are irrelevant to this methodological review.

Similar to the review of the EOD frameworks in Chapter 3, some RAs came to the attention of the author after this review had been completed [e.g., 287, 288]. They were not included in hindsight. Scientific research is dynamic and continuous, which means that not all existing RAs can be considered here. Nevertheless, the review provides a helpful overview of the status quo in UXO RA and EOD RA.

4.3.1 Risk Matrices

A risk matrix can be used to visually display the risk of an event by classifying the probability of its occurrence and the consequences that this event would have were it to occur. Any number of categories, both for the probability and the consequences, can be chosen. It is accordingly necessary to assess both of these risk components for each event under observation. The expression of risk in the form of a matrix is not necessarily numerical and can be a mere visual tool. Risk matrices can lead to difficulties in distinguishing between the risk of different events if the number of categories for probability and consequences is low, thereby leading to a crude result. They are, however, a useful tool for getting a rough overview of risk. [277]

RA1

In a UXO RA study that was performed in preparation for the construction of the Hywind Scotland floating offshore wind park (RA1), a risk matrix is generated. The aim of RA1 is to be able to assess the risk of a UXO detonation during the various activities that had to be performed during wind park construction. The risk matrix consists of five probability categories and five consequence categories. Each category of both components is assigned a value from 1 through 5, with 1 representing the lowest and 5 the highest probability and consequences. A descriptive text for each category for both components is provided. In the matrix, the values of probability and consequences are multiplied by each other, leading to possible risk values ranging from $1 * 1 = 1$ to $5 * 5 = 25$. These risk values are then again subdivided into five categories: low (1-3), low/medium (4 & 6), medium (8 & 9), medium/high (10 & 12), and high (15-25). To assess risk, the study uses various inputs. It distinguishes between four UXO types that were identified as occurring most likely in the area of interest of the construction project. Furthermore, it introduces eight work activities that take place during wind park construction. The study assesses risk for three risk receptors (personnel, equipment, and project progress) in two water depth classes (120 m and < 30 m). The probability of occurrence is defined as a function of the probability of encountering a certain UXO type and of the probability of detonation. The description provided in the report of the study is not comprehensive, but it appears that the value of the probability of occurrence is generated by combining two out of three factors: firstly, the predicted amount of a UXO type and, secondly, whether a work activity constitutes a sediment intrusion or the water depth. The generation of the consequence value is also not clearly described, but it appears to depend on the mass of the explosive materials of the UXO type, the risk receptor involved in a certain work activity, and the water depth. [54]

FIGURE 4.2: Categorisation of RAs using risk matrices.

Theoretical literature states that the study's way of multiplying probability and consequence values into a risk value is error-prone. A risk matrix is a tool for describing risk, not RA. Numerical risk values that are generated in a risk matrix strongly depend on the design of categories for consequences and, more importantly, probability. [277] For example, if the probability had been displayed as logarithmic categories instead of linear ones, the resulting risk values would be completely different.

The results of RA1 are not concerned with EOD activities but with the risk of UXO to construction work. The report notes that the study was performed after the survey [54], which means that it could have been part of the *data interpretation* process during phase II of the EOD framework. Even if the study did not rely on the risk matrix for assessment and used it exclusively for visual representation, it could not be used for the assessment of the key processes.

When applying the RA categorisation tool, RA1 was located at the centre of the axis for three out of five RCs. Figure 4.2 displays it as a blue square. RA1 is a semi-quantitative study (RC1) that evaluates both the probability and consequences of UXO risk. Its focus is slightly shifted towards the probability aspect of risk, which is compounded by the probability of encounter and the probability of detonation (RC3). Since it is a planning effort for wind park development, it was also placed at the centre of strategic and applied decision-making (RC2) that takes place in a mid-term time frame (RC5). Finally, the size of a wind park is the spatial scale of the study, which is a development project (RC4).

RA2

A risk matrix is also utilised in a literature review study of UXO risk (RA2). In the review, the authors identify 21 “UXO risk events” and determine the likelihood of occurrence and the consequence severity for each. The likelihood of occurrence values are derived from descriptions in the literature of how often the events were reported in the past. The study distinguishes eight categories for the likelihood of occurrence, ranging from 1 (uncommon) to 8 (assumed very common). For numerous risk events, the frequency can only be assumed. The study accounts for this fact by conservatively sorting these events into categories with higher occurrence values. For consequence severity, the study introduces four categories that are not mutually exclusive but may occur simultaneously. The categories are ranked 1 (property damage) through 4 (injuries, exposure, or death), and if relevant for the same event, are added up so that a maximum score of 10 can be reached. It is not fully transparent how the authors determine which of the consequence categories apply to which event. It is stated that the worst-case scenario for each event is the basis for the determination of the consequence categories. The authors probably assign them according to their best estimates. Based on the scores for the likelihood of occurrence and the consequence severity, all events are sorted into a risk matrix. In contrast to RA1, RA2 does not multiply the scores to produce a risk value. Instead, it sorts events into one of six priorities based on their location in the risk matrix. [289]

Of the 21 events that RA2 identified, two are part of EOD and are related to the key processes. These events are named “intentionally removed for detonation” and “intentionally detonated in situ”. Nonetheless, RA2 is rather broad in its scope and addresses the overall risk of UXO.

RA2 (green square in Figure 4.2) uses a risk matrix, which is often applied as a tool in semi-quantitative studies. It was rated as being more qualitative than RA1, which derives its probability ratings from a historic study and intrusion depths. RA2, on the other hand, derives probability by counting how often UXO risk events are mentioned in the literature (RC1). The fact that the paper is an overall review of UXO risk means that it is of interest for answering strategic questions on a global level (RC2, RC4). It is both concerned with the probability and consequences of its UXO risk events and was thus placed in the middle of RC3. Finally, in terms of temporal scope, it depends on the UXO risk event in question. RA2 was thus placed at the centre of RC5, even though individual events may warrant a different temporal scale.

RA3

One of the EOD frameworks that was already described in 3.1.1 is the basis for the most comprehensive UXO risk management publication available (RA3) [46]. Unlike most other literature reviewed here, the document does not describe the application of the method to a real-world scenario. Instead, it is a guide on how to deal with UXO in the context of offshore economic development. The method of RA3 sorts risk into a matrix structure. The basis for this is, again, the determination of probability and consequence.

According to the guide, a so-called “UXO threat assessment” is required before the RA. The purpose of the threat assessment is to determine the likelihood of the presence of UXO in a given area of interest. It is informed by military and historic records as well as other reports on UXO discoveries. In this qualitative review, the likelihood of the presence of UXO threats is categorised on a scale from 1 (remote) to 5 (almost certain). Unlike the threat assessment, the subsequent RA is not concerned with the likelihood of the presence of UXO threats but instead with the probability of the occurrence of a “UXO risk event”. In opposition to RA2, there is not a set of events under observation but only a single one: the detonation of a UXO object. The probability component is composed of the probability of encountering UXO and the probability of it detonating. To determine the former, historical factors such as UXO types, dispersal, positions, failure rates, and clearance rates should be evaluated. Furthermore, environmental factors such as bathymetry, geological features, UXO burial, and burial depth are mentioned as being relevant. Factors to be considered to determine the probability of a UXO object detonating are the types and depths of geotechnical investigative activities, the types of installation activities, operational, maintenance, and decommissioning activities, the distance of all of the aforementioned activities to the UXO, the detonation mechanisms of the UXO, and the sensitivity of the UXO. The document does not provide detailed information on how to combine all this information into an assessment. It requires a qualitative judgement to be executed and suggests blending all of the above into a probability score ranging from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high). The consequence component, on the other hand, is determined separately for four receptors (people, equipment, the natural environment, and the historic environment). The force generated by a detonation, blast attenuation that may be provided by the natural conditions, the distance between the detonation and the receptor, as well as the capacity of the receptor to withstand a detonation, are factors that should be included in the assessment. Consequences should then be scored from 1 to 5. Next, the values for probability and consequences are both entered into a risk matrix. They are multiplied by each other and sorted into three risk categories that are translated into inputs for As Low As Reasonably Practicable (ALARP) (see 4.3.6).

The approach described in RA3 is to assess the overall probability of encountering and detonating UXO as well as the consequences of such an event in a given area of interest. It is an assessment that is supposed to take place in preparation for offshore development. As such, it also determines which means of UXO risk mitigation should be applied, which includes earlier stages of EOD, such as performing a technical survey. It is also noteworthy that the publication briefly addresses the concept of a risk source that impacts a receptor via a pathway. However, it does not further explore opportunities for a more detailed and structured RA that present themselves in light of this concept. As was already demonstrated in Figure 3.1 RA3 is linked to phase I and the process *threat assessment* of the EOD framework. For these reasons, it is not a suitable RA for the key processes.

There is considerable methodological overlap between RA1 and RA3. Accordingly, the categorisation of RA3 is the same as for RA1 for all RCs.

Summary on Risk Matrices

Figure 4.2 shows RA1, RA3 (both marked by a blue square due to their identical categorisation), and RA2 (green square) as profiles in the RA categorisation tool. To aid comparability, the profile of the required EOD RA (black pentagons) is also displayed. None of the risk matrices' profiles even remotely resemble the EOD RA's profile. Hence, none of them meets the requirements for this study.

4.3.2 Other Semi-Quantitative Approaches

RA1 and RA3 were characterised as semi-quantitative RAs. Here, two additional RAs are discussed that are also semi-quantitative since they use distinct values on rating scales to express risk. However, neither of them uses a risk matrix to express or display results.

RA4

Albeit being published three years before RA3, a UXO risk and threat assessment that was conducted during the planning of the East Anglia ONE Offshore Wind Farm off the coast of Suffolk is essentially an application of that method (RA4). The main reason it is described here and not above is that it does not apply a risk matrix. The study uses a concept known as a source-pathway-receptor-consequence (SPRC) model for risk identification (for more information, see 5.5). RA4 investigates the probabilities of the encounter and initiation of UXO as well as the consequences of a detonation for five different types of UXO (*source*) and eight types of operations that take place during the wind farm's development (*pathway*). The assessed types of UXO are high-explosive bombs, axis sea mines, allied sea mines, torpedoes, and depth charges. Both probability and consequence are rated from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high), which are then multiplied to give a risk rating. For the probability rating, an informed judgement based on a historical desk survey is made. The *consequences* rating is deduced from the UXO object's mass of explosive materials by grouping its possible size into five categories and estimating the expected consequences for four *receptors* (human health, plant and equipment, vessels, environment). The method allows for a comparative description of the risk that is associated with the different types of operations. [71]

Even though it is more specific and transparent on the nature of the consequence rating than RA1, RA4 is not suitable for assessing the key processes since it is a preparatory RA akin to RA3. It is linked to phase I and the process *threat assessment* of the EOD framework.

Since RA4 is essentially an applied version of RA3 and very similar to RA1, it was categorised in the same manner (blue circle in Figure 4.3). This means that for RC1, RC2, and RC5, nodes were placed at the centre of the axes. For RC3, the RA is leaning towards probability since this risk aspect is stressed more in the method than consequences. The study focuses on a development project and was thus sorted into category 4 of RC4.

FIGURE 4.3: Categorisation of other semi-quantitative RAs.

RA5

The *First Risk Assessment Tool for Subaquatic Ammunition Dumpsites (FRATSAD)* is not available any longer. During its availability, it offered a semi-quantitative approach to assess the hazard and risk of UXO (RA5). At the time this review was written, a description of the tool could be accessed and reviewed [290]. For the tool, roughly thirty conventional UXO compounds and CWAs are ranked according to their level of hazard. Each compound receives a score from 1 to 15. This score is obtained by combining twelve properties of the compounds in an undisclosed manner. The included properties are solubility, hydrolysis, stability, acute human toxicity, chronic human toxicity, carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, teratogenicity, aquatic toxicity, toxic hydrolysis products, bioaccumulation, and arsenic content. The tool asks the user to provide information on the amount of each compound and the size of the area in which it is distributed. This way, it calculates the concentration of each substance and the combined amount of all substances in the area. In the second step, the hazard scores of the substances are combined with the concentrations in the area to generate a hazard value for that area. Finally, the user is required to add information on the surrounding environment. The requested information is water depth, prevalent sedimentation processes, current velocity, whether the area is part of a nature reserve, whether it is used for commercial fishing, and whether other restrictions for use exist, as well as the spatial distances to the closest waterway, the closest coastline, and the closest constructed structure. The tool provides a set of options for each type of requested environmental information that the user can choose from. For each option, an underlying numerical value is used to express how the environmental factor contributes to the hazard

level in the area. By dividing the sum of the maximum possible values by the sum of the underlying values of the options selected by the user, a final hazard value for the area is generated. [290]

While dealing with UXO compounds and CWAs, the results provided by RA5 are not targeted at EOD. They cannot be assigned to any specific phase or process of the EOD framework. Its developer considered RA5 a tool for preliminary assessment. It addresses the general public, providing it with a rough classification of the hazard in an area that is contaminated with UXO or otherwise packaged CWA.

Figure 4.3 displays RA5 as a green circle. While working with discrete values on rating scales and therefore constituting a semi-quantitative assessment, RA5 derives its risk value from numerous measurable properties of CWAs and conventional UXO compounds. It was therefore categorised as rather quantitative (RC1). As it addresses the general public with a rough classification of the hazard of an area, it is rather concerned with strategic decision-making (RC2). It heavily focuses on potential consequences and does not assess the probability of them occurring (RC3). Since it is meant to be applied to any given sub-area of the Baltic Sea, the node was placed at the centre of the spatial scale (RC4). Finally, the tool was designed for long-term decision-making and not for immediate planning of offshore construction or EOD work (RC5).

Summary on Other Semi-Quantitative Approaches

RA4 (blue circle) and RA5 (green circle) were entered into the RA categorisation tool, and the resulting profiles are shown in Figure 4.3. Neither of them meets the criteria that were identified for the EOD RA (black pentagon). RA5 overlaps with the EOD due to its quantitative nature. However, its strong tendency towards assessing the consequences side of RC3 means that the underlying input data (e.g., on carcinogenicity, mutagenity, etc. of substances) are irrelevant for the EOD RA. The methodological algorithm of RA5 is undisclosed, and thus, it cannot be transferred to this dissertation.

4.3.3 Event Trees

Event trees can be used to assess the consequences of a given initiating event. Their purpose is to identify and quantify scenarios that may play out as an effect of the occurrence of the initiating event and to do so in a structured manner. To this end, a series of polar questions are asked. [277] Each of the polar questions represents an additional event that can lead to one of two possible outcomes. As the event tree forks at each of these events, potential scenarios develop, and the possible outcomes of the initiating event are determined. Event trees can be used qualitatively to produce an overview of possible scenarios that may unfold due to an initiating event. They can also be used quantitatively by assigning probabilities to the answers to each of the polar questions and, thus, to each scenario. This allows for assessing the scenarios in greater detail. [277, 291]

FIGURE 4.4: Categorisation of the RA using an event tree.

RA6

A pipeline construction RA that was found uses event trees to assess numerous risks that are related to pipeline construction (RA6). It mistakenly labels its diagrams as “fault trees”. In the study, a series of percentages and probabilities are used to create the event tree. It does so, inter alia, to express the risk of fatalities that may occur due to an unintentional UXO detonation during different pipeline installation operations (anchor handling, rock placement, and landfall operations). One factor that is considered in the study is the UXO density. It is derived from a technical survey that was performed in preparation for another pipeline project. Secondly, the water depth along the pipeline route is included, and depth classes are defined. Thirdly, numerous probabilities are determined: the probability of contact with UXO during the pipeline installation operations, of a subsequent detonation of the UXO object, of certain charge sizes occurring, and of a fatality following the sinking of a vessel. The last probability is determined by reviewing the distribution of four different weather conditions in the geographic region and the success rates of rescuing personnel under each of these conditions. [292]

Like other RAs described in this section, RA6 was prepared during the planning stage and is not directly related to EOD. It was assigned to the *threat assessment* process of phase I. The categorisations in the event tree (e.g., of charge sizes) are very simplified. This may be due to the large scope of the pipeline report.

The event tree method, as applied in RA6, with its series of data-driven percentages and probabilities, is a rather quantitative method (RC1). As it is linked to a specific pipeline project, the decision-making level was considered to be in the middle between

strategic and applied (RC2). Through its event tree approach, RA6 emphasises probability more than consequences, for which it distinguishes only two categories (RC3). Similar to other studies that were reviewed above, RA6's spatial scale is that of a development project (RC4). Finally, it deals with explosion risk on a medium-term temporal scale (RC5).

Summary on Event Trees

RA6 is the only study to use an event tree. Figure 4.4 juxtaposes the profile of RA6 (blue triangle) and the EOD RA (black pentagon). Again, the profiles do not overlap, and thus RA6 cannot be used to perform RA for the key processes. However, its shape is akin to the EOD RA's profile. The report therefore provides a methodological starting point for the EOD RA. The networks of UXO properties (see 2.2.12) and UXO and environmental properties (see 3.4.7) are tree-like. By assigning quantities to the properties, they could be used to calculate risks that may occur during EOD operations.

4.3.4 Risk Assessments Addressing Human and Faunal Health

The following two RAs do not use the same methodology but very different approaches. They are both described in this subsection since they address human and faunal health. While the first one is a toxicological RA, the second one addresses the risk of noise emissions during detonations.

RA7

This study performs a toxicological health RA to examine the risks of *in situ destruction* (RA7). For this purpose, blue mussels were placed in the vicinity of corroded mines, free-lying hexanite, and an area with multiple pieces of exposed explosive material. After the exposure, the mussels were collected, and their tissue was analysed for TNT, 2-amino-4,6-dinitrotoluene (2-ADNT), 4-amino-2,6-dinitrotoluene (4-ADNT), and 2,4-diamino-6-nitrotoluene (2,4-DA-6-NT). [9] Based on the data that were obtained in this analysis, the margin of exposure (MOE) of the compounds for human seafood consumers are calculated by using the Integrated Risk Information System of the US Environmental Protection Agency. An MOE is calculated by dividing a dose-response point by the estimated exposure dose (EED). The EED may be estimated, calculated, or measured and should include all possible sources and routes of human exposure to the substance under investigation. [293] In addition to the concentrations of the compounds in mussel tissues, input information for the calculation is the consumption of fish or seafood per capita in Germany as well as the carcinogenicity values of TNT. [9]

This study's approach differs significantly from the literature presented above. It addresses the potential long-term effects of the process *in situ detonation*. Even though the data were collected at a spatially confined dump site, the results of RA7 are universally valid and not meant to inform individual EOD campaigns. The method would be impractical for integration into the EOD framework and is thus unsuitable for the EOD RA.

FIGURE 4.5: Categorisation of RAs addressing human and faunal health.

Figure 4.5 displays the categorisation of RA7 as a blue diamond. It is very data-driven and thus a largely quantitative study (RC1). The assessment may support policy-makers or EOD companies in deciding on the management of UXO dump sites and is therefore rather strategic (RC2). Through its quantitative approach, it addresses both the probability and consequence aspects of human health risk (RC3). The spatial scale of a dump site is rather local (RC4), and the consequences it addresses are long-term (RC5).

RA8

Another paper uses aspects of RA to assess the impact of detonations on the hearing of harbour porpoises (RA8). Both data on detonation and the seasonal distribution of harbour porpoises were obtained for the Dutch continental shelf. Impact areas for individual detonations are modelled based on the mass of the explosive material in the detonated UXO objects. Existing risk thresholds for sound exposure levels and resulting injuries are used. The thresholds are combined with the modelled impact areas of the sound waves and the harbour porpoise density to calculate the expected number of injuries occurring as a consequence of the detonations. [20]

Even though the results of RA8 were generated on a limited geographic scale, they are significant for other marine areas. Thus, the study is universally valid. If it were applied during the EOD framework's process *UXO identification* in phase IV, the method's results may well impact the decisions that are made. However, since it addresses the consequences

of a planned *in situ detonation* on harbour porpoises, it cannot serve as an EOD RA. Neither is a planned detonation a UE, nor are harbour porpoises the risk receptor in this dissertation (see 5.3.2 and 5.5).

While applying a very different type of model, RA8 has a lot in common with RA7. It is quantitative, but it also translates some of its consequences into semi-quantitative categories (RC1). As it is universally valid, it addresses a rather strategic question (RC2). Furthermore, it deals both with probability and consequences (RC3) on a rather confined spatial scale, that is, the impact radius of the detonation (RC4). However, it differs in terms of temporal scale as it assesses short-term probabilities and consequences (RC5).

Summary on RAs Addressing Human and Faunal Health

In Figure 4.5, both RA7 (blue diamond) and RA8 (green diamond) are plotted. Since they overlap in numerous RCs, the profile of RA7 is only partially visible. Given that the two RAs address completely different issues, it is remarkable how strongly they overlap in the categorisation tool. This demonstrates that methods that address different issues can still pursue their aim by adhering to very similar principles. Nevertheless, neither of the methods strongly overlaps with the EOD RA requirements. RA8 shows similarities in terms of RC1 and RC5. This is related to the fact that it quantitatively addresses the short-term consequences of a detonation. This is also a requirement of an EOD RA, and hence, aspects of RA8 should be integrated there.

4.3.5 Qualitative and Descriptive Approaches

As described in 4.2.1, RA may be executed in a purely qualitative way. For this purpose, methods such as brainstorming, structured interviews, or structured what-if-technique may be used [281]. As long as the assessment is methodologically robust and deals with risk as defined in one of the ways presented in 4.1, it qualifies as an RA. Two qualitative studies were found and reviewed.

RA9

RA9 was performed in preparation for potential EOD activities. These are referred to as “routes to impact”. It was a prerequisite for the construction of a wind park off the coast of Aberdeen, Scotland. The RA had to be prepared to determine whether a specific European Protected Species (EPS) mitigation plan was required for the wind farm’s construction. The study assesses the risk that various EOD activities pose to cetaceans in the area. It is primarily concerned with the potential impacts of EOD activities on the risk receptors and less with the probabilities that these consequences may arise. The routes of impact under consideration are the noise originating from UXO clearance (i.e., *in situ destruction*), noise originating from ROVs equipped with geophysical systems, vessel noise, and the collision of specimens with vessels. The assessment is purely descriptive. It starts by describing the sensitivity of the risk receptors’ hearing, which is relevant background information for the first three of the four routes of impact. Subsequently, it provides an overview of the potential impacts of each route and predicts the impact. Finally, it

FIGURE 4.6: Categorisation of qualitative RAs.

describes and evaluates the significance of each impact by sorting them into categories. RA9 remains ambiguous on the parameters it uses for this evaluation and what is required for an impact route to end up in a specific impact category. [166]

Of the four routes to impact presented in RA9, one is directly connected to EOD (the noise originating from UXO clearance). The study states that *in situ destruction* may be unavoidable under certain circumstances. It describes the potential consequences of this planned operation. Such an assessment might be performed in preparation for the protection concept for the *in situ destruction*. The method is therefore unsuitable for the aim of the RA in this dissertation since it does not cover the other key processes.

In Figure 4.6, RA9 is represented by a blue inverted triangle. It is, by definition, on the qualitative end of the spectrum of RC1. It is meant to answer the rather strategic question of whether an EPS mitigation plan was required for the wind park's construction (RC2). To answer this question, RA9 focuses exclusively on the consequence component of risk (RC3). Like many other RAs discussed here, it addresses the spatial scale of a development project (RC4). Its temporal scale was considered medium-term, as it discusses not only the immediate effects of in situ clearance but also its lasting effects for cetaceans (RC5).

RA10

Another descriptive RA explores the UXO risk connected to a wind park construction project in the German EEZ in the North Sea (RA10). It provides a detailed description of the effects of underwater detonations and formulas for safety distances that are required to be maintained in the event of their occurrence. All these descriptions focus on assessing

the risk for a vessel at the surface, as the main concerns of the study are the life and health of the crew. The study names the likelihood of encounter, the sensitivity of fuses, the impact of construction activities on the UXO, the size of the explosive charge, the distance of the risk receptor to the UXO object, and the protective medium (such as water) as the factors that determine UXO risk. The report also briefly considers the probability of the initiation and ageing of explosive material under water. Finally, it provides objectives for EOD that should be fulfilled before construction proceeds. These provisions are made for various construction activities under consideration of the previously mentioned factors that determine UXO risk. [43]

RA10 falls into the *threat assessment* process of phase I of the EOD framework. This is a preparatory report to determine the reference object (i.e., the smallest object that needs to be detected [23]) for which EOD action, including the technical survey, needs to be taken. RA10 does not deal with the risk during EOD but describes how EOD should be executed to manage UXO risk during offshore wind park construction, which is a much wider scope. It is therefore not relevant for the key processes as defined in 3.2.2.

As it is purely descriptive, RA10 is a qualitative RA (RC1). Similar to RA1, RA10 is a direct preparatory step for an EOD campaign and was thus placed in the middle between strategic and applied levels of decision-making (RC2). It devotes a similar amount of attention to the probability and the consequence of UXO risk during wind park construction (RC3). Like many other RAs, it deals with the spatial scale of a development project (RC4). It focuses on a medium-term temporal scale in its assessment of the probability and consequences of undesired detonations (RC5).

Summary on Qualitative and Descriptive Approaches

In familiar fashion, RA9 (blue inverted triangle) and RA10 (green inverted triangle) were mapped onto the grid of the RA categorisation tool. This is shown in Figure 4.6. As with the majority of previous profiles, these do not correspond to the profile connecting the black pentagons, meaning that the qualitative RAs presented in this subsection do not meet the requirements of the EOD RA.

4.3.6 ALARP

ALARP is not an RA method but rather a principle that supports determining which measures should be taken to reduce risk and which ones should be omitted for reasons of practicability. What degree of risk is considered unacceptable needs to be defined by ‘risk acceptance criteria’. To support determining risk acceptability, ALARP defines three risk regions. Figure 4.7 shows an ALARP carrot diagram with the three risk regions ($R1$, $R2$, and $R3$), which are separated by two thresholds ($T1$ and $T2$). In this diagram, both the horizontal extent of the carrot as well as the location of an event along the y-direction describe the magnitude of the risk. The higher the location of an event in the carrot, the larger the extent of the carrot and, thus, the magnitude of the risk. Any given event can be located somewhere in the carrot and thus fall into either of the three regions. The risk of an event located in $R1$ is so low that it is considered negligible. On the other side

FIGURE 4.7: ALARP carrot diagram.

of the spectrum, the risk of an event located in $R3$ would be so large that it would be above a threshold of risk acceptance and therefore intolerable. This means it must be managed (i.e., reduced) at all costs. By managing a risk, it can be moved to a lower location in the carrot and, if it passes a threshold, fall into another region. Events in $R3$ must be managed in such a manner that they at least fall under $T2$ into $R2$, which is the ALARP region. Here, the risk should be reduced to a reasonably practicable level. [294] Events in the ALARP region challenge the decision-maker to weigh the effectiveness of available actions to reduce the risk against the time, cost, and effort to perform these actions [55]. A risk-reducing action should be implemented as long as its costs are not grossly disproportionate to its risk-reduction benefits [277]. Cost-benefit analysis can be used to inform decisions on managing risks that are located in the ALARP region [294]. The rigour with which the investigation takes place (i.e., determining where an event is located) may depend on the extent of the original risk. Since UXO may present a significant risk, a systematic, transparent, and consistent assessment should be performed. [46]

It should be noted that ALARP is not universally applied all over the world. It is advocated by the Health and Safety Executive of the UK. Consequently, during the literature review that was performed for this section, it was usually mentioned by UK authors and businesses. [46] It is included in this review since three of the RAs apply the principle. The personal experience of the author shows that, in Germany, the use of ALARP is viewed controversially.

For the case of EOD, ALARP is applied under the assumption that not all UXO that may be present in a given area can be found and removed [55]. The principle was used in RA1 and is mentioned in the documents describing RA3 and RA4. Instead of a model with three regions, RA1 and RA4 only use two. In one region, risk needs to be mitigated, and in the other, the risk is residual (see 5.4). This implies that no action must be taken for events in the latter region. The decision-making process for addressing events in the former risk region remains undisclosed in both references. The studies instead point out that in the case of well-known risks, proof of adhering to good practices is sufficient. [54, 71]

This subsection did not introduce any additional RAs but completed the picture of some of the RAs and their risk-based decision-making. For this reason, no additional use of the RA categorisation tool is necessary.

4.3.7 Colloquial Uses of the Term Risk Assessment

Section 4.1 established that the term ‘risk’ is widely used and no exclusively true definition can be provided. In addition to the multitude of academic definitions, ‘risk’ and ‘risk assessment’ are often used colloquially. This is demonstrated by the following examples that were found in the literature. It should be noted that this chapter does not question the following studies’ overall quality but rather whether they qualify as RAs or deal with risk at all.

One example is a study assessing the environmental impacts as well as the potential short- and long-term consequences of UXO in Swedish waters (both lakes and the sea). It is labelled as an *Environmental Risk Assessment*. For the study, water and sediment samples were taken from the UXO-contaminated environments to measure the concentrations of TNT and its degradation products. In the lakes, metals were measured as well, and specimens of different faunae were counted. In addition, laboratory tests were conducted to analyse how TNT binds to sediment and is released from it. Furthermore, a toxicity experiment was conducted by testing the survival of daphnia magna in contaminated water. Finally, the study describes and predicts the potential future consequences of the continued presence of UXO. The authors of the study consider this to be an RA. [229]

It is questionable whether the non-rigorous, descriptive outline of potential future developments given in the study qualifies as an RA. It does not follow any of the methodological approaches that were described for RA1 through RA10. A discussion of potential future scenarios is not an investigation of risk, even if these scenarios are adverse.

Another study describes mechanisms leading to UXO drifting to the shore at the water surface or the bottom and to UXO burying in the seabed. According to the study title, it is *Quantifying the risks of unexploded ordnance drifting ashore or burying in the sea bed*. The author applies a particle drift model to simulate how UXO may drift on the water surface. For surface drift, a probability of UXO beaching is modelled for any given location in the geographic area under investigation. Next, the study describes calculations on the current speed required for UXO mobilisation at the bottom and how tidal currents and wave-induced currents may contribute to the mobilisation of UXO. According to these simulations, UXO cannot beach under the current conditions in the geographic area. Finally, with the help of a scour model, the study explores how UXO is buried in the seabed. No probability of burial is provided. [72]

Even though risk and probability are used synonymously in some studies (see 4.1), the paper at hand should not be considered an RA. It does not contextualise the events for which it calculates probabilities with the potential impacts of beaching or not beaching. The study describes a physical mechanism, but it does not follow any methodological approach for quantifying risk.

The two studies described here were added to demonstrate how the terms ‘risk’ and ‘risk assessment’ are sometimes used colloquially. Since they do not qualify as RA, the categorisation tool is not applied to them.

4.3.8 Offshore UXO Risk Assessment Gaps

The methodological comparison of the reviewed RA with the requirements of the EOD RA revealed that none of the existing methods is rather quantitative and applied to the handling of an individual UXO object to determine both probability and consequences over a short time scale. Some methods apply rather quantitative means (RC1) to determine risk, leaning towards the probability component (RC3), but they fail to meet the other criteria. The least satisfied criterion is the level of decision-making (RC2). Not a single existing framework informs the clearance decision or object handling. Most RAs focus on the spatial scale of a development project (RC4), which is too large for the EOD RA. Only RA8 can support very short-term decision-making (RC5).

In addition, it is possible to determine at what point in the EOD framework the RAs would be executed and towards which phases and processes they would be applied. The description of the investigated RAs already mentioned the required input information for each method, which indicates during which process the RA would take place. On the other hand, the results that the investigated RAs are expected to deliver indicate to which subsequent operations they should be applied.

Table 4.2 shows this information. Five out of the ten reviewed RAs were designed to be executed during the *threat assessment*, which is a process during phase I. This process produces an output that is based on a great amount of data that was collected during the preceding processes: *general site description*, *documentation of the site conditions*, and *historical survey*. The results of the *threat assessment* are relevant for the design of the *survey process*, *data processing*, and *data interpretation* during phase II. This corresponds to the fact that all of these RAs were sorted into category 3 (site management) for RC2 (level of decision-making), category 4 (development project) for RC4 (spatial scale), and category 3 (months) for RC5 (temporal scale). Three RAs cannot be integrated into the EOD framework since they are assessing risk at a more strategic level of decision-making. They are dealing with UXO risk in a more general sense, not with EOD risk. RA8 and RA9 were also not designed to be integrated into the EOD framework. Since they address the risk to marine mammals that arises due to the execution of *in situ detonation*, they could be used to support the preparation of a noise protection concept. These are the only two existing RAs that produce results that can be used during one of the key processes. Table 4.2 also includes a reminder that the purpose of the EOD RA is to guide all three key processes, a requirement that is not met by any of the existing methods.

By reviewing existing RA methods that address either UXO or EOD, it has become apparent that none of them meets the requirements of the EOD RA. Accordingly, two gaps were identified, which the EOD RA should close.

Methodological Gap: A quantitative RA tool that enables applied decision-making on a small spatial and a short-term temporal scale that focuses more on the probability component of risk than on the consequence component.

EOD Workflow Gap: An RA tool that allows determining the risk for the key processes before making an EOD decision.

TABLE 4.2: RA methods and their applicability to the EOD framework.

Risk Assessment	Execution During	Results Apply to
RA1	Threat assessment (phase I)	Phase II
RA2	Not applicable	Not applicable
RA3	Threat assessment (phase I)	Phase II
RA4	Threat assessment (phase I)	Phase II
RA5	Not applicable	Not applicable
RA6	Threat assessment (phase I)	Phase II
RA7	Not applicable	Not applicable
RA8	In situ destruction (phase IV)	In situ destruction (phase IV)
RA9	In situ destruction (phase IV)	In situ destruction (phase IV)
RA10	Threat assessment (phase I)	Phase II
EOD RA	UXO identification (phase IV)	Key processes (phase IV)

4.4 Conclusion—The Case for a Novel Method for EOD RA

Chapter 4 offers an overview of the existing RA methods that deal in one way or another with UXO or EOD in the offshore environment. It does so by first providing some theoretical background knowledge on the concept of risk and by selecting a definition of ‘risk’ for this dissertation. Next, it introduces a categorisation tool for RA methods that helps define the requirements of the method for the assessment of EOD risk. This classification is then used to review a series of existing RA methods, with the outcome that none of them fulfil the requirements of an EOD RA. Accordingly, H_{iii} can be accepted.

H_{iii} : Existing methods are insufficient to assess EOD risk.

Chapter 3 revealed that the three key processes of UXO handling called *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery* are not covered in depth in most of the investigated EOD procedures. This shows that the level of attention that is dedicated to the actual clearance and disposal work is rather low. One may even say it is insufficient. Consequentially, the outcome of Chapter 4 is that no dedicated RA method for these processes exists. The gaps that were identified in this chapter show the need for a new EOD RA method that specifically addresses the key processes. It is necessary to establish an applied, mostly quantitative method that focuses on the probability component and assesses the short-term risk of EOD work on a very small spatial scale. The development and demonstration of such a method are the principle goals of this thesis. The following chapter takes a deep dive into this development and describes the novel method exhaustively.

Chapter 5

Development and Description of the EOD RA Model

The previous chapters established background knowledge about UXO and EOD. Furthermore, existing RA methods that deal with UXO and EOD were reviewed. The lack of a dedicated EOD RA method was identified. Accordingly, this chapter describes the development, components, function, and limitations of the new EOD RA model. The resulting EOD RA model is referred to as the Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded underwater Military Munitions (RUMMs).

5.1 Background of the EOD RA Model

As was described in 4.2.2, a model that answers the requirements for EOD RA is needed. Accordingly, a model that illustrates and represents the interrelationships of factors related to EOD risk was developed.

The model is based on the principle of a bow-tie diagram. Such diagrams are a popular way to graphically represent risk. At its centre, an undesired event (UE) is located, which can also be referred to as a ‘top event’ [295] or an ‘initiating event’ [277]. Figure 5.1 is a bow-tie diagram that displays the most basic version of the EOD RA model. UE is surrounded by grey areas that mark the causal and consequential picture. The causal picture that leads up to UE is depicted to its left. It can be represented by a fault tree. The consequential picture that leads away from UE unfolds on its right and can be represented by an event tree. [277, 295] Theoretically, both sides could expand infinitely to imitate the complexity of reality. However, since this is a model, the dashed ellipse represents the scope of the bow-tie diagram and therefore the RA. The scale-free arrow ‘Causal progression’ illustrates the fact that a development takes place in the x-direction of the diagram. Even though there is a temporal aspect to this causal progression, the arrow does not represent the linear passing of time.

The causal picture is comprised of three interacting systems that jointly impact the materialisation of UE, i.e., whether it occurs or not. These systems are the ‘UXO object’, the ‘EOD procedure’, and the natural ‘Environment’. Each of these systems has properties

FIGURE 5.1: Basic EOD RA model as a bow-tie diagram.

that impact other properties of itself and of the other systems. These systems and their properties were described in 2.2, 3.3 and 3.4, respectively. If UE occurs, all three systems are, to some extent, relevant. The extent of their contribution to UE or the prevention thereof varies depending on the properties of the UXO object, the local environmental conditions, and the used EOD technology. The sizes of the areas that are allocated to the systems in Figure 5.1 do not signify the extent to which they contribute to UE.

The consequential picture is not subdivided into interacting systems but represents the ‘Risk receptors’ that potentially suffer the consequences of UE. The area right of UE marks how the consequences for these risk receptors may unfold. The risk receptors could be regarded as multiple individual systems. However, since the EOD RA model focuses on very specific risk receptors, they are viewed as one system (see 5.5).

The yellow, blue, and red arrows connecting and self-connecting the systems represent the relationships that are relevant for EOD RA. Even though the different systems impact each other as a whole, the arrows do not only represent these high-level relationships. Instead, the arrows are convergent representations of the lower-level control that certain properties of the systems have over other properties of the same or another system. Each of the systems in the causal picture is the starting and ending point of a looped arrow (yellow). These signify that each system has properties that impact other properties of itself. The blue arrows connect both the ‘EOD procedure’ and the ‘environment’ to the ‘UXO object’ as well as the ‘environment’ to the ‘EOD procedure’. Following the logic laid out above, they signify the impacts of one system’s properties on the properties of another one.

The presence and therefore the properties of the UXO object determine the possibility of UE occurring. In other words, if no UXO object existed, there would be no UE and thus no risk. Properties of the ‘UXO object’ influence properties of the ‘risk receptors’ through UE. This idea is represented by the red arrow.

A disadvantage of bow-tie diagrams is their limited flexibility when it comes to depicting dynamic real-world scenarios [295]. It is the opinion of the author that this limitation is mainly connected to treating the left side of the bow-tie diagram as a fault tree. A fault tree analysis investigates the relationship between the failure of a system and the failure of one of its components [277]. This is a useful approach when analysing technical systems

over which the operators have a maximum level of control, for example, as should be the case for an airplane. It is less suitable for operating a known system (e.g., an ROV) in the highly dynamic underwater environment while handling an object over which a limited amount of information is available (e.g., a UXO object). Even if the UXO object was thoroughly investigated and identified in preparation for the key processes (see 3.2.2), uncertainty remains due to the ageing of the object, the great variety of UXO that exists, and the challenging environmental conditions. Accordingly, instead of using a fault tree, the network of UXO and environmental properties that was developed in Chapters 2 and 3 is used to represent the left side of the bow-tie diagram. As is discussed in 5.5, it is not necessary to model the right side of the diagram at all. The extent of this chapter demonstrates that diligent investigation of factors results in a highly complex RA model, even if only the left side of the bow-tie diagram is used.

5.2 Development Process of RUMMs

The model that is presented in this chapter and used in Chapter 6 was developed through an approach that combined an iterative literature review with expert involvement. The development process is depicted in Figure 5.2.

When the process was initiated, an output of the author's previous work was used as a principle resource. During the initial familiarisation with the issue of offshore UXO, a primary literature review had been conducted. To provide structure to this orientation process, a list of factor dependencies related to the topic of offshore UXO was produced. This process yielded a directory of over 250 factor dependencies (including duplicates), each of which consisted of two or more factors. Factors were the properties of UXO, the environment, and EOD methods. They, therefore, corresponded to the systems in Figure 5.1. However, since the list had been produced before the EOD framework (see 3.2) was developed, it featured factors that were irrelevant for the key processes (see 3.2.2). In other words, it concerned the entire EOD procedure. Examples of factors that are insignificant for the key processes are *UXO Magnetic Moment*, *Survey Line Spacing*, and *Sediment Electrical Conductivity*. All of these are only relevant for phase II of the EOD framework.

The factor dependencies were used to produce a UXO factor network of 104 factors and their dependencies. While not all previously listed connections were included, the network still showed the interconnectedness of the many different factors and illustrated the complexity of the UXO problem. However, for several reasons, this factor network could not be used for RA. Similar to the previously generated list, the network included many factors that were irrelevant to the key processes. Furthermore, the sheer number of factors made it impossible to use the network for a comprehensible RA. For some factors, the amount of available literature turned out to be insufficient to reliably include them in the model. Some of these are briefly introduced in 5.8. Finally, since it was purely based

FIGURE 5.2: Development process of RUMMs.

on a literature review without corrective measures by the author and a revision by experts, the level of detail throughout the network varied significantly. Nevertheless, it served as a starting point for the development of RUMMs.

Once the gaps in RA methods for EOD had been identified (see 4.3.8), version 1 of the model was draughted (step 1 in Figure 5.2). For this purpose, a significant number of factors were deleted from the network, and it was redesigned to be directed at the ‘undesired detonation’ as the undesired event. Subsection 5.3.2 substantiates this. Version 1 of the model featured 33 factors (19 UXO, 14 ENV). The UXO factors were further subdivided: 5 general, 3 casing, 5 charge, and 6 ignition chain. The model featured 4 interim model outputs (*Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Suggested EOD Method*, *Probability of Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of Undesired Detonation*) and one final model output (*Risk of Detonation*). This first version of the model is shown in Appendix 2.

Expert workshops were conducted as a means to validate the model. The 1st EOD RA workshop was conducted on September 6, 2021 (step 2 in Figure 5.2) It was attended by nine experts. Seven of them held a certificate of competence per § 20 SprengG or a similar certificate issued internationally or by the military. Of the other experts, one was invited due to their expertise in EOD risk management and the other due to their expertise in explosive materials. The workshop pursued two goals. The first was to validate the existing model and make the necessary changes. The second aim was to define the nature of the relationships between factors and the resulting model outputs. The 1st EOD RA workshop was opened by an introductory presentation by the author. Subsequently, experts were asked to identify both irrelevant and missing factors and comment on the relationships between the factors as displayed in the model. Minutes of the workshop that detail the execution of the session and summarise the experts’ comments are available in Appendix 3. Each comment is presented with a note by the author. When a comment was accepted, the note explains how the model was adapted. When rejected, the note argues why. Furthermore, experts were invited to vote both on the normalisation of factors to model

outputs (see 5.9.4) and on the weightings that should be used during risk calculations (see 5.9.5). Based on the votes, it was determined that expert consensus was reached for 8 out of 17 normalisation relationships and for 12 out of 17 weightings. The four types of relationships that were offered to the experts and that are featured in RUMMs are described in 5.9.4. The significance of the weightings is described in 5.9.5. The voting results of the workshop are shown in Appendix 4 and in greater detail in the supplementary data [296].

Following the workshop, the model was adapted in consideration of the comments of the experts. Based on further literature research, it was continuously amended. The result was version 2 of the model (step 3 in Figure 5.2), which is shown in Appendix 5. Not all changes to the model are specifically explained here, and the reader is referred to the appendix for a comparison of versions 1 and 2. However, some crucial improvements are briefly listed here.

- To reflect on the different states of knowledge before and after the process *UXO identification*, two model layouts were developed: the planning layout and the confirmed layout.
- The model output *Risk of Detonation* was deleted, since experts considered it to be too crude.
- The personnel and equipment at the EOD site were defined as the *risk receptors*. This was done during the 1st EOD RA workshop to allow experts to perform the workshop tasks. For a detailed explanation, see 5.5.
- *Suggested EOD Method* was deleted as a model output. The risk model cannot suggest an EOD method as the selection depends on other factors (e.g., availability; see 3.3.2) than risk. Instead, its risk value can be used to support decision-making during the selection of an EOD method (see 5.11.8).

This version of the planning layout featured a total of 37 factors (21 UXO, 16 ENV). The UXO factors were distributed among subcategories: 7 general, 3 casing, 5 charge, and 6 ignition chain. At this stage, the confirmed layout featured 25 factors (14 UXO, 11 ENV). The UXO factors were subdivided as follows: 3 general, 1 casing, 4 charges, and 6 ignition chain. Both model layouts featured three model outputs: (*Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*).

Two additional workshops were conducted on October 21 and 26, 2021 (step 4 in Figure 5.2). Participation was offered to the attendees of the 1st EOD RA workshop. It was not possible to find a single date that suited all the experts who were interested in participating. The workshops were attended by three experts each. The main goal of both workshops was to discuss and define the relationships between those factors and model outputs, for which no consensus had been reached during the 1st EOD RA workshop. The sessions were opened with a presentation by the author. Subsequently, each of the factors that were up for discussion was debated by the participants. Arguments on how to handle them in the context of the model were exchanged. Minutes of the 2nd EOD RA

workshops (Groups A and B) are available in Appendices 6 and 7. Again, each statement by the experts is commented on by the author. In a similar fashion to the previous workshop, experts were asked to vote on the normalisations and weightings of the discussed factors. This time, voting led to consensus for 5 of the remaining 9 normalisation relationships. For the remainder, no clear result could be achieved, so a reasoned decision had to be made by the author. Voting on the weighting yielded consensus on all 5 of the remaining factors. The poll results and decisions regarding the normalisation types are documented in Appendix 8 and in greater detail in the supplementary data [297]. Note that the weights in the supplementary data differ from the information used throughout this dissertation. This is due to the correction of an error that was identified after the submission of this dissertation. The effects of this correction on the subsequent work presented here can be neglected.

Based on this output and under consideration of continued literature research, a third and releasable version of RUMMs (in both layouts) was devised (step 5 in Figure 5.2). Even though numerous adaptations were made to both layouts, none were as significant as the bullet points for the preceding update that were listed above. No changes were made to model outputs in either layout. The ultimate versions of both model layouts are described and displayed in 5.6.

5.3 Undesired Events

A decision of great importance during the development of RUMMs was the identification of the undesired event. It is the central element of the bow-tie diagram, to which other design decisions and the content of the model must be tailored. It was, therefore, necessary to identify potential undesired events that are related to UXO and EOD and to thoroughly select and define the one that shall be the focus of RUMMs.

This section is structured as follows: the next subsection presents an overview of undesired events that are related to the presence of UXO or the execution of EOD activities. The review is based both on the knowledge of potential adverse effects that was summarised in 2.3, and on the RAs that were reviewed in 4.3. The subsequent subsection describes and scopes the ‘undesired detonation’ that will be the undesired event assessed by RUMMs.

5.3.1 Undesired Events Related to UXO and EOD

In the existing literature, there is no comprehensive assessment of undesired events related to EOD. A very general classification of undesired UXO events is the distinction of (I) direct physical contact, (II) contamination, and (III) detonation [35]. The description of potential negative effects of UXO in 2.3 includes numbers II and III of this classification. Number I can be integrated into the other two classes when disregarding CWAs, as the risk from direct physical contact acts through contamination or detonation. There exists one review paper in which 21 so-called ‘UXO Risk Events’ were identified [289], all of which may also be referred to as ‘undesired’. The review does not define the term ‘UXO Risk Event’, nor does it provide a scope. As a consequence, it lists a wide variety of events.

Nonetheless, a basic categorisation of the listed events is possible. These categories are ‘undesired detonation’, ‘UXO compounds’, ‘presence of UXO’, and various intentional events.

Undesired detonation: All events that are assigned to this category are unintentional detonations. These may be initiated accidentally due to anthropogenic activities. The study does not mention it, but EOD is among the activities and may lead to an undesired detonation.

UXO compounds: This category concerns properties that are inherent to chemical compounds contained within UXO. On top of being high explosives, many compounds in conventional UXO have properties that may cause adverse consequences (see 2.3.2). The release of such compounds is an undesired event that may occur during EOD.

Presence of UXO: The events in this category refer to the presence of UXO at a location, which is better described as a threat than a risk. It is the purpose of EOD to remove UXO and eliminate this hazard. The presence of a UXO, therefore, does not qualify as an undesired event for an EOD RA.

Intentional events: The events assigned to this category are strongly related to EOD, which is a risky activity. However, they are intentional and therefore do not qualify as undesired events for EOD RA.

Out of the list, the categories ‘undesired detonation’ and the release of ‘UXO compounds’ can serve as undesired events that may occur due to EOD activities. The purpose of this dissertation is to develop a model for EOD RA. To maintain a clear scope, it was decided to define the personnel and equipment at the EOD location as the risk receptors (see 5.5). Since the negative consequences of the leakage of ‘UXO compounds’ do not usually affect these risk receptors, this event is not assessed in this study. The ‘undesired detonation’, however, may occur during EOD and have an immediate impact on personnel and equipment at the EOD location. It is therefore placed at the centre of the bow-tie diagram as the undesired event that is assessed by RUMMs.

5.3.2 Undesired Detonation

The ‘undesired detonation’ was chosen as the undesired event of RUMMs. To define the scope of this term, it is helpful to understand the different reasons why detonations of UXO can occur.

Type 1: A detonation that accidentally occurs during either of the key processes while handling the UXO object.

Type 2: An intentional detonation that takes place during the phase IV key process *in situ destruction* (see 3.3.3).

Type 3: A detonation that is an accidental transition from a low-order detonation or deflagration to a high-order detonation or a case in which the use of a low-order method leads to an accidental high-order event (see 5.4.1). These possibilities can occur as part of the *in situ destruction*.

Type 4: An unexplained explosion (see 5.4.2).

Type 5: A detonation that occurs due to an inadvertent interaction with a UXO object by a stakeholder that operates at sea, such as the offshore construction industry, fisheries, or shipping (see 2.3.1).

Detonation types 2 through 5 are not assessed in this dissertation. Type 2 is an intentional detonation, and thus the risk receptors will not be present during the detonation. The same is true for type 3. While it is unintentional, the uncertainties connected to low-order detonation and low-order methods require the absence of the risk receptors during their execution. Type 4 is part of the unavoidable residual risk of working offshore (see 5.4.2). While it is possible to perform a dedicated RA for this matter, its relevant aspects will be inherently included in RUMMs. Finally, type 5 is not connected to EOD and thus is not relevant to this dissertation. This leaves type 1, which can accidentally occur during *underwater transfer, in situ destruction, or recovery*, as the undesired event of RUMMs.

The process that follows after the *recovery* of UXO is *storage and transport*. Since the latter was not defined as a key process in 3.2.2, any detonation that takes place on the vessel or on land is not assessed by RUMMs. To maintain scope, it was decided that the model only applies as long as UXO is below the water surface. The moment it is lifted out of the water, another RA will have to be performed. While many aspects of RUMMs will also be relevant for an RA of UXO above the surface, the model is not considered valid for any activity following the key processes.

5.4 Exceptions, Inherent Risk and Residual Risk

To further clarify the scope of RUMMs, additional explanations are necessary. It should be understood that life in general and working underwater, in particular [206], are inherently risky. Inherent risk is the risk that exists before any action is taken to manage it. The risk that remains after risk management is applied is referred to as residual risk. [298] This residual risk depends on the amount of time, effort, and resources that one is willing to invest in risk reduction measures or another strategy to address the risk (see 4.1). Essentially, the ALARP principle (see 4.3.6) is applied either knowingly or unknowingly to determine the amount of risk that is acceptable to remain as residual risk. Even if infinite time, effort, and resources were available and would be applied, it is usually not possible to reduce the risk to zero. This is because some aspects of life are simply beyond human control, and other risks cannot be identified due to them being ‘perfect storms’ or ‘black swans’. The former refers to the unpredictable randomness of rare known events that are coinciding. The latter refers to so-called ‘unknown unknowns’, i.e., events that one does not even know that they do not know about. [299] Since no risk reduction is possible for these issues, other strategies must be applied. These may be to tolerate, transfer, or terminate (see 4.1). To terminate is not a viable strategy for the issue at hand; the underlying notion of this study is that EOD is a necessary activity. It would therefore require not performing EOD at all. To transfer is a strategy that could be applied by purchasing insurance. However, since human life is at stake, it is impossible to transfer risk

without treating (i.e., managing) it. This leaves tolerating a certain amount of residual risk. Subsections 5.4.2 addresses one such aspect. By definition, no black swans or perfect storms can be addressed.

This section helps to distinguish between the type 1 detonation (the undesired event of RUMMs) and types 2, 3, and 4. Type 5 does not require further specifications to differentiate it from type 1.

5.4.1 Detonations and Safety Distances

This subsection deals with type 2 and 3 detonations. As described in 3.3.3, a distinction between high- and low-order detonations and deflagration, as well as high- and low-order methods, can be made. All these methods are part of the key process *in situ destruction*. This description does not include any operations of preparing a UXO object for *in situ destruction*, such as the placement of a detonator charge. It only refers to the time when the remotely performed *in situ destruction* itself takes place.

As described in 2.2.9, explosive materials are sensitive to heat. The temperature increase that occurs during the application of a low-order method may lead to an unwanted detonation of the main charge. Depending on the confinement, casing material, charge mass, and main charge type, a deflagration can transition into a detonation [212]. This is due to an acceleration of the reaction velocity. The occurrence of such a deflagration to detonation transition (DDT) is more likely in ageing explosive materials [132]. To operate under the uncertainty that is connected to these methods, work always needs to be conducted in such a manner as if a high-order detonation were conducted. A DDT that occurred with a so-called ‘Tallboy’ bomb demonstrates that caution is advisable. [111] Accordingly, safety distances during *in situ destruction* must always be designed to meet the requirements of a high-order detonation of the UXO object in question. Depending on the reference that is consulted, the recommended calculation of safety distances varies [e.g., 43, 51].

Accordingly, from a risk management perspective, deflagration and low-order methods are treated like planned high-order detonations. In other words, if a type 3 detonation (DDT or accidental high-order) occurs, it is treated as if it were a type 2 detonation. Since a type 2 detonation is executed on purpose, it cannot be assessed with RUMMs. The same therefore applies to type 3.

5.4.2 Unexplained Explosion

UXO may detonate for unknown reasons (type 4 detonation). This phenomenon has been labelled ‘self-detonation’ [3], ‘spontaneous detonation’, and ‘spontaneous explosion’ [35]. These terms are collectively misleading. They are used in cases in which the root cause of an explosion of UXO is not traceable. The lack of traceability does not, however, signify that a root cause is absent. Most certainly this type of ‘extraordinary initiation scenario’ is caused by a prior entry of energy [71]. It may be related to corrosion, chemical initiation of a long-period delay detonator, or mechanical stress [290]. The event is therefore neither self-inflicted by UXO nor does it take place spontaneously without the occurrence of some external mechanism. One source uses the term ‘self-detonation’

in instances in which UXO was impacted by anthropogenic actions [290], which makes it even less applicable. The literature has focused on detonation events, presumably due to their high potential impact and the availability of technology to record them. Nonetheless, a deflagration event may occur for the same reasons that are laid out above. For all these reasons, henceforth the term ‘unexplained explosion’ is used.

In 2005, the British Geological Survey (BGS) reported on the number of recorded underwater explosions in the Beaufort’s Dyke area between 1992 and 2004. This abyssal channel between Scotland and Northern Ireland was used as a UXO dump site until 1976. Of the 47 recorded explosions with values above 1.5 ML (Richter local magnitude), only 13 were confirmed to be deliberate. Of the unconfirmed explosions, two were explicitly checked with various sources, but no confirmation that they were intentional was given. The report states that it was not standard practice to investigate the origin of underwater explosions. Thus, these events may either be unreported deliberate explosions or unexplained explosions. [265] It has been claimed that this report confirms the existence of unexplained explosions [e.g., 41, 290, 132] which is incorrect. According to one report, by 2014, no evidence for the unexplained explosions had been documented [54]. Still, the report constitutes supporting evidence that the phenomenon exists. This is further supported by other reports of unexplained explosions at Beaufort’s Dyke. It was reported that 25 unexplained events, such as explosions, took place in the area between 1988 and 1996 [300]. An additional article mentions that BGS measured eight unexplained explosions in 1995 [301]. Finally, a former Royal Navy diver mentioned in an interview that every month, up to three explosions take place in the Irish Sea, a claim that has not been further substantiated [302].

One unexplained explosion event was reported to have taken place in 1980 in Lake Lömtjärn, Sweden. An undisclosed amount of explosive ordnance had been dumped in the lake between 1950 and 1980. [303]

In the study area, some unexplained events have been associated with spontaneous explosions. One source lists seven events of unexplained detonation in the German Baltic Sea between 1945 and 2007. One of these events was initiated by anthropogenic impact and can therefore be ignored, leaving a total of six unexplained explosions. [290]

The effects of ageing on the likelihood to explode (see 2.2.9) and the effects of an explosion (see 2.3.1) apply to unexplained explosions in the same way they apply to deliberate or accidental explosions. It is therefore relevant during key processes. However, the ambiguity of unexplained explosions’ root causes makes them infeasible for this study. In addition, the overwhelming majority of the above information suggests that unexplained explosions that are most likely initiated by natural and other external effects surrounding UXO are extremely rare events [237, 304]. For these reasons, the risk of unexplained explosions is considered part of the residual risk. Once the operations of the key processes temper with a UXO object, unexplained explosions become irrelevant by definition. Any risk event that may occur after work on the UXO object starts is not ‘unexplained’, but is attributed to the respective EOD action.

5.5 Risk Receptors

One of the first comments during the 1st EOD RA workshop was the request to clearly define risk receptors. Referring back to the bow-tie diagram in Figure 5.1, it is clear that the risk receptors are a relevant aspect of the consequence side of the model, i.e., to the right of the undesired event. The idea of a clear definition of a risk receptor is surprisingly absent from much of the theoretical risk literature. References that were used to inform about the concept of risk and the use of the bow-tie diagram do not mention it [277, 275, 294, 295]. The picture is different for applied literature. Out of the ten RAs that were reviewed in 4.3, five explicitly mention risk receptors (*RA1*, *RA3*, *RA4*, *RA9*, and *RA10*). Another four do not use the term but implicitly define at least one risk receptor for the execution of their methodology (*RA5*, *RA6*, *RA7*, and *RA8*). While in some cases the definitions lack specificity, the regular use of the concept shows its importance in applied RA. Only *RA2* neither defines nor applies the concept.

One approach for RA is the SPRC model. It was used by *RA4* and first introduced in 4.3.2. The R stands for ‘receptor’ and hence it is useful to adapt it to RUMMs. According to one definition, receptors in the sense of the SPRC approach are natural, physical, or socio-economic values that are potentially exposed to risk [305]. According to another paper, the receptor (together with the source (S) and pathway (P)) is part of the physical world, while the consequences (C) are a societal construct [306]. Receptors can be people, property, communities, infrastructure, the environment [307] or parts thereof. Receptors that can be affected by an undesired detonation during EOD can be people (crew, divers, and passengers), equipment (vessels and infrastructure), the natural environment (marine mammals, birds, other fauna, and habitats), and even historic sites (shipwrecks) [46]. While this list is not comprehensive, it demonstrates the sheer number of receptors that could be included in an EOD RA. It is noteworthy that *ISO 31000: Risk management — Guidelines* does not mention risk receptors, perhaps because it is implied that the organisation that is performing risk management (and, therefore, risk assessment) is the risk receptor under investigation [278].

Clearly defining one or several risk receptors helps set the system’s boundaries. Approaching RA without it can easily lead to a loss of focus when it comes to the description of the potential consequences of an undesired event. To avoid this, the potential consequences that are explored in an RA should be directly assignable to risk receptors. With all of the above in mind, it was decided that the risk receptors of RUMMs are the ‘personnel and equipment at the EOD site’ while handling UXO. It also includes the vessel, equipment, and personnel at the surface, as well as all equipment or personnel that are located below the surface and are not directly handling the object. For risk receptors at the surface, RUMMs is only valid if they are not keeping a safe distance. As soon as they maintain this distance, they are considered not to be at risk. When referring to equipment under water, risk receptors may be ROVs or crawlers, as well as the tools

they are carrying. Supporting equipment, such as storage baskets or lifting balloons, is also included. The obvious normative difference in the consequences for personnel when compared to equipment is addressed in 5.9.3.

The right side of the bow-tie diagram (see 5.1) represents how the consequences of an undesired event for the risk receptors may unfold. For the undesired detonation and the personnel and equipment at the EOD site, there is an extremely high level of immediacy. This means that if the undesired detonation occurs, the risk receptors will be instantly and almost certainly affected. For this reason, the right side of the bow-tie diagram, i.e., the pathway from the undesired detonation to the risk receptors, was not modelled. Instead, the consequences were directly modelled as a function of factors on the left side of the bow-tie diagram. How this works becomes evident in the description and depiction of RUMMs (see 5.6).

During the 1st EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 3), one group remarked that risk receptors may be insured and, thus, the risk would be transferred to the insurance (see 4.1). While this is economically true, it does not protect affected personnel from the risk of physical and psychological harm or death, nor does it immediately replace lost equipment. The notion of risk transfer is therefore ignored.

5.6 The Two Model Layouts

RUMMs consists of factors (nodes) and relationships (paths) connecting the factors. Following the discussion during the 1st EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 3), two RUMMs layouts were developed that represent different levels of knowledge during the EOD procedure before the execution of the key processes. The following two subsections provide an overall introduction to the two model layouts. The precise meaning of the individual factors and their relationships is explained in detail in 5.7 and 5.9. For the description of the relationships between nodes, the terms ‘parent’ and ‘child’ are used. A parent factor is an input to a child factor. The former is, therefore, further upstream in the model. A factor can be a parent, a child, or both of one or several other factors.

5.6.1 RUMMs—Planning Layout

The planning layout of RUMMs is shown in Figure 5.3. It picks up the network of UXO and environmental properties that was developed in 2.2 and 3.4. The model layout features a total of 34 factors (21 UXO factors, 10 environmental factors, and 3 EOD factors). The UXO factors can be subdivided into the categories general (8 factors), casing (3 factors), charge (7 factors), and fuse (3 factors). The layout has 3 model outputs. Most factors have two boxes underneath their names. They contain the value range of the factor (see 5.7) and the unit in which it is measured. A dash means that no unit exists and that the factor is quantified by an index (e.g., the model outputs) or that it is a date (e.g., *Planned EOD Date*). The factors *Sediment Type* and *Casing Material* can be filled out with the options shown in the box that is shown underneath their names. For factors without such boxes, too many options exist to display them in this figure.

FIGURE 5.3: Planning layout of RUMMs.

FIGURE 5.4: Confirmed layout of RUMMs.

The factors are connected by paths. A solid line represents a regular connection, which refers to all paths that are represented through functions that are implemented in the RUMMs file. A user of RUMMs does not need to use all of these functions to successfully produce model results. How and when it is possible not to use a path is outlined in the descriptions of the individual factors in 5.7.1 through 5.7.30. A chain line signifies a connection where a factor is normalised and weighted as a parent of the model outputs. Subsections 5.9.4 and 5.9.5 explain the meaning of these operations.

The prohibition signs that are shown on three of the chain lines indicate that these factors have a limitation of use (LoU), a concept that is introduced in 5.10.1. Finally, the dashed lines show connections where a parent factor influences a child factor in reality, but this is not implemented in the model. This is either the case because it was not technically possible to implement an operation into the model or because measuring or researching the value of the child factor will produce better results than can be achieved through a function in the model. This notion is exemplified by the factor *UXO Type*, which has nine child factors. To enable automatically filling all these child nodes based on the *UXO Type* would have required connecting the model to a comprehensive UXO database. This was not possible within the scope of the dissertation, as it is not a software development project.

The underlying rationale of the planning layout is that it is useful to perform an RA, even before an EOD expert has been able to visually inspect UXO. This requirement could occur during planning processes throughout the EOD procedure, for example, during the *call for tender and contract award for phases III and IV*. Subsection 6.4.2 provides information on how to implement the use of the model into the EOD framework. During this stage, many assumptions (e.g., on the *Condition of Casing* and the *Fuse Corrosion State*) must be made. The model supports this by calculating values for these factors. Initial knowledge on the possible *UXO Type* that may be present in an area and values for its child factors should have been collected during the phase I process *historical survey*. Information on the *Latitude* and *Longitude* (i.e., the location of a UXO object) and their corresponding child factors ought to be available as a result of the processes *documentation of the site conditions* (phase I), *survey process* (phase II), or both. Using the planning layout requires diligent research. As with any model, the quality of the output data depends on the quality of the input data.

5.6.2 RUMMs—Confirmed Layout

RUMMs in the confirmed layout, as shown in Figure 5.4, comprises of a total of 23 factors (14 UXO factors, 6 environmental factors, and 3 EOD factors). The UXO factors can be subdivided in the following way: 3 general factors, 1 casing factor, 7 charge factors, and 3 fuse factors. It produces 3 model outputs. The depiction of the layout in Figure 5.4 uses the same style of nodes and types of lines that are used for the planning layout. The value ranges and units of the factors, as well as the use of LoUs, are identical as well.

The confirmed layout is designed in such a way that it can be used after the phase IV process *UXO identification*, during which the UXO object and its properties are investigated, ideally visually. During this process, information on many of the UXO factors is obtained, for which the planning layout requires auxiliary calculations and functions. An example is the *Condition of Casing*. Other factors, such as the *Wind Speed* can be measured on location without having to rely on the model to provide representative values, as would be the case for the planning layout. While the model still offers the option to automatically determine a representative value, measuring a value or obtaining a near-future value, for example, from the weather forecast, is preferable. Due to access to more immediate information, the confirmed layout is less complicated and contains fewer factors and relationships. The factors that are included in the planning layout but not in the confirmed layout are listed below. However, the number of parent factors for the model outputs remains the same, as does the way the outputs are computed.

- Original Casing Thickness
- Casing Material
- UXO Shortest Dimension
- Year Sunk
- Time Sunk
- Time Unburied
- Time Buried
- Sediment Type
- Sediment Accumulation Rate
- Corrosion Rate – Unburied
- Corrosion Rate – Buried

5.7 RUMMs Factors

During the development of RUMMs as outlined in 5.2, decisions on the factors of the two model layouts were reached. This section picks up on the descriptions of all the UXO properties (see 2.2) and environmental properties (see 3.4) and explains how they function as factors in RUMMs. Each subsection describes one factor, each of which is assigned a mathematical symbol. In addition, each factor has a value range, i.e., the feature space in which its values can lie. A lower (F^{min}) and an upper (F^{max}) boundary determine the limits of the value range. Many factors, albeit not all, have a unit. All of the above is given in the descriptive text. Some factors appear in both the planning and the confirmed layout; others only exist in one of them. In rare cases, a factor is present in both layouts but works differently. In this case, they are symbolised as F^P and F^C respectively. Factors with an LoU are shown as F^l .

Furthermore, the subsections describe the relationships. A factor's description always includes a detailed explanation of its relationship with its parents (i.e., factors that provide it with input) and children (i.e., factors that it provides input for). Where applicable, the

reader is presented with the formula that is used to express the relationships in the model. RUMMs uses basic mathematical operations that are not specifically introduced to the reader. In some cases, a ceiling function ($\lceil x \rceil$) is used to express that a value is rounded up.

A paradigm that was constantly applied during the development of RUMMs was that of conservative RA. When dealing with uncertainty, RUMMs was always designed in such a way that it calculates higher values for model outputs (which represent higher risk). Some scholars advocate that instead of conservatism, best judgements should be applied during RA to produce optimal results [e.g., 308]. During model design, this argument was ignored since it does not equate to the execution of RA. Conservative RA will lead to an overestimation rather than an underestimation of risk. RUMMs follows this paradigm because divers, whose lives are at stake, are among the risk receptors. On top of that, in EOD, it is best practice to assume the worst-case scenario. This was the consensus during the 1st EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 3). For the same reasons, the descriptions of the factors advise the user to enter conservative values. If the key processes are executed without personnel under water, the user may be less conservative if they are willing to tolerate the risk for their equipment (see 4.1).

This section acts as a manual for using both RUMMs layouts. To use the model, the user should follow the instructions given in the grey boxes, as exemplified below. If the description of a factor does not include a box for user instructions, no action is required. RUMMs was developed as an Excel tool and can be downloaded from a GEOMAR repository¹ [309].

User Instruction

The user should follow the instructions given in these grey boxes. They always refer to the sheet ‘2. Input and Output’ of the RUMMs Excel tool, which is shown in Figure 5.5. If a factor description does not contain such a blue box, no action by the user is required.

5.7.1 Location

The location where the EOD operation takes place impacts all environmental factors that are part of the model. Section 3.4 introduces environmental properties affecting EOD and establishes that all of them are location-dependent. The location is expressed as a pair of coordinates for *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}).

ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} are available in both model layouts. ϕ_{EOD} ranges from 52.871° North to 55.919° North, and λ_{EOD} ranges from 3.350° East to 14.750° East. These coordinates are the outer limits of the German inland waters, territorial sea, and EEZ. Locations that lie outside the study area should not be entered.

In the planning layout, *Latitude* and *Longitude* always act as parents to *Visual Range Under Water*, *Corrosion Rate*, and *Sediment Accumulation Rate*. They may furthermore be parents to *Current Velocity* and *Wind Speed* if the user is not able to obtain this information from other sources. In the confirmed layout, the location entered by the user

¹<https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/59931/>

RUMMs Model Layout						
Model Layout		Selection		Remark		
Planning Layout						
Confirmed Layout				Please select one of the model layouts by entering "x" in the respective cell.		
Planning Factors						
Factor	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
Latitude	ϕ_{EOD}	52.871	55.919		' (decimal degrees)	
Longitude	λ_{EOD}	3.350	14.750		' (decimal degrees)	
Planned EOD Date	PD	07.01.2025				
UXO Risk Factors						
UXO Type	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
UXO Mass	m_u		1	1300	kg	
UXO Longest Dimension	l_l		20	3000	mm	
UXO Shortest Dimension	l_s		20	1000	mm	
Year Sunk	T		1914	1949	-	
Casing						
Factor	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
Casing Material	CM					
Original Casing Thickness	CT _o		1.00	200.00	mm	
Condition of Casing	CC		0	5	-	
Main Charge Type						
Factor	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
Charge Mass	m_c		1	350	kg	
Fuse Type						
Factor	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
Fuse Corrosion State	FC		0	100	%	
Fuse Present	fp ₁		0	1	-	
Fuse Armed	fp ₂		0	1	-	
Fuse without Battery	fp ₃		0	1	-	
Electrolyte in Vial	fp ₄		0	1	-	
Spring Loaded/Cocked Striker, Diaphragm	fp ₅		0	1	-	
Chemical Long-Delay Fuse	fp ₆		0	1	-	
More than one Fuse	fp ₇		0	1	-	
More than one Fuse Type	fp ₈		0	1	-	
Environmental Risk Factors						
Factor	Variable	Value	Value range		Unit	Remark
			Minimum	Maximum		
Sediment Type	S		-	-	-	
Sediment Accumulation Rate	SAR		0.0	325.8	mm/a	
Burial State	B		0	100	%	
Current Velocity	v_c		0.00	1.50	m/s	
Wind Speed	v_w		0.0	50.0	m/s	
Significant Wave Height	$H_{1/2}$		0.0	3.0	m	
Visual Range Under Water	R		0.0	2.0 or l_l	m	
Water Depth	D		2	71	m	
Change of Default Settings for Limitations of Use						
Factor with Limitation of Use	Variable	Changed Default Value	Remarks			
Current Velocity	v_c		Default value for Limitation of Use = 1.50 m/s			
Significant Wave Height	$H_{1/2}$		Default value for Limitation of Use = 3.0 m			
Water Depth	D		Default value for Limitation of Use = 71 m			
Model Output						
Factor	Variable	Value	Remarks			
Probability of an Undesired Detonation	P	No layout selected				
Consequence of an Undesired Detonation	C	No layout selected				
Complexity of the EOD Operation	E	No layout selected				
Limitation of Use Exceeded	-	No layout selected				

FIGURE 5.5: RUMMs Excel tool user interface.

may influence *Visual Range Under Water*, *Current Velocity*, and *Wind Speed* if values for these factors are not acquired through other means. Otherwise, it serves no purpose in the confirmed layout.

User Instruction

The user must enter ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} in degrees and decimal degrees to the third decimal in the cells **D10** and **D11**, respectively. RUMMs has no way of retracing whether a location lies within the study area or not, and thus the user must ensure that they are located in German inland waters, the territorial sea, or the EEZ.

5.7.2 Planned EOD Date

The *Planned EOD Date (PD)* is an important piece of information for the planning layout and may be relevant for the use of the confirmed layout. It is the day on which the execution of the key processes of the EOD operation is assumed to take place.

This factor can take any value from the day on which the model is used to the future. In the rare case that it is intended to review past EOD operations, it is also possible to enter a date that lies in the past. RUMMs will still work properly.

In the planning layout, *Planned EOD Date* is required to calculate the factor *Time Sunk* and to determine seasonally representative values for *Visual Range Under Water*, *Current Velocity*, and *Wind Speed*. In the confirmed layout, it can similarly be used to estimate values for *Visual Range Under Water*, *Current Velocity*, and *Wind Speed* if no on-site values are available.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must enter *PD* in the cell **D12**. For the confirmed layout, it is possible that *PD* is not used for the calculation of model outputs. This depends on the availability of information on its child factors. Hence, the user is encouraged to always enter *PD* for the confirmed layout.

5.7.3 UXO Type

The factor *UXO Type* (*U*) is one of the starting points and initiating factors of performing RA with both model layouts. There exist thousands of different values for *U*. The munitions database of Sprengschule Dresden (i.e., the ‘Academy for Explosive Materials in Dresden’) offers a munitions database that contains 4.750 data sets on munitions types from Germany and the Allied powers, which were commonly used during WWII and subsequent conflicts [310]. It does not claim to be comprehensive. Hence, the number of different *U* that may be found in the study area is even larger.

If the planning layout is used, the results of the phase I process *historical survey*, determine which *U* must be expected in an area of interest and should thus be analysed with RUMMs. To use the confirmed layout, an EOD expert must have successfully finalised the process *UXO identification* to determine *U*.

Once the *UXO Type* is known, information on many other factors can be obtained. These factors are the *Main Charge Type*, the *Charge Mass*, the *Fuse Type*, the *UXO Mass*, and the *UXO Longest Dimension* in the planning layout. In the confirmed layout, the *Original Casing Thickness*, the *Casing Material*, the *UXO Shortest Dimension*, and the *Year Sunk* depend on it as well. The model does not automatically determine values for those child factors.

User Instruction

The user must enter *U* in cell **D15** for documentation purposes.

5.7.4 UXO Mass

A comprehensive overview of the potential mass of UXO objects was given in 2.2.2. The subsection also looked at the mass distribution of a sample of cleared UXO objects in an EOD dataset. The *UXO Mass* (m_u) depends on the *UXO Type* (*U*). Thus, after the process *UXO identification*, an EOD expert will be able to determine the m_u value.

The factor m_u has a value range from 1 kg to 1300 kg. Due to the extent of the range and the minuscule effect that changes of less than 1 kg have on the model outputs, it was decided to round values up to integers, so that m_u^{min} is 1 kg. m_u^{max} is a threshold value. Subsection 5.10.2 further specifies the rationale of thresholds in RUMMs. While the case of a so-called ‘Tallboy’ bomb in the river Świna near Szczecin shows that even UXO objects with a mass of 5391 kg may be present in the study area [111], most objects have considerably smaller masses. Hence, the threshold value was introduced. It was determined by assessing the available EOD dataset (see 2.2).

The subsample size of EOD operations for which m_u was available ($n_{m_u} = 227$) was considered sufficient to establish a representative threshold. The maximum n_m value of the dataset was 6371 kg, which was followed by 1139 kg, 963 kg, and 810 kg. Thus, to identify an appropriate m_u^{max} , it was necessary to determine whether these values are outliers or not. Looking back at the distribution of values in Figure 2.2, it appears that the data are not normally distributed. The data were therefore tested for goodness of fit to a normal, log-normal, and logarithmic distribution to check whether outlier detection methods that are appropriate for these distribution types could be applied.

To do so, the chi-square test was used. In preparation, the 227 (n_{m_u}) data entries were sorted into 20 equally large bins. Next, the expected probabilities ($P(E)$) that a given data entry of the sample lies in a certain bin were calculated for all three distributions. For the normal and log-normal distributions, $\bar{x} = 203$ kg and $s = 458$ kg (standard deviation) of the dataset were used. For the logarithmic distribution, $\lambda = \frac{1}{\bar{x}} = 0.0049$ was used. Next, the expected frequency ($f(E)$) of occurrence in each bin was calculated for all distributions by multiplying n_{m_u} with all three $P(E)$. Finally, the chi-square test was applied. P-values of 0.0002 for the normal distribution and 0 for both the log-normal and logarithmic distributions were obtained. The p-value for the normal distribution is only based on bins 1 to 12 since expected frequencies for bins 13 to 20 are so small that Excel treats them as a value of 0. As chi-square requires division by $f(E)$ and division by 0 is not possible, these bins could not be included. Given the p-values, the dataset does not follow any of the mentioned distributions. Further distributions were investigated but did not yield any relevant p-values either. Outlier detection based on distribution type is thus not possible.

Next, the data were plotted in Figure 5.6 to assess the goodness of fit visually instead of mathematically. The high $f(E)$ numbers for the normal and log-normal distributions in bin 1 can be explained by the extreme sample maximum of 6371 kg. This maximum leads to a concentration of most other entries in low bins. Surprisingly, and despite the low p-value, the plot reveals a very close fit between the actual frequency ($f(A)$, red square) and the expected frequency of the logarithmic function ($f(E_{log})$, green diamond). Again, $f(E_{log})$ is heavily dependent on the 6371 kg value, which has a large impact on the mean (\bar{x}) and thus λ . Removing this single value would change them to 175 kg and 0.0057, respectively.

Furthermore, P and f per bin were reviewed for the actual (A) data and for the expected logarithmic distribution (E_{log}). These are listed in Table 5.1. Bins 9 to 19 all have frequencies and probabilities of 0 and are therefore consolidated in one line. The table

FIGURE 5.6: Actual ($f(A)$) and expected normal ($f(E_{nor})$), log-normal ($f(E_{lon})$), and logarithmic ($f(E_{log})$) frequency distributions of the *UXO Mass* (m_u) [adapted from 107].

TABLE 5.1: Probability (P) and frequency (f) per bin of the actual (A) data and expected logarithmic (E_{log}) distribution of the *UXO Mass* (m_u) [adapted from 107].

Bin	Bin Start (kg)	Bin End (kg)	$P(A)$	$f(A)$	$P(E_{log})$	$f(E_{log})$
1	0.0	318.6	0.8062	183	0.7926	180
2	318.6	637.1	0.1454	33	0.1644	37
3	637.1	955.7	0.0352	8	0.0341	8
4	955.7	1274.2	0.0088	2	0.0071	2
5	1274.2	1592.8	0.0000	0	0.0015	0
6	1592.8	1911.3	0.0000	0	0.0003	0
7	1911.3	2229.9	0.0000	0	0.0001	0
8–19	2229.9	6052.5	0.0000	0	0.0000	0
20	6052.5	6371.0	0.0044	1	0.0000	0

shows similar values for $P(A)$ and $P(E_{log})$ and, consequentially, for $f(A)$ and $f(E_{log})$. In fact, when removing bin 20 from the chi-square test, the p-value jumps to 0.9999. While not being able to use a standardised statistical test to eliminate the value of 6371 kg as an outlier, Table 5.1 supports the process of determining a threshold for m_u^{max} . In bin 5 $f(A)$ drops to 0. The same is true for $f(E_{log})$ for a dataset with $n = 227$. The sum of all $P(E_{log})$ values for bins 5 to 20 is 0.0019, meaning that out of 1000 UXO objects, less than two will have $m_u \geq 1274.2$ kg. This bin was therefore considered critical for the threshold discussion. To arrive at a rounded value and to introduce a buffer, it was defined that $m_u^{max} = 1300$ kg. Looking back at 2.2.2, it is known that modelled weight values for m_u tend to be overestimated when compared to measured values. The value 6371 kg originated from magnetic modelling. With that in mind, 1300 kg appears to be a sound value for m_u^{max} . Any m_u entry that is larger than m_u^{max} is treated to be equal to this value by the model.

In RUMMs, the *UXO Mass* is a parent to only one factor: the model output *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. It is used that way in both model layouts.

User Instruction

The user must enter m_u in cell **D18**.

5.7.5 UXO Longest Dimension

The *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l) is another property of the UXO object (see 2.2.3). It therefore depends solely on the *UXO Type* (U). The factor exists in both model layouts. For the confirmed layout, once the phase IV process *UXO identification* has been conducted, an EOD expert will be able to determine this value for the object. For the planning layout, the value depends on the assumption that was made for U .

The factor l_l can have values ranging from 20 mm to 3000 mm. The lower value range boundary (l_l^{min}) was defined because 20 mm was the shortest dimension of all UXO in subsample n_l of the EOD dataset (see Table 2.5). Considering corrosion and other mechanisms, it is theoretically possible that smaller objects exist. The model, therefore, allows for lower values than l_l^{min} . This does not affect the contribution of l_l to the model outputs. The upper boundary of the value range (l_l^{max}) was determined by reviewing subsample n_l of the EOD dataset (Table 2.5). Even though larger UXO exists, none of the objects in the EOD database showed $l_l > 3000$ mm. In fact, there were two objects with $l_l = 3000$ mm, one object with $l_l = 2600$ mm and again two objects with $l_l = 2000$ mm. It was therefore decided to introduce a threshold value of $l_l^{max} = 3000$ mm. Since this value is rather close to other values in n_l and since the data do not follow any regular distribution type, no outlier detection like the one in 5.7.4 was performed. If the user enters a value that is larger than l_l^{max} , the model applies the threshold and continues with $l_l = 3000$ mm. For more information on the use of thresholds, see 5.10.2.

In both model layouts, the factor *UXO Longest Dimension* acts as a parent factor to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. It is also relevant for the *Visual Range Under Water*.

User Instruction

The user must enter l_l in cell **D19**.

5.7.6 UXO Shortest Dimension

The *UXO Shortest Dimension* (l_s) is another UXO factor. It is only included in the planning layout and depends on the assumed *UXO Type* (U). Some information on the value distribution for this factor is provided in 2.2.3.

The value range for l_s is 20 mm to 1000 mm. It was determined by reviewing the distribution of l_s values of subsample n_l of the EOD dataset (see Table 2.5). Objects with l_s values outside this value range may exist, especially since biofouling and corrosion can change the shape and dimensions of UXO. If such values are entered, the tool uses them, ignoring the defined value range.

This is possible because, unlike *UXO Longest Dimension*, the *UXO Shortest Dimension* does not have a threshold value and is not directly connected to a model output. It is therefore not normalised (see 5.9.4). Instead, it is a parent factor to the *Time Buried*, *Time Unburied*, and *Burial State*.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must enter l_s in cell **D20**.

5.7.7 Sediment Type

The *Sediment Type* (S) is one of the environmental properties that have an impact on the sedimentation and burial of UXO (see 3.4.1). In reality, the sediment type depends on the location where the EOD operation is planned. However, the model does not have a feature to determine S based on latitude and longitude. Hence, S has no parent factors. This means that the user has to enter it. Information on the sediment type should have been collected during the *documentation of the site conditions*, which is a process of phase I [23].

Due to the availability of measured sediment accumulation rate (SAR) data in parts of the North Sea (see 5.7.8), this factor is only utilised for the Baltic Sea. As discussed in 3.4.1, there exist different sediment classification maps, with varying numbers of sediment types, for the Baltic Sea. To allow for easy data entry into RUMMs, only three classes for S (mud and clay, sand, and hard bottom) were implemented. These classes were adapted from a dataset that was used to determine SAR in the Baltic Sea part of the study area (see 5.7.8) [311].

The *Sediment Type* is a parent factor of the *Sediment Accumulation Rate* if EOD takes place in the Baltic Sea. As the prediction of such processes is not relevant if the UXO object has already been investigated (i.e., confirmed), the factor is only included in the planning layout.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must select S from the drop-down menu in cell **D51**.

5.7.8 Sediment Accumulation Rate

The *Sediment Accumulation Rate* (SAR) is measured in mm a^{-1} . It is only included in the planning layout. Its input factors are the *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}) of the EOD operation. Due to limited data availability, RUMMs uses different functions to determine SAR in the North and Baltic Seas. If ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} are located in the North Sea, SAR depends on the *Water Depth* (D). If ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} are located in the Baltic Sea, SAR depends on the *Sediment Type* (S).

For the North Sea, SAR values were derived from the morphological evolution of the German Wadden Sea for *Water Depth* (D) ≤ 20 m. The underlying dataset was first introduced in 3.4.1 [225]. It shows annual morphological changes in the German North Sea in waters of up to 20 m depth at a resolution of 500 m * 860 m. The data were available as a netCDF file and were converted into a GeoTIFF. Using QGIS' function 'Raster pixels

to points’, the raster cells of the GeoTIFF were converted into vector points. The point coordinates and respective *SAR* values are included in the sheet ‘5. SAR North Sea’ of the RUMMs Excel tool. It uses a combination of the LOOKUP and FREQUENCY functions, as well as the haversine formula, to find the sediment accumulation value at the nearest geographical neighbour to ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} . With the haversine formula, it is possible to calculate the great-circle distance on a sphere. The haversine is a trigonometric function that is given in equation (2). Here, d is the great-circle distance between two points, and r is the radius of a sphere—in this case, planet Earth. Furthermore, ϕ_F and λ_F are the latitude and longitude of the raster cell centre coordinate from the morphological evolution data, respectively.

$$\text{hav}\left(\frac{d}{r}\right) = \sin^2\left(\frac{\phi_F - \phi_{EOD}}{2}\right) + \sin^2\left(\frac{\lambda_F - \lambda_{EOD}}{2}\right) * \cos(\phi_F) * \cos(\phi_{EOD}) \quad (2)$$

The model uses FREQUENCY to calculate the haversine distance between each point in ‘5. SAR North Sea’ and ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} . The location with the lowest distance is selected via the LOOKUP function.

Since the North Sea dataset is only valid for $D \leq 20$ m the model only uses the dataset for such areas. Even though extensive literature research was performed, no representative values for the deeper North Sea areas could be found. Performing extrapolations, as was done for the Baltic Sea (see below), is inappropriate. This is because parameters that impact sedimentation, such as the distance to the coast, tidal regime, and water depth, differ considerably from the shallower areas included in the dataset. Data from $D \leq 20$ m indicate that *SAR* tends to decrease with distance to the coast. Accordingly, if $D > 20$ m, the model assumes $SAR = 0 \text{ mm a}^{-1}$.

For the Baltic Sea part of the study area, no dataset with measured or modelled *SAR* data existed. Hence, a workaround was developed by combining two readily available datasets. The first dataset is a benthic biotope classification of the entire Baltic Sea that is based on geological sediment data and light availability data [311]. The data were available as vector data with polygons exhibiting photic and non-photoc areas of mud and clay, sand, and hard bottom sediment types. The classification into photic and non-photoc areas was ignored, and the three sediment types were used for this analysis.

The second dataset was already mentioned in 3.4.1. It is a machine learning-based *SAR* prediction for the greatest part of the Baltic Sea [219, 224]. The resulting data were available as a GeoTIFF raster. Unfortunately, they do not include the western Baltic Sea, i.e., they do not cover the area west of Rügen (Germany) and Smygehuk (the southernmost point of Sweden) and include only a small section of the study area.

Therefore, an extrapolation of the *SAR* prediction data to the study area was necessary. To do so, *SAR* data were distinguished for the three sediment types in the first dataset. Water inflows from the North Sea influence the Western Baltic Sea and may resuspend sediments. Accordingly, not all *SAR* prediction data could be included, as this would mean that, for example, data from the Gulf of Finland and the Bothnian Bay would be used to predict sedimentation in German waters. HELCOM subdivides the Baltic Sea

TABLE 5.2: *Sediment Accumulation Rates (SAR)* in the Arkona and Bornholm Basins [adapted from 224, 311, 313].

S	\bar{x} (mm a ⁻¹)*	\tilde{x} (mm a ⁻¹)*	$X_{(1)}$ (mm a ⁻¹)*	$X_{(n)}$ (mm a ⁻¹)*
Mud and clay	2.9	2.7	1.2	14.0
Sand	3.8	3.3	1.0	14.5
Hard bottom	3.9	3.6	1.0	13.4
All	3.4	2.9	1.0	14.7

* Rounded to the first decimal place.

into 17 sub-basins, which are consistent in terms of their hydromorphological, physicochemical, and biological characteristics [312]. The Arkona and Bornholm Basins overlap with the study area and contain SAR prediction data. As a consequence, only data from these two basins were used for the extrapolation. Using QGIS, both datasets were clipped to the two relevant basins. Next, QGIS’ zonal statistics tool was used to calculate mean (\bar{x}), median (\tilde{x}), minimum ($X_{(1)}$) and maximum ($X_{(n)}$) SAR values for the three sediment types individually and combined. Table 5.2 shows all of these values for each S . The fact that the overall $X_{(n)}$ value is larger than that of each sediment type individually can likely be attributed to the clipping of data in QGIS, which may have led to the discrimination of some grid cells. \bar{x} and \tilde{x} are close for each sediment type, hinting at rather symmetrical SAR distributions that are skewed to the right (i.e., towards the $X_{(n)}$ value). Larger $X_{(n)}$ values for mud and clay and all led to a larger delta between \bar{x} and \tilde{x} .

Table 5.2 is included in ‘3. Lookup Lists’ of the RUMMs Excel tool. If the EOD operation takes place in the Baltic Sea, RUMMs uses \tilde{x} for the given S . To automatically select the correct SAR value, the model uses the VLOOKUP function.

The value range of SAR is 0.0 mm a⁻¹ to 325.8 mm a⁻¹. While the model only uses three different values with a much smaller value range for the Baltic Sea, the North Sea dataset offers many different location-specific values if $D \leq 20$ m.

In the planning layout, the *Sediment Accumulation Rate* is a parent factor of three other factors. These are *Time Unburied*, *Time Buried*, and *Burial State*. Referring back to 3.4.1, it should be noted that other modes of burial (impact burial, scour burial, burial by sand dunes) exist. Including all of these in the model would have been very complex and would have gone beyond the scope of this dissertation. It was therefore decided to implement only the SAR into RUMMs to calculate burial.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, if a value for SAR is available, the user must enter it into cell **D52**.

5.7.9 Year Sunk

The temporal scope of the entry of explosive ordnance into the sea for this dissertation was defined as the years from 1914 until 1949 (see 2.1.2). As demonstrated in numerous subsections of 2.2 and 3.4, the duration that a UXO object is submerged determines how strongly environmental properties can influence it. Hence, it is relevant to know when a UXO object was submerged. This is signified by the factor *Year Sunk* (T).

The EOD expert must base the assessment of T on several factors. Different types of ordnance were only used in certain periods during the 36 year duration. Therefore, by precisely determining the UXO type (U), the possible period for T can be narrowed down to fewer years. Key periods of UXO entry were the two world wars and the time of dumping after WWII. The precise *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}) of the UXO object can help determine the year an object may have been submerged. If found at a dump site, it is unlikely to have been used in combat during the wars. The model does not automatically use any of this information to determine T .

To arrive at a conservative RA, experts should enter the earliest year when a UXO object was potentially sunk. This assessment should be informed by the output of the *historical survey* process. The earlier T , the higher the risk will usually be. The notable exception is the case in which corrosion renders a fuse inoperable (see 5.7.23).

The *Year Sunk* affects the *Time Sunk*, which is explained in the next subsection. It exists in the planning layout but not in the confirmed layout.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must enter T into cell **D21**.

5.7.10 Time Sunk

In the planning layout, the number of years that a UXO object is submerged is referred to as the *Time Sunk* (t_s). The factor has one parent, which is the *Year Sunk* (T).

Any UXO object that can be assessed with RUMMs was submerged 74 years to 109 years ago at the time of publication of this dissertation (i.e., the year 2023). This constitutes the value range of t_s . The factor is only included in the planning layout. It acts as a parent factor to the *Time Buried*, *Time Unburied*, and *Burial State*.

5.7.11 Time Unburied

The three factors *Time Sunk* (t_s), *Sediment Accumulation Rate* (SAR), and *UXO Shortest Dimension* (l_s) determine the *Time Unburied* (t_u). The mechanisms of sedimentation and burial are described in more detail in 3.4.1. The factor t_u is only included in the planning layout.

To calculate t_u from the three input factors, RUMMs uses equation (3). The formula calculates the time it takes until an object is fully buried. The if-function was introduced because t_u cannot be larger than t_s (line 2) and because t_u cannot be negative (line 3). The resulting value range of t_u is 74 years to 109 years. The symbol a stands for ‘years’.

$$t_u = \begin{cases} \frac{l_s}{SAR} & , \text{ if } \frac{l_s}{SAR} \leq t_s \\ t_s & , \text{ if } \frac{l_s}{SAR} > t_s \\ t_s & , \text{ if } SAR \leq 0 \text{ mm a}^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The model uses l_s and not the *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l). By doing so, it calculates a smaller t_u value. A longer t_u tends to lead to greater model output values, i.e., higher risk. This contradicts the paradigm of always pursuing a conservative assessment. The rationale is that many UXO objects have a cylindrical or conical shape. It is therefore considered far more likely that objects do not stand upright but instead lie on the side. While it is impossible to generalise, images from German dump sites support this notion.

The *Time Unburied* exists in the planning layout. It has one child factor, which is the *Condition of Casing*.

5.7.12 Time Buried

The factor *Time Buried* (t_b) is the opposite of the *Time Unburied* (t_u). In the planning layout, both factors share many properties. t_b has the same input factors: *Time Sunk* (t_s), *Sediment Accumulation Rate* (SAR), and *UXO Shortest Dimension* (l_s). It also has the same value range of 74 years to 109 years.

To calculate t_u , RUMMs uses equation (4). The if-function is necessary because t_b cannot be negative. The rationale for using l_s instead of l_l is the same as for t_u (see 5.7.11).

$$t_u = \begin{cases} t_s - \frac{l_s}{SAR} & , \text{ if } \frac{l_s}{SAR} \leq t_s \\ 0 \text{ a} & , \text{ if } \frac{l_s}{SAR} > t_s \\ 0 \text{ a} & , \text{ if } SAR \leq 0 \text{ mm a}^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In the planning layout, *Time Buried* is a parent factor of the *Condition of Casing*.

5.7.13 Casing Material

As outlined in 2.2.4, there are three materials that UXO casings are mainly made of: aluminium, brass, and steel. For the planning layout, the main material of a *UXO type* (U) is defined to be an object's *Casing Material* (CM). Accordingly, if an object's casing consists of a majority of steel parts and some brass, the object is treated as having a steel casing. This is due to the assumption that it is the main material of the container for the main charge and fuse.

The selected *Casing Material* value is a parent factor to the *Corrosion Rate*. The factor does not exist in the confirmed layout.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must select CM from the drop-down menu in cell **D26**.

5.7.14 Original Casing Thickness

The *Original Casing Thickness* (CT) depends on the *UXO Type* (U). It is measured in millimetres. The factor exists in the planning layout. It is absent from the confirmed layout because the process *UXO identification* allows assessing the *Condition of Casing* (CC) without having to calculate it from CT and the *Corrosion Rate* (CR_u and CR_b) as is necessary in the planning layout (see 5.7.16). The CT value must be researched by an EOD expert, for example, from historical documents or a UXO database. If no precise value is available, a sensible assumption needs to be made.

As mentioned in 2.2.5, it was not possible to collect many CT values in the literature or public UXO databases. The value range is therefore not based on such research but on an educated guess by the author. It was defined to be 1.00 mm to 200.00 mm. Unlike some other factors, for CT the value range is offered for the user's orientation only. The model allows the user to enter larger values and ignores the defined value range. This is possible because CT is not directly connected to one of the model outputs.

Knowing the spot where an object's casing is thinnest is considered important to assess its environmental relevance [3] because it is here, where leakage of the explosive compounds into the environment may start. At the same time, it is where the explosive material interfaces with salt water and may therefore undergo changes in its properties (see 2.2.9). Therefore, if an object's CT is not uniform but a range, the lowest value should be used.

In the planning layout, the *Original Casing Thickness* is an input to the *Condition of Casing*.

User Instruction

For the planning layout, the user must enter CT in cell **D27**.

5.7.15 Corrosion Rate

Subsection 3.4.2 described the overall state of knowledge regarding the corrosion of UXO. It presents a wide range of corrosion predictions that indicate how many years it is expected to take until the content of a UXO object (in the case of conventional UXO, the main charge and the ignition chain) interfaces with seawater. The *Corrosion Rate* (CR) is a relevant factor for the planning layout. Thus, a solution for RUMMs had to be found.

The corrosion rates of UXO casings are rather poorly understood, and the state of corrosion of objects that were not explicitly investigated is subject to a high degree of uncertainty. [35, 233]. Some authors consider modelling corrosion rates for UXO casings to have limited benefit due to the highly dynamic parameters impacting corrosion. It is thus challenging to arrive at a reliable prediction. [127, 314] Others consider corrosion modelling a valuable contribution to UXO research. It was performed in at least two studies, one in the US [231] and one in Poland [118]. There was also one attempt to determine corrosion rates through repeated surveying [315].

Working with annual corrosion rates is common practice in other areas of application, such as offshore wind turbines and steel sheet pilings. Accordingly, it is reasonable to include the annual *Corrosion Rate* (CR_b for the time the object is buried and CR_u for the time it is unburied) into the planning layout. Table 5.3 compiles CR values from the literature dealing with UXO, offshore wind turbines, and corrosion in general. Rates of corrosion for the splash zone—the surface of the sea where it interfaces with air—were also found in the literature. Even though this is the zone with the strongest corrosion [316], the studies were left out of this listing. UXO is usually located on the seabed and is not subjected to the dynamics of the splash zone. Objects that are located on a tidal flat and are unburied while the tidal elevation is at the same level are exceptions. These are disregarded here.

It would be ideal to know the corrosion rate at the given location of a UXO object. This value could either be measured or generated by a reliable model. Neither of these options is realistic. A model that considers all the controlling factors of corrosion (both environmental and inherent to the corroding object) is not available. Measuring values is infeasible as it requires a long-term investigation of the object in question or the production and surveying of coupons from the same material as the UXO object. Both the assessment of coupons or the UXO object itself would take too long for an RA model that is required to enable short-term decision-making (see 4.2.1). In addition, the corrosion rate is only a relevant factor for the planning layout. Once the object is fully investigated, assessing corrosion and predicting the condition of the UXO object becomes irrelevant as the condition can be assessed directly.

For all the reasons stated in the previous paragraph, a limited number of fixed values for CR are used as model assumptions for the planning layout. Limiting model input to six values is an oversimplification of corrosion processes. This problem cannot be solved at this moment. Under consideration of the range of values shown in Table 5.3, the assumptions that were selected are listed in Table 5.4. For steel, individual values are given for the periods that an object is buried or unburied, both in the North and Baltic Seas. One study's claim that the corrosion rates for buried and unburied steel in the Baltic Sea can be expected to be similar is not considered here as it is purely based on pH values. Other parameters were not investigated to substantiate this claim. [118] For aluminium and brass, location-unspecific values are given for the periods that an object is buried or unburied. It should be noted that the values for steel in the North Sea originate from a study that investigated general and pitting corrosion [317]. Pitting corrosion is very localised and creates small but potentially deep holes in the surface. The Baltic Sea values for unburied UXO were calculated by applying a weight loss method to material coupons, which is unsuitable to predict pitting corrosion [318]. This circumstance may explain the comparatively high corrosion rate value for unburied steel in the North Sea. The table also provides a rationale for the defined values. The model limitations that are connected to these assumptions are further explained in 5.11.3.

TABLE 5.3: Selected corrosion rates (CR) for UXO and other areas of application.

Area of Application	CR (mm a ⁻¹)*	Environment	Depth Zone	Origin of Value	Ref.
UXO	0.15	Not specified	Abyssal Plain	Assumed	[304]
UXO (Jgr. 18 AB shell)	0.05	Baltic Sea	On seabed	Assumed	[118]
UXO (bombs)	0.05 to 0.58	Baltic Sea	On seabed	Assumed and calculated	[120]
UXO	0.10	Not specified	On seabed [†]	Not specified	[229]
UXO (bombs)	0.04	Baltic Sea	On seabed [†]	Measured	[119]
UXO	0.03	Baltic Sea	Buried in sediment	Measured	[119]
UXO (artillery)	0.08	Ślupsk Furrow (Baltic Sea)	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
UXO (artillery)	0.12	Bornholm Deep (Baltic Sea)	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
UXO (bombs)	0.02	Gdansk Deep (Baltic Sea)	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
UXO (bombs)	0.11	Ślupsk Furrow (Baltic Sea)	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
UXO (bombs)	0.10	Bornholm Deep (Baltic Sea)	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
UXO (aluminium)	0.00 to 0.01	Baltic Sea	On seabed [†]	Measured	[318]
Offshore wind turbines	0.83	North Sea	Closest point to seabed	Measured	[317]
Offshore wind turbines	0.06 to 0.10	Not Specified	Buried in sediment	Assumed	[317]
Offshore wind turbines	0.10 to 0.20	Not Specified	Submerged zone	Assumed	[317]
Not specified	0.09 to 0.12	Sjaelland (Baltic Sea)	Not specified	Measured	[319]
Not specified	0.04 to 0.11	Polish Coast (Baltic Sea)	Not specified	Measured	[320]
Not specified (brass)	0.60	Laboratory	Not specified	Measured	[321]

* Rounded to the second decimal place.

[†] Not explicitly stated in the text but assumed from context.

TABLE 5.4: RUMMs' model assumptions for *Corrosion Rates (CR)*.

Sea	Burial State	Material	CR (mm a ⁻¹)*	Rationale
Baltic Sea	Unburied	Steel	0.12	Highest measured value for UXO materials in the Baltic Sea [318]. The value of 0.58 mm a ⁻¹ was ignored since it refers to contact corrosion.
Baltic Sea	Buried	Steel	0.00	No values in literature.
North Sea	Unburied	Steel	0.83	Highest measured value for offshore wind turbine materials in the North Sea [317].
North Sea	Buried	Steel	0.10	Assumed as the maximum value for contemporary offshore wind turbine materials in literature [317].
Both	Unburied	Aluminium	0.01	Highest measured value for UXO materials [318].
Both	Buried	Aluminium	0.00	No values in literature.
Both	Unburied	Brass	0.60	Measured value for brass in literature [321].
Both	Buried	Brass	0.00	No values in literature.

* Rounded to the second decimal place.

As can be inferred from Table 5.4, the *Corrosion Rates* (CR_b and CR_u) are controlled by the *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}) of the UXO object and its *Casing Material* (CM). To automatically select the correct values for the corrosion rates, the RUMMs Excel tool uses a combination of the MATCH and INDEX functions. It uses MATCH to browse through the locations and casing materials and it uses INDEX to select the values CR_b and CR_u in a matrix that corresponds to the content of Table 5.4.

In the planning layout, the *Corrosion Rate* value controls two child factors: *Condition of Casing* and *Fuse Properties*.

5.7.16 Condition of Casing

Subsection 2.2.5 reviewed reports on the *Condition of Casing* (CC). It showed that UXO casings can be found in a great variety of conditions. Both RUMMs layouts feature the factor, but it is implemented in two different ways. In the planning layout, it is denoted as CC^p in the confirmed layout, it is denoted as CC^c .

The academic literature does not describe a way to classify the condition of the casing. However, the platform AmuCad.org offered such classes (see Table 5.5). When adding an object to the platform, the user could either select one of six images to specify its 'state of corrosion' or specify that this parameter is unknown. [322] AmuCad.org classified the 'state of corrosion' in the image in the second line as 'very low'. It shows a single breach,

TABLE 5.5: Categories for graphical representations of the *Condition of Casing (CC)*.

Graphic*	'State of Corrosion'*	Condition of Casing	CC
	None	No breach	5
	Very low	Single breach	4
	Low	Several breaches	3
	Medium	Numerous breaches	2
	High	Less than 50 % present	1
	Very high	(Almost) not present	0

* Adopted from AmuCad.org [322].

and $CC = 4$ is therefore regarded as an object with one minor hole in its casing. Beyond this stage, continued deterioration of CC leads to lower categories. The graphics are shown in Table 5.5. They are adapted for RUMMs and converted into six numerical categories to describe CC . The introduction of six stages is a model limitation that is further explained in 5.11.3.

In the planning layout, CC^p needs to be assessed based on available information. The factors *Original Casing Thickness* (CT), *Time Buried* (t_b), *Time Unburied* (t_u) and *Corrosion Rate* (CR_b for the time the object is buried and CR_u for the time it is unburied) are parents of CC^p . RUMMs calculates CC^p as stated in equation (5). CT is multiplied by 5 because the six categories lead to five value facets. The rationale for the if-function is that CC^p cannot be lower than 0. Thus, whenever the sum within the brackets is larger than $CT * 5$, then CC^p must be 0. It would be possible to use the calculated value with its decimals as inputs to the child factors of CC^p . However, they are rounded up to integers to make sure that the categories work identically as the input to the confirmed layout.

$$CC^p = \begin{cases} \left\lceil \frac{CT*5-(t_u*CR_u+t_b*CR_b)}{CT} \right\rceil & , \text{ if } t_u * CR_u + t_b * CR_b \leq CT * 5 \\ 0 & , \text{ if } t_u * CR_u + t_b * CR_b > CT * 5 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In the confirmed layout, it is not necessary to calculate CC^c . Instead, it can be assessed based on the visual information during the *UXO identification* (see 3.2.2). As a model input, it is then categorised by the images displayed in Table 5.5.

In the planning layout, *Condition of Casing* is a parent factor of *Complexity of the EOD Operation* and *Impact Sensitivity*. In the confirmed layout, a third child factor, the *Fuse Corrosion State*, is added.

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter CC^c in cell **D28**.

5.7.17 Main Charge Type

As described in 2.2.6, there are many different *Main Charge Types* (M) that were used during the historical scope (see 2.1.2). M depends solely on the *UXO type* (U).

The information, which M is present in a UXO object, can be an output of the *historical survey*. As noted before, over the course of their deployment, UXO types may have been filled with different M . In such cases, one M that was used in a specific type of explosive ordnance must be selected for use in RUMMs. There are three potential options to address this issue.

- Option 1 is to select M that is most probably contained in the UXO object in question. If it is known how much of the deployed ordnance was filled with which M , the one that was used most often is selected.
- Option 2 is to calculate an average or weighted average of the impact sensitivity base values that are provided as an input to the calculation of the *Impact Sensitivity*. The concept of base values is explained in 5.7.19. For a weighted average, it would be required to know the distribution of all M over the entire amount of deployed objects for U .
- Option 3 is to select M with the highest impact sensitivity base value. This is a conservative approach that will include the value that leads to the highest values for the model outputs.

In EOD, it is best practice to assume the worst-case scenario (see 5.7). Accordingly, for the way forward, option 3 is selected for both model layouts.

The *Main Charge Type* is included in both model layouts. It is a parent factor of the *Impact Sensitivity* and the *Relative Effectiveness*. Many different *Main Charge Types* exist [128]. The RUMMs Excel tool only includes those for which a value for at least one of the child factors was found in the literature. All other M , are summarised under ‘unknown (maritime)’ and ‘unknown (non-maritime)’.

User Instruction

The user must select M from the drop-down menu in cell **D30**.

5.7.18 Charge Mass

The *Charge Mass* (m_c) is a property of the UXO object and thus depends on the *UXO Type* (U). An EOD expert can determine m_c , once the *UXO identification* has been finished. For background knowledge and an investigation of the distribution of the factor in the EOD dataset, the reader is referred to 2.2.7. Note that UXO can also be filled with smoke-producing and incendiary substances, irritants, or residues thereof [31]. These are not referred to in this section. Nevertheless, RUMMs can be used to assess the risk of an undesired detonation of such objects.

Values for m_c may range from 1 kg to 350 kg. UXO objects or parts thereof may not contain any explosive material (i.e., $m_c = 0$ kg). Handling such objects still requires supervision by an EOD expert. Nevertheless, they are ignored here since no risk originates from them. Similar to *UXO Mass* (see 5.7.4), variations in m_c that are smaller than 1 kg have virtually no impact on the model outputs. Therefore, the factor is rounded up to integers and $m_c^{min} = 1$ kg. Values are always rounded up since an object with, for example, 0.01 kg of explosive material may still undergo an undesired detonation.

The case of the so-called tallboy, with its 2359 kg explosive charge [113] is an extreme example of how large m_c can be. The review in 2.2.7 showed that most objects have a much lower m_c . Therefore, a threshold value for m_c^{max} was introduced. For more information on the rationale behind thresholds, see 5.10.2. The largest m_c value in the EOD dataset was 340 kg. Since this value is rather close to other values in the dataset (see Figure 2.6) and since the data do not follow any regular distribution type, no outlier detection like in 5.7.4 was performed. A buffer was introduced, and it was decided that $m_c^{max} = 350$ kg. If $m_c > 350$ kg, RUMMs applies the threshold and continues with $m_c = 350$ kg. This is necessary to ensure the proper functionality of the model.

One comment during the 1st EOD RA workshop was that the *Main Charge Type* (M) that is included in a UXO object can influence m_c . This is likely a result of the density of M . When in doubt, users of RUMMs are therefore advised to assume that UXO is filled with M with the greatest m_c .

In RUMMs, the factor m_c is the mass of all explosive material in the UXO object (including primary, booster, and main charges). Even though they are technically not part of the main charge m_c also includes the propellants if they have explosive properties. The name of the factor remained *Charge Mass* since the main charge is expected to constitute the majority of explosive material in most cases. Exceptions are, for example, dumped artillery shells, which contain more propellant material than main-charge explosive (see 6.3.2). Still, the simplification is possible since the *Charge Mass* is only a parent to the *Shock Factor*. The implications of this decision and the resulting model limitations are discussed in 5.11.4.

User Instruction

The user must enter m_c in cell **D33**.

5.7.19 Impact Sensitivity

Subsection 2.2.9 described the overall state of knowledge on the ageing of explosive materials in UXO. It focused on the *Impact Sensitivity* (I) of main charges and discussed some of the chemical processes that lead to an increase in impact sensitivity when explosive material interfaces with seawater and ages. The *Current Impact Sensitivity* (I_c) of the main charge of a UXO object is relevant for EOD risk. However, measuring it before conducting the key processes is not feasible. This would require sampling each UXO object, bringing explosive material on board a specifically equipped vessel, and testing it before the EOD activity commences. In theory, knowledge about the historical condition and composition of main charge materials as well as information about site conditions would

TABLE 5.6: *Original Impact Sensitivity* (I_o) values for different *Main Charge Types* (M).

M	I_o (N m)*	Published in	Ref.
Cyclotol	3 [†]	1938	[323] [‡]
Fp 40/60 or Amatol 60/40	5 [§]	1937	[323] [‡]
Fp 50/50 or Amatol 50/50	6 [§]	1937	[323] [‡]
Fp 60/40 or Amatol 40/60	6 [§]	1937	[323] [‡]
Pentolite	3 [†]	1937 or 1946	[323] [‡]

* Rounded to integers.

[†] Not measured in accordance with the contemporary method mentioned in 2.2.9 [150]. Instead, sensitivity to impact (causing 50 % of explosions).

[‡] This source references other works in Polish that are not publicly available.

[§] Not measured in accordance with the contemporary method mentioned in 2.2.9 [150]. Instead, sensitivity to impact (causing 10 % of explosions).

allow predicting the current state of the materials [132]. The ability to roughly estimate I_c of a *Main Charge Type* (M) without having to measure it would be very valuable. To do so, knowledge about the *Original Impact Sensitivity* (I_o) of different M at the time the explosive ordnance was submerged is required.

For the great majority of explosive materials that were used in the period that is the scope of this dissertation (see 2.1.2), no I_o values are available. Table 5.6 lists the values that were found in the literature. Note that the level of purity of explosive material used during WWII does not correspond to that of explosives produced today. [139] This makes it difficult to reproduce the historical material compositions and perform measurements on them. This makes the values in Table 5.6 all the more valuable.

In addition to the values in Table 5.6, one source published in 1949 claims an I of a Schießwolle (gun cotton)-type explosive of 40 cm to 50 cm. The value was acquired with a drop test with 2 kg. [324 in 132] This would correspond to a relatively high I of 7.85 N m to 9.8 N m. On the other hand, one textbook claims that deflagration (see 3.3.3) of gun cotton only occurred when fired at with a 2 cm high explosive shell gun [325 in 132]. In this case, I could be below the limit of quantification of 49 N m. Such contrasting values are not helpful. To address this issue, it is possible to artificially age explosives and measure I or to measure I_c of the main charges of recently cleared UXO. The reliability of artificially ageing explosives to a condition resembling material that is up to 100 years old was challenged in the literature [146]. Hence, the analysis of recently cleared explosive material is the preferred option. Table 5.7 lists I_c values that were found in the literature. These values were published in 2012 [148] and 2017 [326] and are therefore considered to be timely when compared to 1949, which is the latest point in time the UXO could have been submerged (see 2.1.2). Unfortunately, the data presented in Table 5.7 were not obtained from experiments with statistically significant sample sizes. [148] The table includes information on the *UXO type* (U) and M for which I_c was measured. Remember that the lower the value, the less impact energy is required to lead to a detonation, and thus the higher I . For example, I_c of the loose explosive is higher than that of the Schießwolle 39 in the moored mine. The literature usually does not indicate the *Condition of Casing* (CC) of the UXO. This information would be valuable as it would be an indication of how long the

TABLE 5.7: *Current Impact Sensitivity* (I_c) measurements for different *Main Charge Types* (M) in different *UXO Types* (U).

UXO Type	M	I_c (N m)*	Ref.
Explosives chunk (black crust) [†]	Schießwolle 39a	1 [‡]	[148]
Explosives chunk (outer area) [†]	Schießwolle 39a	10 [§]	[148]
Explosives chunk (inner area) [†]	Schießwolle 39a	10	[148]
Ground Mine (Mark VI)	Amatol [#]	50	[327]
Torpedo Head	Unknown	25	[327]
Moored Mine	Schießwolle 39	25	[327]
Ground Mine (Mark IV)	Minol [#]	50	[327]
Loose Explosive	Unknown	6	[327]

* Rounded to integers.

[†] Collected in the area around a detonation site, possibly after a detonation was executed.

[‡] For two out of five samples. For the other three, $I > 5$ N m.

[§] Medium value from five powder samples. A slice of the same material showed an impact sensitivity of 12 N m.

^{||} Medium value from five powder samples. A slice of the same material showed an impact sensitivity of 13 N m.

[#] Explosive materials in the *UXO Types* that were mentioned in the original sources had to be identified in another document [328]. These are generalised designations that do not refer to the exact mixture.

explosive filling had interfaced with seawater. The loose explosive is an exception, as it is clear that no casing was present (i.e., $CC = 0$). All table entries concern explosive material from UXO that was submerged in the marine environment. Additional measurements from onshore UXO are available in the literature. They address main charge types that are not included in Table 5.7. They were ignored here since they were subject to other ageing mechanisms.

The lack of both historical I_o values for these materials and a description of the casing of the UXO objects makes estimating the expected I_c difficult. Calculating it, for example, by applying a function to values collected from historical material and to measured values from current experiments is not possible. Adding to the complexity of the issue is the multitude of different explosive mixtures, many of which have their own specific ageing properties (see 2.2.9). Understanding the impact sensitivity's rate of change would be very beneficial, but currently, this is not achievable. The effect that environmental parameters such as salinity, temperature, or pH have on this rate of change is not sufficiently understood. It is also not possible to draw general conclusions from the composition of main charges, as one study found that there appears to be no correlation between the fraction of TNT and I [146]. To tackle this issue on a more comprehensive scale, the development of a site-specific database was suggested in the literature [132].

In RUMMs, each M is assigned an *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* (I_b) that decreases gradually to a value I_c . For the implementation of such a function in RUMMs, some assumptions were made that are described below. The model limitations that were introduced with these assumptions are further explained in 5.11.5.

TABLE 5.8: *Impact Sensitivity Base Values (I_b) for different Main Charge Types (M).*

M	I_b (Nm)*	Rationale	Ref.
Amatol (unspecified)	50	Measured	[327]
Cyclotol	3	Measured	[323] [†]
Fp 40/60 or Amatol 60/40	5	Measured	[323] [†]
Fp 50/50 or Amatol 50/50	6	Measured	[323] [†]
Fp 60/40 or Amatol 40/60	6	Measured	[323] [†]
Minol (unspecified)	50	Measured	[327]
Pentolite	3	Measured	[323] [†]
PETN	3	Standard value	[329]
RDX	8	Standard value	[329]
Schießwolle 39	25	Measured	[327]
Schießwolle 39a	10	Measured	[148]
TNT	15	Standard value	[130]
Any other type & if M is unknown	10	Lowest value measured for a main charge in Germany, except for the black crust and loose explosive	[148]

* Rounded to integers.

[†] This source references other works in Polish language that are not publicly available.

- Except for the loose explosive, all samples presented in Table 5.7 originate from UXO objects with intact casings.
- For main charge types for which no measured values are available, $I_b = 10$ Nm. This is the lowest value for explosive material from a UXO with an intact casing (i.e., $CC = 5$).
- When $CC = 5$ no changes in I take place ($I_c = I_b$).
- Once breached, I increases linearly. Hence, the lower CC , the higher I_c .
- Since M of the loose explosive material is unknown, any explosive material that interfaces with seawater can reach I_c up to 6 Nm. The value of 1 Nm for two out of five samples for Schießwolle 39a was likely obtained from material that was collected after a detonation. For the other three samples, I was lower. 1 Nm is therefore not considered appropriate as the lowest possible value of I_c .

In both RUMMs layouts, I_c is controlled by I_b and CC . For explosive materials from Table 5.6, $I_b = I_o$. All I_b values are shown in Table 5.8. To select the correct I_b , the RUMMs Excel tool uses the VLOOKUP function.

Based on the assumptions above, both RUMMs layouts calculate I_c according to equation (6). The number 5 is required both as a divisor and minuend in the formula due to the six possible categories of CC . The value of 6 Nm is included as it is assumed to be the highest I_c that any explosive material can reach when the casing is breached. The only exception are materials for which $I_b < 6$ Nm. The division calculates the increase in I_c per decrease in CC category.

TABLE 5.9: *Impact Sensitivity Classification (IC)* [329].

IC	Description	Impact Sensitivity (N m)
1	insensitive	> 40
2	less sensitive	35–40
3	sensitive	4–35
4	very sensitive	< 4

$$I_c = \begin{cases} I_b & , \text{ if } I_b \leq 6 \text{ N m} \\ I_b - \frac{I_b - 6 \text{ N m}}{5} * (5 - CC) & , \text{ if } I_b > 6 \text{ N m} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

I can be sorted into four groups according to the United Nations classification for the transport of dangerous goods. This *Impact Sensitivity Classification (IC)* is shown in Table 5.9. Due to a recommendation during the 2nd EOD RA workshops (group A; see Appendix 6), RUMMs assigns I_c to the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification (IC_c)* in accordance with Table 5.9. When $I_c = 35$ N m, then $IC_c = 3$, due to this being the more conservative approach.

The *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* is a parent factor of the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. This is the case for the planning and the confirmed layouts.

5.7.20 Relative Effectiveness

There are numerous ways to measure the performance of explosive materials. The *Relative Effectiveness (RE)* is one of them. Background information on the factor was provided in 2.2.8, which also highlighted its many uncertainties. In RUMMs, the factor depends on the *Main Charge Type (M)*.

Table 5.10 lists RE values that were found in the literature. The first column contains the name of the explosive material. It includes both mixtures that were used in explosive ordnance and pure substances (such as TNT, RDX, or PETN) that were not used as fillings but as parts of mixtures. The second column contains the highest RE value for each explosive material that was found in the literature. As discussed in 2.2.8, RE can vary widely, depending on the RE definition and on the method that was used to determine a value. Using the highest available value is the most conservative approach. Values that are solely based on heat energy and thus do not consider any kinetic energy were ignored. The third column informs the reader about the method used to generate the value. For detailed information on the experimental setups and calculation methods, the reader is referred to the reference in column four. For all explosive materials that are not listed in the first column, the model uses $RE = 1.00$ for non-maritime UXO and $RE = 1.30$ for maritime UXO, thereby following the procedure from *RA10* (see 4.3.5). The rationale for this distinction lies in the fact that maritime UXO usually contains more powerful explosive

TABLE 5.10: *Relative Effectiveness (RE)* values for different explosive materials.

Explosive Material	<i>RE</i>	Origin of Value	Ref.
Ammonium Picrate or Explosive D	0.98	Calculated - Hydrodynamic work	[137]
Composition A3	1.41	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Composition B	1.35	Unknown	[330]
Composition C3	1.35	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Cyclotol 60/40	1.30	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Cyclotol 70/30	1.35	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Cyclotol 75/25	1.37	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Depth Bomb Explosive (DBX)	1.43	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Ednatol	1.22	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Fp. 20/80 or Amatol 80/20*	1.17	Unknown	[330]
Fp. 40/60 or Amatol 60/40*	1.12	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Fp. 50/50 or Amatol 50/50*	1.14	Calculated - Power index	[134]
HBX-1	1.17	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure)	[136]
HBX-3	1.16	Experiment - Air blast test	[137]
MINOL-2	1.45	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Nitrocellulose	0.50	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure and impulse)	[136]
Nitroglycerine	1.00	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure and impulse)	[136]
Octol 70/30	1.09	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure and impulse)	[136]
Octol 75/25	1.06	Experiment - Air blast test (impulse)	[136]
Pentolite	1.56	Calculated - Power index	[134]
PETN	1.66	Unknown	[330]
Picratol	1.03	Calculated - Power index	[134]
PTX-1	1.23	Calculated - Power index	[134]
PTX-2	1.34	Calculated - Hydrodynamic work	[137]
RDX	1.60	Unknown	[330]
Tetryl (unspecified)	1.07	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure and impulse)	[136]
Tetryl 75/25	1.09	Experiment - Air blast test (peak pressure and impulse)	[136]
TNT	1.00	Unknown	[330]
Torpex	1.43	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Tritonal	1.20	Calculated - Power index	[134]
Any other type & if <i>M</i> is unknown (non-maritime)	1.00	Working assumption	[43]
Any other type & if <i>M</i> is unknown (maritime)	1.30	Working assumption	[43]

* Füllpulver (filling powder) (Fp.)

materials than non-maritime UXO. [43] Based on the selection of M by the user (see 5.7.17), the RUMMs Excel tool uses the VLOOKUP function to select the correct RE value as listed in Table 5.10.

It should be noted that all of the values in Table 5.10 were obtained without considering any ageing effects. The changes in the properties and performance of explosive materials that are outlined in 2.2.8 and 2.2.9 suggest that changes in RE may occur due to ageing and interaction with salt water. However, no data on such changes are available.

The *Relative Effectiveness* is one of the parent factors of the *Shock Factor*, which is described in the next subsection. It is included in both model layouts.

5.7.21 Shock Factor

When a UXO object detonates under water, several effects occur (see 2.3.1). The one that is commonly used to describe the severity of a detonation is the shock wave. The impact of this shock wave on a vessel can be quantified by a *Shock Factor* (SF). It can also be used to quantify the impact on any other equipment or personnel in the water. SF is a function of the factors *Charge Mass* (m_c , in lbs) and *Relative Effectiveness* (RE). It also depends on the slant range (SR , in ft) and the depression angle (θ , in $^\circ$) between the detonating UXO object and the impacted risk receptor, as shown in equation (7). The higher m_c , RE , or both, the higher SF . SR is the diagonal distance between two points at different altitudes. A larger SR leads to a lower SF . θ is the angle between the horizontal plane at the location of a risk receptor and the direction of SR . If the receptor was above the UXO object, θ would be 90° , and if the receptor was at the same altitude as the UXO object, θ would be 0° . SF increases with θ . [160]

$$SF = \frac{\sqrt{m_c * RE}}{SR} * \frac{1 + \sin \theta}{2} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) can be simplified for use in RUMMs. Neither SR nor θ can be known at all times during the EOD operation. It may be possible to predict these values for the vessel, but not for all other equipment or divers performing the EOD operation. The worst case (i.e., the most conservative scenario) is that these are located right above the UXO object when the undesired detonation occurs. It can hence be assumed that $R = 1$ ft and $\theta = 90^\circ$ [43]. This leads to equation (8), which is used by RUMMs. The RUMMs Excel tool performs the conversion of m_c from kg to lbs.

$$SF = \frac{\sqrt{m_c * RE}}{1} * \frac{1 + 1}{2} = \sqrt{m_c * RE} \quad (8)$$

SF is used to predict the damage to vessels and calculate safety distances during planned explosions. The lower SF , the lower the expected damage to a vessel. Table 5.11 shows the expected range of damage to vessels for various shock factors. The matter of safety distance calculation is not further explored here.

TABLE 5.11: Degree of damage for various *Shock Factor* (SF) values [155 in 43].

SF	Description of Damage [according to 43]
< 0.1	Insignificant damage such as light bulb and fuse failures, etc.
$0.1 - 0.15$	Tube, relay, fuse, and light bulb failures; general electronic failures, piping leaks, and possibly pipe rupture.
$0.15 - 0.2$	Increase in above damage, piping ruptures likely, machinery misalignments likely.
0.2	General machinery damage.
> 0.2	Severe damage to the vessel.
> 0.5	Typically results in total loss of vessel.

The worst-case assumption outlined above leads to $SF = 0.5$, even for a small amount of explosive material ($m_c = 0.25$ kg), with $RE = 1$. Since m_c is rounded up to be at least 1 kg in RUMMs (see 5.7.18), the total loss of equipment is expected in each scenario. The value range of SF is 1 to 36. In reality, even larger SF values are possible. However, due to the introduction of the threshold of $m_c^{max} = 350$ kg an upper value range boundary (SF^{max}) of 36 is introduced here.

Even though in the worst case scenario the loss of equipment is always expected, the *Shock Factor* is acknowledged as a useful way to quantify the expected damage caused by a detonation and is thus used as a parent factor to the model output *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. It performs this function in both model layouts.

Note that RUMMs does not consider the sound wave that is produced by a detonation (see 2.3.1). The pressure wave of the detonation (as expressed by the *Shock Factor*) is the more relevant effect for the personnel and equipment at the EOD site.

5.7.22 Fuse Type

The *Fuse Type* (FT) is considered very relevant to assess the risk that is connected to a UXO object [154]. It depends on the *UXO Type* (U). An EOD expert must be consulted to determine it for both model layouts. If the planning layout is used, knowledge about FT is a result of the *historical survey*. If the confirmed layout is used, additional information is acquired during the *UXO identification*.

Knowing the *Fuse Type* is a prerequisite to determining its *Fuse Properties*. It is also a parent factor of the *Fuse Corrosion State*.

User Instruction

The user must enter FT in cell **D35** for documentation purposes. If no fuse is present, the user must enter the value ‘none’.

5.7.23 Fuse Corrosion State

The condition of the fuse is an important piece of information to assess a UXO object during the EOD process [3]. In RUMMs, this notion is represented by the factor *Fuse Corrosion State* (FC). In the planning layout, it is denoted as FC^p in the confirmed layout, it is denoted as FC^c . Some introductory information that explains the relevance of the factor was provided in 2.2.11.

FC is given as a percentage, ranging from 0% to 100%. The lower the value, the stronger the corrosion of the fuse. As stated during the 2nd EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 6), strong corrosion of the fuse increases the risk of handling UXO. However, if a value of 0% is reached, no fuse exists, and hence the risk of its undesired initiation is eliminated. Note that an undesired detonation of the UXO remains possible due to the *Impact Sensitivity* of the main charge.

When using the confirmed layout, the EOD expert should investigate the UXO object and enter a value for FC^c based on their observations. Objects that are not fused are exceptions. For these, no value for FC^c is required since the absence of a fuse removes its contribution to EOD risk. The effect is the same as if the fuse were fully corroded (i.e., $FC^c = 0\%$). It is not always possible to assess the condition of the fuse during the *UXO identification*. For example, cluster munitions are difficult to investigate if they are inside an intact dispenser [3]. In this case, the planning layout should be used, or a worst-case scenario (i.e., a fuse with $FC^c = 1\%$) should be assumed.

In the planning layout, FC^p is calculated. It is controlled by the *Condition of Casing* (CC^p) and the *Fuse Type* (FT). As the casing gradually corrodes and is eventually breached (i.e., $CC^p \leq 4$), the fuse interfaces with water. The longer the casing is breached, the lower CC^p . It follows that the fuse is subjected to saline water for a longer period, and hence FC^p must be lower. This simplification of the corrosion processes of the fuse was necessary to develop a functional model. The implications of this simplification are explored in 5.11.3.

The planning layout calculates FC^p as shown in equation (9). The number 5 is required both as a divisor and minuend, due to the six possible categories of CC^p (see 5.7.16). The value of 100% is included because it is assumed that a fuse is in mint condition when the casing is breached. The if-function expresses that the absence of a fuse leads to $FC = 0\%$, which removes its contribution to EOD risk. By using CC^p and applying equation (9), the value for FC can take one of six possible values. The possible outcomes are shown in Table 5.12.

$$FC^p = \begin{cases} 100\% - \frac{100\%}{5} * (5 - CC^p) & , \text{ if } I \neq \text{'none'} \\ 0\% & , \text{ if } I = \text{'none'} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

In both model layouts, the *Fuse Corrosion State* is a parent factor to two of the three model outputs. These are the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* and the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*.

TABLE 5.12: *Fuse Corrosion State (FC^p) based on the Condition of Casing (CC^p) in the planning layout.*

CC	FC (%)
0	0
1	20
2	40
3	60
4	80
5	100

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter FC^c in cell **D38**.

5.7.24 Fuse Properties

From the literature review in 2.2.10 and 2.2.11, it became apparent that the degree to which a fuse may contribute to the risk of an undesired detonation depends on its properties. Some literature makes general statements about how likely the fuses of different classes of UXO (bombs, torpedoes, mines, etc.) can lead to an undesired detonation [e.g., 54]. This approach is rejected here since the UXO types in each class, as well as the types of fuses, are extremely diverse.

Fuse Properties (FP) depend on the *Fuse Type (FT)* and *Fuse Corrosion State (FC)*. When an EOD expert has determined FT , it is possible to research FP in the literature and UXO databases (if the planning layout is used) and, additionally, consider the results of the *UXO identification* (if the confirmed layout is used). Based on the literature review, eight properties (fp_n) that contribute to the risk of an undesired detonation were identified. These are listed and briefly described in Table 5.13. For explanations of the used terminology and additional context, the reader is referred back to 2.2.10 and 2.2.11. Note that, in reality, some properties depend on others. Firstly, fp_1 is a prerequisite for any other fp_n . Secondly, fp_7 is a prerequisite of fp_8 .

Each fp_n can take a value of 1 or 0, depending on whether it applies or not. The values are then added up to produce FP . The more properties that apply to the UXO object, the higher FP . In RUMMs, FP is accordingly expressed as a number of points ranging from 0 to 8. If $FC = 0\%$, there is no fuse (either because the UXO object is not fused or because the fuse is fully corroded), and therefore, FP becomes irrelevant. In this case, RUMMs assumes $FP = 0$, notwithstanding the entry of the individual fp_n . This is expressed in equation (10).

$$FP = \begin{cases} \sum_{n=1}^8 fp_n & , \text{ if } FC > 0\% \\ 0 & , \text{ if } FC = 0\% \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

TABLE 5.13: *Fuse Properties (FP)* in RUMMs.

<i>FP</i>	Variable	Description
Fuse Present	fp_1	The UXO object is fused, i.e., the fuse is present.
Fuse Armed	fp_2	The UXO object is armed, i.e., the fuse is in a state in which it can initiate the detonator, which can initiate the main charge.
Fuse without Battery	fp_3	The fuse is not equipped with a battery.
Electrolyte in Vial	fp_4	The fuse is equipped with at least one electrolyte in a vial.
Spring Loaded/Cocked Striker, Diaphragm	fp_5	The UXO object is equipped with one of these long delay fuses.
Chemical Long Delay Fuse	fp_6	The UXO object is equipped with a chemical long delay fuse.
More than one Fuse	fp_7	The UXO is equipped with at least two fuses.
More than one Fuse Type	fp_8	The UXO is equipped with at least two types of fuses.

A technical supervisor for EOD is expected to be able to assess *FP* with the help of databases and historical documents. RUMMs is designed in such a way that more *Fuse Properties* apply (i.e., the higher *FP*), the higher the EOD risk). To follow a conservative RA approach, users are recommended to assume that $fp_n = 1$, when in doubt.

In both model layouts, the *Fuse Properties* factor influences the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.

User Instruction

Depending on whether fp_1 through fp_8 apply or not, the user must enter the value 1 or 0 in cells **D39** through **D46**.

5.7.25 Burial State

Many factors control a UXO object's *Burial State* (B). These are described in 3.4.1. B is the relative degree to which a UXO object is covered by sediment. It is thus indicated by a percentage. Depending on the model layout, it has either no inputs (confirmed layout) or three inputs (planning layout). When using the confirmed layout, B is assessed after the *UXO identification* has been conducted by an EOD expert.

On the other hand, the planning layout uses the factors *UXO Shortest Dimension* (l_s), *Sediment Accumulation Rate* (SAR), and *Time Sunk* (t_s) to calculate B . The rationale for using l_s and not any other dimension of the UXO object is the same as outlined in 5.7.11: It is considered more likely for an object to lie on its side than to stand upright. The calculation of B is done as shown in equation (11). The if-function exists to avoid values $> 100\%$. Even though UXO objects may be buried at depths several times their

own l_s value, this is not relevant for RUMMs. An object that is buried deeper into the sediment may require additional effort to uncover. However, dredging operations before the *UXO identification* do not affect the key processes.

$$B = \begin{cases} \frac{t_s * SAR}{l_s} * 100 \% & , \text{ if } \frac{t_s * SAR}{l_s} * 100 \% \leq 100 \% \\ 100 \% & , \text{ if } \frac{t_s * SAR}{l_s} * 100 \% > 100 \% \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

It is possible that an object was identified and is still partially unburied. Accordingly, the value range in both model layouts is 0 % to 100 %. It is not considered realistic that $B > 50 \%$ for the confirmed layout since *UXO identification* requires that an object be somewhat visible. This was also pointed out during the 1st EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 3). Nevertheless, it was decided to have the same B^{max} value in both model layouts. Introducing a lower B^{max} value for the confirmed layout would have led to different contributions to their influenced factor, which is not desirable. In addition, defining another value than 100 % for B^{max} would have been difficult and may have resulted in an arbitrary number.

The *Burial State* is a factor that influences only one other factor in both model layouts. This is the model output *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter B into cell **D53**.

5.7.26 Current Velocity

The *Current Velocity* (v_c) is an environmental factor that has a direct impact on the EOD operation (see 3.4.3). It has no mathematical inputs in either of the model layouts. Instead, it needs to be determined in other ways. The sources that can be consulted depend on the model layout that is used. For the confirmed layout, v_c is best derived by measuring it on location, for example, by use of an acoustic Doppler current profiler.

For the planning layout, measuring the momentary v_c is not beneficial as its meaningfulness for the actual value during the EOD key processes is limited. Alternative sources need to be consulted. If planning is conducted for the next 24 h and if the UXO object is located in a depth of less than 5 m, the current velocity service of the BSH can be consulted² [331]. For all other cases, the planning layout determines a representative v_c value based on the *Planned EOD Date* (PD) and the *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}). This is achieved by using the point data that were generated from the raster file that was introduced in 3.4.3 to understand current velocity's potential impact on EOD in the study area. In the RUMMs Excel tool, the dataset is saved in the sheet '6. Current Velocity'.

The tool uses the same combination of the LOOKUP and FREQUENCY functions as well as the haversine formula that was used to determine SAR values (see 5.7.8). The functions are used to output the median current velocity of the selected location for

²https://www.bsh.de/DE/DATEN/Vorhersagen/Stroemungen/stroemungen_node.html

each season. Finally, the INDEX function is used to return the median wind speed value for the season of *PD*. In theory, the confirmed layout can perform the same calculation. However, a measured value is always preferable to the median value provided by RUMMs.

The factor v_c has a value range from 0.00 m s^{-1} to 1.50 m s^{-1} . The data analysis in 3.4.3 showed that median current velocities essentially never surpass 1.40 m s^{-1} . While that still means that higher current velocities occur in certain areas at certain times, v_c^{max} was defined to be 1.50 m s^{-1} since current velocities are lower for more than 50 % of the time in the entire study area.

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter v_c in cell **D54**. For the planning layout, the user must enter v_c in cell **D54** if a value is available. If no value for v_c is available, the user must leave cell **D54** empty. If an LoU exists, the user must enter v_c^l in cell **D63**. If $v_c^l < v_c$, the field *Limitation of Use Exceeded* (cell **D73**) jumps to YES. This signifies that EOD must not be conducted or continued at all.

Since v_c is one of the factors that has an LoU, v_c^{max} doubles as v_c^l (for an explanation of this concept, see 5.10.1). The LoUs were introduced after the 1st EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 3). As described in 3.4.3, even WROVs usually cannot operate when $v_c > 1.50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Hence, if such strong currents occur, no EOD work must be executed. If divers are performing EOD work, v_c^l value must be lowered (e.g., to 0.50 m s^{-1}). Lowering v_c^l leads to a change in the model outputs in a similar manner as an increase in v_c would.

5.7.27 Wind Speed

An overview of *Wind Speed* (v_w) in the study area and how it impacts the sea state and consequently the ability to perform EOD work was given in 3.4.4. How a value for v_w is obtained varies significantly between the model layouts.

For the confirmed layout, measurements aboard the EOD vessel can be used. Alternatively, for example, the BSH marine forecast presents the current wind speed throughout the German North and Baltic Seas. It uses data from the German Meteorological Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)) and is available online³ [332]. On this website, the user can enter coordinates to receive a v_w value at the desired location. Thus, for the confirmed layout, there is no parent factor in RUMMs.

If the planning layout is used for EOD RA in the near future, the same methods as above can be used. In all other cases, the issue was solved differently. In 3.4.4, a dataset from MUDAB was analysed. The same dataset is used by RUMMs [255]. The map in Figure 3.8 shows the distribution of measurement stations. This was considered sufficient to produce representative values for any location throughout the study area. The MUDAB dataset is saved in the sheet ‘7. Wind Speed’ of the RUMMs Excel tool. Pivot tables were generated, one for each meteorological season for the North and Baltic Seas. Each pivot table contains all stations with at least ten measured values for the season and region.

³<https://marineforecast.bsh.de/>

The tables also list the stations' coordinates and median seasonal wind speed. For each table, the tool uses the same combination of the LOOKUP, FREQUENCY, and INDEX functions as well as the haversine formula as is applied for the *current velocity* (see 5.7.26). With this method, it is possible to obtain a seasonally representative (i.e., depending on the *Planned EOD Date (PD)* value for the EOD *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD})). The limitation on stations with at least ten values per season leads to different subsets of stations that are available for the subsequent steps. Some stations may be included in all four seasonal tables, while others may be available in fewer or even none of the tables. It is therefore possible that the closest station to ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} differs for the individual seasons.

The value range boundaries are $v_w^{min} = 0.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $v_w^{max} = 50.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The upper value is based on the assumption that this is the maximum sustained wind speed in the southern North Sea [259]. It is theoretically possible that higher wind speeds occur, but RUMMs treats higher values as though they were 50.0 m s^{-1} for the following reason: The next subsection introduces an LoU value for the *Significant Wave Height* ($H_{1/3}$). This value leads to a situation where if $v_w \geq 14.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the LoU for $H_{1/3}$ will be exceeded and no EOD work is permissible. For more information on LoU values and the interpretation of model results when LoU values are exceeded, see 5.10.1.

The factor *Wind Speed* is a parent to only one factor, which is *Significant Wave Height*. The tool only uses *Wind Speed* if no value for *Significant Wave Height* is available.

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter v_w into cell **D55**. For the planning layout, the user must enter v_w in cell **D55** if a value is available. If no value for v_w is available, the user must leave cell **D55** empty.

5.7.28 Significant Wave Height

Significant Wave Height is another environmental factor that is relevant to determining EOD risk. For this dissertation, the definition according to which the significant wave height is the mean of the highest third of waves is used ($H_{1/3}$) since this is the definition that is used by the BSH [247]. As for wind speed, some background on the significant wave height was provided in 3.4.4.

There are numerous options for obtaining a value for $H_{1/3}$. The value can be collected from a DWD service, which predicts the sea state for large parts of the study area for up to 72 h into the future⁴ [333]. A more precise option is the BSH marine forecast, introduced in the previous subsection. It uses DWD data on the current sea state. Here it is possible to obtain $H_{1/3}$ for a precise set of coordinates.⁵ [332] Accordingly, if the execution of key processes is imminent and either the confirmed layout is used or if short-term planning is conducted and the planning layout is applied, these services can be used.

⁴<https://www2.bsh.de/akt/dat/Seegang/vorhersage/wiwe.htm>

⁵<https://marineforecast.bsh.de/>

TABLE 5.14: Beaufort scale with value facets for *Wind Speed* (v_w) and *Significant Wave Height* ($H_{1/3}$) [260].

Beaufort Number	v_w (m s^{-1})*	$H_{1/3}$ (m)	Description of Sea Surface†
0	0.0	0.0	Sea like a mirror.
1	1.0	0.1	Ripples with the appearance of scales are formed, without foam crests.
2	2.0	0.2	Small wavelets are still short but more pronounced.
3	3.0	0.6	Large wavelets; crests begin to break; foam of glassy appearance.
4	5.0	1.0	Small waves becoming longer; fairly frequent white horses.
5	8.0	2.0	Moderate waves taking a more pronounced long form.
6	11.0	3.0	Large waves begin to form; probably some spray.
7	14.0	4.0	Sea heaps up; spindrift begins to be seen.
8	17.0	5.5	Moderately high waves of greater length.
9	21.0	7.0	High waves; sea begins to roll; spray affects visibility.
10	24.0	9.0	Very high waves with long overhanging crests; rolling of the sea becomes heavy.
11	28.0	11.5	Exceptionally high waves; sea is covered with long white patches of foam.
12	33.0	14.0	The air is filled with foam and spray; visibility is very seriously affected.

* In contrast to this table, DWD mainly provides ranges of values for v_w with an overlap between subsequent Beaufort numbers.

† Abbreviated descriptions from Encyclopædia Britannica [334].

Alternatively, the optional parent factor *Wind Speed* (v_w) can be used in both model layouts. To convert values for v_w into values for $H_{1/3}$, the Beaufort wind force scale of DWD is used [260]. Table 5.14 shows the scale and provides typical $H_{1/3}$ values [335], meaning that it cannot be assumed that the actual $H_{1/3}$ will precisely match the table value at all times. In the first column, the table shows the Beaufort number. For v_w , DWD mainly provides value ranges that overlap for two subsequent Beaufort numbers. In the second column (v_w), Table 5.14 shows the lower boundary of the Beaufort number. In RUMMs, the overlapping v_w value of two neighbouring Beaufort numbers was always assigned to the higher one. For example, if v_w is 3.0 m s^{-1} , the value is translated into Beaufort Number 3 and not Beaufort Number 2 (or 0.6 m and not to 0.2 m for $H_{1/3}$ in the third column), even though DWD would allow for both interpretations. This approach leads to a more conservative function of the factor in the model. A combination of the MATCH and INDEX functions is used by the RUMMs Excel tool to perform the value transition from v_w into $H_{1/3}$ according to Table 5.14. Note that this conversion can lead to an overestimation of $H_{1/3}$ (see 3.4.4).

$H_{1/3}$ is one of the factors with an LoU ($H_{1/3}^l$) (see 5.10.1). There exist heavy weather conditions in which EOD action, or work that involves lowering personnel and gear into the water, should not take place at all. A value of 3.0 m is considered a wave height limit in one study on the maintenance of marine renewable structures [336]. It can therefore be used as a predefined LoU value in the model, i.e., independently from the deployed equipment, no EOD is permissible when $H_{1/3}^l > 3.0$ m. In practice, however, the LoU may be lower since it depends on the available equipment, including the vessel. If the expected or momentary significant wave height exceeds the LoU, the EOD operation must not be executed or continued. Hence, while the lower boundary of the value range ($H_{1/3}^{min}$) is 0.0 m, the upper value range boundary is equal ($H_{1/3}^{max}$) to the LoU. The maximum upper value range boundary is 3.0 m, but it may be lower due to the equipment.

The *Significant Wave Height* is one of many parent factors for the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. This is the case for both model layouts.

User Instruction

The user must enter $H_{1/3}$ into cell **D56** if a value is available. If no value for $H_{1/3}$ is available, the user must leave cell **D56** empty. If an LoU exists, the user must enter $H_{1/3}^l$ in cell **D64**. If $H_{1/3}^l < H_{1/3}$, the field *Limitation of Use Exceeded* (cell **D73**) jumps to YES. This signifies that EOD must not be conducted or continued at all.

5.7.29 Visual Range Under Water

An introduction to the impact of turbidity and the *Visual Range Under Water* (R) on EOD and an overview of the factor's value distribution in the study area were given in 3.4.6.

If the information on R can be collected by the user of RUMMs, it has no parent factor in the confirmed layout. It can be estimated after *UXO identification* has been executed by a diver or with the help of an ROV or crawler.

If no such estimation is attainable or if the planning layout is used, it is possible to derive a representative value for R from the EOD action's *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}) and *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}) as well as the *Planned EOD Date* (PD). To achieve this, RUMMs uses a dataset of Secchi depth measurements in the study area. It was downloaded from MUDAB and described in 3.4.6 [255]. In the RUMMs Excel tool, the data are stored in the sheet '8. Visual Range Under Water'. The locations of measurement stations where these values were obtained are shown in Figure 3.11.

In the Baltic Sea, the stations were distributed similarly to those for *Wind Speed* measurements. To obtain a value for R in the Baltic Sea, the tool performs the identical operations that are used for the *Wind Speed* (see 5.7.27). Pivot tables were used to filter for stations with at least ten measured values per season. From these tables, the seasonal median Secchi depth of the station that is located closest to ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} is calculated by using the haversine formula, as well as the LOOKUP, FREQUENCY, and INDEX functions of Excel.

For the North Sea, the number of stations with at least ten values per season was considered too low (e.g., only two stations for spring). Hence, the overall annual median of the nearest measurement station is used. Accordingly, for the North Sea, the RUMMs Excel tool works independently from PD but uses ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} to determine R . The user should recall the low station coverage in the North Sea (see Figure 3.11) as well as the over-representation of measurements that were taken during spring (see 3.10).

In RUMMs, the lower limit of the value range (R^{min}) is 0.0 m, as this is the point at which no more visual information can be obtained. The upper limit of the value range (R^{max}) is either 2.0 m or the value of *UXO longest dimension* (l_l), whichever is larger. On the one hand, $R^{max} = 2.0$ m was selected as the standard upper limit, as it allows for good orientation under water. On the other hand, ideal handling of a UXO object requires visually monitoring it during EOD (see Appendix 6). Therefore, l_l is the required visual range. Accordingly, equation (12) applies. Note that there exists a threshold value $l_l^{max} = 3000$ mm. However, if a larger value for l_l is entered, R^{max} is still adapted to this value.

$$R^{max} = \begin{cases} l_l & , \text{ if } l_l > 2 \text{ m} \\ 2 \text{ m} & , \text{ if } l_l \leq 2 \text{ m} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

If the value for R that is estimated by the EOD service provider or that is derived from the closest measurement station is larger than R^{max} , then R is treated as equal to R^{max} since it is sufficient for good orientation underwater and enables viewing the entire UXO object.

For both model layouts, the *Visual Range Under Water* is a parent factor to the model output *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.

User Instruction

For the confirmed layout, the user must enter R in cell **D57** if a value is available. If no value for R is available, the user must leave cell **D57** empty.

5.7.30 Water Depth

Background information on the *Water Depth* (D) in the study area was provided in 3.4.5. The factor depends on the location of the EOD operation. This was, however, not implemented as a function into the model as tides and sediment accumulation can change D at many locations, especially in the North Sea (see 3.4.5 and 3.4.1).

If the planning layout is used, a value for D must be acquired during the phase I process *documentation of the site conditions*. In case the confirmed layout is used, the value for D for the specific target point should be available in the target list that was created as part of the process *data interpretation* during phase II.

Following the maximum D in the study area, its value range is 2 m to 71 m. Note that $D_{max} = 71$ m is the highest number and the deepest point. If the EOD operation takes place in the Baltic Sea, the highest possible value is 47 m. It was furthermore decided that

$D_{min} = 2$ m. If an EOD operation takes place in shallower waters, it should be treated as if executed onshore. RUMMs is not suitable for use in such cases. The same is true if D_{min} is undercut at any point during the EOD operation, either during the key processes *underwater transfer* and *recovery* or because of low tide.

D is among the three factors that have an LoU (D^l). As described in 3.4.5, divers face operational limits regarding the depth at which they can operate. The same is true for some equipment (e.g., cameras). If no such limitation exists, it is defined that $D_{max} = 71$ m. However, if a limitation exists and is entered by the user, the model assumes $D_{max} = D^l$. This has two consequences. Firstly, if $D^l < D$ no EOD can commence until other equipment is available. Secondly, the calculation of the model outputs is changed when an LoU value is entered. To better understand this, the reader is referred to 5.10.1.

The *Water Depth* is the only factor that is a parent both to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. In this regard, both model layouts work identically.

User Instruction

The user must enter D in cell **D58**. If an LoU exists, the user must enter D^l in cell **D65**. If $D^l < D$, the field *Limitation of Use Exceeded* (cell **D73**) jumps to YES. This signifies that EOD must not be conducted or continued at all.

5.8 Omitted Factors

Numerous factors that were included in earlier versions of RUMMs did not remain in the model's release version. They were removed either because there is insufficient information to implement them into the model in a meaningful way, because they were considered too insignificant, because they introduced too many uncertainties, or combinations thereof. The most relevant of these omitted factors are briefly presented here.

Burial Angle of Object, Total Burial Depth, and Migration Status

The burial angle, total burial depth, and migration status are properties of UXO that can be regarded as affecting the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. These were all proposed during the 1st EOD RA workshop and are therefore discussed under the same headline.

If an object is buried at an unfortunate angle, it is possible that parts that are decisive for the decision on which key process to pursue can only be investigated after complete *object uncovering* has taken place. In the opposite case, seeing only a small part of the object may be sufficient to make a decision. However, it is impossible to define universally valid rules for how an object must be buried for it to be at an ideal angle for *UXO identification*. This depends on the *UXO Type* and especially on the *Fuse Properties*. RUMMs uses the factor *Burial State* (B) to express the degree to which an object is covered by sediment. The greater B , the higher the likelihood that important information is concealed. Hence, no additional factor that expresses the burial angle was added.

The deeper an object is buried, the more technically and financially demanding an EOD operation will usually be. It is, however, unlikely that the removal of sediment layers above a deeply buried UXO contributes to the risk of an undesired detonation as defined in 5.3.2. Given that unexplained explosions (see 5.4.2) are considered part of the residual risk, the total burial depth of an object was considered irrelevant for RUMMs. On the other hand, once the *object uncovering* reaches the point at which the object proper becomes visible, accidentally moving or touching the object is a possible scenario. This is again expressed by *B*.

UXO may be located in areas in which it may migrate due to sediment mechanics, currents, or anthropogenic processes (see 2.1.3 and 3.4.3). Depending on the extent of these mechanisms, this may lead to time pressure for the execution of the key processes. However, other situations, such as UXO that is located near traffic routes, can put EOD under time pressure as well. These are not included in RUMMs either. The fact that UXO may migrate does not by itself contribute to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* or *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. Accordingly, RUMMs does not feature factors related to UXO migration.

Brisance

Brisance was first mentioned in 2.2.8. It is a performance indicator for explosive materials that expresses the shattering effect that a charge has on its surroundings. It depends on the heat of the detonation, the detonation velocity, and the density of the explosive. [130] It can be used for one of the numerous options to calculate the *Relative Effectiveness (RE)*. Since it only has a single definition, brisance is actually superior to *RE* in expressing performance. However, unlike brisance, *RE* can be used to calculate the *Shock Factor*, which is a factor that depends on *Charge Mass* to express the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. This makes *RE* more useful than brisance in the context of RUMMs. The latter was therefore omitted.

Friction Sensitivity

Even though friction sensitivity is an important property when determining how sensitive an explosive material is, this factor was not included in RUMMs. Real-world observations have confirmed changing impact sensitivities, but increases in friction sensitivity have not been regarded as a major issue. [132] The same materials that were tested for impact sensitivity, which are shown in Table 5.7, were also tested for friction sensitivity. For all of the measured samples, a friction sensitivity value of 360 N or higher was reported [148, 326]. Therefore, even though the literature mentions potential changes in the parameter (see 2.2.9), this has not been demonstrated for main charges that were found offshore.

It should be mentioned that in a friction sensitivity study with newly produced material samples, values of 360 N were measured for all mixtures containing TNT. Furthermore, in 90 samples from onshore sites, no value beyond 360 N was measured for mixtures that were mainly TNT-based. Higher sensitivities were, however, reported for mixtures con-

taining PETN (up to 60 N for pure PETN dry and wet) and for pure RDX (up to around 110 N). It is noteworthy that a higher sensitivity is inherent to PETN and RDX, even without artificial or real ageing. [144] Another study determined the friction sensitivity of TNT to be 108 N, and measured 96 N for a WWI main charge with a concentration of over 96 % TNT [146]. Nevertheless, the factor is not included in RUMMs since no data for offshore UXO are available that demonstrate an increase in friction sensitivity.

Heat Sensitivity and Thermal Stability

In the literature, heat sensitivity is commonly mentioned as a property of explosive materials that changes due to ageing and therefore increases the risk of an undesired detonation (see 2.2.9). Due to these claims, it is generally advised that EOD be executed with caution when it comes to subjecting UXO to temperature shifts, especially temperature increases. There are, however, no studies available that quantify the heat sensitivity or the changes thereof of explosive materials that are contained in UXO. Consequently, it was not possible to establish a basis for including the property as a factor in the risk model.

Impact Sensitivity of the Detonator

The matter of changing properties of explosive materials was discussed at length in 2.2.9 and implemented for the *Impact Sensitivity (I)* of the main charge in 5.7.19. It is appropriate to assume that similar changes occur to the primary explosive material in the detonator. Still, after a comment during the 2nd EOD RA workshop, it was decided to remove this factor from the model. Primary explosives have a low *Impact Sensitivity Base Values (I_b)*, i.e., they are very sensitive. In addition, no literature was found in which *Current Impact Sensitivity (I_c)* values of primary explosives were discussed. Therefore, the RA would not benefit from the inclusion of this factor.

Indication of Other UXO in the Vicinity

According to the EOD procedure, the *UXO identification* is preceded by the *survey process, data processing, and data interpretation*, which are executed to produce a target list of locations at which data indicate the presence of a UXO object of a given size—the reference object. Hence, by the time the process of *UXO identification* is conducted, nearby locations at which UXO may be present will usually be known. In case *object identification* is conducted for several target points before beginning with the key processes, target points may even be confirmed. On the other hand, since the *survey process* is always designed to find a given reference object, smaller UXO in the vicinity may not have been detected.

This information is relevant since an undesired detonation of one object can lead to sympathetic detonations of other objects [161]. The factor was part of the model until the 2nd EOD RA workshop (see Appendix 5). At that point, it was decided to remove it from RUMMs, as keeping it would have introduced too many uncertainties. If other UXO objects are present in the vicinity, it would be necessary to assess their *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* based on their properties. This could lead to a situation in which it is required to assess not only two

but multiple objects in one model run with RUMMs. This removes a lot of transparency for the user. Instead, users are advised to assess the risk of a sympathetic detonation by running RUMMs repeatedly with the properties of the nearby UXO.

Oxygen Level, pH, Salinity, and Temperature

The oxygen level, pH, salinity, and temperature are among the environmental properties that determine the *Corrosion Rate (CR)* at a given location. These relationships were discussed in 3.4.2. In earlier versions of the model, it was planned to deviate *CR* from these properties. As discussed in 5.11.3, the current implementation of *CR* in RUMMs (fixed annual values) has its limitations. However, numerous challenges would have to be overcome to calculate *CR* from other environmental properties. Firstly, it would be necessary to obtain representative data at a sufficient spatial resolution for each of the additional factors. Secondly, these properties do not account for processes such as pitting or galvanic corrosion. Thirdly, as 3.4.2 points out, corrosion also depends on the properties of the casing of a UXO object, which means that a complex calculation would not reliably produce better results than the current implementation. Hence, these factors were deleted from the model after the 2nd EOD RA workshop.

5.9 Model Outputs

RUMMs describes two types of relationships: those between two factors and those between a factor and one of the three model outputs *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. The former type of relationship was covered in 5.7. These relationships mathematically express how the properties of UXO, the environment, and EOD technology interact. They were developed through literature research and data analysis and describe the physical environment.

For the second type of relationship, performing literature research or statistics with the aim of finding a scientific explanation of how a factor influences a model output is bound to be unsuccessful. The reason is that there are knowledge gaps on this type of relationship. No sufficiently large number of occurrences of the undesired event exist, so no statistical relationship between factors and model outputs can be inferred. Accordingly, information on these relationships and on the way they should be implemented into the model was obtained by conducting EOD RA workshops with experts (see 5.2). The underlying assumption of organising these workshops was that experts could provide new information on how to meaningfully converge all the different factors into the model outputs. Normalisation and weighting were used to do so. The following subsections describe the model outputs, provide some theoretical background on these operations, explain how workshop participants contributed to their definition, and present how they are implemented in the model.

5.9.1 Complexity of the EOD Operation

The *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) is one of the three model outputs of RUMMs. It is the model node with the most parent factors. In both model layouts, these are *UXO Mass* (m_u), *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l), *Burial State* (B), *Condition of Casing* (CC), *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* (IC_c), *Fuse Corrosion State* (FC), *Fuse Properties* (FP), *Current Velocity* (v_c), *Significant Wave Height* ($H_{1/3}$), *Visual Range Under Water* (R), and *Water Depth* (D). The fact that E has so many inputs reflects that EOD is in fact an activity that requires attention to many details. The following list provides rationales for connecting each of the input factors to E .

UXO Mass: UXO with low m_u can be lifted by divers, ROVs, and crawlers alike. High m_u means that larger and more specialised equipment is required for the execution of the key processes.

UXO Longest Dimension: Objects with high l_l are more challenging to handle as they have larger leverage. The larger an object, the more challenging it is to maintain an overview of it under water. Large objects have a larger surface area against which water currents can flow.

Burial State: The higher B , the more challenging the execution of the key processes. Note that *object uncovering* is not part of the RA. Still, accessibility to the object is limited if it is partially buried. When *underwater transfer* or *recovery* need to be executed, UXO needs to be dragged, lifted, or otherwise removed from the sediment.

Condition of Casing: If an object has a low CC it is more difficult to handle. It might break apart when it is lifted, or the casing may collapse when it is grabbed.

Current Impact Sensitivity Classification: The higher IC_c , the easier the main charge may detonate. Hence, handling has to be done with additional care to avoid accidentally impacting the main charge (e.g., by dropping the object or by hitting it with the manipulator of an ROV or crawler).

Fuse Corrosion State: A less preserved fuse (i.e., a lower value for FC) was indicated to require more careful handling by the experts during the 2nd EOD RA Workshop (see Appendix 6), as it is less predictable in its behaviour and thus the object must be handled more carefully. If no fuse is present or if it is fully corroded, handling the object is less demanding.

Fuse Properties: A higher FP value indicates that more features of the fuse (or fuses) exist that increase the challenge during the handling of the object. If no fuse is present, other fuse properties are irrelevant.

Current Velocity: A higher v_c makes the underwater work more challenging. It requires more proficient divers and stronger thrusters on ROVs. There are LoUs for all types of equipment that prohibit work when currents become too strong.

Significant Wave Height: Large $H_{1/3}$ has a stronger wave effect, which makes working in shallow waters more challenging. Furthermore, it increases the challenges during the deployment and return of equipment and personnel. This introduces LoUs. The factor also directly affects the UXO if the process *recovery* is executed.

Visual Range Under Water: The lower R , the more challenging is orientation, and the more difficult is monitoring work. It can also prevent seeing an object or nearby equipment that is required for EOD.

Water Depth: While very shallow waters produce their own set of challenges, for the model it was decided to assume that greater D increases E since all types of equipment, and especially divers, have LoUs for D .

The purpose of E is to quantify how complex the EOD operation is expected to be based on the properties of the UXO and the natural environment. The complexity of an operation is not a measurable quantity, but it can be expressed as an index, which is why E is treated as such in RUMMs. It has a value range from 0.0 to 10.0. To understand how E is calculated, it is first necessary to understand factor normalisation (see 5.9.4) and weighting (see 5.9.5). The same is true for the other model outputs. Formulas for their calculation are therefore given in 5.9.6.

While it is a model output, *Complexity of the EOD Operation* also acts as a parent factor to *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*. It fulfils this double role in both model layouts.

5.9.2 Probability of an Undesired Detonation

Probability of an Undesired Detonation (P) is another model output of RUMMs'. It has four parent factors: *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* (IC_c), *Fuse Corrosion State* (FC), *Fuse Properties* (FP), and, as mentioned in the previous subsection, *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E). The following list provides the reader with an understanding of these connections. The factors IC_c , FC , and FP all influence P directly as input factors and indirectly via E . This runs the risk of over-representing these factors. However, when this issue was raised with the experts during the EOD RA workshops, it was not considered a concern. While the direct connection to P represents the fact that an undesired detonation may happen during the key processes, the indirect connection via E increases or reduces P depending on the complexity of the situation. Below, a rationale for each of the connections is given.

Current Impact Sensitivity Classification: The higher IC_c , the easier the main charge may detonate. This means that the undesired denotation does not occur due to the UXO object performing its intended purpose of detonating via the fuse but rather by a direct entry of energy into the main charge.

Fuse Corrosion State: A deteriorated fuse (i.e., a low FC value) is assumed by experts to trigger the ignition chain more easily and in situations in which it was not originally intended to operate, i.e., it leads to a higher P . This issue is removed if no fuse is present or if it is fully corroded.

Fuse Properties: The FP value indicates the number of properties of a UXO object's fuse (or fuses) that may lead to its detonation. Therefore, a higher FP value leads to a higher likelihood that the fuse may operate as originally intended, which means an increase in P .

Complexity of the EOD Operation: The underlying notion of this connection is that the higher the value for E , the higher the chance of accidents or errors during the key processes and the higher the likelihood of the undesired event. E expresses how benign or hostile the environmental conditions are and how much care needs to be applied during the execution of the key processes. Therefore, a larger E value is associated with a rise in P .

P represents the probability component of the RA (see 4.2.2). In probability calculus, a probability of occurrence is usually expressed as a percentage or a value ranging from 0 to 1. It was decided not to express P this way. In 3.3.1, it was demonstrated how common EOD is in the study area. No accidents due to an undesired detonation have been reported so far, and hence, expressing probability in the usual way would lead to very low numbers. This would produce two problems. Firstly, a number that is several orders of magnitude below 0 can be misinterpreted as negligible. It is, however, a basic assumption of this study (and of EOD practitioners) that EOD is a risky activity. Even working underwater, entirely unrelated to the issue of UXO, is risky [206]. Hence, providing extremely small numbers as a model output for P is considered inappropriate. Secondly, even if a sense of caution prevails with low probability numbers, interpreting these is far from intuitive and impairs comparability. Furthermore, overlooking an order of magnitude can easily lead to a misinterpretation of the results. A value range from 0.0 to 10.0 is considered easier to comprehend. An inexperienced user of RUMMs will nevertheless find it challenging to interpret the P value. Later sections on model exploration (6.1 and 6.2) and exemplified model application (6.3) offer guidance on this matter.

5.9.3 Consequence of an Undesired Detonation

The third model output is the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C). There are two factors that act as its input: *Shock Factor* (SF) and *Water Depth* (D). It should be reiterated that this value expresses the consequences for the risk receptors as defined in 5.5, i.e., the personnel and equipment at the EOD site. The two input factors are connected to C for two reasons.

Shock Factor: SF by definition expresses how strongly a shock wave can impact vessels, equipment, or personnel in the water. Therefore, the higher SF , the greater the expected consequences of an undesired event for the risk receptors.

Water Depth: The greater D , the lower the expected C of an undesired detonation if a risk receptor is further away from the object. If the risk receptor is located right next to the UXO, D is not expected to change the consequences.

C represents the consequence component of the RA (see 4.2.2). Similar to E and P it is an index. It does not quantify the consequences, for example, in monetary terms. The reason lies in the variability of potentially deployed equipment or personnel. If an undesired

detonation were to occur, a high C would mean the likely loss of life of divers. However, whether and how many divers are on site is not a matter of calculation by RUMMs but of standard operating procedures. Similarly, the loss in economic value depends on the value of the deployed equipment. Accordingly, C always expresses the consequence for any risk receptor on site. It never answers the normative question of the value of different subjects of protection. In different contexts, the various subjects of protection may be assigned values in relation to each other. They may also be treated as equals. Commonly, the life and health of humans are valued higher than economic goods. This is reflected in the fact that diving should be avoided if other technical means for an EOD operation exist (see 3.3.3). This paradigm exists independently of any structured RA.

The user is expected to know which risk receptors are at the EOD site. Therefore, it is their responsibility to assess the possible value lost or damaged if the undesired event occurs. Guidance on the interpretation of C is given in Chapter 6 in the same sections as for P .

5.9.4 Factor Normalisation

The term ‘normalisation’ describes numerous concepts and processes in various fields of science, such as statistics, sociology, and linguistics. Even though it differs mathematically, the type of normalisation applied here is akin to the concept of ‘rescaling’ or ‘min-max normalisation’ in machine learning. This method allows rescaling data with a given range of values to a range that scales from 0 to 1 [337]. A comparable approach is used for the method of ‘life cycle assessment (LCA)’, which can be used to assess the environmental footprint of products and services. Values are rescaled, albeit, in the case of LCA, not to a specific value range. Applicants of the method use normalisation to make the values of different environmental impact categories comparable. This allows for assessing the overall environmental impact of a product or service [338]. Experts in life cycle assessment reportedly perceive normalisation as relevant for decision-making [339].

The motivation for implementing a normalisation method in RUMMs is to make its very different factors comparable and allow for their convergence into model outputs. To do so, the equations below are used to produce rescaled values. RUMMs uses four normalisation types, which are shown in Figure 5.7. These are symbolised as F_1^n , F_2^n , F_3^n , and F_4^n . In each of the four graphs, the x-axis represents the factor, i.e., the original value with its respective value range as given in the columns F^{min} and F^{max} of Table 5.15. The y-axis always represents the normalised value after the normalisation process, with the value range 0.0 to 10.0 or 1.0 to 10.0. Figure 5.7 presents positive relationships between a factor and a model output as solid graphs. However, some relationships are negative (F_{-1}^n , F_{-2}^n , F_{-3}^n , and F_{-4}^n). In such cases, the lower the value of the factor, the higher its normalised value. These cases are represented by the dashed graphs in Figure 5.7, which vertically mirror the solid ones. The legend entries in the figure correspond to the variables used in equations (13) through (23). The normalisation types in Figure 5.7 are characterised as described below.

- **Type 1 - Linear** is a linear normalisation function. Here, the normalised value changes by the same relative proportion as the factor. In the model, type 1 occurs for three factors.
- **Type 2 - Exponential** is an exponential normalisation function, which the model uses for three factors. It is characterised by a gradual increase in the steepness of the function. That means that at the lower end of the value range, a change in the factor leads to a minor change in the normalised value. The relative change in the normalised value increases along the value range of the factor.
- **Type 3 - Root** is another exponential normalisation function, which occurs four times in the model. It is characterised by a gradual decrease in the steepness of the function. That means that at the lower end of the value range, a change in the factor leads to a major change in the normalised value. The relative change in the normalised value decreases along the value range of the factor.
- **Type 4 - Incremental** shows an incremental normalisation function. It occurs eight times in the model. It is characterised by ten incremental value facets. The value of the factor falls into one of these ten value facets and is associated with the respective normalised value. These value facets increase linearly.

As described in 5.2, experts were presented with the four normalisation types to vote on the function that should be applied to which of the factors. If the poll during the 1st EOD RA workshop yielded an absolute majority, the normalisation type was accepted for RUMMs. The remaining factors were discussed during the 2nd EOD RA workshop and again voted on. After the second poll, a normalisation type for each factor could be defined. For a detailed description of the discussions on these normalisations and for the polling results, please refer to Appendices 4 and 6 to 8. It should be noted that experts were presented with only five incremental value facets for the incremental normalisation (type 4). The decision to achieve higher granularity by using ten facets instead of five was made after the workshops. Furthermore, to avoid confusion, experts were only presented with graphs that represented positive relationships.

Table 5.15 gives an overview of all parent factors of the model outputs *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. The columns F^{min} and F^{max} contain the lower and upper boundaries of the value ranges of the factors, respectively. Next, the table lists the factors' units before their normalisation takes place. The column 'N-Type' shows the normalisation type that is used in the model based on expert voting and discussions. Phrased differently, it shows which of the curves in Figure 5.7 best describes the relationship between the factor and the model output, according to the experts. The column 'Equation' indicates which of the equations below is implemented in the model. Next, the columns $F^{n\ min}$ and $F^{n\ max}$ contain the boundaries of the value ranges after the normalisation (i.e., the operation performed by the corresponding equation was executed). The n signifies that the values are normalised, which distinguishes them from the original and weighted boundaries (see 5.9.5). For all factors, $F^{n\ max} = 10$ since that is the purpose of the normalisation. $F^{n\ min}$ can either be 0.0 or 1.0, depending on whether a factor's contribution to the model outputs

FIGURE 5.7: Normalisation types in RUMMs.

can be eliminated or not. This concept is explained in the following paragraph. Finally, the ‘N-Variable’ is the variable of the value after normalisation. Some factors are inputs to more than one model output. Therefore, their normalised variable is denoted as F^{nP} when contributing to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, F^{nC} when contributing to the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*, and F^{nE} when contributing to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.

With the normalisation, each of the factors is rescaled to a range from 1.0 to 10.0 or from 0.0 to 10.0 depending on its original value range. For example, the *Condition of Casing* can range from 5 if the casing is in perfect shape to 0 if it is fully corroded. Hence, the inversely rescaled value can range from 0.0 to 10.0 as well. The *Water Depth* on the other hand cannot be 0 m as this would mean an EOD operation onshore (or on a tidal flat), which is out of scope. Thus, the value range of the resulting rescaled values runs from 1.0 to 10.0.

The model performs rescaling as stated in the equations below. It should be noted that the rescaled values lose all units of the original factor values. Operations that are not used within the model, such as an inverted incremental (type 4) normalisation, are not listed.

TABLE 5.15: Normalisation types that were applied to factors in RUMMs.

Factor	Variable	F^{min}	F^{max}	Unit	N*-Type	Equation	$F^{n min}$	$F^{n max}$	N*-Variable
<i>Normalisation to Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>									
Current Impact Sensitivity Classification	IC_c	1	4	-	Incremental	(23)	1.0	10.0	IC_c^{nP}
Fuse Corrosion State	FC	0	100	%	Inverted root	(21)	0.0	10.0	FC^{nP}
Fuse Properties	FP	0	8	-	Root	(18)	0.0	10.0	FP^{nP}
Complexity of the EOD Operation	E	0.0	10.0	-	Incremental	(22)	0.0	10.0	E^n
<i>Normalisation to Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>									
Shock Factor	SF	1	36	-	Root	(19)	0.0	10.0	SF^n
Water Depth	D	2	71	m	Inverted linear	(14)	1.0	10.0	D^{nC}
<i>Normalisation to Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>									
Current Impact Sensitivity Classification	IC_c	1	4	-	Incremental	(23)	1.0	10.0	IC_c^{nE}
Fuse Corrosion State	FC	0	100	%	Inverted exponential	(17)	0.0	10.0	FC^{nE}
Fuse Properties	FP	0	8	-	Exponential	(15)	0.0	10.0	FP^{nE}
UXO Mass	m_u	1	1300	kg	Incremental	(22)	1.0	10.0	m_u^n
UXO Longest Dimension	l_l	20	3000	mm	Incremental	(22)	1.0	10.0	l_l^n
Visual Range Under Water	R	0.0	2.0/ l_l	m	Inverted root	(20)	1.0	10.0	R^n
Burial State	B	0	100	%	Incremental	(22)	0.0	10.0	B^n
Current Velocity	v_c	0.00	1.50	ms^{-1}	Linear	(13)	0.0	10.0	v_c^n
Significant Wave Height	$H_{1/3}$	0.0	3.0	m	Linear or incremental [†]	(13) or (22) [†]	0.0	10.0	$H_{1/3}^n$
Water Depth	D	2	71	m	Incremental	(23)	1.0	10.0	D^{nE}
Condition of Casing	CC	0	5	-	Inverted exponential	(16)	0.0	10.0	CC^n

* Normalisation.

[†] Following the discussion of the 2nd EOD RA workshop, it was decided to use the incremental type for the planning layout and the linear type for the confirmed layout.

With equation (13), a factor value is rescaled according to the linear normalisation (type 1) to a range from 0.0 to 10.0. Here, F_1^n is the normalised value, F is the original value of the factor, and F^{max} is the highest possible value of the factor, i.e., the upper boundary of its value range. The multiplication with 10 is necessary since the division alone would rescale to 0 to 1 instead of the desired 0.0 to 10.0.

$$F_1^n = \frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10 \quad (13)$$

To rescale according to an inverted linear (type 1) normalisation to a range from 1.0 to 10.0, equation (14) is applied. In this equation, F_{-1}^n is the inverted normalised value, F is the original value of the factor, and F^{max} and F^{min} are the upper and lower boundaries of the factor's value range, respectively. The inclusion of the subtraction of F^{min} is required for factors for which $F^{min} \neq 0$. The multiplication with 9 instead of 10 is necessary due to the reduced targeted value range (1.0 to 10.0 instead of 0.0 to 10.0). The subtraction from 10 performs the inversion.

$$F_{-1}^n = 10 - \frac{F - F^{min}}{F^{max} - F^{min}} * 9 \quad (14)$$

For an exponential (type 2) normalisation, equation (15) is used. The exponentiation by the power of 2 and the division by 10 are required to rescale to the squared exponential function.

$$F_2^n = \frac{\left(\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10\right)^2}{10} \quad (15)$$

To perform inverted exponential (type 2) normalisations, equations (16) and (17) are used for the value ranges, starting with lower boundaries of 0.0 and 1.0, respectively.

$$F_{-2}^n = 10 - \frac{\left(\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10\right)^2}{10} \quad (16)$$

$$F_{-2}^n = 10 - \frac{\left(\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 9\right)^2}{9} \quad (17)$$

For the root normalisation (type 3), RUMMs applies equation (18) for the value range from 0.0 to 10.0 and equation (19) for 1.0 to 10.0. The square root and the multiplication with 100 or 81, respectively, are necessary operations to rescale the root function. In equation (19), the addition of 1 enables using the reduced value range.

$$F_3^n = \sqrt{\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 100} \quad (18)$$

$$F_3^n = \sqrt{\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 81 + 1} \quad (19)$$

To inversely root normalise (type 3), equations (20) and (21) are used for the value ranges starting with lower boundaries of 0.0 and 1.0, respectively.

$$F_{-3}^n = 10 - \sqrt{\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 100} \quad (20)$$

$$F_{-3}^n = 10 - \sqrt{\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 81} \quad (21)$$

Equation (22) describes how a factor is rescaled according to incremental normalisation (type 4). It works analogously to equation (13) but rounds the value up to integers to arrive at an incremental function. For factors that use this equation, the depiction of the incremental normalisation in Figure 5.7 is not precise, as a value of 0 would be rescaled to 0.0.

$$F_4^n = \left\lceil \frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10 \right\rceil \quad (22)$$

Equation (23) works like equation (22), but was adapted for factors with a range from 1.0 to 10.0 for which $F^{min} \neq 0$.

$$F_4^n = \left\lceil \frac{F - F^{min}}{F^{max} - F^{min}} * 9 + 1 \right\rceil \quad (23)$$

It is important to understand that even though types 2 and 3 use exponential and root functions to perform the normalisation, the resulting rescaled value will always lie in the range 0.0 to 10.0 or 1.0 to 10.0. Consider a fictional factor with a unit of measure (UM) that ranges from 0 UM to 100 UM. Table 5.16 displays the resulting rescaled values when applying the equations for all four normalisation types (when non-inverted) to a range from 0.0 to 10.0. All values in Table 5.16 are rounded to the first decimal place. For F ranging from 0 UM to 50 UM, steps of 5 UM are shown to demonstrate the difference between linear (F_1^n) and incremental (F_4^n) normalisation.

The summary of the results in Table 5.16 is a brief reiteration of the descriptions of the four normalisation types. F_1^n is a linear normalisation. F_2^n is an exponential normalisation with an increase in the relative change in the normalised value along the value range of the factor. F_3^n is an exponential normalisation with a decrease in the relative change in the normalised value along the value range of the factor. Finally, F_4^n is an incremental normalisation that is based on a linear curve.

For some factors, normalisation has additional components that briefly warrant further specification. For *Fuse Corrosion State*, inverted normalisation types are used. However, once the factor's value drops to 0%, the inversion is cancelled and the normalised value is 0.0 instead of 10.0 (see 5.7.23). The factors *UXO Mass* and *UXO Longest Dimension* have threshold values for F^{max} (see 5.10.2). For these factors, if $F > F^{max}$, it will always

TABLE 5.16: Example of factor normalisation.

F (UM)	$F_1^n = \frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10$	$F_2^n = \frac{(\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10)^2}{10}$	$F_3^n = \sqrt{\frac{F}{F^{max}} * 100}$	$F_4^n = \left\lceil \frac{F}{F^{max}} * 10 \right\rceil$
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5	0.5	0.0	2.2	1.0
10	1.0	0.1	3.2	1.0
15	1.5	0.2	3.9	2.0
20	2.0	0.4	4.5	2.0
25	2.5	0.6	5.0	3.0
30	3.0	0.9	5.5	3.0
35	3.5	1.2	5.9	4.0
40	4.0	1.6	5.9	4.0
45	4.5	2.0	6.3	5.0
50	5.0	2.5	6.7	5.0
60	6.0	3.6	7.1	6.0
70	7.0	4.9	7.7	7.0
80	8.0	6.4	8.4	8.0
90	9.0	8.1	8.9	9.0
100	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0

be reduced to the value of the threshold. The *Shock Factor* is impacted by the threshold value of the *Charge Mass*. Finally, visual range can be influenced by the threshold value of the *UXO Longest Dimension*, if $l_i > 2.0$ m (see equation (12) in 5.7.29).

In summary, this section presents the rescaling of factor values to normalised value ranges from 0.0 to 10.0 or 1.0 to 10.0 in RUMMs. Four different types of normalisation were implemented: a linear one, two exponential ones, and an incremental one. This method makes the values of all factors comparable. It is now possible to use the normalised values for factor weighting.

5.9.5 Factor Weighting

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, ‘weighting’ is “a level of importance given to something compared to something else” [340]. The concept of weighting is widely used in science. It is, inter alia, applied to evaluate survey data, for example, in political or social sciences, to improve a sample’s answers’ representativeness of its population. This way, it is possible to account for the under-representation of subpopulations in a sample. [341] Another example is, as for normalisation, the application of weights in LCA. Here, they are used to quantify the relative severity of different environmental impact categories. Applying weights enables LCA practitioners, for example, to emphasise a product’s or service’s contribution to climate change to a stronger degree than its contribution to resource depletion when discussing its overall environmental impact [342].

In RUMMs, weighting fulfils a similar function but applies it to the factors. After the factors have been made comparable by normalisation, their weights express how strongly each of them contributes to the model outputs for which they act as parents.

TABLE 5.17: Weights (W) that were applied to normalised factors in RUMMs.

Factor	W^* -Variable	W	$F^{w\ min}$	$F^{w\ max}$
<i>Weighting to Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>				
Current Impact Sensitivity Classification	IC_c^{wP}	2.125	2.125	21.150
Fuse Corrosion State	FC^{wP}	4.875	0.000	48.750
Fuse Properties	FP^{wP}	4.750	0.000	47.500
Complexity of the EOD Operation	E^w	2.750	0.000	27.500
<i>Weighting to Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>				
Shock Factor	SF^w	3.667 [†]	3.667	36.670
Water Depth	D^{wC}	1.333 [†]	1.333	13.330
<i>Weighting to Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>				
Current Impact Sensitivity Classification	IC_c^{wE}	2.750	0.000	27.500
Fuse Corrosion State	FC^{wP}	4.125	0.000	41.250
Fuse Properties	FP^{wP}	4.000	0.000	40.000
UXO Mass	m_u^w	2.875	2.875	28.750
UXO Longest Dimension	l_l^w	3.000	3.000	30.000
Visual Range Under Water	R^w	4.250	0.000	42.500
Burial State	B^w	3.375	0.000	33.750
Current Velocity	v_c^w	3.333 [†]	0.000	33.330
Significant Wave Height	$H_{1/3}^w$	2.500 [†]	0.000	25.000
Water Depth	D^{wE}	3.250	3.250	32.500
Condition of Casing	CC^w	3.167 [†]	0.000	31.670

* Weighting.

† Weight defined after the 2nd EOD RA workshops.

As there is no way to measure the magnitude of these contributions in the field, weights were determined by expert polls (see 5.2). Workshop participants were asked to vote on the weight of each factor on a scale from 1 to 5. The values were offered as integers. From the answers of the experts, the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (s) were calculated. If $s < 1.5$, then \bar{x} of a factor from the 1st EOD RA workshop was accepted as its weight. A small s was considered expert consensus, so no further discussion on the weight was necessary. If $s \geq 1.5$, factors were discussed during the 2nd EOD RA workshop, and experts were asked to vote once more. Again, \bar{x} was calculated to produce weights. With one exception, an $s < 1.5$ could be reached after the second vote. For the exception (*Significant Wave Height*), \bar{x} from the 1st EOD RA workshop was used due to the higher confidence, which resulted from the greater number of responses. More details on the workshop discussions and the polling results can be found in Appendices 4 and 6 to 8.

Table 5.17 presents the weights for the factors, as determined during the workshops. The weights represent the combined and moderated opinions of the involved experts. The first column shows the factors' names, and the second one lists their variables. Some factors are inputs to more than one model output. Therefore, their weighted variable

is denoted as F^{wP} when contributing to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, F^{wC} when contributing to the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*, and F^{wE} when contributing to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*. The table furthermore lists the value ranges for the weighted values in the columns $F^{w\min}$ and $F^{w\max}$. These are obtained by applying equation (24) to the normalised minimum and maximum values ($F^{n\min}$ and $F^{n\max}$). All values were rounded to the third decimal place.

Equation (24) is also used in RUMMs to obtain a weighted value of a factor (F^w), by multiplying its normalised value (F^n) with its weight (W).

$$F^w = F^n * W \quad (24)$$

Some of the weights produced by the expert polls are notable. They are briefly discussed below.

- Weights range from 1.333 to 4.875. Even though they are \bar{x} values, the results cover almost the full range of values that were offered in the poll (i.e., 1 to 5). This proves that, according to expert opinion, factors have significantly different importance for EOD risk.
- Only five factors received weightings ≥ 4 . This applies twice to *Fuse Corrosion State* and *Fuse Properties* and once to *Visual Range Under Water*. It can therefore be concluded that experts regard the condition of the fuse as the largest contributor to EOD risk. This corresponds with the impression that the author got from non-documented conversations with experts both during the EOD RA workshops and in other instances. The fuse factors' contribution to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* is considered more significant than that to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.
- Only *Water Depth* as an input to *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* received a value lower than 2. This shows that the great majority of factors in the model are considered relevant by the experts. It could be argued to remove the *Water Depth* due to its low contribution to the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. It was kept in the model for the following reasons:
 - The factor is also a parent of the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, where it received a higher weight. Thus, only the connection to the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* could have been deleted.
 - The weight in Table 5.17 was determined during the second round of workshops after an in-depth discussion of the factor. The poll from the 1st EOD RA workshop resulted in a higher weight but was rejected due to its large standard deviation.
 - Without the *Water Depth*, *Shock Factor* would be the only contributor to the consequences. This would remove the purpose of the model.
 - Despite the low weight, the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* turned out to be sensitive to changes in the *Water Depth* (see 6.1).
- All other factors received weights $2 < W < 4$. These numbers suggest that experts believe that they contribute to EOD risk to a relevant but not extreme degree.

- It is remarkable that the *UXO Mass*, *UXO Longest Dimension*, and *Condition of Casing* received lower weights than the *Visual Range Under Water*, *Burial State*, *Current Velocity*, and *Water Depth*. This demonstrates that environmental factors appear to have a greater impact on the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* than UXO factors.
- The *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* received comparatively low weights. This may be related to a lack of available information on the factor. This is explored in 5.11.5. It is assumed that experts assign lower weights to factors that they have limited knowledge about to avoid overstating their contribution to EOD risk.
- The contribution of the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (and its parents) to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* is rather low. Hence, experts consider *Fuse Corrosion State* and *Fuse Properties* to be more relevant than the combination of all factors influencing the challenges of the EOD operation.

The weighted values can be used to perform the final calculations in RUMMs. These operations are described in the following subsection.

5.9.6 Model Output Calculation

RUMMs does not provide the user with a singular, definitive risk value. During the 1st EOD RA Workshop, there was a request to provide the EOD expert with a more differentiated picture of the risk (see Appendix 3). Thus, the model features three model outputs: *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*.

All three model outputs (O) can be calculated by applying equation (25). Here, $\sum F^w$ is the sum of the weighted values of its parent factors, and $\sum F^{w\ max}$ is the sum of the upper boundaries of the parent factors' value ranges. The multiplication with 10 is a linear rescaling operation (see equation (13)) to express the result in a range from 0.0 to 10.0 for *Complexity of the EOD Operation* and *Probability of an Undesired Detonation*. For the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* values lie in the range from 1.0 to 10.0. This difference originates from the value ranges of the respective parent factors.

$$O = \frac{\sum F^w}{\sum F^{w\ max}} * 10 \quad (25)$$

The model output *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) has the weighted factors *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* (IC_c^{wE}), *Fuse Corrosion State* (FC^{wE}), *Fuse Properties* (FP^{wE}), *UXO Mass* (m_u^w), *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l^w), *Visual Range Under Water* (R^w), *Burial State* (B^w), *Current Velocity* (v_c^w), *Significant Wave Height* ($H_{1/3}^w$), *Water Depth* (D^{wE}), and *Condition of Casing* (CC^w) as parents. Accordingly, E is calculated by using equation (26).

$$E = \frac{IC_c^{wE} + FC^{wE} + FP^{wE} + m_u^w + l_l^w + R^w + B^w + v_c^w + H_{1/3}^w + D^{wE} + CC^w}{IC_c^{wE \max} + FC^{wE \max} + FP^{wE \max} + m_u^{w \max} + l_l^{w \max} + R^{w \max} + B^{w \max} + v_c^{w \max} + H_{1/3}^{w \max} + D^{wE \max} + CC^{w \max}} * 10 \quad (26)$$

The model output *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P) has four weighted factors as parents. These are: *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* (IC_c^{wP}), *Fuse Corrosion State* (FC^{wP}), *Fuse Properties* (FP^{wP}), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E^w). To calculate P , equation (27) is used.

$$P = \frac{IC_c^{wP} + FC^{wP} + FP^{wP} + E^w}{IC_c^{wP \max} + FC^{wP \max} + FP^{wP \max} + E^{w \max}} * 10 \quad (27)$$

The model output *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C) has two weighted parent factors: *Shock Factor* (SF_c^w) and *Water Depth* (D^{wC}). To calculate C , RUMMs uses equation (28).

$$C = \frac{SF_c^w + D^{wC}}{SF_c^{w \max} + D^{wC \max}} * 10 \quad (28)$$

User Instruction

The user can see P , C , and E in cells **D70**, **D71**, and **D72**, respectively.

5.10 Other RUMMs Functionalities

The previous sections described how each of the factors in RUMMs works and how they are connected with each other in their parent-child-factor relationships. Calculating this type of relationship and normalising and weighting factors to converge them to model outputs are the main functionalities of RUMMs. There are two additional functionalities that were regularly mentioned in the factor descriptions in 5.7. These are LoUs and threshold values. Both were developed following the discussion of the 1st EOD RA Workshop. They only apply to a small number of factors. The following two subsections describe how these functionalities work, explain why they are necessary, and demonstrate how they impact the model outputs.

5.10.1 Limitations of Use

Both model layouts include three factors that feature an LoU value that can be entered by the user. These factors are *Current Velocity* (v_c), *Significant Wave Height* ($H_{1/3}$), and *Water Depth* (D). These were introduced in response to a comment during the 1st EOD RA Workshop, which called for risk mitigating factors (see Appendix 3). In bow-tie diagrams, this kind of feature is sometimes referred to as a ‘preventive barrier’, since its purpose is to reduce the probability of the occurrence of the undesired event [295].

In RUMMs, a large LoU value expresses that EOD operations are possible, even in challenging environmental conditions. If the value for any of the three factors mentioned surpasses the respective LoU, the EOD operation must not be executed.

The factors v_c and $H_{1/3}$ have predefined absolute LoU values. These signify the conditions under which no EOD work is possible at all. They are independent of the available equipment. In addition, the user of RUMMs has the option to enter equipment-dependent LoU values in cells **D63** for v_c^l , **D64** for $H_{1/3}^l$, and **D65** for D^l . If the equipment-dependent LoU allows working under more challenging conditions than the absolute LoU, RUMMs continues with the absolute value. If the former is stricter than the latter, RUMMs continues with the LoU of the equipment. Since many different pieces of equipment are used during EOD, the user should find the one with the lowest LoU values for each of the factors and enter them into the respective cells.

If an LoU is exceeded, cell **D73** jumps to YES, thereby signifying that EOD cannot be conducted or continued at all. Note that the RUMMs Excel tool will continue to calculate the model outputs. These are, however, not reliable under the condition that a factor's value is larger than its LoU allows.

The dynamic nature of the equipment-dependent LoUs impacts the model output *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) to which all three factors act as parents. This is due to the fact that LoUs decrease the upper boundaries of the value ranges of v_c , $H_{1/3}$, and D . For a better understanding, consider an example calculation for E in which $v_c = 0.50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $H_{1/3} = 2.0 \text{ m}$, and $D = 50 \text{ m}$. All other parent factors of E take on their lowest possible value.

First, consider that a crawler is used during the EOD operation. In this case, RUMMs is using the predefined absolute LoU values, i.e., $v_c^l = 1.50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $H_{1/3}^l = 3.0 \text{ m}$, and no LoU for D . If all other parents of E are set to a value that equals the lower boundaries of their value ranges, then $E = 1.7$. Next, imagine that divers are deployed instead of the crawler, which means that, in accordance with the descriptions in 3.4, equipment-dependent LoUs are introduced. These are $v_c^l = 0.50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $H_{1/3}^l = 2.0 \text{ m}$, and $D^l = 50 \text{ m}$. In this case, no LoU is surpassed by the environmental conditions, and the EOD operation is still permissible. Nevertheless, now $E = 2.7$. This signifies that the three environmental factors for which RUMMs allows entering an LoU would have a stronger impact on a diver than on a crawler. Accordingly, E is higher for the former.

In summary, LoUs have two functions in RUMMs. Firstly, they act as a restriction in case environmental factors surpass the allowable conditions for the execution of EOD. Secondly, they increase the *Complexity of the EOD Operation*, if equipment-dependent LoU values are entered.

5.10.2 Threshold Values

As introduced in 5.7, every factor has a value range. A lower and an upper boundary determine its limits. For the great majority of factors, these value range boundaries were determined by understanding the natural conditions in the study area or the properties of

FIGURE 5.8: Comparison of the distributions of normalised *UXO Mass* entries (m_u^n) in the EOD dataset with different upper value range boundaries (m_u^{max}) [adapted from 107].

UXO that must be expected to be present. However, for three factors (*UXO Mass* (m_u), *Charge Mass* (m_c), and *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l)), the upper value range boundaries were not determined this way. This subsection briefly elucidates and contextualises this decision.

The case of the British ‘Tallboy’ bomb, with its $m_u = 5391$ kg, $m_c = 2359$ kg, and $l_l = 6400$ mm was mentioned in 2.2.2, 2.2.3, and 2.2.7. Given that this type of UXO can be found in the study area, it would be possible to introduce value ranges from 1 kg to 5391 kg for m_u , from 1 kg to 2359 kg for m_c , and from 0.1 m to 6.4 m for l_l . The assumption would be that these factors reach their largest possible value with this object. Independently of whether this assumption would be true, threshold values were introduced for the factors. These threshold values reduce the factors’ upper value range boundaries (F^{max}). The decisions were based on assessments of the EOD dataset (see 5.7.4, 5.7.5, and 5.7.18).

To demonstrate how the thresholds work, it is possible to apply the normalisation of m_u to the EOD dataset with and without the thresholds. For this purpose, m_u^{max} was once set to the threshold value that is used in RUMMs ($m_u^{max} = 1300$ kg) and once to the values of the British ‘Tallboy’ bomb (now referred to as T-RUMMs; $m_u^{max} = 5391$ kg). A type 4 incremental normalisation was applied to rescale to a value range from 1.0 to 10.0 (see 5.9.4). The results of these calculations can be compared.

The distributions of m_u^n are displayed in Figure 5.8. The figure displays that for T-RUMMs (hatched bars), 212 (i.e., all but 15) data points rescale to $m_u^n = 1.0$. On the other hand, for RUMMs (black bars), only 133 data points result in $m_u^n = 1.0$. The rest is distributed among all other m_u^n values. Since the factor is normalised incrementally, for example, a UXO object with a weight of 592 kg would be the lowest value that results in $m_u^n = 2.0$ for T-RUMMs. The same weight results in $m_u^n = 5.0$ in RUMMs. This example shows why almost all data entries produce $m_u^n = 1.0$ for T-RUMMs. While being far from evenly distributed, RUMMs leads to a picture where at least one data entry is rescaled to each m_u^n value. Considering that m_u is an input to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E), T-RUMMs would lead to a situation in which hardly any

EOD operation is negatively affected by m_u . Thus, the mathematical rationale for the introduction of the threshold value is to guarantee the significance of each factor in the model. The same applies to the threshold values of m_c and l_l .

It could be argued that a lower threshold value would further distribute the m_u^n values. This was not done for numerous reasons. Firstly, the lower the threshold, the larger the group of UXO objects that rescale to $m_u^n = 10.0$. Fixing the threshold must therefore balance producing an appropriate distribution with the size of the group that rescales to the highest normalised value. Therefore, and secondly, the m_u^{max} that RUMMs uses was obtained by thoroughly investigating the EOD dataset (see 5.7.4). Thirdly, $m_u = 130$ kg is the highest value that produces $m_u^n = 1$. The underlying notion is that any EOD service provider should be able to lift such objects without technical difficulties.

In addition to the numerical rationale provided above, it should also be noted that the ‘Tallboy’ is considered one of the most demanding types of UXO in existence. The find in the Świna was the largest hazardous object to be treated in the history of Poland and required a non-standard approach for clearance. [111] Hence, it is possible to consider this UXO type as a special case. Therefore, it is appropriate to introduce threshold values and reduce the upper boundary values for m_u , m_c , and l_l .

The functionality of thresholds in RUMMs is straightforward. If $m_u > 1300$ kg, if $m_c > 350$ kg, or if $l_l > 3000$ mm the factors’ value is reduced to the threshold value.

5.11 Model Limitations

The planning and the confirmed model layouts were both developed through a process of literature research and a series of workshops (see 5.2). Even though work was done thoroughly and rigorously, it must be acknowledged that the resulting model is limited by the current state of knowledge on the included factors. In addition, the model was affected by the biases of the author of this dissertation as well as the experts that participated in the workshops. This is exemplified by the inclusion of the factor *Impact Sensitivity*. This issue is not well represented in the literature on offshore UXO and EOD. Section 5.7.19 highlights the fact that information on the changes in *Impact Sensitivity* over time is limited. Still, the factor was included in RUMMs because the author was informed about it during the project RoBEMM (see Appendix 1). If the author had developed the model without previously participating in that project, the factor may not have been included in RUMMs.

5.11.1 UXO Type and Fuse Type

This is not a model limitation but rather a limitation of the current version of the RUMMs Excel tool. Currently, a user can enter free text into the cells **D15** and **D35** for *UXO Type (U)* and *Fuse Type (FT)*, respectively. One might expect that entering *U* would lead to an automatic entry of other UXO factors, such as *UXO Mass* or *Casing Material*. For *FT* it could be anticipated that *Fuse Properties* are filled in automatically. However, entering information on *U* or *FT* does not trigger any functionality of the tool. This would have required including a UXO database or connecting it via an interface.

While no database exists that contains all the required information for all potentially relevant UXO types, this could significantly reduce the effort for the user. Connecting RUMMs to a database is a potential endeavour for the future (see 7.2). It is nevertheless recommended that the user enter a value for U and FT so that a copy of the RUMMs Excel tool can be saved for documentation purposes.

5.11.2 Sediment Accumulation Rate and Burial

Sediment Accumulation Rate (SAR) is the factor that requires the most caution when using the planning layout of RUMMs. In the North Sea, if the *Water Depth* $D \leq 20$ m the data that are included in RUMMs are considered very reliable. The data in the Baltic Sea are less reliable since a rather crude extrapolation was performed. It is debatable whether this process is valid since data from the eastern part of the German Baltic Sea were extrapolated to its very west, which is several hundred kilometres away and has a very different current regime. On the other hand, the data were the best *SAR* information available, which makes the extrapolation the best available approximation. Finally, for North Sea areas with $D > 20$ m, RUMMs assumes $SAR = 0.0 \text{ mm a}^{-1}$ since no other information was available. Even though *SAR* in deeper North Sea waters may be low, certainly, it is not 0.0 mm a^{-1} throughout the entire area. No information was found in the literature, and the user is strongly encouraged to enter a value into cell **D52** if any information on a typical *SAR* for an area of interest is available.

During the 1st EOD RA Workshop (see Appendix 3) it was argued that reaction speed is sometimes crucial since very strong sedimentation can lead to the reburial of UXO. This case is ignored as the key processes of EOD are considered to take place in the immediate future after performing RA with the confirmed layout. If a UXO object is indeed reburied, the value of the *Burial State* must be adapted.

5.11.3 Corrosion and Condition of Casing

The planning layout uses *Corrosion Rate (CR)* as a controlling factor for the *Condition of Casing (CC)*. As outlined in 3.4.2 and 5.7.15, the corrosion rate is very complex, and thus some simplifications regarding the relationship to its child factors were necessary.

RUMMs assumes a constant average annual corrosion rate, which is based on the location (North Sea or Baltic Sea) and *Burial State* (buried or unburied) of the object. In reality, corrosion is very dynamic and depends on many environmental and UXO properties. Using a non-linear corrosion model was proposed in other fields of application, such as ship hulls [343]. However, using such a model requires detailed knowledge about many environmental properties and the corroding material, which is not available for the full study area. RUMMs also assumes uniform corrosion for the entire object, which would mean that the thinnest part of the casing always breaks first. In reality, since corrosion depends on multiple other environmental and object-related properties, other parts of an object may corrode first instead. However, assuming the thinnest part of the casing to break first enables performing a conservative RA, as it provides an assumption for the earliest point in time at which *CC* decreases.

Furthermore, long-term changes in the chemical properties of the seawater can lead to a shift in annual corrosion rates over time. Climate change impacts numerous controlling factors of the corrosion rate [230] and an increase in storms may also lead to more abrasion of casings. The average annual corrosion rate may therefore increase in the long term. This is not problematic for RUMMs, as its purpose is not to predict EOD risk many years into the future.

Nevertheless, using the output of a corrosion model for the German Baltic and North Seas as input for RUMMs would be beneficial. In the planning layout, the annual corrosion rates are assumed to be uniform across the entire German Baltic Sea and the entire German North Sea. In reality, corrosion varies within these large areas. If indeed current velocity is the most important environmental property, as claimed in one study [120], corrosion rates will vary greatly for different locations. For example, in the Baltic Sea, thirty-year mean surface current velocities are considerably higher in the Fehmarn Belt and Cadet Channel (up to 0.10 m s^{-1}) than in Kiel Fjord or Lübeck Bay (around 0.02 m s^{-1}) [344]. Bottom salinity also varies throughout the German Baltic Sea. It decreases from west to east, with values ranging from > 15 psu (practical salinity unit) at the German-Danish border to < 8 psu at the German-Polish border [345]. A corrosion model that enables predicting average corrosion rates on a kilometre-scale is a research gap. If the gap were closed, this would be very beneficial for the planning layout.

The planning layout considers one hypothetical point of the casing to be most affected by corrosion. This was implemented to account for the fact that corrosion does not homogeneously affect the surface of the casing. However, the most affected point may change over time. This may be due to changing environmental factors if the UXO object is moved to a different location or reoriented by natural or anthropogenic effects. Furthermore, a partially buried UXO object will be subjected to different corrosion rates for the parts below and above the sediment surface. A more detailed understanding of corrosion dynamics on a microlevel would be beneficial for the model.

For CC , RUMMs uses six categories. For the planning layout, the factor is calculated as described in 5.7.16. Category 4 represents an object with a single breach. Since the extent of the value facets between two categories is always the same, this means that a twofold reduction of *Original Casing Thickness* corresponds to CC^p category 3, a threefold reduction to category 2, a fourfold reduction to category 1, and a fivefold reduction to category 0. For a UXO object that is always unburied at a stable corrosion rate, this would mean that five times the duration it takes until the casing is initially breached ($CC^p = 4$) would be the time that the casing is (almost) not present ($CC^p = 0$). Accordingly, an object with a casing that would require 25 years to be breached would be almost fully degraded in 125 years. It is impossible to check this presumption's validity. Nevertheless, this option is to be preferred over assuming uniform corrosion for the entire casing, which would mean that it would simultaneously be breached and fully disappear. In addition, using the same categories as in the confirmed layout allows using CC as an input for the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* in both model layouts.

In the planning layout, *Fuse Corrosion State (FC)* depends exclusively on *CC*. In ideal circumstances, *CR* would be used to determine *FC*. It was decided not to do so. There are hundreds of different *Fuse Types* made from different materials [310]. While some fuses are very simple, others are highly complex. To use *CR* to determine *FC* would have required information on the dimensions of the fuses and their parts. Implementing this into the RUMMs could be misinterpreted as a reliable way of determining *FC*. Instead, it was decided to simplify the calculation by assuming that a lower value for *CC* leads to a lower value for *FC*. This is intuitive, and the fact that this assumption was used conveys the uncertainty that lies in *FC*, when calculated by the planning layout of RUMMs. The reader must be reminded that *FC* depends on *CC*, which in turn depends on *CR*, *Original Casing Thickness*, *Time Buried*, and *Time Unburied*. These again depend on various other factors. Through the numerous calculations that are performed, uncertainties are introduced, and errors can occur and propagate through the model. RUMMs was designed under conservative assumptions to avoid underestimating risk. Nevertheless, caution is advised.

5.11.4 Charge Type and Charge Mass

As mentioned in 5.7.18, the factor *Charge Mass (m_c)* does not only refer to the actual weight of the explosive main charge. Instead, the user should enter the total weight of the primary, booster, and main charge, as well as the propellants if they are explosive. The underlying rationale is that all explosive materials combined contribute to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*.

However, combining all of the previously mentioned materials into one value for m_c introduces a simplification into the model. Because they each serve a different purpose, all of these materials have different properties, namely *Relative Effectiveness (RE)* and *Original Impact Sensitivity (I_o)*. As pointed out in 2.2.10, primary explosives have a higher I_o than typical main charge explosives. Propellants have a lower *RE* than other materials (e.g., see Nitrocellulose in Table 5.10). However, in an unused artillery grenade, propellants can make up the largest fraction of material with explosive materials. The current version of RUMMs is only able to use *RE* and I_o of the selected *Main Charge Type (M)*. It would be ideal to use the mass of each material individually and combine it with the respective *RE* to calculate the *Shock Factor*. In addition, the highest I_o should be used. This would increase the workload for the model user but also generate more precise model output values. For the current version of RUMMs, users are advised to combine all materials into one value for m_c and use I_o and *RE* of *M*.

5.11.5 Impact Sensitivity

Subsection 5.7.19 described how RUMMs uses *Impact Sensitivity (I)* as a factor. In reality, the matter is more complex than can be represented in the model. However, to be able to include the factor, some simplifications had to be made.

The model assumes that for any *Main Charge Type* (M), it is possible that the *Current Impact Sensitivity* (I_c is 6 N m. It is, however, not known whether main charges can reach even lower I_c values (i.e., higher impact sensitivity). The value of 1 N m from the black crust of an explosives chunk was deemed inappropriate as it was possibly gathered after a detonation of the material. In RUMMs, a linear incremental increase in I_c is modelled since the value changes are connected to the *Condition of Casing* (CC). This leads to an effect according to which I_c of comparatively insensitive M increases faster than that of sensitive ones. In addition, for UXO with a larger value for the *Original Casing Thickness*, I_c decreases slower than for objects with thinner casings. Numerous alternatives would have been available, such as assuming a non-linear relationship between CC and I_c or making I_c a child factor of the amount of time the casing is breached. Another alternative would have been to assume that any I_c value can decrease to 12 % of I_b (since $\frac{6 \text{ N m}}{50 \text{ N m}} = 0.12$). This would, however, imply that the value of 6 N m was obtained for Minol or Amatol (see 5.7), which is not known. It would also follow that Schießwolle 39 could reach an I_c value of 3 N m, for which there is no evidence. There is no room to assume that any of these options reflect reality better than the one that was implemented in the model.

The model also assumes that the values for I_c and the base values I_b are uniformly valid for the entire surface and volume of the main charge. In reality, I may even vary in a single object [132]. It should also be noted that in the North Sea, ongoing corrosion can decrease CC even while UXO is fully buried. In this case, the explosive material does not primarily interface with salt water but with the sediment the object is buried in. Ageing may differ in such cases. However, RUMMs treats buried and unburied objects similarly, as no relevant literature exists.

5.11.6 Fuse Properties

Subsection 5.7.24 established that *Fuse Properties* (FP) is implemented in RUMMs as a score. It signifies how many individual properties (fp_n) apply to a UXO object. This way, each fp_n is treated identically in terms of their contribution to the model outputs. In reality, these properties likely do not all contribute to the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* or the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* in the same way. During the 2nd EOD RA Workshop, spring-loaded strikers (fp_5) were mentioned twice, which may be an indication that this property is particularly important. Nevertheless, a list of properties such as the one used in RUMMs was suggested during the same workshop. While it is not perfect, it allows implementing FP into RUMMs in a quantifiable way. To improve it, weighting the fp_n against each other could be performed in a dedicated expert workshop.

Possibly, some fp_n are mutually exclusive. For this dissertation, this was not researched. It would have required a comprehensive review of all UXO types that are relevant to the study area, which was considered out of scope. If mutually exclusive fp_n exist, this would mean that the upper value range boundary FP^{max} would not be 8 but lower. This would have implications for the functionality of RUMMs since $FP^{max} = 8$ is used for the normalisation (see 5.9.4).

5.11.7 Visual Range Under Water

If the user of RUMMs directly enters a value for the *Visual Range Under Water* (R), the uncertainty of this value depends on their ability to assess it. On the other hand, if RUMMs determines R based on the *Latitude* (ϕ_{EOD}), *Longitude* (λ_{EOD}), and *Planned EOD Date*, the model relies on a Secchi depth dataset from MUDAB [255]. There are some shortcomings in using these data to assess R . First of all, performing the measurements is not possible in heavy weather. Such conditions, which would likely lead to low R , may therefore be under-represented in the dataset. In addition, a Secchi depth is the depth at which the disc disappears from sight. This is expected to be a greater distance than the one at which relevant details, such as the *Fuse Type* or the *Condition of Casing* of UXO, can be assessed visually.

Furthermore, there are some shortcomings in the MUDAB dataset [255]. Some measurement stations were only used for a single year, especially in the North Sea. If more than ten measurements were taken during that year, the station was still included in RUMMs. Coupled with the rather poor coverage of the North Sea part of the study area (see Figure 3.11), the representativeness of the Secchi depth dataset for this area is limited. This applies especially when ϕ_{EOD} and λ_{EOD} are located at a great distance from the next measurement station.

It is also important to note that visibility in surface waters does not necessarily match R in deeper layers. The chemical and physical properties of water change at numerous strong vertical gradients, most prominently the halocline. The halocline prevents the mixing of lower-salinity water at the surface with more saline water below. [346] MUDAB also contains a dataset on suspended particles in water, which might be more suitable to analyse deeper waters [255]. However, translating such measurements into R would introduce new uncertainties. Therefore, the Secchi depth dataset is used in RUMMs, especially in the planning layout. It indicates a typical R value at a given location for a certain season. While it is not ideal, no better approach could be found to implement the factor.

5.11.8 Complexity of the EOD Operation

In RUMMs, the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) is a value that represents how the properties of the UXO and the environment influence how difficult EOD in a given situation is. While the author is confident that it appropriately reflects these factors, it must be acknowledged that two issues are not represented in RUMMs.

Firstly, the model does not assign different levels of complexity to the key processes *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. Initially, it was planned to do so. The advantage would have been model outputs that determine risk based on the planned processes with the available equipment, i.e., a stronger inclusion of EOD information. However, since the key processes' contributions to E are not measurable physical quantities, this approach would introduce new uncertainties into the model. On top of that, additional expert workshops would have been required to quantify the processes' contribution to E .

Each key process can be characterised in greater detail. For the *in situ destruction*, deflagration and detonation processes could be distinguished, thereby indicating whether one of these is more complex. These could, in turn, be further subdivided into the available techniques for their execution. For example, deflagration can be achieved with either a Pluton or a Magma charge, both of which come with their own specific advantages and disadvantages, which affect the probability of their successful application. [111] This would have required a more comprehensive review of available tools and techniques for EOD than is given in 3.3. Furthermore, the aspect of the availability of the different tools and methods would require attention. In summary, it would have added a considerable amount of complexity to RUMMs.

Secondly, other factors that were not included in the model can influence how complex an EOD operation is. There are aspects beyond the omitted factors (see 5.8). As outlined in 3.2.2, *underwater transfer* is performed when relocation of an object is necessary because performing the process *in situ destruction* can be unacceptable due to a UXO object's proximity to human activity or infrastructure. If both processes are executed instead of one, the EOD operation is more complex. On the other hand, environmental and UXO properties determine whether *underwater transfer* is permissible in the first place. The requirements of the EOD RA method that were developed in 4.2.2 state that a small spatial scale that focuses on the UXO object is required. The risk receptors that are addressed by RUMMs are the personnel and equipment at the EOD site. Addressing a UXO object's distance to infrastructure, other human activities, and even other UXO objects would have required significant changes in the spatial scope and an adaptation of the risk receptors. To avoid further extension of the already large RUMMs, neither of these definitions was changed.

5.11.9 Normalisation and Weightings

Normalisation and weighting are the two types of operations that are applied to convert and converge the factors of RUMMs to model outputs. They are mathematical operations that cannot be substantiated with arguments from the literature. To overcome this gap and decide on normalisation types and weights, experts were polled during EOD RA workshops. Naturally, this introduces a novel type of uncertainty that is absent from all operations that are based on investigations of the natural environment. There are some general caveats to both methods. Experts sometimes consider them uncertain and lacking in robustness. Yet they perceive both procedures as positive in terms of their relevance for decision-making processes. [339] Given the lack of superior alternatives, the route of normalisation and weighting was taken when developing RUMMs.

Regarding the normalisation, the author introduced a bias by pre-selecting four types (linear, exponential, root, and incremental; see 5.9.4. It would have been possible to present the experts with fewer or additional normalisation types. The exponential and root functions could have featured different exponents than the ones that were used in RUMMs. The incremental function could have featured fewer or more increments, and they could have followed another function (e.g., exponential increments). The four types that were offered to the experts were considered to sufficiently represent basic statistical correlations.

Exponential or logarithmic incremental functions were considered too complicated by experts. Except for one comment during one of the 2nd EOD RA workshops, no comment by experts stated that the given normalisation types did not sufficiently express the relationship of a factor to EOD risk. (see Appendix 6)

The weights that RUMMs uses were determined through a simple poll that offered increments from 1 to 5 and by subsequently calculating the mean from the answers. Factors for which the dispersion of answers was considered too large were discussed with experts and polled again. The resulting weights are considered to reliably reflect the opinions of the experts in terms of the factors' contributions to EOD risk. Nevertheless, it must be mentioned that other, more sophisticated methods for the generation of weights exist. One of these is the analytic hierarchy process (AHP). This method is targeted at group decision-making and allows for organising and analysing complex matters. It requires the preparation of a hierarchy tree, which, in this case, could be based on RUMMs. The criteria of the hierarchy tree (in this case, the factors of RUMMs) must then undergo a pairwise comparison, which allows for generating weights. [347] This method requires a greater effort than the one that was used for this dissertation. When RUMMs is updated in the future, it may be reasonable to use AHP and compare the weights to the ones in this study.

5.12 Conclusion—The Case for Model Exploration and Testing

The identification of a methodological gap in Chapter 4, led to the development of a new EOD RA approach in Chapter 5. Initially, the chapter provides a rough overview of the idea of such a model. It continues by describing the development process of RUMMs. Subsequently, a series of necessary definitions for model scoping (undesired event, model exceptions, and risk receptors) are made, and the concept of two model layouts is introduced. Next, the model is described in detail. This is done by introducing the factors that are included (but also the ones that were omitted), the model outputs, other model functionalities, and their computation. Finally, Chapter 5 outlines some model limitations.

The great spatial extent of this chapter demonstrates not only the great effort that was required to produce a model such as RUMMs but also its complexity. The reviewed literature as well as the comments of the experts during the EOD RA workshops led to RUMMs in the release version. Taking the current state of knowledge and expert opinions into account was a key principle during its development process. The model's complexity has resulted in a situation that makes it challenging to predict how model outputs will react if the user changes a given factor. To better understand RUMMs and to support the user in interpreting model results, it is necessary to explore RUMMs and apply it to a series of realistic EOD scenarios. Doing so is the purpose of Chapter 6.

Chapter 6

Methodological Exploration and Application

With all the knowledge that was gathered throughout the preparation of the previous chapters and with RUMMs fully set up, it was possible to explore and apply it. The purpose of the model exploration was to understand how the model inputs and factors interact with each other and how they lead to both common and extreme model output values. This effort contrasts with the description in Chapter 5, which is solely focused on the mechanisms of the model but not on the interplay of factors. The exploration is executed using local sensitivity analysis and MCS. While the former explores the relevance of the model inputs for the outputs, the latter explores the model outputs' distributions. Subsequently, the model was applied to real-world data. Data on UXO in German waters were entered into RUMMs for planning layout trial runs, and data from past EOD activities were used to test the confirmed layout. With all of the above, it was possible to understand the model, develop advice on how to use it, and implement it into the EOD framework.

6.1 Local Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis is considered an essential part of any RA [348]. The fact that gaps in knowledge are sometimes closed by using assumptions and including expert opinions requires an understanding of how a model's parameters (in this case, the factors) influence its behaviour [349]. Sensitivity analysis is a tool that is used for many purposes, ranging from the detection of technical errors in models to the identification of critical inputs or the prioritisation of research. [350] It can also be used to detect how uncertainties in the model inputs lead to uncertainties in the model outputs [351].

Sensitivity analysis often uses mathematical derivatives to perform these tasks [350] as expressed by equation (29). Here, a sensitivity coefficient (SC) is used to measure the sensitivity of an output variable (o) at the y th observation point versus a given input variable (i) at the same observation point. i is always independent, while o is always dependent. [352] In addition, n and m signify a case in which there are multiple output and input variables, respectively. In the case of this dissertation, i is a given input

factor of RUMMs (as described in 6.1.1) and o one of the three model outputs (see 5.9). SC is the resulting mathematical derivative. Equation (29) can be read as SC being the quotient of the percentage change of an output variable given the percentage change of an input variable. To understand the meaning of SC , consider that $SC = 1$ means that in equation (29) the dividend equals the divisor. In other words, the percentage change of i equals the percentage change of o . Furthermore, an $SC = 2$ or $SC = 0.5$ would mean that the percentage change of i leads to twice or half as high a percentage change in o , respectively.

$$SC = \frac{\frac{\delta o_n}{o_n y}}{\left| \frac{\delta i_m}{i_m y} \right|} \quad (29)$$

This method is commonly used in a wide array of scientific fields, ranging from scientific energy performance modelling [e.g., 353] to applied financial modelling [e.g., 354]. It is commonly referred to as the one-factor-at-a-time (OAT) sensitivity analysis [355] and is a type of local sensitivity analysis. To perform it, three steps are executed.

1. Define the base case. Enter the base case values for each i into the model and take note of the resulting value for each o .
2. Change each i individually and note the resulting value for each o . After each i , return to the base case.
3. Calculate SC as per equation (29).

The approach has been subject to heavy criticism in cases in which the model is non-linear and the model input is uncertain. The problem is that it only assesses the sensitivity of a model from a single base point and does not explore the remainder of the potential value space of the i variables. In complex non-linear models, it is possible that a significant change in one i leads to no change in o , if the definition of the base case is unfavourable. The definition of another base case could lead to a completely different situation. Even the most thoroughly prepared base case is not free of some arbitrariness. When referring to RUMMs, it is, for example, possible that even a stark change in the *Time Sunk* does not affect the model outputs if high *Original Casing Thickness* and *Sediment Accumulation Rate* do not allow for corrosion to alter the properties of the UXO object. This does not, however, necessarily mean that the model is insensitive to *Time Sunk*. In other scenarios, a slight alteration to i may lead to a noteworthy shift in o . It is therefore considered good practice to perform an OAT for several scenarios and obtain an average SC [355]. Accordingly, a fourth step should be added to those listed above.

4. Calculate the average SC of all scenarios.

The following subsections explore RUMMs by performing an OAT. Subsection 6.1.1 explains the set-up and application of the analysis and 6.1.2 describes its results. Lastly, 6.1.3 provides conclusions that support the user of RUMMs.

6.1.1 Application of the Local Sensitivity Analysis

The local sensitivity analysis was performed according to the description in 6.1. Before the scenarios could be defined, it was necessary to identify which of the factors in RUMMs would serve as i . Referring back to the depictions of the model layouts in Figures 5.3 and 5.4 it is clear that the factors *UXO Type*, *Latitude*, *Longitude*, and *Planned EOD Date* are the initial inputs on which every other factor in the model depends. However, numerous relationships are not automated within the model functions (see 5.6.1), so *UXO Type* was not a useful factor for the sensitivity analysis. *Latitude*, *Longitude*, and *Planned EOD Date* were not appropriate either, because calculating their percentage change as required by equation (29) was meaningless to determine model sensitivity. Hence, the most independent factors (i.e., those most to the left in the model depictions) for which a value change was meaningful in terms of the sensitivity analysis were used. The analysis was done for both model layouts individually, as the factors that were used as i differed, which led to different outcomes.

Table 6.1 provides an overview of all factors that were used as i . The second and third columns inform about the model layout for which they were used during the sensitivity analysis. Note that this does not indicate whether a factor is included in one of the model layouts. For example, *Burial State* is included in both model layouts but was only used as i for the sensitivity analysis of the confirmed layout. The fourth through sixth columns show which of the three o could be impacted. Since the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) is an input to the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P), each factor impacting E has the potential to impact P . The *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C) is rather isolated in the model; it has only two inputs, one of which it uses exclusively. The *Water Depth* was the only i , which could change all three o . In the following steps, sensitivity was only calculated in those cases for which an i could affect an o since it was meaningless to assess the sensitivity of, for example, *Fuse Properties* on C .

With i and o identified, it was possible to define the base case (step 1). To avoid representing only a single potentially non-representative scenario (see 6.1), the sensitivity analysis was performed for three scenarios.

Most likely scenario: For each of the factors that were used as i the most likely value was identified. This does not necessarily mean that the resulting scenario was the most likely one.

Low-risk scenario: The scenario with the lowest risk, which was defined as the one where the sum of the values of all three o was lowest.

High-risk scenario: The scenario with the highest risk, which was defined as the one where the sum of the values of all three o was largest.

In the most likely scenario, several soft rules were applied. For those factors for which distributions had been investigated throughout the sections 2.2 and 3.4, a central value of the bin with the highest count was selected. For example, the most common *Water Depth* in the study area lies between 40 m to 45 m. The base case value that was used for the most likely scenario was therefore 42.5 m. In cases for which no distribution was available,

TABLE 6.1: Input (*i*) and output (*o*) variables for the sensitivity analysis of both model layouts.

<i>i</i>	Used in Layout		Impacted <i>o</i>		
	Planning	Confirmed	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>
Burial State		x	x		x
Charge Mass	x	x		x	
Condition of Casing		x	x		x
Current Velocity	x	x	x		x
Fuse Corrosion State		x	x		x
Fuse Properties	x	x	x		x
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	x	x	x		x
Original Casing Thickness	x		x		x
Corrosion Rate - Buried	x		x		x
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	x		x		x
Relative Effectiveness	x	x		x	
Sediment Accumulation Rate	x		x		x
Significant Wave Height	x	x	x		x
Time Sunk	x		x		x
UXO Longest Dimension	x	x	x		x
UXO Mass	x	x	x		x
UXO Shortest Dimension	x		x		x
Visual Range Under Water	x	x	x		x
Water Depth	x	x	x	x	x

best guess values were used. This, inter alia, applies to the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*. Here 10 Nm was used as this is the fallback value for the model for all *Main Charge Types* without a proprietary value. In a third group of cases, this was not deemed appropriate, and the central point of the factor's value range was selected, such as 0.05 mm a^{-1} for *Corrosion Rate - Unburied*, which can range from 0.00 mm a^{-1} to 0.10 mm a^{-1} . For a full overview of the rationale for each base case value in the most likely scenario, please refer to Appendix 9. Note that even though this scenario is referred to as 'most likely', it is not superior to the other two scenarios.

In the low- and high-risk scenarios, the base case values were arranged in such a way that the sum of the three *o* was the highest. As the *Water Depth* has an oppositional effect on *E* and *C*, it is not possible to achieve a scenario in which all three model outputs show a value of 10. Furthermore, since the percentage change in the input value must be calculated following equation (29), no base case values of 0 were allowed. Base case values at the lower end of their value spectrum were also chosen in such a way that their increase by 50% led to a change of at least the second decimal place.

Once these three scenarios were defined, step 2 of the sensitivity analysis could be executed. In all scenarios, each *i* was changed, and the change in the affected *o* was noted. To remain consistent, every *i* was changed by 50%. In the most likely scenario, this was done as an increase and a decrease in value; for the low and high-risk scenarios, it was

done in such a way that the o values increased or decreased, respectively. For example, for the low-risk scenario, the *Charge Mass* base case value was 1 kg. To increase o , the value had to be increased to 1.5 kg. The decrease was omitted. For the high-risk scenario, a decrease from 350 kg to 175 kg was executed.

Next, step 3 was performed by applying equation (29) for every single combination of i and o , for all three scenarios for both model layouts. These individual scenario results offered many insights, some of which are discussed in 6.1.2. To obtain information on the general sensitivity of the model to an i , the overall model sensitivity was additionally calculated (see equation (30)). Here, SC is the quotient of the cumulative percentage change of *Probability of an Undesired Event* (P), *Consequence of an Undesired Event* (C), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) given the percentage change of an input variable.

$$SC = \frac{\delta P + \delta C + \delta E}{P_i + C_i + E_i} \frac{|\frac{\delta I_m}{I_m}|}{i} \quad (30)$$

Finally, the average SC over all three scenarios was calculated during step 4. The purpose of step 4 was to ensure that an unfavourable base-case definition fails to reveal the sensitivity of an o to a specific i . Even though the most likely scenario is a more realistic one than the low- and high-risk scenarios, all three scenarios were equally important for this task. Hence, a simple average without weighting was applied. The outcomes are presented in the next subsection.

6.1.2 Results of the Local Sensitivity Analysis

This subsection begins by describing the results of the planning layout. It presents the average SC for the three scenarios for P , C , and E individually and for RUMMs overall. Subsequently, the same is done for the confirmed layout. The detailed numerical results of the local sensitivity analysis are disaggregated in Appendix 9 and in the supplementary data [356].

The bar chart in Figure 6.1 shows the SC scores of the *Probability of the Undesired Event* (Probability, green), *Probability of the Undesired Event* (Consequence, red), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (EOD Complexity, blue) for each factor that was used as i in the planning layout. Increases in the i value, when compared to the base case value, are shown in hatched bars and decreases in solid bars. This way, it was possible to show that, for example, a decrease in *Water Depth* led to a positive SC for C and vice versa. Bars are stacked, which is only relevant for *Original Casing Thickness*, where decreases and increases both led to negative SC . If no bars are shown, that can mean either of two things: either the o was very insensitive for the selected scenarios (i.e., $SC = 0$) or the i does not mathematically influence the respective o at all (see Table 6.1). For the interpretation, it is important to remember that this does not mean that an i must always affect an o to the extent displayed in the graphs. They merely display a tendency that is based on the three scenarios. In other scenarios, the model may behave differently. The next paragraph describes some remarkable observations. Another important aspect of

FIGURE 6.1: Sensitivity of individual model outputs in the planning layout.

FIGURE 6.2: Overall model sensitivity in the planning layout.

RUMMs' design that must be considered is that more *i* have an influence on *E* and *P* than on *C*. Therefore, high *SC* values are more likely for the latter, as each individual *i* has a large relative impact on it.

Figure 6.1 displays the SC for the planning layout. The greatest value $SC = 1.39$ was obtained for a decrease in *Water Depth* and its effect on C . A 50% decrease in *Water Depth* led to an increase in C of $> 50\%$. This large coefficient mainly originated from the high-risk scenario, in which *Water Depth* decreased from 71 m to 35.5 m, and to a lesser degree from the most likely scenario. At the same time, a decrease in water depth led to a negative score ($SC = -0.32$) for E . Another factor that elicited high SC scores was the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*. This was an effect of the base case value decreasing in the low-risk scenario. The *Time Sunk* is a special case since increases and decreases of 50% required the factor to leave its designated value range (see Appendix 9). Nevertheless, it appears to be a factor to which P and E are sensitive. The *Original Casing Thickness* is a particularly remarkable case, as both the most likely and high-risk scenarios resulted exclusively in negative SC scores. Within the most likely scenario, the base case value decrease and increase both contributed to this effect. This notable model response can be attributed to the fact that *Original Casing Thickness* affects many factors. This includes the *Current Impact Sensitivity*, *Condition of Casing*, and *Fuse Corrosion State*, which can counteract each other in terms of their effect on P and E . Some factors result in only very minor SC scores for E when decreased. These are *Current Velocity*, *Significant Wave Height*, and *UXO Mass* (all $|SC| < 0.05$). The model is thus rather insensitive to these factors. They are direct inputs to E , albeit with low weights (see 5.9.5). This is likely because E has eleven input factors in the model, so a single factor will only have a limited influence on the result.

The overall model sensitivity for the planning layout is displayed in Figure 6.2. It was calculated by using the equation (30). This way, opposing effects, such as that of *Water Depth* as described in the previous paragraph, were to a degree cancelled out. The further apart the increase and decrease bars are, the greater the overall model sensitivity to a factor. Accordingly, the planning layout is very sensitive to *Fuse Properties*, *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*, *Original Casing Thickness*, *Time Sunk*, and *Water Depth*. Overall, it is also more sensitive to 50% decreases in a base case value than to increases of the same relative magnitude. This is mathematically plausible since a 50% increase of a low base case value represents a smaller absolute change than the 50% decrease of a high base case value. While there are eight i with an $|SC| > 0.10$ for decreases (i.e., 50% decrease in i leads to a 5% change in o), there are only two i with similarly strong effects for increases.

Figure 6.3 shows the SC scores of the individual model outputs for the confirmed layout. Again, *Water Depth* is the factor to which the model is most sensitive. Two factors, which were not part of the planning layout, the *Condition of Casing* and the *Fuse Corrosion State* also led to high SC scores approaching or above 0.5. These two factors are likely to be very influential in the planning layout as well. However, in the planning layout, they are calculated from other factors and were therefore not assessed during this analysis. In combination with the importance of the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*, these factors show that a deterioration in the overall state of a UXO object (which the model expresses as

FIGURE 6.3: Sensitivity of individual model outputs in the confirmed layout.

FIGURE 6.4: Overall model sensitivity in the confirmed layout.

a value decrease) leads to higher P and E values, at least as long as the fuse is not fully corroded. On the other hand, the *Burial State* can be added to the list of factors to which the model is rather insensitive.

A look at Figure 6.4 reveals that the confirmed layout is sensitive to the same factors as the planning layout. This includes *Fuse Properties*, *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*, and *Water Depth*. As already observed in Figure 6.3, the factors *Condition of Casing* and *Fuse Corrosion State* must be added to this list. Again, the layout is more sensitive to value decreases (seven i with $|SC| > 0.10$) than to value increases (two i).

6.1.3 Conclusions from the Local Sensitivity Analysis

The first conclusion of the local sensitivity analysis is that each of the i affects at least one of the o . Hence, the model reflects the outcome of the literature research and the 1st EOD Risk Workshop, during which the model layout was discussed. Irrelevant factors were rejected, and only factors that affect EOD risk remain. Their level of relevance, however, varies.

The user of RUMMs is advised to place the most scrutiny on the research and measurement of those factors to which RUMMs is most sensitive. For some factors, this can be achieved with little effort; for example, information on the *Water Depth* is easy to obtain. The situation is more challenging for *Charge Mass*, *Fuse Properties*, *Original Casing Thickness*, and *Time Sunk*. However, a seasoned EOD expert should be able to obtain this information or make educated assumptions based on the outcome of the *historical survey* and the *UXO identification*. For other factors, greater difficulties arise. As the descriptions of the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* in 5.7.19 and the *Corrosion Rate - Unburied* in 5.7.15 show, values for these factors are rare in the literature and challenging to obtain in experiments. It is therefore recommended to abide by the principle of performing a conservative assessment, as was suggested throughout Chapter 5 to avoid grossly underestimating EOD risk. The *Sediment Accumulation Rate* is another challenging factor (see 5.7.8). For the Baltic Sea, this factor was obtained through a workaround using modelled, non-confirmed data. For the greatest part of the North Sea, no data were available, and the model assumes a value of 0.0 mm a^{-1} based on the EOD location. Conclusions on this matter are given in 7.3.

Both model layouts are rather insensitive to changes in *Current Velocity*, *Significant Wave Height*, *UXO Longest Dimension*, and *UXO Mass*. The fact that their change only affects *Complexity of the EOD Operation* and not the *Probability of the Undesired Event* shows the importance of the former as a model output instead of only treating it as a regular factor, as was the case in the early drafts of the model. However, their low SC values do not mean that these factors are not relevant to the model and can be deleted or neglected. The SC values are averages of the three scenarios, which means that in individual scenarios, the model can be more sensitive to them. Based on the location and season of the EOD operation, the model automatically provides representative values for *Current Velocity* and *Significant Wave Height* (see 5.7.26 through 5.7.28). Given the low sensitivity of the model to these factors, the user may rely on this automated feature. Still, a measured or modelled value from the exact EOD location and the anticipated time that can be obtained with low effort is preferable. The factors may also correlate; for example,

a UXO object with a low *UXO Longest Dimension* will likely have a low *UXO Mass*, so that the effects of both factors will complement one another in a cumulative way and notably change E .

6.2 Monte Carlo Simulation

In an MCS, random sampling and statistical modelling are utilised to imitate the behaviour of complex systems such as RUMMs. To conduct an MCS, one needs to perform four steps [357].

1. Set up the system or model of interest.
2. Define a probability density function (PDF) for each model input. It is necessary to define input parameter tolerances between which the sampling takes place [358].
3. Take a large random sample from the PDF for each input.
4. Investigate the behaviour of the model outputs, which are also expressed as PDFs.

A relevant question when executing MCS is the number of model runs that should be executed to arrive at a representative output distribution (step 3). In other words, this is the number of randomly taken samples for each model input and subsequent calculation of model outputs. A method to perform an a priori estimate for the number of required model runs (n) is given in equation (31) [359, 360]. To do this, it is suggested to perform several preliminary model runs, which allow for obtaining the sample standard deviation (s). In equation (31), Δ is the change in the model output value that one is interested in investigating, and z is the z-score of the confidence interval that one requires for the resulting distribution. The underlying assumption for the use of this equation is the central limit theorem, according to which the model outputs' mean tends towards a normal distribution, even though they are randomly sampled since the input variables are not normally distributed [360]. Essentially, equation (31) therefore calculates the size of n at which this tendency towards a normal distribution is satisfied, given the requirements of Δ and z . Resampling the preliminary model runs yields different values for s . This means that n resulting from equation (31) is an approximation only. Hence, increasing the number of n is necessary to ensure that the requirements of Δ and z are met. Note that the inputs of the MCS are RUMMs' model input factors. They are not identical with the ones in sensitivity analysis, which were parent factors of the model outputs.

$$n = \left(\frac{s * z}{\Delta} \right)^2 \quad (31)$$

6.2.1 Application of the Monte Carlo Simulation

In some cases, such as weather modelling, the computational resources required to perform MCS can be very high. [357] This is not the case for RUMMs, which is Excel-based. The MCS that is described here was done on a personal computer. Of the four steps described in 6.2, step 1 was already completed due to RUMMs existing in both of its layouts.

To explore RUMMs both with regard to its full potential and realistic scenarios, two different sets of input PDFs were designed (step 2). In both PDFs, each sample represents a single fictional UXO that is subject to an EOD operation.

Uniform distribution set: All factors that are used as inputs were assigned a uniform distribution. This was done independently of the level of realism that was achieved by the resulting sample of hypothetical EOD operations. This set of distributions was intended to help understand the full range of potential model outputs.

Realistic distribution set: For all factors, the distribution was selected in such a way that it balanced achieving a high level of realism with providing relevant input for an MCS. This set of distributions was designed to help understand the most typical model outputs that the user must expect.

For the realistic distribution set, a normal distribution adapted from the mean (\bar{x}) of the data that were analysed throughout the sections 2.2 and 3.4 was used for most factors. The respective standard deviation (s) was defined in such a way that $\bar{x} \pm 3 * s$ would approximate the upper or lower end of the factor's value range, whichever is closer. For other factors, this method was not considered appropriate. For example, most UXO in the study area is not fused and is located in the munitions dump sites, where it has remained since the years following WWII. Even though it would lead to the most realistic outputs, designing the MCS according to this notion would have reduced the potential value space of the model outputs significantly. Therefore, uniform distributions were assigned to the factors *Year Sunk*, *Fuse Type*, and *Fuse Properties*. For the remaining factors for which no data analysis had been possible throughout this dissertation, \bar{x} was defined to be the central value of their value range. Accordingly, $\bar{x} \pm 3 * s$ approximates the upper or lower end of the factor's value range simultaneously. This was, for example, the case for the *Corrosion Rate - Buried* and *Corrosion Rate - Unburied*. A detailed explanation of the distribution rationale for each factor and other notes are given in Appendix 10. Note that this set of distributions could still produce unrealistic factor combinations, such as an object with a large *UXO Mass* but a small *UXO Longest Dimension*, since data for each risk factor were distributed individually.

For the application to the planning layout, the distribution was further subdivided. On the one hand, the MCS was performed while using a uniform distribution for the factors *Latitude* and *Longitude* to represent locations within the area of interest. A uniform distribution was also considered to be suitable as the realistic distribution since EOD can take place throughout the entire study area. In this case, the planning layout used RUMMs' lookup tables to determine representative values for various location-dependent factors (*Sediment Accumulation Rate*, *Current Velocity*, *Wind Speed*, *Visual Range Under Water*, and *Water Depth*) in combination with the haversine formula (see (2)), as well as the LOOKUP, FREQUENCY, and MATCH functions in Excel (see 5.7.8. As a side note, it should be mentioned that a tendency towards clearance at dump sites can be assumed for

the future. This is not considered here. On the other hand, the MCS was also performed by populating the factors listed above individually and without consideration of the EOD location.

Independently from the distribution set, some rules were integrated to prevent non-sensical scenarios. The *UXO Mass* was not allowed to be smaller than the *Charge Mass*, and the *UXO Shortest Dimension* was not allowed to exceed the *UXO Longest Dimension*.

For the uniform distributions, the upper and lower limits of their value ranges were defined as the tolerances of the inputs. In the case of normal distributions, the tolerances were more fuzzily defined by $\bar{x} \pm 3 * s$.

Once the model inputs were set up for the MCS, it was possible to apply the equation (31) to determine the required number of model runs (n). Since the purpose of the MCS was to understand the overall model behaviour when using random inputs, changes to the model outputs < 0.1 were considered irrelevant. It was thus decided that the investigated change (Δ) in each of the model outputs (P , C , and E) would be 0.1, which is 1% of the possible value range (0 to 10). A 95% confidence interval was chosen, leading to $z = 1.96$. Therefore, the middle 95% of the resulting distributions are well represented, while the tails are not. This is acceptable since the MCS does not seek to investigate extreme model outputs. This was already achieved by the sensitivity analysis (see 6.1.1). Furthermore, this does not mean that the tails of the resulting distributions cannot be investigated, but that there is less confidence in them. Equation (31) was applied to each of the three model outputs for both model layouts. P in the confirmed layout and the realistic distribution set required the highest value of runs with $n \approx 1370$. Hence, 1500 model runs were executed for each combination of distribution sets and model layouts to account for the variability in s (see 6.1.3). Data of all model runs are available in the supplementary data [361]. Tests with other z-scores revealed that this number of runs was even sufficient to achieve a 99% confidence interval for C and E in both model layouts.

With the distributions and the required number of model runs defined, it was possible to populate the MCS with values. For the uniform distributions, this was done using Excel's RANDBETWEEN function. For the normal distributions, a combination of NORM.INV and RAND was used. Subsequently, some manual correction of values needed to be performed for cases in which an LoU was exceeded. This was necessary for a few *Water Depth* and *Wind Speed* values in the realistic distribution set. In such cases, they were corrected to the closest value that lies within the allowable value range of the factor. Finally, the model was run 9000 times (i.e., samples were taken—step 3) to investigate all combinations of distribution sets and model layouts. The resulting PDFs of the model outputs are described in the following subsection (step 4).

6.2.2 Results of the Monte Carlo Simulation

Figures 6.5 and 6.6 show the results of the MCS as distribution functions for the planning layout and the confirmed layout, respectively. For the planning layout, the two top plots in Figure 6.5 are the results, which are based on the MCS' that include *Latitude* and *Latitude*, while the two bottom plots ignore the EOD location and populate location-

dependent factors independently. The figures show plots for the uniform distribution set on the left and for the more realistic distribution set on the right. Each of the six plots contains a distribution function for the three model outputs *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P , green), *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C , red), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E , blue). The x-axis shows bins of possible model output values ranging from 0 to 10. The y-axis shows the percentage of MCS model runs.

At first glance, the distribution functions look very similar, with P being distributed more strongly among lower values and C among higher values. In all combinations of input distributions and model layouts, P has the strongest global peak at 1.5 to 2.0 in all graphs. This is followed by local minima in bins ranging from 2.5 to 3.5 and smaller local maxima. P is therefore the only bimodally distributed model output. This distribution can be attributed to the fact that UXO without a fuse or with a fully corroded fuse produces low P values and is distributed into the narrow and steep peak to the left. UXO with an intact fuse produces higher P values and is more broadly distributed in the flat peak to the right. P can approach 0. It hardly reaches values > 8.0 . Depending on the input distribution set and the model layout, E reaches its global maxima in bins of values anywhere between 2.5 to 4.5. Maxima of C are located in the range from 6.5 to 8.0. E values are distributed from 0.5 to 8.0 and C values from 2.0 to 10.0. Values < 3.5 are the exception for the latter.

It is noteworthy that the realistic distribution sets (right side) all reach higher maxima, are distributed more narrowly, and have steeper curves than their uniform counterparts (left side). These tend to be flatter and cover larger value ranges. This is expected as the realistic distribution set focuses input values into a smaller range (usually based on a mean and a standard deviation; see 6.2.1). Therefore, the MCS achieved its goal of better understanding the full range of potential model output values by using the uniform distribution. The lowest and highest bins of each distribution curve on the left side show this potential. The model is expected to only very rarely produce values below and above these bins. The realistic distribution instead emphasises the output values that the model is expected to generate most commonly. These are the global maxima of each curve on the right side of Figures 6.5 and 6.6. Another interesting observation lies in the uniform distributions of the planning layout in Figure 6.5 (left side). While the value ranges are similar, the maxima of C and E are more pronounced for the MCS that included the EOD location (top) than for the one that did not (bottom). Even though locations were uniformly distributed throughout the study area, the underlying look-up tables for many factors, such as *Visual Range Under Water* or *Current Velocity* lead to a narrower distribution of output values than if these are normally distributed themselves.

All distributions were tested for normality. None of them are normally distributed, even though this could be expected according to the central limit theorem. Nevertheless, a visual assessment of the curves shows that especially C and E are more normally distributed than the input variables (compare with the distributions shown for UXO and environmental properties in 2.2 and 3.4).

FIGURE 6.5: Distributions of model outputs of the MCS in the planning layout.

FIGURE 6.6: Distributions of model outputs of the MCS in the confirmed layout.

Based on the above assessment, it can be stated that the low- and high-risk scenarios of the sensitivity analysis (see 6.1.1) are extremely unlikely to occur. None of them are included in the distributions shown here. On the other hand, the most likely scenarios of the sensitivity analysis for both model layouts lie within the value ranges shown in the MCS distributions. However, the most likely scenario outputs do not correspond with the global maxima of the MCS distributions. This cannot be expected since the most likely scenario was determined by a different method than the realistic distribution set of the MCS.

6.2.3 Conclusions from the Monte Carlo Simulation

The MCS offered insights into the overall value range and the most commonly occurring values for all three model outputs. Over time, users of RUMMs are expected to collect experience on commonly occurring model output values and what certain combinations of output values mean for an EOD activity. Until such a level of experience is reached, the user of the model is encouraged to return to Figures 6.5 and 6.6 to understand how the risk of a specific EOD operation compares to the entire population.

To offer some guidance for interpreting the model outputs, it is possible to categorise them. In semi-quantitative risk matrices, such as the one presented in Section 4.3.1, the determination of what constitutes a high value for probability and consequences is determined by a linear scale from 1 to 5, with, for example, 1 referring to negligible, 3 to moderate, and 5 to very high consequences. This is done indiscriminately, regardless of how frequently these values occur in reality. Consider a scenario in which 80 % of real-life EOD operations would be distributed in category 1, 15 % in level 2, 4 % in level 3, 1 % in category 4 and 0 % in level 5. In this case, an EOD operation in level 3 may be misinterpreted as an average activity in terms of its potential consequences. However, given the distribution of operations, it is quite out of the ordinary and should be executed with extreme care. This does not mean that the assessment of the operation having moderate potential consequences is wrong. However, creating awareness that the EOD operation is irregular would be important for all parties involved.

Therefore, the categorisation of the RUMMs outputs was done under consideration of the results of the MCS. To avoid confusion, only one categorisation was developed independently from the model layout. For this purpose, all six MCS distributions from 6.2.2 were included. The results of all 9000 model runs were converged, and the means (\bar{x}) and standard deviations (s) of P , C , and E were calculated. In addition, the same measures of P were computed for all fused objects. This was done because P showed a bimodal distribution for the full sample. Here, $\bar{x} = 3.3$, which is considerably lower than the local maximum of the broadly distributed right peak (compare, e.g., Figure 6.5). Next, s and $2s$ were added and subtracted from \bar{x} . The results of these calculations are shown in Table 6.2.

Based on the numbers in Table 6.2 it was possible to determine useful and distribution-dependent *risk levels*. For C and E , the levels were determined along $\bar{x} \pm s$ and $\bar{x} \pm 2s$. As mentioned above, for P , \bar{x} was calculated both for the full sample and a subsample consisting only of fused objects. Given the fact that fused UXO objects produce considerably

TABLE 6.2: Statistics of the MCS for both model layouts.

Measure	P	P (fused)	C	E
\bar{x}	3.3	4.7	6.9	3.7
s	1.8	1.5	1.0	0.9
$\bar{x} - 2s$	-0.4*	1.8*	4.9	1.8
$\bar{x} - s$	1.4	3.2*	5.9	2.7
$\bar{x} + s$	5.1*	6.2	7.9	4.6
$\bar{x} + 2s$	6.9*	7.7*	9.0	5.6

* Not relevant for risk levels (see Table 6.3).

TABLE 6.3: Risk levels for the interpretation of model outputs.

Level	P	C	E
Very Low	≤ 1.3	≤ 4.8	≤ 1.7
Low	1.4 to 3.2	4.9 to 5.8	1.8 to 2.6
Medium	3.3 to 4.6	5.9 to 7.8	2.7 to 4.5
High	4.7 to 6.1	7.9 to 8.9	4.6 to 5.5
Very High	≥ 6.2	≥ 9.0	≥ 5.6

FIGURE 6.7: Risk levels for the model outputs.

higher P values than ones that are not fused, using \bar{x} of the full sample would have led to an underestimation of the risk levels. Hence, the level ‘medium’ was assigned to all values between \bar{x} of the sample and \bar{x} of the subsample. The other boundaries were then determined by applying $\bar{x} - s$ to the full sample and $\bar{x} + s$ to the subsample. Categories for all three model outputs were separated in such a way that values from Table 6.2 were included in the higher levels. For example, $\bar{x} + s$ for $C = 7.9$ was assigned to the *high* level and not to its *medium* level.

Figure 6.7 visually depicts the content of Table 6.3. It shows the five risk levels in a colour-coded way from light grey (*very low*) to black (*very high*) for all three model outputs. It emphasises the fact that the *very low* level covers a larger portion of the value

space of C , when compared to P and E . It is the other way around for the *very high* level. This reflects the MCS' output value distributions. The same graph is also included in the RUMMs file. Here, a green dot indicates the values for each of the three model outputs that are produced by the model in real-time.

6.3 Application of RUMMs

The exploration of RUMMs in the previous two sections allows the user to better understand and interpret model outputs. Given these observations, the application of RUMMs is not a mere calculating exercise. Instead, the results can be discussed in detail. For the model application, ten real-world UXO objects were selected for each of the two layouts. The two following subsections each briefly introduce the underlying data and the selection procedure. Subsequently, they describe the chosen UXO objects, the environmental conditions (i.e., the input data), and the resulting model outputs. For the confirmed layout, it was additionally possible to discuss the outputs in light of real-world EOD decisions.

6.3.1 Application of the Planning Layout

To test and apply the planning layout, it was first necessary to select appropriate data. Following the EOD framework, it would be possible to select target points that were found during phase II of an EOD project but were not yet cleared (see 6.4.2). Obtaining such data externally or acquiring them anew was not necessary, as data that had been gathered by GEOMAR during the project ‘Boost Appplied munition detection through Smart data in Tegration and AI workflows’ (BASTA) [362] were accessible. The data had been collected during cruises AL548 [363] and AL567 [364] with Research Vessel Alkor. The purpose of these cruises was to investigate and perform experiments at numerous German munitions dump sites. Among the methods used for the investigations was detailed optical mapping of previously selected target areas with GEOMAR’s GIRONA 500 AUVs. These were equipped with cameras that took downward-facing images of the sea floor every second, while typically moving forward with a velocity of 0.5 m s^{-1} at an altitude of 1.0 m to 1.5 m. If visibility under water was sufficient, the images could be used to generate photomosaics [24]. These were then used to pick individual UXO objects to train artificial intelligence and to set up a database of UXO in the German dump sites [106]. All of the above was executed by the BASTA consortium.

For this dissertation, the resulting list of picked UXO objects was browsed, and ten items were selected as test applications for the planning layout of RUMMs. In this case, it was decided not to randomly sample from the available objects but to select a variety of objects from different dump sites. This resulted in a diverse sample. Even though most UXO in dump sites is not fused (see 2.1.2), one mine for which a fuse may be present was included in the trial dataset. Figure 6.8 shows photomosaic crop-outs of the selected UXO objects. The red dot at the centre of each image denotes the objects that were used for the model application.

FIGURE 6.8: Photomosaic crop-outs of the UXO objects that were selected for the application of the planning layout (© GEOMAR).

To identify these objects and be able to enter the values for input factors into the model, munitions expert Uwe Wichert was consulted [365]. He provided information on the *UXO type (U)*, which allowed the author to research additional information on the objects in

the literature. The resulting information was again confirmed with Uwe Wichert [366, 367]. The input factors for all ten objects are listed in Table 6.4. Additional calculation information is available in the supplementary data [368]. As suggested in 5.7, a conservative RA was executed. In the case of uncertainty regarding any factor, values that were associated with higher risk were used as model inputs. This was the case for numerous *Charge Type* (M), *Charge Weight* (m_c), *UXO Weight* (m_u), and *Original Casing Thickness* (CT) values. Some values were found in the historic literature of the Allied forces, which contained measurements in pounds. This means that for German ordnance, some uncertainty may have been introduced when the authors of these documents converted weights from kilogramme to pounds and again when they were converted back from pounds to kilogramme for this dissertation. The same is true for inches and millimetres. In some cases, conflicting values were found, even within the same reference. In such cases, the value that led to higher model outputs was selected. Some CT values did not exist in writing, and thus, cutaway drawings that were to scale were used to measure the factor. The *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* (I_b) and the *Relative Effectiveness* (RE) were determined from M . Unless otherwise indicated below, dimensions (l_l and l_s) were measured in the photomosaics. While all other factors had to be researched and some uncertainty remained, these measurements are the most reliable data. For the *Year Sunk* (T), the respective years of the end of WWII (i.e., 1945) and the end of dumping activities (i.e., 1949) were entered. For the *Fuse Type* (FT), some objects were assumed not to be fused, and the value ‘none’ was entered. For objects without a fuse, all *Fuse Properties* (FP) were set to no (‘n’). For the fused objects, FP were entered as found in the literature. As a reminder, these are again listed here.

- fp_1 : Fuse Present
- fp_2 : Fuse Armed
- fp_3 : Fuse without Battery
- fp_4 : Electrolyte in Vial
- fp_5 : Spring Loaded/Cocked Striker, Diaphragm
- fp_6 : Chemical Long Delay Fuse
- fp_7 : More than one Fuse
- fp_8 : More than one Fuse Type

Finally, environmental input factors were determined through the *Latitude* and *Longitude* of the EOD operation and a random *Planned EOD Date* (which resulted in a random season) via the lookup tables that are included in the RUMMs Excel tool. These are *Sediment Type* (S), *Current Velocity* (v_c), *Wind Speed* (v_w), and *Visual Range Under Water* (R). Note that a bias for v_w may have been introduced since images were available for objects 1 through 10. The *Water Depth* (D) was checked in GEOMAR’s bathymetric measurements. Even though the photomosaic crop outs allow assessing the *Condition of Casing* and the *Burial State*, these two factors were calculated. This was not necessary to be able to use RUMMs and perform RA. Nevertheless, it was done to test the planning layout. Accordingly, Table 6.4 also contains information on the *Sediment Accumulation Rate* (SAR).

TABLE 6.4: UXO and environmental factors of the selected UXO objects for the application of the planning layout.

No.	U	M	I_b (N m)	RE	m_c (kg)	m_u (kg)	l_l^* (mm)	l_s^* (mm)	CM	CT (mm)
1	Cluster bomb AB 500 (German)	TNT	15	1.00	26	415	2000	470	Steel	3.20 + 9.50 [†]
2a	15 cm cartridge (German)	Nitrocellulose	10	0.50	20	25	427	171	Steel [‡]	3.80 [§]
2b	Submunition SB-3 kg (German)	Unknown (non-maritime)	10	1.00	2	3	427	171	Steel	1.59
3	Ground mine BMA or BM 1000 (German)	Hexanite	10	1.30	647	998	1268	625	Steel	2.60 [§]
4	Ground mine TMC (German)	Hexanite	10	1.30	930	1112	3000	520	Aluminium	6.00
5	Charge container of EMC or EMF moored mine (German)	Hexanite	10	1.30	350 [#]	375	1124	1096	Steel	1.38 ^{§α}
6	Ground mine Mk V (British)	Minol (unspecified)	50	1.45	318	490	2008	493	Steel [‡]	3.00
7	Box with 3.7 cm munitions ^β (German)	Nitrocellulose (mainly)	10	0.50	1	3	460	53	Steel [‡]	3.80 [§]
8	General purpose bomb SC 50 (German)	Amatol (unspecified)	50	1.17	25	56	646	225	Steel	4.06
9	Tail fin of armour piercing bomb PC 1,400 (German)	Amatol 40/60	6	1.17	320	1400	2836	543	Steel	31.80
10	Torpedo head (German)	Schießwolle 39a	10	1.30	300	330	1318	516	Bronze ^γ	unknown

* Values were measured in the photomosaics and not taken from the referenced literature to account for possible changes due to corrosion.

[†] Values of the casing of the cluster bomb container and the casing of the contained submunition.

[‡] No information was found in the literature. Steel is the most common CM . It was therefore used as an assumption.

[§] Measured in historic cutaway drawings in the literature.

^{||} Values from unknown (maritime).

[#] Data for EMF mine.

^α Data for EMC mine.

^β All values are given for an individual munitions object.

^γ Could also be steel. Since the object is in very good condition, bronze was assumed with *Corrosion Rate - Buried* to be 0.00 mm a^{-1} .

TABLE 6.4: *Continued*

No.	T	FT	fp_1	fp_2	fp_3	fp_4	fp_5	fp_6	fp_7	fp_8	S	v_c (m s ⁻¹)	$H_{1/3}$ (m)	R^δ (m)	D (m)	Ref.
1	1949	Many types possible	y	n	y	n	y	n	y	y	Mud and clay	0.02	0.6	4.8	23	[369, 310]
2a	1949	None (only primer)	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Mud and clay	0.03	1.0	5.5	22	[370, 371]
2b	1949	(23) a	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Mud and clay	0.03	1.0	5.5	22	[369]
3	1945	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Sand	0.02	2.0	5.6	11	[310, 372]
4	1945	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Sand	0.02	1.0	5.1	11	[310, 372, 373]
5	1945	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Sand	0.02	1.0	5.5	11	[310, 372, 374]
6	1945	Magnetic induction, acoustic	y	y	n	y	n	n	n	y	Sand	0.02	2.0	6.0	11	[310, 375, 376]
7	1949	Many types possible	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Mud and clay	0.02	0.6	4.9	19	[310, 370, 371]
8	1949	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Mud and clay	0.02	0.6	4.9	19	[310, 369]
9	1949	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Mud and clay	0.02	1.0	4.7	19	[310, 369]
10	1945	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	Sand	0.02	1.0	5.0	17	[375, 377]

^δ For all cases, $R > l_i$, hence l_i was used for calculation (see 5.7.29).

Once all of the information had been collected, the model was used to determine the EOD risk for the ten UXO objects. For a better understanding, the following paragraphs describe each of the objects. Not all of the factors in Table 6.4 are mentioned in the text of each object, as some of them do not require any additional explanations. The main purpose of these descriptions is not to educate about the precise mode of operation of each of these objects but to list the information that is required for the RA. For each of the objects, the text presents the model output values *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P), *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E). They are subsequently interpreted by assessing which factors are responsible for the resulting values and discussing them in light of the risk levels in Figure 6.7.

Object 1—Cluster bomb AB 500 (German)

Object 1 is a German cluster bomb that is located at the Pelzerhaken dump site in the Bay of Lübeck. Cluster munition is “conventional munition that is designed to disperse or release explosive submunitions” [378]. The object that is visible in Figure 6.8 is the *UXO Type* Abwurfbehälter (container) (AB 500) [369]. It could contain different types of submunitions, none at all, or (since it was dumped) completely atypical content. For this assessment, 74 pieces of SD 4 HL hollow charge anti-personnel and vehicle bombs were assumed to be inside the container. A hollow charge allows directing the energy of the detonation products in a desired direction via the shape of a hollow cavity in which the explosive material is located [379]. Each of these bombs has a filling of 0.34 kg of explosive material. This resulted in an aggregate rounded 26 kg *Charge Mass*. No *Charge Mass* values for other submunition types were found in the literature, so higher aggregate masses may exist. Due to this being a container with potential submunitions, the *Original Casing Thickness* consists of the AB 500 container (3.2 mm) and the submunition SD 4 HL (9.5 mm). The filling with SD 4 HL would have a *UXO Mass* of 47 kg. A filling with 392 SD 1 mortar bombs would weigh 415 kg. As the content of the container is unknown, the heavier option was selected. The *Charge Type* of SD 4 HL and SD 1 could be TNT. It could, however, also be a TNT-RDX-mixture (SD 4 HL) or Amatol 30/70 (SD 1) for which no *Impact Sensitivity* and *Relative Effectiveness* values are known. The *Charge Type* was, thus, set to TNT. There is no knowledge of whether the container was dumped with a fuse or not. The AB 500 container was equipped with a spring-loaded type Z 89B clockwork fuse in conjunction with Z 69D or Z 69E electric fuses with a pyrotechnic delay. It was not reasonable to assume that submunitions were fused immediately before deployment. Therefore, it was expected that each submunition item be equipped with a fuse that is not armed. SD 4 HL was equipped with a Z (66) impact fuse, i.e., a fuse that fires when the bomb hits its target [380]. Note that the combination of different types of submunitions, as was done here, leads to an RA of an object that does not exist in reality. The model outputs are therefore higher than they would be if the type of filling were known. This is the essence of performing a conservative RA.

$$P = 4.5 \text{ (medium)}; C = 5.6 \text{ (low)}; E = 2.9 \text{ (medium)}$$

The object's P lies at the upper end of the medium risk level. This demonstrates that a fused object remains at the medium risk level as long as the *Fuse Corrosion State* is not deteriorating and as long as it does not meet too many of the *Fuse Properties* (in this case 5 were met). A high *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* is counterbalanced by a medium risk E value. The very good *Condition of Casing*, the low *Water Depth*, and the sufficient *Visual Range Under Water* prevent a higher E value. Finally, C is at the low risk level.

Object 2a—Initial Assessment—15 cm cartridge (German)

Object 2 is a cartridge for a 15 cm shell [371] that is located at the Pelzerhaken dump site in the Bay of Lübeck. It is important to understand that this object is not the artillery shell that is fired by an artillery gun. It is the cartridge that contains the propellant that is required to accelerate the shell out of the gun barrel. Therefore, it does not contain a main charge explosive material but a propellant, which can nevertheless explode (see 2.2.7). Germany used several types of propellant for its cartridges. Of these, a *Relative Effectiveness* value could only be found for nitrocellulose, which is why it is used here. The *Original Casing Thickness* is given as 3.8 mm. It was measured in a cutaway drawing of a historic document [370]. This value was used to determine the *Condition of Casing*. However, since the cartridge may be open at the top (i.e., at the position where the shell would be placed), a value of 0.0 mm was used to determine the current *Impact Sensitivity*. The rationale lies in the fact that the propellant can be expected to immediately interface with the seawater and hence change the *Impact Sensitivity*. During the use of artillery, the empty cartridge would be released at the back or side of a gun and could be refilled and reused. Due to the material shortage after the war, it is expected that these cartridges were not dumped unless they had been filled, which would have made recycling the steel more complicated than with an empty cartridge. The largest *Charge Mass* that was found in the literature amounts to 20 kg, but it could also be less than half of that. Accordingly, the *UXO Mass* could be lower than presented in Table 6.4 as well. The cartridge may be made from brass, but a steel casing is more likely. The cartridge was potentially fused in the sense that it was equipped with a primer at the centre of its base. The firing pin of a gun is meant to hit this primer to initiate the explosion. This primer is not regarded as a fuse for this RA, as this is the same principle that applies to all modern cartridge ammunition, including pistol and rifle ammunition. It is extremely unlikely to initiate it unless strong force is applied at the precise location of the primer, for example, with a hammer.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 4.9 \text{ (low)}; E = 2.8 \text{ (medium)}$$

The P and C values of the object are at the lower end of the low risk level. The P value is driven by the *Impact Sensitivity*. Here the model assumes 10 N m since no other value was available in the literature. Since nitrocellulose is not a high-performance explosive material, the *Impact Sensitivity* is likely lower in reality and thus P is overestimated. Considering that the *Charge Mass* might be lower than the 20 kg given in the table, C might also

be lower than calculated here. However, the paradigm of performing a conservative risk assessment produces this value. Finally, E is at the medium risk level. Like P , it might be overestimated due to the lack of information on the *Impact Sensitivity*. The E value is furthermore driven by the *Burial State*. If this object did not lie on a pile of UXO, it would have been buried in the sediment and would require dredging.

Object 2b—Adapted Assessment—Submunition SB-3 kg (German)

After the initial assessment of object 2 had been completed, personal communication of the author with the EOD service of the state of Schleswig-Holstein revealed that object 2 was likely a submunition of container AB 500 (object 1). Of the submunitions that were found in the literature, the shape of the *UXO Type* SB-3 kg [369] best fits the image shown in Figure 6.8. The measurements are not matching precisely, and the literature suggests that this *UXO Type* occurs very rarely. Nevertheless, for this assessment it was used as a best estimate. No information on the *Charge Type* was found, so it was set to unknown (non-maritime), which led to standard values for the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* and the *Relative Effectiveness* of the explosive material. In addition to these factors the *UXO Mass*, *Charge Mass*, *Original Casing Thickness*, *Fuse Type*, and *Fuse Properties* differ from the initial assessment (object 2a). All other factors are identical.

$$P = 5.1 \text{ (high); } C = 3.8 \text{ (very low); } E = 4.2 \text{ (medium)}$$

In light of the fact that the submunition was found on the same UXO pile as the container (object 1), it is considered likely that this adapted assessment is correct. Nevertheless, both results were included in this discussion, as it demonstrates how essential high-quality visual data collection and comprehensive historical research are for a reliable RA. The least significant is the change in the E value, which remains in the medium risk range. After the adaptation of input data, C is now a very low risk value (when it was a low risk value for object 2a). Even though the *Relative Effectiveness* of object 2b (1.00) is double that of object 2a (0.50), the considerably smaller *Charge Mass* (2 kg vs. 20 kg respectively) at an identical *Water Depth* led to this decrease in C . The most significant change can be observed in P . RUMMs calculates a high risk value in the adapted assessment, while it had initially provided a low value. The fact that a fuse is present and that RUMMs predicts a 20% *Fuse Corrosion State* drives P of object 2b. For EOD, it is essential to find out whether these objects (of which there are hundreds on the UXO pile) are in fact fused. If not, the risk will be reduced significantly.

Note that while much of the input data for objects 2a and 2b are identical, model outputs vary remarkably. The interpretation of the results may lead to different suggestions for the EOD process, depending on which object is actually encountered. Approaches for results interpretation are discussed in 6.4.2.

Object 3—Ground mine BMA or BM 1000 (German)

Object 3 is a German ground mine Bombenmine (bomb mine) A (BMA) or BM 1000 [372] that is located at the Kolberger Heide dump site. These *UXO Types* are very similar in size and appearance, so it is not possible to distinguish them on the photomosaic. The *Charge Type* would be expected to be a non-maritime one since this type of object was originally a bomb that was used by the German air force as a mine. However, one reference explicitly states that it was hexanite [310], which was a maritime explosive mixture. Its *Charge Mass* amounted to 647 kg for BMA or 726 kg for BM 1000, which means that the value is above the threshold value (see 5.10.2). Accordingly, RUMMs calculates with 350 kg. It is not realistic that this mine was laid in the Kolberger Heide area or in its vicinity since it is a German offensive mine that is located in German waters. It is therefore assumed that the object was dumped and is therefore not fused. The BMA was heavier than the BM 1000, so the *UXO Mass* of the former is used in RUMMs. There existed different BMA models (BMA I, BMA II, and BMA III), all with identical *UXO Mass*.

$$P = 1.8 \text{ (low)}; C = 9.3 \text{ (very high)}; E = 3.3 \text{ (medium)}$$

Because the object is likely not fused, it has a low risk *P* value that is similar to that of object 2. The value is slightly higher since *E* is larger. It lies well at the medium risk level. The output is driven by the fact that the object's *UXO Mass* and *UXO Longest Dimension* are considerably larger than for objects 1 and 2. In addition, the *Significant Wave Height* at Kolberger Heide can be up to 2.0 m during winter, which is the season that was randomly assigned to this object. In terms of the *C* value, object 3 differs significantly from the previous examples, which can be attributed to the *Charge Mass* at the upper threshold of the value range.

Object 4—Ground mine TMC (German)

Object 4 is a German ground mine Torpedomine (torpedo mine) C (TMC) (torpedo mine) [372] that is located at the Kolberger Heide dump site. As the name suggests, submarines fired it like a torpedo. There existed two models (TMC I and TMC II) of the same size and appearance. It is therefore not possible to distinguish them in the photomosaic. Since the *UXO Mass* of TMC I is larger (1112 kg), the assessment is continued with this value. The *Charge Mass* of TMC I is also larger than that of TMC II. However, since 930 kg exceed the threshold value, RUMMs calculates with 350 kg. Neither a value for the *Original Casing Thickness* nor a drawing could be found in the literature. The TMC was an enlarged version of the TMB mine, so it was possible to gather and use information from the TMB. This way, it was possible to identify the *Original Casing Thickness* of 6 mm [373] and the *Casing Material* to be aluminium. It is not unlikely that aluminium was not available towards the end of WWII, leading to TMC production from steel. This is, however, not backed by the literature. The *Main Charge Type* was again found to be hexanite [310]. Remarkably, no *Impact Sensitivity* or *Relative Effectiveness* values for this compound can be found in the literature since this appears to be a common explosive material in marine UXO. Unfortunately, this meant that the values associated

with the entry unknown (maritime) had to be used in the calculation. Finally, similar to object 3, it is not realistic that this mine was laid at Kolberger Heide area or in its vicinity. Accordingly, an object without a fuse is expected.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 9.3 \text{ (very high)}; E = 3.0 \text{ (medium)}$$

With a *Charge Mass* at the upper value range boundary and a very low *Water Depth*, it is not surprising that *C* is located at the very high risk level. This expresses that if an undesired detonation occurs, the consequences will be dire. Due to the lack of a fuse in the TMC, *P* is located at the low risk level, which makes the occurrence of a detonation rather unlikely. *E* displays a medium value, which is mainly driven by *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*, *UXO Longest Dimension*, and *UXO Mass*. This means that the complexity is not exclusively determined by the necessity to handle the object with care but also by its sheer size and weight.

Object 5—Charge container of EMC or EMF moored mine (German)

Object 5 is the charge container of a German Einheitsmine (standardised mine) C (EMC) (uniform mine) or EMF moored mine [372] at the Kolberger Heide dump site. Since it was not possible to determine which of the two mine types the charge container belonged to, the description below is a combination of the two. The floating body of the mine does not exist, either due to it not being dumped or due to corrosion. The *Charge Mass* of 341 kg originates from the EMF mine, as it is higher than the EMC's. The *Charge Type* of both mines was hexanite [310]. Similar to objects 3 and 4, since no *Impact Sensitivity* and *Relative Effectiveness* values for this type of explosive material were available, unknown (maritime) was selected in RUMMs. The *Original Casing Thickness* was measured in an EMC cross-section. It is the thickness of the charge container's casing and not of the floating body, which would be the casing of the mine itself. The *UXO Mass* of 375 kg is the object's weight without the mine chair (i.e., the anchor that connects the mine to the seabed) and the mooring cable. Since no value was found in the literature, it was estimated by adding a threshold that represents the weight of the casing and baseplate to the *Charge Weight*. This weight was chosen instead of the full weight of the mine (which would be 1124 kg) because all EMC and EMF mines that were found in this area in the past were not equipped with a mine chair or mooring. Like objects 3 and 4, it is presumed that this object is not fused. The fact that only the charge container is visible further supports this assumption. Similar to object 1, the combination of two *UXO Types* led to overestimated model outputs but also to a conservative RA.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 9.3 \text{ (very high)}; E = 2.7 \text{ (medium)}$$

The fact that the object is not fused is responsible for the low risk *P* value. It could only be lower if the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* or *E* were lower. The object has an *E* value at the lower end of the medium range. It is driven by the object's *Condition*

of *Casing* and *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*. Environmental conditions that can be easily handled counterbalance this. The object has a very high risk *C*, for which the *Charge Mass* at the threshold level and the low *Water Depth* are responsible.

Object 6—Ground mine Mk V (British)

Object 6 is a British Mark V (Mk V) ground mine [375] that is located at Kolberger Heide. The mine was equipped with a magnetic fuse. Due to this being an English mine in German waters, it had to be assumed that it was fused. This type of mine could be equipped with combinations of acoustic, magnetic, and contact fuses. It is also possible that it was disarmed by the bomb disposal squad of the state of Schleswig-Holstein and transported to Kolberger Heide for later disposal [181]. In this case, the object would be a charge container without a fuse. The photomosaic does not support the latter option. The *Original Casing Thickness* of this object was determined from a photograph of an Mk IV, which was a very similar mine. The British ground mines Mk I through IV and VI all had steel casings [310], so it is fair to assume the same for the Mk V.

$$P = 5.7 \text{ (high); } C = 9.3 \text{ (very high); } E = 4.6 \text{ (high)}$$

Of the ten assessed UXO objects, Mk V is the one with the highest overall risk scores. Similar to other larger mines (e.g., objects 4 and 5), it has a very high risk *C* value that is a result of the large *Charge Mass* and shallow *Water Depth*. In terms of *P* and *E* it differs from the other mines since it had to be assumed that this British mine was deployed during the war and, thus, that it was fused. The 4 out of 8 Fuse Properties as well as a 40% *Fuse Corrosion State* are the main contributors to a *P* at the high risk level. *E* remains at the medium risk level due to benign environmental conditions, but it is the largest value for all objects.

Object 7—Box with 3.7 cm munitions (German)

Object 7 is a box with twelve pieces of 3.7 cm munitions [371] that is located at the Haffkrug dump site in the Bay of Lübeck. Each object consists of an artillery shell and a cartridge with a propellant. The first question that needed to be answered was whether the EOD and therefore the RA should be performed for the individual object or the entire box. The poor condition of the box (i.e., the fact that it is open) was expected to make lifting it in its entirety difficult. EOD of the individual objects was considered preferable, and RA was therefore conducted individually. There were many different types of ordnance with a calibre of 3.7 cm in use, so it is impossible to determine the exact model from the photomosaic. Fortunately, the properties that are relevant for the RA are relatively similar. The object could be an armour-piercing shell (Panzergranate) or an explosive shell (Sprenggranate). It could also be tracer ammunition. Even the explosive ordnance types with the largest *Charge Mass* contain < 1 kg of both explosive material and propellant combined. The *Main Charge Type* could be one of many different mixtures or compounds, depending on which type of 3.7 cm shell this is. Either way, the propellant contributes more to the mass of explosive material than the main charge, which is why nitrocellulose was

entered in RUMMs. The model was set up to use the same *Original Impact Sensitivity* that it would use, for example, for TNT, but the lower *Relative Effectiveness* of nitrocellulose. Accordingly, the performance of the explosive material was assumed to be driven by the compound with the largest mass. This option is not available in the RUMMs Excel tool. The *UXO Mass* of *UXO Types* that come into question ranges from < 1 kg to 3 kg. The cartridge may be made from brass, but a steel casing is more likely. For *Original Casing Thickness* and *Casing Material* the cartridge's and not the shell's casing was used as it is thinner. The measurement of the historic cutaway drawing that was determined for object 2 was reused [370]. For this type of small UXO, a fuse was possibly already present even when transported in boxes, but it is highly unlikely that it was armed.

$$P = 3.1 \text{ (low)}; C = 2.8 \text{ (very low)}; E = 2.2 \text{ (low)}$$

For object 7, RUMMs returns a low risk *P*, a very low risk *C*, and a low risk *E*. In opposition to object 2, this one is a shell (which may have a fuse present) and a cartridge, which leads to a comparatively higher *P*. The *E* value of object 7 is slightly lower than that of object 2 because RUMMs calculated a better *Condition of Casing*. This is because the planning layout assumes the object to be freely lying on the seabed and therefore being buried over time. In reality, object 7 is likely in a less favourable condition, which in turn would potentially lead to a worse condition of the fuse. On the other hand, EOD is less complex for an unburied object. This discrepancy demonstrates that there is a level of uncertainty connected to using the planning layout. The most noteworthy difference between objects 2 and 7 lies in the fact that *C* is higher for object 2. The driver is the greater *Charge Mass* (to be precise, the propellant).

Object 8—General purpose bomb SC 50 (German)

Object 8 is a German general-purpose aerial bomb SC 50 [369] that is located at the Haffkrug dump site in the Bay of Lübeck. According to the literature, it could be filled with TNT, Amatol, or Trialen. Since no properties for Trialen could be found in the literature and the expert considered TNT to be an oversimplification, Amatol 40/60 was entered as *Charge Type*. This specific amatol mixture was entered in RUMMs as it is the one with the highest *Original Impact Sensitivity*. Because this object is without its tail fin and located on a munitions pile in a dump site, it is assumed that this object was dumped and is therefore not fused.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 5.8 \text{ (low)}; E = 2.6 \text{ (low)}$$

The *P* value lies at the low risk level. It is among the lowest values of all of the objects because it was not fused and because of the very favourable environmental conditions, which leads to a low level *E*. The *E* value is mainly increased by the object's predicted 89% *Burial State*, which was a virtual value for the purpose of demonstrating the planning layout (as mentioned in the introduction of this section). Figure 6.8 shows that the object

is actually buried to a much lesser degree. For a less buried object, E and, therefore, P would have been even lower. For this object, C lies at a low risk level as well. In summary, the clearance of the object is not considered challenging.

Object 9—Tail fin of armour piercing bomb PC 1,400 (German)

Object 9 is the tail fin of a German aerial bomb that is located at the same dump site as objects 7 and 8. There are numerous bombs to which this tail fin could be attached. The object with the largest *Charge Mass* that comes into question with a tail fin of this diameter is the Panzerbombe, Cylindrisch, 1400 kg (cylindrical armour piercing bomb) (PC 1,400) [369]. However, this *UXO Type* has a *UXO Longest Dimension* of 2836 mm. It can be questioned whether such a large bomb can be vertically buried in the sediment. The predicted *Sediment Accumulation Rate* for the location does not allow for such a deep burial. The rather fine sediment in combination with the *UXO Mass* of 1400 kg could have led to a certain degree of burial upon impact. However, the almost full vertical burial of such a large object is unlikely. Other smaller bombs on the same pile reveal that tail fins are sometimes detached from objects. It is possible that a large object lies horizontally or tilted under the sediment. The object may also have a considerably lower *Charge Mass* (e.g., a PC 1,000 with 152 kg, which is less than half of the PC 1,400 with 320 kg). The conservative RA approach requires using the data from PC 1,400 until further information is available. For the *UXO Mass*, PC 1,400 surpasses the threshold value, so RUMMs calculates with 1300 kg instead of 1400 kg. Similar to object 8, Amatol 40/60 was entered as *Charge Type* since the literature did not specify the amatol mixture, and this is the one supporting the conservative RA. Because only the tail fin is visible in the photomosaic, the *UXO Longest Dimension* value was, as an exception, acquired from literature instead of being measured.

$$P = 1.8 \text{ (low)}; C = 8.7 \text{ (high)}; E = 3.0 \text{ (medium)}$$

The bomb is an object with a high risk C value, which is once again attributed to the large *Charge Mass* and shallow *Water Depth* at the dump site. The mines (i.e., objects 3 through 6) have a higher C value due to their being located in even shallower waters than object 9. If either of these objects detonates, the consequences will be catastrophic, which is well reflected by all the C values being located at high and very high risk levels. The value for E is among the highest of all objects (even though it is only 3.0). It is important to gather experience with the model to be able to interpret the outputs and not disregard a 3.0 as an unproblematic EOD operation. Still, the environmental conditions are favourable, so that E remains in the medium range. P is low, mainly because the object was expected to be without a fuse.

Object 10—Torpedo head (German)

Object 10 is a German torpedo head that is located in the vicinity of the Falshöft dump site. It is important to understand that this is the part of the torpedo that carries the payload (i.e., the main charge) and does not include the rear section, in which the

mechanics and propellant are located. The object's *Casing Material* could be steel or bronze [377]. Due to the good condition shown in Figure 6.8, it was assumed that the latter is true. This impression was confirmed by the individual photos of which the photomosaic was produced. These showed a green patina on the object, which may be hinting at bronze disease. Since bronze is very resistant against corrosion, a *Corrosion Rate - Unburied* of 0.00 mm a^{-1} was assumed. A worst-case scenario was assumed for the *Charge Mass*. A warhead may well contain a smaller amount of explosive material than 300 kg. It was not possible to obtain values for the *Original Casing Thickness* or the *UXO Mass*. While the former is irrelevant due to the lack of corrosion, the latter poses a challenge since it impacts the model output E . To estimate the *UXO Mass* a mass of 30 kg was added to the *Charge Mass*. However, this value is unreliable. Like other objects, the torpedo was most likely dumped. If it was fired in combat, the object would not be limited to the warhead but also include the rear section. Accordingly, the object is assumed to be without a fuse.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 8.8 \text{ (high)}; E = 2.2 \text{ (low)}$$

Given that object 10 is not fused, it joins multiple other objects with their low risk P and E values. The only two factors that drive E are the *UXO Longest Dimension* and *Burial State*. On the other hand, C is a high risk value and borders on the very high risk range, which starts at 9.0.

Results of the Planning Layout

The bar chart in Figure 6.9 summarises the outcome of the application of the planning layout on objects 1 through 10. It shows the P , C , and E values for all ten objects. The chart demonstrates the kind of results that RUMMs returns when used to assess real-world UXO. The discussion below refers to the adapted assessment of object 2b and ignores the initial one (object 2a).

The model returned very high risk level C values for four objects and high risk level values for another two. No medium risk level values, two low risk level values, and two very low risk level values were generated. This distribution strongly contradicts the output distribution of the MCS. Two reasons were identified. Firstly, all UXO objects are located in shallow water dump sites. The vast area of deeper waters in the German North Sea is not represented. No dump sites exist in this area, and hence no photomosaics were acquired by GEOMAR. This means that objects in this area could not be part of this assessment. Secondly, the selection of objects on the existing photomosaics followed no methodology except for achieving great diversity in *UXO Types*. Since larger objects are easier to distinguish (and consequently easier to identify by an expert), these happen to be overrepresented in the subset of UXO used for this application of RUMMs. This is not problematic. The idea of this model application was not to select a representative group of UXO, which may have resulted in a subgroup of objects with medium risk output values. Instead, it is now clear that the planning layout consistently returns large C values for the larger objects and that small objects return very low risk level values, even when located in shallow waters (e.g., see object 7).

For seven objects, P lay at the low risk level. This is not surprising for a set of UXO objects that are mostly without a fuse. The fact that a fuse might be present but not armed in object 7 elevated P but not sufficiently to lift it into the medium risk level. Still, it is remarkable that no object had a very low risk P . An even friendlier environment has the potential to have led to lower P values, but the German Baltic Sea is already a very forgiving working environment when compared to, e.g., the North Sea. A problem that was identified during the assessment of objects 1 through 10 is the functionality of the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification*. Even though RUMMs predicted *Current Impact Sensitivity* values ranging from 6 N m to 24 N m, all objects had a *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* of 3. This stands for ‘sensitive’ materials ranging from 4 N m to 35 N m (see 5.7.19). This is problematic since it trivialises a complex issue. In a future version of RUMMs, this transformation from *Current Impact Sensitivity* to *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* should be eliminated, despite this being an expert recommendation when the model was prepared (see 5.7.19). It is expected that higher values (i.e., lower impact sensitivity) will then lead to lower P values. Of the remaining three objects, one lay at the medium risk level and two lay at the high risk level. Here, RUMMs demonstrated well that it responds to the *Fuse Properties* and the *Fuse Corrosion State*. The fact that it returned higher P values the less favourable the state and set-up of the fuse shows its reliability.

For E , RUMMs returned values ranging from 2.0 to 4.6, which means that they lay in the low to high risk levels. Only object 6 was barely at the high risk level, which was mainly attributed to it being fused. Three objects had low and six had medium E values. Due to E having many parent nodes, these have the potential to cancel each other out and lead to many medium output values. On the one hand, the ten objects are mostly located in accessible environments, and numerous are not fused, which decreases E . On the other hand, many of them would be rather challenging to handle in terms of their physical properties (weight and size), which increased E . To produce lower values, the model requires small UXO in a benign environment, such as objects 7 and 8.

Overall, RUMMs produced values ranging from low to high risk levels for all three model outputs. For P , no outputs at very high and very low risk levels were produced, and for E , they were very rare. Given that the risk levels were originally determined by analysing the standard deviations of the MCS results (see 6.2.3), the distributions of these model outputs lie within the range of expected values. While it might be tempting to expect spectacular values and predict very easy or very challenging EOD operations, the model reflects the reality that most operations pose an average risk. This demonstrates that RUMMs users must familiarise themselves with the nuances of changes in the model outputs for these average objects. On the other hand, C tended towards extreme values, which was attributed to the combination of shallow *Water Depth* and large *Charge Mass*. Further applications of different objects in deeper waters are required to obtain a better understanding. Such data were not available for the testing of the planning layout. The different MCS runs distributed objects throughout the study area or water depth without considering that,

FIGURE 6.9: Model outputs of the application of the planning layout.

in reality, most objects would be located in shallow water dump sites. The real-world UXO data show that objects with high level C values will be encountered regularly when performing clearance in these areas.

6.3.2 Application of the Confirmed Layout

For the application of the confirmed layout, the EOD dataset [107] that was already used to understand UXO properties (see 2.2) and EOD decision making (see 3.3.2) was utilised once more. To do so, 20 of the 230 dataset entries were sampled. Random sampling was used since it was assumed that the EOD dataset represents the overall population of UXO objects in the study area. If certain types of UXO occur more frequently, they will be included in the dataset (and thus in the sample) more often than others. Non-random sampling for the sake of obtaining a diverse dataset, as was done for the planning layout in 6.3.1, would have limited the ability to consider the results of the confirmed application representative for the study area. For the 20 entries, information on as many UXO and environmental properties as possible was collected from documents from the data provider. Missing UXO data were obtained through literature research. Ultimately, the ten objects for which the most information was available were used for the application of the confirmed layout. Figure 6.10 shows images from the EOD dataset that were taken by the dataset provider. Image quality varies based on whether an object was recovered, which meant that a photo could be taken in air or detonated in situ, which led to poorer image quality. For some objects, no image was available at all.

The *UXO Type* (U) of each object was confirmed with expert Uwe Wichert [381]. Table 6.5 contains all available information on the objects. Additional calculation information is available in the supplementary data [368]. Values for *UXO Mass* (m_u) and *UXO Longest Dimension* (l_l) were sometimes included in the EOD dataset. In other cases, they had to be researched in the literature. For each object, the *Main Charge Type* (M) and *Charge Mass* (m_c) were checked in all available sources to identify the highest value and answer to the requirement of performing a conservative RA. If available, the *Casing*

FIGURE 6.10: Images of the UXO objects that were selected for the application of the confirmed layout (objects 11 through 17 © SeaTerra, objects 18 and 19 [374], object 20 © Uwe Wichert).

Condition (CC) was assessed from the photos in Figure 6.10. For objects 18, 19, and 20, it was calculated as if the planning layout were used. The EOD dataset contained information on the *Burial State (B)* of all assessed objects. Note that since this is the confirmed model, no value $> 50\%$ should be entered (see 5.7.25), i.e., the process *UXO identification* could only take place after *object uncovering* was performed.

Some of the required environmental data were given in the EOD dataset. Gaps could be filled by entering the *Latitude* and *Longitude* of the EOD operation and the *Planned EOD Date* (which in this case was a real EOD date in the past). The lookup tables in the RUMMs Excel tool then provided the best possible assumption for the missing information. This was done for the majority of objects for the *Current Velocity* (v_c), *Wind Speed* (v_s), and *Visual Range Under Water* (R) as well as for some objects for *Water Depth* (D).

Since the EOD dataset was used to select the objects and to obtain a great deal of data on them, it was known which EOD process was executed during UXO handling. Some specific remarks are given in the object descriptions below. More general hints on the interpretation of RUMMs model outputs and the implications for EOD are given in 6.4.2.

No detailed information on the location of the objects beyond the details provided in the object descriptions below can be given. This way, no information on contracting parties involved in the EOD campaign can be inferred (see 2.2). Apart from object 17, which was located in the Baltic Sea, all EOD operations took place in the German North Sea.

The following paragraphs are structured in a similar fashion to 6.3.1. They first describe the model inputs and outputs. In addition, the EOD data allow discussing the values for the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P), *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* (C), and *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) in light of the key processes that were executed to handle these objects.

Object 11—30.5 cm artillery shell (German)

Object 11 was a German 30.5 cm artillery shell that was first used during WWI but continued to be in use during WWII [382]. It is not clear which *UXO Type* exactly was found. It might have been a coastal artillery high-explosive projectile (German: Sprenggranate) L/5,3. However, the *UXO Mass* given in the literature (424 kg [382]) deviates quite significantly from the value that was determined during the EOD operation (455 kg [383]). It is, thus, not possible to determine the precise *Main Charge Type* it was filled with. Possible options are combinations of Fp. 1, which could not be identified, or Fp. 5, Fp. 10, and Fp. 15, all of which are mixtures of TNT and wax in different compositions [384, 128]. Even though this UXO object was used by the German navy, the *Main Charge Type* is not treated as a maritime one since these mixtures of TNT and wax were not specifically designed for the user under water. The higher *Relative Effectiveness* that is associated with maritime explosives (see 5.7.20) is, therefore, not expected for object 11. Accordingly, the entry unknown (non-maritime) was selected, which led to standard values for the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* and the *Relative Effectiveness*. The *Fuse Type* was a base fuse at the rear end of the shell, either type Bodenzünder (ground fuse) (Bdz.) mVuK or Bdz. 36. Both fuses were primed upon firing and were designed to detonate upon impact [310]. Since the documentation of the EOD dataset contained information on the *Significant Wave Height* [385], the *Wind Speed* data are ignored. Finally, it is worth mentioning that

TABLE 6.5: UXO and environmental factors of the UXO objects that were selected for the application of the confirmed layout.

No.	U	EOD Process*	M	I_b (N m)	RE	m_c (kg)	m_u (kg)	l_l (mm)	CC	B^* (%)
11	30.5 cm artillery shell (German)	<i>Recovery</i>	Unknown (non-maritime)	10	1.00	27	455*	1250*	5*	50
12	10.5 cm artillery cartridge (German)	<i>Recovery</i>	Nitrocellulose (mainly)	10	0.50	6	6*	600*	3*	50
13	10.5 cm artillery round (German)	<i>Recovery</i>	Nitrocellulose	10	0.50	10	55*	980*	4*	0
14	21 cm artillery shell (German)	<i>Recovery</i>	TNT with wax	10 [†]	1.00 [†]	4	120	825 [‡]	5*	50
15	10 cm mortar projectile (German)	<i>Underwater transfer and in situ destruction</i>	TNT	10	1.00	2*	9	435	5*	50
16	GP 500 lbs bomb (US American)	<i>In situ destruction</i>	Composition B	10	1.35	125	243	1613 [§]	4*	50
17	Part of an INC 30 LB incendiary bomb (British)	<i>Recovery</i>	None	0	0.00	0	14	560*	3*	50
18	UMA moored mine (German)	<i>Underwater transfer</i>	Hexanite	10	1.30	30	160*	800*	0 [#]	0
19	BMC moored mine (German)	<i>Underwater transfer</i>	Hexanite	10	1.30	54	500*	1450*	0 [#]	0
20	Ground mine Mk I-IV (British)	<i>In situ destruction</i>	Minol (unspecified)	50	1.45	344	700*	3000	3 [#]	50

* Values were provided with EOD dataset.

[†] Values from unknown (non-maritime).

[‡] Measured in historic cutaway drawing in the literature.

[§] Data for Mk 12 Mod 2.

^{||} Values from unknown (maritime).

[#] Since no image was available, the *Casing Condition* was calculated based on the *Corrosion Rate – Buried* or *Corrosion Rate – Unburied* and *Original Casing Thickness*.

TABLE 6.5: *Continued*

No.	<i>FT</i>	<i>fp</i> ₁	<i>fp</i> ₂	<i>fp</i> ₃	<i>fp</i> ₄	<i>fp</i> ₅	<i>fp</i> ₆	<i>fp</i> ₇	<i>fp</i> ₈	v_c (m s ⁻¹)	v_w (m s ⁻¹)	$H_{1/3}$ (m)	R^α (m)	D (m)	Ref.
11	Bdz. mVuK or Bdz. 36	y	y	y	n	n	n	n	n	0.63		0.8*	0.3	19*	[310, 382, 383, 384, 385]
12	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0.89		0.2*	2.5	19	[371, 386, 387]
13	None (only primer)	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0.88	6.2	1.0	2.5	19	[371, 388]
14	Bdz. mVuK or Bdz. 36	y	y	y	n	n	n	n	n	0.57	6.2	1.0	2.5	12*	[310, 389, 390, 391]
15	Wgr. Zdr. 36*	y	y	y	n	n	n	n	n	0.30	6.4	1.0	6.3	22*	[310, 371, 392]
16	Various options	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	0.30	6.4	1.0	6.3	25*	[310, 393, 394, 395]
17	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0.01	7.0	1.0	5.0	9	[113, 396, 397]
18	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0.88	6.2	1.0	2.5	19	[372, 374]
19	None	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0.88	6.2	1.0	2.5	19	[372, 374]
20	Magnetic induction, acoustic, impact	y	y	n	n	y	n	n	y	0.34	10.1	2.0	0.5	29*	[310, 375, 376]

* Values were provided with EOD dataset.

^α For all cases, except for object 11, $R > l_l$, hence l_l was used for calculation (see 5.7.29).

the object's location is the only case where the seasonal *Visual Range Under Water* that was determined automatically by RUMMs was smaller than the *UXO Longest Dimension*, which poses an additional challenge during EOD.

$$P = 4.1 \text{ (medium); } C = 5.8 \text{ (low); } E = 3.5 \text{ (medium)}$$

Even though object 11 was fused, the fact that it is expected to be in good condition (i.e., not corroded) and that only 3 *Fuse Properties* applied results in a medium risk value for P . The UXO properties and environmental conditions are manageable, so E is also in the medium risk level. A main driver of E is the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification*. The issue that this factor contributes to all objects in the same manner and that this needs to be addressed when updating RUMMs was already mentioned in the conclusion of Section 6.3.1. Another booster of E is the *Visual Range Under Water*. If operators had the opportunity to wait for better conditions, this would lead to an ever lower E value (e.g., in the same scenario, if $R = 1.0$ m, then $E = 3.2$). A small *Charge Mass* leads to a low (albeit almost medium) risk C value. During the EOD operation, the process *recovery* was executed for object 11, which is in line with the low to medium risk model outputs.

Object 12—10.5 cm artillery cartridge (German)

Object 12 was a 10.5 cm artillery cartridge without a projectile. This made it comparable to the initial assumption that was made for object 2. It contained only the propellant and no main-charge explosive. Hence, the main charge type was set to nitrocellulose, with its rather low *Relative Effectiveness*. The values for *Charge Mass* and *UXO Mass* are identical (6 kg). While the latter was obtained from the EOD dataset [386], the former was the highest value for the mass of the propellant that was found for the 10.5 cm calibre cartridge [371]. Given that the casing was strongly corroded, with a *Casing Condition* of 3 (see Figure 6.10), it was realistic to assume that the majority of the object's mass can in fact be attributed to the propellant. This renders the identical values for *Charge Mass* and *UXO Mass* somewhat plausible. The cartridge could not be fused, and due to its poor *Casing Condition* not even a functioning primer may have been present. Like for object 11, the *Significant Wave Height* information had been documented [387], so that the *Wind Speed* data were ignored. RUMMs automatically obtained the *Visual Range Under Water* of 2.5 m from the nearest measurement station (see 5.7.29). This value was very likely overestimated, since the company performing the EOD operation reported challenging visibility during the campaign [104]. *Water Depth* data were not given in the EOD dataset, so RUMMs determined them based on the EOD location.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low); } C = 4.4 \text{ (very low); } E = 2.7 \text{ (medium)}$$

All three model outputs display very low to low risk levels. Object 12 is lightweight, has small dimensions, is not fused, and contains only a propellant and not a main-charge explosive. All these factors contribute to barely medium E and low P values. The only remarkable environmental factor is the *Current Velocity* (0.89 m s^{-1}). As discussed above, the *Visual Range Under Water* is likely overestimated. Reducing its value, e.g., to 0.2 m,

would drive E to a medium risk value (3.5). P would, however, remain in the low-risk region (1.8), despite E being one of its parents. The *Fuse Properties* and *Fuse Corrosion State* control P to a much greater degree. The UXO object has a low *Charge Mass*, and the *Water Depth* is sufficiently large to lead to a very low value for C . Given these model outputs, it is not surprising that the *recovery* process was performed for object 12.

Object 13—10.5 cm artillery round (German)

Object 13 was a complete 10.5 cm artillery round, consisting of a cartridge (such as object 12) and the associated projectile. Hence, the *Charge Mass* of 10 kg consisted of both the main charge and the propellant. The masses of the *UXO Types* that were found in the literature do not even closely correspond to the *UXO Mass* that was given in the EOD dataset (55 kg). It was, thus, impossible to determine which type of projectile is part of this UXO object, so the one with the highest value for the mass of the main charge (a high-explosive projectile for a 105 mm gun) was entered for the sake of producing a conservative RA. [371] Since nitrocellulose (i.e., the propellant) made up the greater part of the *Charge Mass*, its *Relative Effectiveness* was entered into RUMMs. The *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* of 10 N m was identical for the propellant and main charge (unknown (non-maritime)). Even though a projectile was present, it was again assumed that the object was not fused because it was found at the Minsener Oog dump site (see 2.1.2). The fact that the cartridge was attached to the object proves that it was not fired, which is another indicator that no fuse was present. Unlike object 12, this one was not buried, which is remarkable since it was corroded to a lesser degree. For object 13, no *Significant Wave Height* was reported, so RUMMs obtained the value automatically. The *Visual Range Under Water* of 2.5 m was attained in the same way as for object 12 and is again likely overestimated.

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low)}; C = 4.4 \text{ (very low)}; E = 2.3 \text{ (low)}$$

Object 13 is very similar to object 12, and RUMMs calculates similar model outputs for both objects. Despite object 13 being a full artillery round, while object 12 was only a cartridge, the E value is even lower. This is mainly due to object 13 being unburied and its better *Casing Condition*. The greater *UXO Mass* (55 kg vs. 6 kg) cannot counteract these factors. The P value of both objects is equal. This is due to the fact that E is normalised with the incremental (type 4) function, i.e., it is rounded up (see 5.9.4). Therefore, $E^n = 3$ for both objects. Despite the higher *Charge Mass* for object 13 (10 kg vs. 6 kg for object 12), both UXO objects have identical very low risk C values. This can be explained by the fact that the *Shock Factor* calculation in RUMMs uses rounding. Again, the EOD process *recovery* was executed.

Object 14—21 cm artillery shell (German)

Object 14 was another artillery shell. This one had a calibre of 21 cm. According to the EOD dataset, it was an armour-piercing grenade (German: Panzersprenggranate) L/2,9. The *Main Charge Type* was a mixture of TNT with wax [310], for which no *Impact*

Sensitivity Base Value and *Relative Effectiveness* were found in the literature. Hence, the fall-back values of RUMMs were used. Unlike the calibre, the *UXO Longest Dimension* could neither be found in the EOD dataset nor in the literature, so it was measured in a cutaway drawing [389]. Since object 14 was not equipped with a cartridge, it had to be assumed that it had been fused. The potentially present base fuses happened to be the same ones as for object 11.

$$P = 3.9 \text{ (medium); } C = 4.6 \text{ (very low); } E = 2.4 \text{ (low)}$$

For this object, RUMMs calculates a medium risk value for P , which can be attributed to the presence of the fuse. It fulfilled 3 of the 8 *Fuse Properties* and the very good *Casing Condition* led to a prediction of a very good *Fuse Corrosion State*. Hence, P remains manageable. The model output E indicates low risk. Of all its parents, only the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* had a normalised value > 5 . Accordingly, none of the factors drive E into higher risk levels. As for objects 12 and 13, the C value is very low. This can be attributed to the small *Charge Mass* (4 kg). The process of *recovery* was performed for object 14.

Object 15—10 cm mortar projectile (German)

Object 15 was a German 10 cm explosive mortar projectile 40 (German: Wurfgranate 40 Spr). Data for most UXO factors had been provided in the EOD documentation [392]. This included the *Fuse Type*, indicating that the object was used in combat and allowing the identification of the precise *UXO Type*. The object's *Charge Type* was TNT, which led to ordinary values for *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* and *Relative Effectiveness*. The fuse was a specific Wurfgranatenzünder (mortar fuse) (Wgr. Zdr.) 36, which detonated upon impact. It did not have any remarkable features, such as a cocked striker or a chemical long delay function. The environmental conditions at the EOD location were not remarkable.

$$P = 3.9 \text{ (medium); } C = 3.8 \text{ (very low); } E = 2.2 \text{ (low)}$$

Due to its small *Charge Mass* and the sufficient *Water Depth* RUMMs calculates a very low risk C . For P , on the other hand, it produces a medium risk value. This is a regularly occurring risk level for UXO objects with a primed fuse. Despite the fuse, E is low due to the environmental conditions. Particularly, the *Current Velocity* (0.30 m s^{-1}) and *Visual Range Under Water* (6.3 m) prevent a higher E value. This object was first subject to *underwater transfer* and subsequent *in situ destruction*. This demonstrates that UXO with a medium-level P value can, in some cases, be detonated in situ. Object 11 has a slightly higher $P = 4.1$ and was recovered. Hence, it is not possible to determine a definite value at which *in situ destruction* becomes mandatory.

Object 16—GP 500 lbs bomb (US American)

Object 16 was identified as an American general purpose (GP) 500 lbs bomb [393]. The image in Figure 6.10 does not allow identifying which *UXO Type* exactly was found. Accordingly, the data in Table 6.5 represent a conservative worst-case scenario for the RA.

Unless otherwise indicated in the table, all data for UXO factors concern the model AN-M64A1, as it had the highest values for *Charge Mass* (125 kg), *UXO Mass* (243 kg) and its *Charge Type* Composition B had the highest *Relative Effectiveness* (1.35). Object 16 could be equipped with several types of different fuses, so another worst-case scenario was assumed for the *Fuse Type*. This resulted in the highest value for the *Fuse Properties* count (8) of all investigated UXO.

$$P = 5.9 \text{ (high); } C = 7.3 \text{ (medium); } E = 4.3 \text{ (medium)}$$

The model outputs for object 16 are among the highest of the objects that were assessed during the application of the confirmed layout. P is a high risk value (approaching very high risk) and is mainly driven by the high number of *Fuse Properties*. Accordingly, if it could be verified that the object was another *UXO Type* or was equipped with another *Fuse Type* this would reduce the *Fuse Properties* value and, thus, P . RUMMs calculates a medium risk E value, despite the complex situation regarding the fuse. Most of the other parents of E do not have any remarkable values that would drive it up, thereby counterbalancing the *Fuse Properties*. Finally, object 16 has a medium risk value for C . It had the second-largest *Charge Mass* of the objects 11 through 20. This value is still dwarfed by the charges of, e.g., objects 3 and 4, which result in significantly higher C values. The object was subject to an *in situ destruction* process. This shows the significance of RUMMs' model outputs. For a UXO object with a high P it is advisable not to perform *recovery* or *underwater transfer*.

Object 17—Part of an INC 30 LB incendiary bomb (British)

Object 17 was a part of a British incendiary bomb of the type INC 30 LB (German designation) [397] or I.B. 30 lb. (American designation) [113]. A look at the image in Figure 6.10 reveals that this UXO object had likely been used in combat and that it burst open and released its incendiary payload, which was indicated by the black colour. Independently of whether the payload was released, this *UXO Type* did not contain any explosive material, neither in the main charge nor in the fuse. Since it seemed to have functioned as designed, it can also be assumed that no fuse was present. If a fuse was present, the *Fuse Types* that were used in this *UXO Type* contained very small amounts of black powder [398], which is an explosive material [130]. This object is, in several ways, not ideal for an assessment with RUMMs. Firstly, the fact that neither a fuse nor any explosive material were present contradicted the lower boundary of the factor *Charge Mass*, $m_u^{min} = 1$ kg. Consequentially, the *Impact Sensitivity Base Value* and *Relative Effectiveness* violated their lower boundaries ($I_b^{min} = 1$ N m) and $RE^{min} = 0.50$) as well. Secondly, if any incendiary material was left in the object, RUMMs was not prepared to assess the risk for this situation as this scenario was not investigated throughout this dissertation. All of the environmental data were automatically determined by RUMMs based on the EOD location.

$$P = 0.0 \text{ (very low); } C = 0.0 \text{ (very low); } E = 1.7 \text{ (very low)}$$

Given the violation of the value ranges of multiple factors, it was decided that RUMMs should output 0.0 for C and P , if $m_u = 0$ kg and $FT = \text{'none'}$. This reflects the fact that no detonation was possible with no fuse or explosive charge present. The model output E is exclusively determined by the environmental factors. Due to the calm working environment, it is a very low value. If the environmental conditions were particularly uninviting (i.e., all environmental factors would lead to normalised values of 10), then $E = 5.7$. This would be a value at the very high risk level. This demonstrates that RUMMs can be used to evaluate the risk of EOD activities, even if only parts of UXO are recovered or the process of *debris removal* takes place. It must be reiterated that if there was any doubt about whether incendiary material was left in the UXO object, RUMMS would not produce reliable results and should not be used.

Object 18—UMA moored mine (German)

Object 18 was reported to be a German moored mine of the type U-Bootmine (submarine mine) A (UMA). Since no images of the cleared object were available, it cannot be shown here. Instead, Figure 6.10 shows a depiction from a historic document. Since no image was available, the *Casing Condition* of 0 was predicted by using the planning layout. For this purpose, the *Original Casing Thickness* (4.5 mm) [374] and the *Corrosion Rate - Unburied* for the North Sea (0.83 mm a^{-1}) were entered. If the *Casing Condition* was this poor, it would not have been impossible to identify the *UXO Type*. Hence, in reality, the object was likely in a better state. The *Main Charge Type* was block-fitted hexanite, for which no parameters could be found in the literature. The *UXO Mass* of 160 kg differs considerably when compared to the values in the literature (50 kg for the mine or 277 kg for the mine with its anchor). [372] The value in the EOD dataset was considered most reliable and was, thus, entered in RUMMs. A UMA mine is equipped with five chemical horns and three switch horns [374]. However, due to the expected poor condition, a *Fuse Corrosion State* of 0% was expected, so the ignition chain was assumed to be interrupted. Similar to objects 12 and 13, this object was handled at the Minsener Oog dump site. This means that, similar to objects 3, 4, and 5, it is unlikely that the mine had been fused and laid but rather that it had been dumped. The location is an indicator that the *Visual Range Under Water* may be overestimated (see objects 12 and 13).

$$P = 1.6 \text{ (low); } C = 6.0 \text{ (medium); } E = 2.9 \text{ (medium)}$$

The model output C (medium risk) can be considered reliable since its parent factors *Water Depth* and *Shock Factor* were not associated with high uncertainty. The other two model outputs are strongly driven by the *Fuse Properties* and *Fuse Corrosion State*. The fact that no image was available required making a prediction based on *Original Casing Thickness* and *Corrosion Rate - Unburied*. This leads to a low risk P and a medium risk E . If the fuse was not fully corroded but in poor condition (i.e., *Fuse Corrosion State* of 20%), the values would be $P = 6.8$ (very high risk) and $E = 4.6$ (high risk range). The fact that the process *underwater transfer* was executed may indicate that the same

considerations may have played a role during EOD. *in situ destruction* was avoided since it was likely unnecessary, but *recovery* aboard the EOD vessel was possibly considered to be associated with too much uncertainty.

Object 19—BMC moored mine (German)

Object 19 was a BMC, which is a technical successor to object 3, if it was a BMA [372]. Even though it was a different *UXO Type* than object 18, there were numerous similarities between the two objects. Again, no image was available, so the *Casing Condition* of 0 could only be estimated. Even though the object was found with its anchor, it was likely dumped, which means that it had not been fused and had never been used in operation. Again, the *Main Charge Type* was hexanite. Other factors, such as *Charge Mass* (54 kg), *UXO Longest Dimension* (1450 mm), and especially *UXO Mass* (500 kg) are considerably larger than for object 18. Environmental conditions are identical between both objects since they were located in the same area and handled during the same season.

$$P = 1.8 \text{ (low)}; C = 6.5 \text{ (medium)}; E = 3.2 \text{ (medium)}$$

Due to the similar input values of objects 18 and 19, the model outputs are at the same risk levels. RUMMs calculates slightly higher model outputs for this object. The increase in *E* is driven by the higher *Charge Mass* and *UXO Longest Dimension*. Therefore, *P* (which is a child of *E*) also displays a larger value. The higher *C* is an effect of the greater *Charge Mass*. This object was also subject to *underwater transfer*.

Object 20—Ground mine Mk I-IV (British)

Object 20 was a British ground mine for which the precise *UXO Type* was not reported. It could have been Mk I, II, III, or IV, which were very similar [310, 375]. It originated from the same series as object 6 (Mk V). Information on object 6 was scarce and relied heavily on data from other objects in this series of ground mines. Accordingly, objects 6 and 20 have similar properties, which is reflected in their *Main Charge Type*, *Fuse Type*, and their child factors. Obviously, confidence in these input data is higher for object 20. No photo was available for this EOD operation, and the *Original Casing Thickness* of this object was determined from a photograph of an Mk IV. Since the object was buried before it was cleared, the expected *Casing Condition* was calculated by using the estimated *Original Casing Thickness* and the *Corrosion Rate - Buried* in the North Sea.

$$P = 5.3 \text{ (high)}; C = 8.8 \text{ (high)}; E = 4.9 \text{ (high)}$$

Among the objects that were used to apply the confirmed layout, object 20 has the highest *C* value. This is not surprising when considering its large *Charge Mass* (344 kg), which is very close to the upper value boundary $m_c^{max} = (350 \text{ kg})$, and the high *Relative Effectiveness* (1.45). The resulting *Shock Factor* cannot be counterbalanced by the greatest *Water Depth* value among all objects. RUMMs furthermore calculates a high risk *P*, which is only surpassed by object 6 (i.e., the ground mine Mk V). *P* is this high because 4 out of the 8 *Fuse Properties* apply and because the *Casing Condition* accounts for a rather poor

Fuse Corrosion State (60%). Finally, object 20 has a high risk E , which is the highest value among all investigated objects. The main drivers are the challenging *Fuse Corrosion State*, a poor expected *Casing Condition* (3), the *UXO Longest Dimension* (3000 mm), and the *Significant Wave Height* (2.0 m). Given these model outputs, the fact that the EOD process *in situ destruction* was executed comes as no surprise.

Results of the Confirmed Layout

Figure 6.11 shows the results of the application of the confirmed layout as a bar chart. On the y-axis, it lists the individual UXO objects that were assessed. On the x-axis, it displays their P , C , and E values as calculated by RUMMs.

For C , RUMMs produced a completely different distribution of values than what was observed during the application of the planning model. This time, five objects have a very low risk, one has a low risk, and three have a medium risk C value. Only object 20 is at the high risk level. While the *Water Depth* values are in a similar range for objects 1 through 20, the *Charge Masses* are in general considerably lower for this sample. Even though C values differ greatly from the planning layout, the output distribution is again not in line with the results of the MCS. This can be explained by the fact that the distribution of MCS input data for the *Charge Mass* corresponded neither to the distribution of real-world EOD data (see 2.2.7), nor to objects 11 through 20. A greater sample of real world objects would need to be assessed both with the planning and confirmed layouts. It may then be necessary to revisit the MCS and correct the risk levels for C . At this point, it is too early for adaptations. It happens that the great group of objects with a *Charge Mass* ranging from 80 kg to 200 kg that exist in reality (see Figure 2.6) is only represented by object 16. This group would likely return medium risk C values.

6.4 Revision of the Gap Analysis

The model output P is distributed more evenly than it was for the planning layout. Object 17 had no fuse and, thus, presents very low risk during EOD. Four objects show low risk, three medium risk, and two high risk. This means that none of the 20 objects had a very high risk value for P . Similar to the sample to which the planning layout was applied, there is again a high number of objects for which no fuse is expected (in this case, five). These tend to end up at the very low and low risk levels, thereby skewing the sample into these regions. The distribution of P fits the outcome of the MCS with its bimodal distribution (see Figures 6.5 and 6.6). The issue with the *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* that was described in the results section of 6.3.1 remains and was observed again for the confirmed layout. Note that objects with a high risk P value were always subject to the process *in situ destruction*, which means that RUMMs' model outputs are in line with real-world decision-making. However, object 15, to which the same EOD process was applied, has a medium P . *Recovery* was performed for other objects with similar values. This is a hint that EOD decision-making when handling objects with medium P values must be particularly diligent and should be rationalised carefully.

FIGURE 6.11: Model outputs of the application of the confirmed layout.

The results for the model output E are distributed more narrowly. They range from 1.7 to 4.9. Values are similar to the planning layout but are slightly more spread out. Among the objects, there are one with a very low risk, three with a low risk, five with a medium risk, and one with a high risk E . Most of the objects are rather lightweight and small. The combination with environmental conditions that were usually not particularly challenging prevents E values from reaching the high or even very high level. The reader is reminded that for numerous objects, *Visual Range Under Water* was likely overestimated by RUMMs through the nearest neighbour search (see 5.7.29). Once more, this demonstrates that reliable on-site data should be acquired prior to the EOD operation whenever possible so that they can be entered in RUMMs and produce the best possible model outputs. The nearest neighbour method relies on measurement stations and should only be regarded as a fallback option—particularly when using the confirmed layout.

With RUMMs in place, explored, and applied, it is possible to look back at the gaps that were identified in 4.3.8 which existed before this study was conducted. Before model development, two gaps had been identified.

Methodological Gap: A quantitative RA tool that enables applied decision-making on a small spatial and a short-term temporal scale that focuses more on the probability component of risk than on the consequence component.

EOD Workflow Gap: An RA tool that allows determining the risk for the key processes before making an EOD decision.

It is now possible to test, whether the gaps were closed. The following two subsections qualitatively investigate if and how RUMMs succeeds in fulfilling this task. They also explore additional functions of RUMMs that had not been identified as original model requirements.

6.4.1 Closing the Methodological Gap

The RCs that were developed were based on the literature review in 4.2.1. These were used to identify the methodological gap in EOD RA. The graphical representation of the required EOD RA methodology's profile of the new method resulted in the characteristic shape as shown in Figure 6.12 as a reminder. With the comprehensive description of RUMMs and the experience that was collected during its exploration and application in mind, each of the five RCs can be revisited to confirm whether the model fulfils the requirements.

RC1 - Study Type: Due to the lack of accident data, it was assumed from the beginning that no fully quantitative RA would be possible for EOD activities. The amount of numerical data for the relevant UXO and environmental properties that needed to be incorporated into RUMMs turned out to be larger than expected. It was always possible to develop a quantitative approach to incorporate them into the model. Still, the data foundation for some factors turned out to be far from satisfying, and workarounds had to be developed that introduced uncertainties into RUMMs (e.g., for *Sediment Accumulation Rate* or *Impact Sensitivity*). Due to the higher level of complexity and the greater number of factors, the planning layout is more likely to be impacted by these uncertainties. The user is advised to diligently research numerical values for factors whenever possible and to enter conservative values as inputs to avoid underestimating risk. As predicted, experts had to be involved to support the model set-up with a semi-quantitative rating that was obtained during EOD RA Workshops. Expert input was necessary to transform and converge quantitative input factors into the three model outputs. Since the data are processed via normalisation and weighting steps, the model outputs are not strictly quantitative. *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* is not issued as a percentage, and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* is not expressed as lives lost or a monetary value. RUMMs is therefore not *purely quantitative* but *rather quantitative* (see Table 4.1). Hence, the previously defined requirement for the model is met.

RC2 - Level of Decision Making: As discussed in the paragraph on RC5 (see below), RUMMs can be applied at any point in time before the decision on the execution of the three key processes *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery* is taken. The confirmed layout relies on the availability of first-hand on-site information on the UXO and its immediate surroundings, which is ideally gathered immediately before the key processes commence. The use of the planning layout is more flexible. It uses averaged values for many environmental conditions and predicts factors such as the *Condition of Casing* and *Fuse Corrosion State* before visual investigations are available. This allows the planning layout to be used throughout the EOD procedure to support multiple processes and, therefore, levels of decision-making. Some of these options are outlined in 6.4.2. In summary, the requirement of providing a model for applied decision-making for *object handling* is met by the confirmed layout.

RC3 - Risk Assessment Component: Due to the high expected consequences of detonations, the primary goal of EOD is to deal with UXO while avoiding undesired detonations. The decision-making process is thereby inherently more focused on the probability component of risk than the consequence component. While the RUMMs model output *Probability of an Undesired Detonation (P)* does not have higher validity than the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation (C)*, both model layouts demonstrate a certain focus on probability. *P* has four input factors in both model layouts, while *C* has only two. More importantly, the *Complexity of the EOD Operation (E)* with its many inputs is, in turn, an input to *P*, demonstrating that the overall model set-up is focused on probability. The model results for *P* and *E* can also be utilised when assessing the risk for subjects of protection other than the risk receptors that are the scope of RUMMs (see 5.5). The *C* value of RUMMs can only be applied to the personnel and equipment at the EOD site. The definition of other risk receptors and refinement of *C* hold great potential for the future extension of the model. This will require the incorporation of concepts such as resistance and resilience of the risk receptors into the model (see 6.5.1). While *P* helps determine, which steps to take (i.e., whether to perform *in situ destruction* or *recovery*), the current incorporation of *C* into the model still offers a basis for the decision of which methods to use during the key processes (e.g., whether to deploy a crawler or a comparatively less valuable ROV). Therefore, the requirement of developing an EOD RA that is *mainly probability* focused is met.

RC4 - Spatial Scale: The focus on the risk receptors on site enabled the development of an EOD RA that is very spatially focused. It was not necessary to consider the extent of the shock and sound waves over large distances. The confirmed layout relies on first-hand on-site information as inputs. Once the user can obtain the required information from the EOD location, RUMMs is a model that focuses solely on the UXO object and its immediate environment. For the use of the planning layout, the degree to which the model represents spatial information depends on the user's ability to obtain detailed information on environmental factors. The release version of RUMMs heavily relies on the measurement stations for environmental properties that were introduced in 3.4. The maps in, for example, Figures 3.8 and 3.12 show that information on *Significant Wave Height*, and *Visual Range Under Water* is on a rather large spatial scale when relying on the lookup function of the model. Overall, the requirement of developing an RA with a small spatial scale is met, but it depends on the quality of the input data, provided by the user.

RC5 - Temporal Scale: The *undesired detonation* may materialise in an extremely short time frame and would lead to very immediate consequences. The confirmed layout of RUMMs was designed to be applicable right before executing either of the key processes by incorporating the most up-to-date information on UXO and environmental properties. Thus, it meets the requirements for the temporal scale that were defined in 4.2.2. The planning layout, on the other hand, relies on a higher number of assumptions. It is therefore recommended to use it for the preparation of clearance activities months or weeks in

FIGURE 6.12: Methodological categorisation of RUMMs.

advance (see 6.4.2). The strength of the planning layout lies in its ability to assess EOD risk based on limited information, but it does not fulfil the initial requirements for a very short-term temporal scale.

In summary, RUMMs meets the requirements for all five RCs as defined in 4.2.2, when the confirmed layout is utilised. The fulfilment of two of these requirements (RC4 and RC5) can be compromised when faulty or uncertain data are entered as the model input. When environmental data are not timely or originate from the EOD site, the model output will not be on a small local scale or a short-term temporal scale. For the other RCs, the model design prevents failure to meet the requirements. The planning framework meets the requirements for RC1, RC2, and RC3, but not for RC4 and RC5. As the next subsection demonstrates, this does not mean that it should be abandoned or that it cannot support the EOD procedure.

6.4.2 Implementing the Model into the EOD Framework

The second gap that was identified was the EOD workflow gap. It concerned the fact that no RA method existed that addressed the three key processes *underwater transfer*, *in situ destruction*, and *recovery*. RUMMs fills this gap, and due to the existence of the two different model layouts, performing RA is possible throughout the EOD workflow. The areas of application for the two model layouts are described below.

The Planning Layout

As the name suggests, the planning layout was developed to perform RA at earlier stages of the EOD workflow to inform decision-making for later processes. Theoretically, it is possible to use this layout at any stage. In practice, two processes lend themselves to its application. These are the *threat assessment* in phase I and the *creation of the final report on the technical survey*, during which the threat assessment should be updated, in phase II. These two processes are ideal for the use of the planning layout of RUMMs for two reasons. Firstly, they produce outputs that are based on a great amount of data that were collected during preceding processes. Secondly, these reports are among the most important inputs for the beginning of the consecutive phases (i.e., phases II and III, respectively). In contrast to the confirmed layout, the planning version enables the user to perform RA without having immediate access to the object. It predicts certain child factors based on environmental parent factors. This is useful since it makes RA at earlier stages of the EOD workflow possible. If a given region in the study area is supposed to be cleared of UXO, the EOD risk in this region can be assessed well before operations take place. Naturally, the less immediate the input data, the higher the uncertainty of the model output. To exemplify: for the planning layout, the *Casing Condition* is calculated by using *Original Casing Thickness*, *Casing Material*, *Time Buried*, *Time Unburied*, and *Corrosion Rate*. For the confirmed layout, the same factor is determined visually during the process *UXO identification*. Naturally, the latter will be a more reliable assessment. The planning layout is therefore considered to produce less precise results when compared to the confirmed layout. Nonetheless, the MCS demonstrated that typical model output values lie in the same value range for both model layouts (see 6.2.3).

When applied during the *threat assessment*, the planning layout relies on data that were collected during phase I during the processes *documentation of the site conditions* and *historical survey*. These processes should be used to research the environmental and UXO factors that are required as model input. In terms of environmental factors, users may rely on the lookup tables that are integrated into the model (e.g., for the seasonally and geographically dependent representative values of *Current Velocity* and *Wind Speed*). Depending on the size of the area under investigation, it may be appropriate to run the model with a range of values for different factors (e.g., along a cable trajectory, *Water Depth* and other environmental factors may vary significantly). Users may also enter their own data for these factors as instructed in the blue hints that are given throughout 5.7. For information on UXO, the *historical survey* is expected to produce a list of *UXO Types* that must be expected in an area of interest. Accordingly, running the model and performing an RA for a variety of different UXO would be possible. Using the planning layout at this stage gives a first impression of EOD risk. In the case of very high EOD risk, this may act as an early-stage termination criterion for further engaging in an offshore development project in an area. It may also be considered a prompt for the relocation of the project to an area with lower EOD risk. In addition, using RUMMs may help determine the reference object for the *technical survey* in phase II. It is the smallest object that is required to be found

during the survey. That means that the survey will be designed in such a way that objects that are smaller and have a lower iron mass may remain undetected. It is an effort that requires balancing the chance of not detecting certain objects, the physical limitations of the commonly used survey methods (i.e., usually multi-beam echosounder (MBES), side-scan sonar (SSS), and towed magnetics), and the financial boundaries of the offshore project. [25] Failing to detect objects may pose a risk for the utilisation of an area after EOD has been completed. The *Probability of an Undesired Detonation (P)* and *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation (C)* values that were calculated for numerous *UXO Types* that must be expected in an area may help determine the reference object. Note that in this case, no EOD RA as defined by the in the gap analysis is performed. The results should therefore be treated with caution.

It is also possible to use the planning layout to run an MCS similar to the one presented in 6.2. However, instead of covering the entire value range, all input factors should be limited to the value range that is supported by information from the *documentation of the site conditions* and the *historical survey*. The distribution of the input data may be uniform or it may be arranged depending on how often certain types of UXO are expected to be present in the area of interest. This way, a risk distribution can be calculated for the three model outputs. This approach is not further investigated here but is an interesting prospect to further explore the possibilities of RUMMs in the future.

When using the planning layout during the *creation of the final report on the technical survey* at the end of phase II, it can rely on information that was acquired during the *survey process* and the subsequent *data processing* and *data interpretation*. These insights are added to the previously available information from the *documentation of the site conditions* and *historical survey* or they replace them. The principle output of the *data interpretation* process is a so-called ‘target list’, which is a register of all potential UXO objects in the surveyed area. Based on the information in this target list it might be possible to narrow down the types of objects that are expected to be located in the area. While MBES and SSS data can be used to measure the size of objects, magnetic data can be consulted to estimate their iron mass and *Burial State*. Another vital piece of information that is collected during the *survey process* is the *Water Depth* for any given location in an area. Other data, such as *Current Velocity* and *Sediment Type*, can be acquired as well, even though this is not part of a regular UXO survey [23]. It would be possible to perform a conservative worst-case RA for each object on the target list. Since EOD companies report that up to 94% of treated objects during EOD campaigns are not UXO but other objects [104], this can be considered inefficient. It is therefore recommended to check whether objects on the target list align with the findings from the *historical survey*. Based on these findings, RUMMs’ planning layout can be run to assess those target points for which the presence of UXO is considered most likely. If it is not possible to determine such a likelihood, random sampling among target points may be performed to produce a representative picture of EOD risk in the surveyed area.

The results of the planning layout can be used to inform phase III (*investigation of target points*) of the EOD workflow. Very high model output values for specific target points may be used as a rationale to argue for the avoidance of the point in subsequent construction. To do so, e.g., offshore installations could be limited to areas beyond a safety distance from a target point [46], when their clearance is considered too risky or costly. RUMMs offers a way to define a threshold value for EOD risk to justify such a decision, even before an investigation takes place. Furthermore, the planning layout outputs can be used to plan the EOD work for phases III and IV. The *Complexity of the EOD Operation (E)* lends itself to the assessment of potential costs. High *E* can be expected to be connected to high efforts and costs. Due to the high level of uncertainty that exists up to the point at which an object has been identified, *E* can be a new approach to estimating effort at an early stage, when uncertainty is great. Currently, it is not possible to demonstrate this application of the model as it would require analysing multiple past EOD projects and drawing conclusions for costs and efforts. The model output *P* can be used to select equipment and methods for the EOD operation. The higher *P*, the less advisable is the use of divers during the operation. It also indicates that special caution should be taken during the *object uncovering* process until the object has been identified and the confirmed layout can be used for a more precise assessment. Higher *P* also indicates that the potential need for an *in situ destruction* is greater. This way, the required resources may be allocated well in advance of the final decision to perform a detonation. Furthermore, a high value for *C* indicates that larger safety distances are required. Finally, only a minimum amount of personnel and equipment should be close to the target point for the shortest possible time since an undesired detonation is bound to have fatal consequences.

The Confirmed Layout

The confirmed layout was designed as the more immediate way of performing RA with RUMMs. While the layout offers some comfort functions, such as determining environmental factors from the *Location* of the EOD operation, the user is urged throughout 5.7 to acquire as much up-to-date information as possible from the EOD site. Other factors that are required as model input, such as *Charge Mass*, *UXO Longest Dimension*, *Condition of Casing*, and *Condition of Fuse* are not calculated by the model but must be acquired by the user. This is only possible with confidence once the process *UXO identification* of phase IV of the EOD framework has been performed thoroughly. The EOD workflow suggests that the decision on the treatment of UXO, i.e., which, if any, of the three key processes should be performed, should be the final step of the *UXO identification*. Accordingly, it is recommended to integrate the use of the confirmed layout into this process.

It must be mentioned that the use of RUMMs does not replace an independent assessment of a technical supervisor for EOD who holds a certificate of competence per § 20 SprengG. It is the responsibility of this person to decide on the treatment of the UXO object (see 3.2.4). RUMMs cannot replace the years of experience and the human intuition of an expert. It is a support tool for decision-making during EOD. The benefit of RUMMs lies in the fact that it provides the same RA values for a given set of input

values independently of experience, professional background, personal mood, fatigue, time pressure, and even cultural background [399] (which influences the willingness of a person to accept risk). This is why it is recommended that the technical supervisor perform their own RA without RUMMs and then compare their personal assessment to the model output. This means that experience in interpreting the model results is required. To this end, the exploration of the model in 6.1 and 6.2, as well as the descriptions in 6.3 provide initial insight for the inexperienced user. The personal assessment by the expert must not be methodologically rigorous, but they should be able to argue why they assess risk to be at a certain level. It is recommended that if the assessments of RUMMs and the expert deviate from each other, the expert should either reassess or, if they believe their assessment to be superior to that of RUMMs, argue in writing why that is the case. This justification should make use of the factors in the model.

The confirmed layout enables the user to assess which factors need to change to lower the value for the *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E). Waiting for better environmental conditions might lead to a more favourable (i.e., lower) E value, which may allow different handling of a UXO object (or allow handling at all). The user can enter the current environmental conditions as input factors and change environmental factors to see under which conditions E drops to a desired value. The other two model outputs are rather independent of environmental factors, but it is possible to reassess a scenario of an object after a disarming procedure has taken place. This would be expected to lower both E and the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* (P).

6.5 The Future of RUMMs

Chapter 6 is dedicated to the exploration and application of RUMMs. It is commonplace to delve into future research in the concluding chapter of a scientific thesis. Such recommendations are given in Chapter 7. The purpose of this section, on the other hand, is to explain how RUMMs can be adapted on a more technical level in the short-term future.

6.5.1 Expanding and Changing RUMMs

To understand how RUMMs can be expanded or changed, it is worth revisiting the basic EOD RA Model (Figure 6.13) that was first presented in 5.1. RUMMs can be expanded and changed to the left or to the right of undesired event (UE). It is also possible that UE itself is changed or that the scope of the model is adapted.

There are various possibilities to expand RUMMs by including additional factors to the left of UE. Some obvious choices would be the omitted factors that are described in 5.8. The ones that could be implemented are friction sensitivity, heat sensitivity, and the indication of other UXO in the vicinity. Data on friction sensitivity and heat sensitivity are sparse, and additional research for the most common *Charge Types* would have to be conducted to allow their inclusion in the model. The inclusion of the indication of other UXO in the vicinity might be possible after a review of the literature on sympathetic detonations. Another potential way to extend RUMMs is through the discovery of factors

that were previously not considered. Much experience will likely be gathered during upcoming EOD campaigns during offshore development and proactive clearance of dump sites in Germany. Together with insights from future research on UXO, new factors that may be worth integrating into RUMMs could be discovered. Finally, subdividing existing factors into more precise ones would be another option. *Charge Mass* in RUMMs includes not only the main charge but also the weight of the primary and booster charges as well as propellants (see 5.7.18). Each of these materials has its own properties, namely, *Relative Effectiveness* and *Impact Sensitivity Base Value*. Being able to assess them individually would be informative and improve the significance of model outputs.

The potential to expand the model is even greater to the right of UE. Changing the risk receptors is possible but has many implications. Some risk receptors that would be worth investigating are listed below.

- Other vessels than the EOD vessel at the surface.
- Individuals or the population of a species of interest, such as the harbour porpoise.
- Sectors of the maritime economy, such as fisheries, shipping, and tourism.

It is important to understand that the spatial and temporal immediacy of the current risk receptor *personnel and equipment at the EOD site* would be removed. Accordingly, model changes would be expected for the calculation of the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation*. It would be necessary to implement the distance to the site of UE. For the shipping sector, it would require knowledge of the density of vessel traffic and, for the harbour porpoise population, migration and calving behaviour. Therefore, not only the *Probability of an Undesired Detonation* would be investigated but also the probability that the materialisation of UE has adverse effects on the risk receptors. It might be possible to produce a probability distribution of the *Consequence of an Undesired Detonation* for different scenarios. Furthermore, the risk receptors' resilience would need to be included if the investigation of longer-term consequences was the aim of the RA. The model would still be a tool to assess EOD risk, not UXO risk. Therefore, risk mitigation measures such as the establishment of safety distances around the EOD site would need to be considered. The inclusion of other risk receptors requires a reassessment of model outputs, as done via the local sensitivity analysis (see 6.1) and the MCS (see 6.2).

It would also be possible to assess another UE altogether. Subsection 5.3.1 presented the release of UXO compounds as an alternative UE to be placed at the centre of the RA. This would most certainly entail a change in the risk receptors since the leakage of such compounds likely does not pose a risk to EOD personnel and equipment. Instead, populations of fish or other marine biota could be risk receptors under investigation. Seafood consumers would be another option. The pathway from the materialisation of UE to the occurrence of consequences (i.e., health effects, see 2.3.2) is quite complex, and toxicological studies need to be consulted to understand the causality between UXO compound spread, fate, and health effects at different endpoints. Changing UE would also require adaptations on the left side of the model. Properties such as solubility would need

FIGURE 6.13: Basic EOD RA model as a bow-tie diagram.

to be included in the model, and other factors, such as *Current Velocity*, would need to be recontextualised to meet the model's requirements. In the end, the RA model would be expected to differ significantly from the release version of RUMMs.

Furthermore, it would be possible to adapt the scope of the model. The background information in Chapter 2 was used to scope the content of this dissertation and, with it, the field of application of RUMMs. The scope could be changed, for example, by assessing CWAs, or extended, for example, by including UXO in wrecks. Doing so would necessitate reassessing UE, the causal picture that may lead up to it, and the risk receptor. It is important to understand that RUMMs, despite constant hints by the author that more data and research on many aspects of UXO is required, rests on a solid basis of academic and grey literature and expert knowledge. Despite a certain level of uncertainty, RUMMs' results can be confidently used to inform the work during the key processes. For CWA or UXO in wrecks, the level of confidence in the results would be reduced significantly since there is very little experience with the management of such objects.

Finally, the current version of RUMMs was designed to assess EOD risk in German waters. Adapting it to other geographic contexts will certainly affect the value ranges of UXO and environmental factors. Other countries will have more benign or harsher environmental conditions. The range of potentially present UXO types will often be smaller, especially if no dumping or less naval combat took place in their waters. It is also possible that readily available data are insufficient to automatically determine environmental factors. In this case, the planning model would require additional adaptation. On the other hand, superior data may exist for other factors (e.g., the *Sediment Accumulation Rate*). Changes in threshold values will change the results of the normalisation when factors are converged to model outputs. While the results of the local sensitivity analysis are expected to stay very similar, the distributions produced by the MCS may vary more significantly. This is not problematic as long as the model outputs that were produced for different countries are not compared with each other. To allow for such comparisons, a European version of RUMMs would be required.

6.5.2 Other Options for Adaptations

It might also be worthwhile to subdivide RUMMs into smaller parts to answer specific questions. The *Complexity of the EOD Operation* (E) is a model output that is a rather uncommon result of an RA. It also acts as an input factor to the *Probability of the EOD Operation* and is an integral part of RUMMs even if E was not treated as a model output.

It is possible to be interested in performing UXO RA instead of EOD RA. The aim could be to understand the risk of the presence of UXO at a given location without performing EOD. In this case, E and its exclusive inputs could be removed from the model. A redefinition of the risk receptor would be in order, which is expected to lead to an extension of the model in other areas, as described in 6.5.1.

On the other hand, it is also possible to extract E and its inputs from the model. This way, no RA would be possible, but new opportunities would arise. The research project ‘CONcepts for conventional MARine Munition Remediation in the German North and Baltic Sea’ (CONMAR) prioritises the clearance of UXO piles in contamination hotspots in German waters. The researchers in the project are developing a multi-criteria analysis to do so. The effort that is required for the clearance of such UXO piles is one of the many criteria under investigation. [400] It is challenging to quantify the effort. Since E can be interpreted as a derivative of the required effort to perform the key processes, its integration into the analysis might be useful.

6.6 Conclusion—The Case for Real World Application

Over the course of this dissertation, the issue of UXO was introduced (see Chapter 2), the challenges during EOD were described (see Chapter 3), and the gaps in EOD RA were identified (see Chapter 4). All this led to the development of RUMMs (see Chapter 5), which was explored and tested in Chapter 6. Two methodologies for exploration were used. The local sensitivity analysis helped understand how strongly the model outputs react to changes in model inputs. The other method, the MCS, was used to determine the model outputs’ distribution functions over a total of 9000 model runs. RUMMs was then applied to 20 UXO objects and their EOD operations.

This chapter demonstrates that RUMMs works as intended. Given thorough and diligent research of the model’s input data, it reliably calculates the three model outputs. The local sensitivity analysis informs the user about the impact of model inputs on model outputs. A look at the MCS provides insights into how an assessed UXO object and EOD operation compare to others and, thus, whether a model output’s value must be considered low, medium, or high. The application of the confirmed layout demonstrates that RUMMs’ outputs match the decisions of a professional EOD service provider, which is proof of the reliability of the RA that is performed by the model. The subsequent section revisits the gap analysis of Chapter 4 and concludes that the gaps were closed and, hence, that the objectives of this dissertation were met. Accordingly, the author suggests that the next step be a real-world application, either in preparation of an EOD campaign or during its execution. This is, however, outside the scope of this dissertation and cannot be

discussed here. Instead, the final chapter concludes the work at the current state and offers a look into the possible future of RUMMs in particular and its role in the forthcoming decades of EOD in general.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

After the issues of offshore UXO and EOD were extensively explored, after the wide array of RA methods was reviewed and organised, and after a new model for offshore EOD RA was developed, described, and tested, Chapter 7 concludes this dissertation. On the one hand, it reviews the hypotheses that were stated in Chapter 1. On the other hand, it offers an outlook into the future. This concerns the author's next steps in further developing RUMMs and advocating the model's application during EOD. It also concerns the overall field of UXO and EOD research, an area in which many open questions remain. Some of these were addressed by this dissertation, and some became increasingly apparent as the development and testing of RUMMs progressed. Ultimately, the author addresses the greater picture of German EOD and offers a possible way forward.

7.1 Recap of the Research Hypotheses

This dissertation was initiated with the idea of developing an RA method for EOD. However, instead of simply starting to set up such a model, it was necessary to make three minor hypotheses (H_i , H_{ii} , and H_{iii}) which needed to be tested and accepted to prove that a demand for such an RA method existed. Once this was successfully done, the main hypothesis of this study could be tested as well. This section recaps the content of the dissertation by repeating the individual hypotheses and summarising how the individual chapters contributed to their assessment.

H_i : UXO requires handling by specialists who execute a professional EOD workflow.

Chapter 2 described the issue of offshore UXO in general and of conventional UXO that were submerged in German waters from 1914 to 1949 more specifically. It provided much background information on the matter, much of which was used to scope the study to ensure focused research. In addition, the background information demonstrated the overall complexity of the issue of UXO in the sea. The second half of the chapter focused on UXO properties and their interrelationships. Through this investigation, it was revealed that UXO is not only hazardous in itself and specifically when handled, but also that it is

extremely diverse. Extensive knowledge is without a doubt required when working with UXO. This important observation becomes even more significant when considering the expected increase in EOD activities in the upcoming years. Accordingly, H_i was accepted.

H_{ii} : EOD requires structured RA to understand the risk to which EOD personnel and their equipment are subjected.

Chapter 3 elaborated on the methods that are used to deal with UXO in the sea, a procedure that is referred to as offshore EOD. To ensure focused work in this dissertation, several EOD frameworks were compared, and one was selected as a frame of reference for the remainder of this study. Three key processes of EOD (*underwater transfer, in situ destruction, and recovery*) were identified, which guided all further discussion. The chapter also described how EOD is conducted and which human and technical resources are required. The description demonstrated the great level of complexity of working with UXO. Chapter 3 also stressed the variability and diversity of environmental conditions that pose additional challenges. Ultimately, when considering all the information given in Chapters 2 and 3, it became apparent that an RA of individual EOD operations is necessary before the three key processes can be executed. Hence, H_{ii} was accepted.

H_{iii} : Existing methods are insufficient to assess EOD risk.

Chapter 4 briefly introduced the reader to RA and offered a methodological review in the context of UXO. It clarified that RA is not a one-size-fits-all solution but that a specific methodology that is tailored to the issue at hand is required. Accordingly, the prerequisites for determining EOD risk were specified, and ten existing methods were tested against them by using five review criteria. It turned out that the existing methods neither met these review criteria nor assessed the risk of performing the key processes. Hence, H_{iii} was accepted.

H_M : Structured RA improves the decision-making of specialists during EOD.

With the three minor hypotheses accepted, the main purpose of the dissertation could be tackled. To this end, Chapter 5 was dedicated to the development of an RA model (i.e., RUMMs) that meets the criteria formulated in Chapter 4 and considers the knowledge that was presented in Chapters 2 and 3. A planning layout (34 factors) and a confirmed layout (23 factors) of RUMMs were designed to reflect the gap in information that is filled by the *UXO identification* process. It was also necessary to identify the factors that the model consists of and confirm this with a group of experts. It was necessary to make each of these factors quantifiable and usable in the context of RUMMs. Furthermore, they needed to be converged to meaningful model outputs, which was also done with the support of the same group of experts. Some potentially relevant factors had to be excluded due to a lack of information that would have allowed their meaningful integration into the model or due to a potential loss in model scope.

Next, Chapter 6 explored the model and applied each of its layouts to ten EOD operations. The exploration was a mandatory step since, without it, the model's complexity would have rendered the interpretation of model results impossible. The application to a series of real and potential EOD cases demonstrated how the model can be used to support EOD decision-making. RUMMs produces three outputs that can be used as indicators for this decision, but they do not determine which of the three key processes to execute. This is in line with the notion that decisions during EOD must ultimately be taken by the technical supervisor. An experienced user can use RUMMs to confirm and challenge these decisions. To use RUMMs it is necessary to diligently collect and enter information. This requires a workflow for reliable data acquisition. RUMMs is not limited to information that is commonly used during EOD decision-making. It also includes factors that are relevant for EOD risk but that are thus far not considered in a rigorous manner during the decision-making process. When using the model, a decision will rest on a more solid base of information than without it. Hence, the main research hypothesis (H_M) was accepted.

The hypotheses and the fact that they were accepted and hence proven to be true are the principle messages of this dissertation. They signify the relevance of professional EOD work, the relevance of RA as a means of understanding risk to EOD personnel and equipment, the lack of appropriate methods to perform EOD RA, and, most importantly, the benefits that lie in the development and utilisation of RUMMs as a structured RA method to support EOD decision-making.

7.2 Outlook on RUMMs

The development of RUMMs was executed with great diligence and detailed consideration of the current state of knowledge on UXO and EOD. Nevertheless, a model such as RUMMs is never finished. There always remains room for improvement in the model, its handling, and its application. This section provides an overview of what could be done next to increase the benefits of RUMMs.

The Further Development of RUMMs

Entire sections of this dissertation were dedicated to the description of factors that were not included in RUMMs (see 5.8) and other model limitations (see 5.11) that were identified during its creation. After the initial application of the model, further room for improvement (see 6.3) and other development opportunities for RUMMs (see 6.5) were identified. This section does not repeat these technical and methodological aspects. Instead, it gives a more general outlook on the intentions of the author to further develop and use RUMMs.

Addition of Factors: Some factors that are not included in RUMMs were omitted due to a lack of relevant information and knowledge. Others were left out to avoid further growth in model complexity. The latter group, which involves, inter alia, the presence of

other UXO, could be incorporated after a discussion with experts. Adding new factors would require a poll for their normalisation and weights if they turn out to be parents of the model outputs.

Expert Feedback: While Chapter 6 explored and demonstrated RUMMs, the model has not yet been tested in practice. Gathering feedback from users and experts is an important next step in its rollout. This will enable understanding whether the model functionalities and results interpretation are comprehensible. It may turn out that certain factors are too challenging to research or are not meaningful for the model outputs. This opens the option of deleting factors to reduce model complexity. User feedback will have to be gathered via a structured process that has not yet been designed.

Improve Data: There are two dimensions to the improvement of the data foundation of RUMMs. For some factors, the data that are currently available are incomplete (e.g., *Impact Sensitivity*). The most critical ones are discussed in 7.3. For other factors, data are available and were implemented in RUMMs but could be reviewed for room for improvement. For example, the *Current Velocity* data that RUMMs uses were taken from readily available peer-reviewed flow models. No research on whether these models are the best of their kind was undertaken. The same is true for environmental factors that were modelled based on MUDAB data. Better data for, e.g., *Wind Speed* or *Significant Wave Height* may exist. Finding them and juxtaposing them to the ones that are used in RUMMs requires an additional comparative study.

Improve Weights: Some general criticism on weighting was already voiced in the section on model limitations (see 5.11.9). Weights in RUMMs were generated through an expert involvement process that included discussions and polls. Even though the process that was undertaken applied a mechanism to reduce uncertainty, more sophisticated approaches such as AHP could be used to further improve the weights. The results of different weighting approaches or expert groups could be compared and discussed to obtain the most representative values.

RUMMssoft

In 6.4.2, it became apparent that RUMMs can be used in numerous ways and at different points of the EOD workflow. Even though there are many opportunities for a meaningful application of the model, the degree to which it will be utilised by EOD experts in the commercial or public sector remains to be determined. One way to make RUMMs more accessible is to transform it from its current form as an Excel tool into easy-to-use software (RUMMssoft). There are numerous advantages to such software over the current RUMMs Excel tool.

User interface: Developing software offers the chance to design an intuitive user interface. Instead of the current *Input and Output* tab in the RUMMs Excel tool, it is possible to guide the user with a dialogue, prompting them to enter the relevant data. This way, the likelihood of overlooking a specific input factor or forgetting to update it can be decreased. Functionalities such as automatic unit or coordinate system conversion would allow for easier usability.

Live environmental data: For environmental factors, the RUMMs Excel tool relies on lookup lists and the user's measurements. While spatially and temporally immediate on-site measurements will always be the most precise source of information, it would also be possible to access live or forecast data on factors such as *Current Velocity* and *Wind Speed* from online interfaces.

Connection to UXO database: The current version of RUMMs requires the user to collect data for the UXO factors from the sources at their disposal. An existing UXO database could be integrated. This way, a user could select the *UXO Type* and all information in the integrated database could be accessed automatically. While this information might not always be sufficient to run RUMMs, it would reduce the effort for the user.

Feature integration: There are countless possibilities for additional features that are challenging to implement in Excel. One would be a report that could be generated after running the model, which informs about the reason why the model outputs have turned out the way they have. This could be similar to the descriptions given in 6.3. It would also be possible to allow the user to perform MCS for a specific value range to understand the risk distribution in an area of interest.

Due to these advantages, an alpha version of RUMMssoft is under development at the time of this dissertation's submission. Nonetheless, there are advantages to the current RUMMs Excel tool over a software version. These make the ongoing maintenance of the Excel file viable.

Ease of initial use: The RUMMs Excel tool is very small in size and does not require any installation. It can be opened and utilised immediately without having to understand a user interface. Since essentially anyone knows how to operate Excel, the file does not introduce any entry barrier to the user.

Backend accessibility: Making changes to the backend (i.e., the way the model works) is simple in Excel. It is not necessary to possess skills in software development. This allows easy adaptation and experimentation with the model (as was done by the author throughout the model's development). Therefore, changes in the model as proposed in 6.5.1 are best implemented and tested in the RUMMs Excel tool first to understand what these changes mean for the use of the model.

Other Fields of Application

Working at sea is inherently riskier than performing the same task onshore. This means that especially activities that are already hazardous when performed on land will require special attention when executed offshore. It was already pointed out that RUMMs could be adapted to address CWAs or UXO in wrecks (see 6.5.1).

To further benefit from the methodological insights of this dissertation, it is possible to devise additional models for completely different high-risk offshore activities. As Chapter 1 pointed out, the offshore economy is expected to grow in the near and mid-term future. Dismantling and decommissioning of offshore structures will be required in

unprecedented quantities as offshore wind parks reach their end of life [401]. Experience with carbon capture and storage offshore is limited, and related risk still needs to be better understood [402]. Wrecks carrying heavy oil or other hazardous substances may need to be cleared of their cargo or fuel [403]. These are just some examples of activities that could be assessed by a model that is similar to RUMMs and applies the same principles. In each case, a combination of environmental properties and parameters that are inherent to the subject of work will show a similar degree of interconnectedness to the network of UXO and environmental properties that was the basis of RUMMs. For each of the three activities that were mentioned above, the occurrence of a UE may have immediate and dire consequences for risk receptors such as personnel and equipment in the vicinity. These examples indicate a great potential for transferring the methodological approach of RUMMs to other fields of application.

7.3 Recommendations for UXO and EOD Research

A principle outlook that concerns the further development of RUMMs was that of an improved data foundation for numerous model factors (see 7.2). For some of these, the implementation and utilisation of already existing data could be improved (such as by using live *Current Velocity* or *Wind Speed* predictions for the confirmed layout). For other factors, the data foundation needs to be improved altogether. These factors are *Sediment Accumulation Rate*, *Visual Range Under Water*, *Corrosion Rate*, and *Impact Sensitivity*. Working on these issues would not only benefit RUMMs but also have other applications, both in the field of UXO research and elsewhere. For this reason, this section gives some suggestions for future research on these factors. It also comments on the room for improvement concerning UXO databases.

Section 3.4.1 described the issue of the burial of UXO. RUMMs applies numerous workarounds to use *Sediment Accumulation Rate* to predict *Burial State* and may be considered incomplete in this regard (see 5.7.8 and 5.7.25). For a better understanding of sedimentation, repeated high-resolution and high-quality bathymetric MBES surveys over several years would be required in areas of high interest. Munitions dump sites or proposed areas for offshore development (such as the construction of wind parks) can be considered to be such areas. Similar surveys are already commonplace to monitor the depth of waterways to prevent vessels from running aground [404]. Simultaneous monitoring of other environmental parameters may allow for inferring how they influence sediment accumulation or decumulation. This information may also benefit EOD. In areas with very low or negative sediment accumulation rates, no burial of objects would be expected. It might therefore be possible to perform magnetic measurements further away from the seabed during phase II of the EOD framework. On the other hand, in areas with very high accumulation, time pressure may arise to manage objects that are located on the surface before they are fully buried.

Visibility under water is affected by many factors (see 3.4.6). Sediment properties, water pollution, eutrophication, oxygen, and sunlight availability, as well as current velocity and weather conditions, may need to be considered. Sampling water is among the most common activities during research cruises, and taking additional samples for subsequent lab analysis of the turbidity of near-bottom waters would require very little effort. Conducting lab experiments might prove more time-consuming, but the ability to predict the *Visual Range Under Water* has many potential benefits. In terms of EOD, it could improve the planning of larger-scale operations to avoid times of the year when certain geographic areas suffer from poor visibility. Instead, the affected months could be used to perform technical surveys that do not require visual orientation at the seabed. Other fields of offshore work may benefit as well. Qualified ROV pilots and divers are sought-after specialised personnel. Efficiently using their skills to their full potential is economically recommended. Therefore, forecasting when turbidity is low and visibility under water is high could steer these limited personnel resources towards higher efficiency.

Another factor for which the data foundation should be improved is the *Corrosion Rate*. The description of the issue (see 3.4.2) and of its implementation (see 5.7.15) demonstrated a lack of reliable data. One approach would be to place pieces of historic casing material in the study area, remove them after a given amount of time to investigate corrosion (e.g., by measuring the weight loss), and produce a model for its prediction. However, the relatively short time the metal would be submerged may lead to errors as many of the factors that control corrosion (temperature, salinity, oxygen availability, etc.) fluctuate over longer periods. Instead, the casing of cleared UXO may be investigated after the thermal treatment of the object at a disposal facility is finalised. This method requires knowledge of the *Original Casing Thickness* of the investigated object. Corrosion assessment after thermal treatment may be done by laser scanning [405]. A positive side effect of thermal treatment might be the removal of biofouling. However, it may also lead to a deformation of the casing, which would make corrosion assessment difficult. In summary, both approaches have shortcomings but would likely generate knowledge of the current and predicted corrosion state of UXO. This would not only support RUMMs but also help predict the release of explosive compounds and thus contamination of water, sediment, and biota.

Finally, more solid data on the *Impact Sensitivity* would improve RUMMs results but also the RA of operations such as *storage and transport* and thermal treatment that take place after the key processes. Sampling explosive compounds either in situ or after the *recovery* process enables specialists to measure *Impact Sensitivity*, but also other parameters such as friction sensitivity, heat sensitivity, and relative effectiveness. The composition of the explosive compound should also be tested whenever possible to confirm whether an object contains the expected *Main Charge Type*. For UXO for which *in situ destruction* is necessary, sampling may not be advisable for safety reasons. Hence, UXO types that are often not safe to handle and transport should be sampled whenever risk allows (e.g., when an unfused object of this type is found). To assess British and American UXO, it may be advisable to acquire samples from British and American dump sites.

All of the investigations described above would be especially relevant for dump sites and UXO located therein. Knowledge of the conditions and the state of UXO at these sites would benefit the German immediate action programme. If this effort leads to a continuous clearance of UXO from these highly affected areas, research might benefit the majority of EOD operations in Germany over the next decades. While research on *Sediment Accumulation Rate* could be done independently from the immediate action programme, analysis of the *Visual Range Under Water*, *Corrosion Rate*, and *Impact Sensitivity* should be coupled to it. This would eliminate the need to conduct dedicated sampling and research cruises. Instead, sampling could be implemented into the EOD workflow, i.e., regularly taking water samples during the execution of key processes and continuously probing explosive compounds and casing material that are won before and after thermal treatment, respectively.

Consulting the munitions database of Sprengschule Dresden [310] to inform the data input during the application of both model layouts (see 6.3) proved very useful. At the same time, research in other (usually historic) references was necessary, as not all of the required information could be found in the database. Numerous reasons were identified. Firstly, the database is not targeted at maritime UXO, and secondly, it does not contain all the information that RUMMs requires as inputs, likely since information such as *Original Casing Thickness* is not usually considered relevant during EOD onshore. For some *UXO Types*, information such as the *Fuse Type* was not included; for others, the information from the database contradicted what was found in other references. RUMMs is the first approach to quantitatively assess EOD risk, and thus the idea to quantify specific risk-driving *Fuse Properties* is novel and was not previously required. All of this means that it is very advisable to continuously update the database by performing archival research. On top, providing value ranges instead of single values for factors such as *UXO Mass* and *Charge Mass* or a list of options for the *Charge Type* would be the more representative approach. Ideally, all required data would be thoroughly documented during all future EOD operations in Germany. It could be done in a similar fashion to the EOD dataset that was introduced in 2.2, but tailored more specifically to RUMMs' requirements. Even onshore data could help clear up the picture. The effort would be massive, and the benefits may only become visible after years of collecting and converging data. However, doing so could greatly improve munitions databases and ultimately lead to better and more precise results when using RUMMs. This would also further improve the benefits of connecting a UXO database to RUMMs during the development of RUMMssoft (see 7.2).

7.4 RUMMs' Response to Other Demands

Section 4.3 identified a number of methodological gaps. Closing these was the principle goal of developing RUMMs, which was successfully achieved (see 6.4). In addition, it is possible to assess which other demands in offshore EOD were met as a by-product of this study. Before this dissertation was initiated and while it was being prepared and written, an abundance of expert groups, committees, and roundtables on offshore UXO met and

published minutes, reports, and position papers. These irregularly appearing outputs of such dialogue formats commonly contain recommendations or otherwise outline a vision of the measures that should be taken next.

A commonly voiced demand is that of decision support systems [406]. RUMMs answers this request by providing a very detailed approach to assessing the risk of an ‘undesired detonation’ for ‘personnel and equipment at the EOD site’ during EOD. Another decision support system had already been developed and presented during the project ‘Decision Aid for Marine MunitiONs’ (DAIMON) [22]. Compared to RUMMs it is less specific and operates on a larger scale. It addresses the risk of explosion and corrosion for the risk receptors flora and fauna, shipping, fisheries, infrastructure, tourism, and diving. Based on its assessment, it proposes a way to manage one or numerous UXO objects at a given location. It addresses fewer UXO and environmental properties but focuses more on parameters concerning the risk receptors, such as the intensity of different modes of fishing and traffic density or the biodiversity in an area. [407] Another decision support system was already briefly mentioned in 6.5.2. It is currently under development as part of the research project CONMAR and aims to prioritise UXO piles in contamination hotspots in German waters for clearance. [400] While not yet finalised, it is already known that the risk for numerous receptors will be evaluated and that issues like socio-economic benefits and costs of clearance will be considered as well. Even though some overlap in analysed factors and risk receptors exists, each of the three systems responds to different questions at different levels of decision-making (see 4.2.1), which is why they should be used in a complementary manner.

DAIMON: How should UXO at a given location in the Baltic Sea be managed?

CONMAR: Which piles of dumped UXO in the German Baltic Sea should be prioritised for clearance?

RUMMs: What is the risk of an undesired detonation for personnel and equipment at the EOD site during the key processes?

With these three methods of analysis in place, the call for decision support should be answered to a great degree. Instead of developing additional tools, it is recommended to use the existing ones to identify possible areas of improvement and to collect and provide data that enable their meaningful application. Future calls for new tools and decision frameworks should specify exactly what the respective expert group is expecting them to do and how they would complement the existing decision support systems.

Another demand is the collection and appropriation of relevant data on UXO and relevant environmental parameters [406]. With a look at the omitted factors (see 5.8) and model limitations (see 5.11), this request must be supported. However, the data that are required for RUMMs do not concern the distribution of UXO or the environmental risks of contamination with explosive compounds that are commonly stipulated. Instead, RUMMs requires data on very specific issues (see 7.3). As RUMMs was developed to assess a spatial scale that is limited to UXO and its immediate surroundings, environmental information is required to be highly site-specific. Another type of data that expert groups often request

to be collected are historic information in archives [70, 408, 409]. Similar to the overall demand for data, 7.3 provides more precise suggestions on which historic data should be gathered to aid RUMMs and therefore perform archival research with a purpose.

Over the past years, the call for the execution of clearance campaigns has become more intense [70, 408, 410]. Technological development and environmental concerns about contamination appear to have reached a stage at which proactive management of the issue of offshore UXO has become desirable. This led to the German immediate action programme [14]. While this programme did not exist when this dissertation was initiated, RUMMs arrives just in time to support EOD decision-making during these efforts. If picked up by EOD practitioners, there are many opportunities to better understand the model and to fill some of the data gaps that were mentioned in the previous paragraph.

7.5 RUMMs and the Way Forward in Offshore EOD

Over the course of this dissertation, it has become abundantly clear that offshore EOD has been ongoing as a regular activity and will continue to do so. It is difficult to imagine a future in which no more UXO will be handled. Expertise in EOD will likely never become obsolete. However, the next decades will be a decisive period for EOD. The German immediate action programme focuses on dump sites, while the energy transition requires access to an unprecedented amount of cleared space at sea. More UXO than ever will require handling.

This expected increase in EOD activities may act as a driver for innovation, both in terms of technical equipment and management practises. RUMMs is intended to be a contribution to the latter. EOD experts are highly skilled professionals. Some have decades of experience and have handled hundreds of UXO objects. However, for a high-risk activity, an over-reliance on routine can easily lead to accidents. Every single object must be thoroughly assessed before a decision on the next steps can be taken. RUMMs is not affected by fatigue, repetitiveness, lack of focus, or personal mood. For a given set of input values, it will always produce the same output values. Its results are reproducible and can be reviewed in post to learn from past EOD actions. It must be reiterated that RUMMs cannot take a decision and relieve experts from their responsibility. Even the current surge in machine learning applications will not be able to do this. Instead, the essence of this dissertation is a different one: Structured RA with RUMMs adds a solid additional layer of reliability to every expert's personal assessment and can therefore significantly improve EOD decision-making.

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Appendix 1: Generation of the Selected EOD Framework

The *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* is the EOD framework that was selected for this dissertation's reference (see 3.2). It was developed prior to RUMMs during the project RoBEMM. Next to the guideline's main authors, who moderated the process, the preamble lists 42 cooperating experts who supported its creation. The process of generating the quality guideline is shown in Figure A1 and is subsequently described here. All steps displayed were conducted twice, covering two phases of EOD each. The rationale was to avoid working on all phases simultaneously. This way, it was possible to streamline discussions with experts. Not all experts would be able and willing to contribute to all phases. They could thus choose to participate in either or both strings of activities.

The process was initiated by an extensive literature review that had three goals: (1) To draft a process flow chart, (2) to understand the interrelationships between relevant technical and environmental factors during EOD and (3) to define the required results of the four EOD phases (see sec:eod.procedure). The literature that was used for this purpose consisted of publications by relevant authorities, scientific literature, pre-existing related norms and standards, as well as concepts and reports from real-world EOD projects.

(1) To draft the guideline's process flow chart, a comparative analysis of pre-existing flow charts was conducted. This was executed in a similar but less rigorous fashion than in 3.1. Next to frameworks F2 through F6, additional flow charts covering the treatment of chemical UXO or land-based UXO were included. This type of comparative assessment informed the authors about redundancies and gaps in the pre-existing schemes, so that a more comprehensive flowchart could be deduced. This was the foundation for creating the selected framework F1 (see 3.1.1).

(2) The interrelationships between the relevant technical and environmental factors were initially gathered as a list of over 250 factor dependencies, most of which consisted only of one controlling factor and one controlled factor. Only a few of these dependencies included more factors than these two. There was considerable redundancy in these factor dependencies, which was, however, eliminated by linking them into a comprehensive network of factors. This was the same network that was the same list that was the basis of RUMMs (see 5.2).

(3) Finally, the required results of the different phases were mainly drawn from available reports as well as related norms and standards. A table sorting all items required for final reports of the individual phases, as identified in (1), was developed. This made it possible to define the actions that would be required to answer the reporting requirements.

The results of this literature review were provided to industry experts, who were invited to prepare presentations on different processes along the EOD flow chart. These presentations were given during two workshops. The first workshop focused on what would eventually become *Phase I: Preliminary survey* and *Phase II: Technical survey*, while the second one addressed the content of *Phase III: Investigation of target points* and *Phase IV: Clearance and disposal* (see Figure 3.1). The workshops were structured around

FIGURE A1: Generation of the *Quality Guideline on Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal*

eight and seven presentations, respectively, each of which was followed by a discussion with the workshops' audiences. The first workshop was attended by 50 participants [411] and the second one by 41 participants [412].

The workshops had two goals. Firstly, they further processed the results of the literature review. It was hence possible (1) to add more detail to the EOD framework, (2) to complete the network of relevant technological and environmental factors, and (3) to better understand the required results of each phase in the EOD flow chart. The second goal was to ensure the strong involvement of those stakeholders who would ultimately be affected by the final quality guideline. It was assumed that close cooperation with stakeholders would be of great importance for the recognition and acceptance of the guideline after its publication. [413] Accordingly, all steps that followed the workshops were conducted in close cooperation with representatives of EOD survey and clearance companies, employers, competent authorities, and scientists working in the field.

Following the first workshop, five of those experts, who had given presentations, were interviewed. After the second workshop, four interviews were conducted. Three interviewees were presenters during the second workshop. In addition, one presenter from the first workshop was interviewed for the second time. While it was initially planned to interview every presenter at least once, not all of them were available. The interviews were unstructured and strongly based on the presentations that had been given. Questions focused on gaining additional insights into how the EOD process (1) was conducted by different actors.

Given the knowledge that had been gathered thus far, it was possible to draft a primary version of the quality guideline. This primary version was distributed to stakeholders, who were requested to comment on it. The purpose of this annotation process was to improve the content of the quality guideline by tapping expert knowledge. In addition, it increased the degree to which the document would represent different stakeholders. The document that was drafted after the first workshop and the first round of interviews was sent to 62 stakeholders. In this first annotation period, 17 replies were submitted, which contained a total of 297 comments. This corresponds to a response rate of 27.4%. Since not all of the comments given were fully comprehensible, all respondents were contacted for clarifications. Of the overall number of comments, 176 were accepted, 103 were partially accepted, and only 18 were rejected. [414] Duplicates were not excluded, as all experts received responses to each of their comments. The document was redistributed to experts after the second workshop and the second round of interviews, now covering all four EOD phases. This time, it was therefore possible to comment not only on the content that was covered in the second workshop but also on the amendments that had been made after the first annotation period. For this second annotation period, 108 stakeholders were asked to provide comments, 17 of which responded. The higher number of stakeholders addressed resulted from the increasing

TABLE A1: Processing results of annotation periods

Process	Annotation Period 1		Annotation Period 2	
	Absolute	Relative (%)	Absolute	Relative (%)
Total	297	100.0	205	100.0
Accepted	176	59.3	110	53.7
Partially accepted	103	34.7	41	20.0
Rejected	18	6.0	4	2.0
Unprocessed	0	0.0	50	24.4

attention that the generation of the quality guideline received among experts. The response rate was 15.7%, which was considerably lower than during the first annotation period. This is an indication that the growth in parties who were interested in the generation of the quality guideline did not go along with an increased willingness to support the development. This type of commitment was limited to a core group of experts. During the second annotation period, 205 comments were submitted. Of those, 110 were accepted, 41 were partially accepted, 4 were rejected, and 50 could not be fully processed due to time constraints. [415]

The annotations led to major revisions of the quality guideline. Table A1 summarizes how the comments were processed during both annotation periods. The overall number of comments received was considerably lower during the second annotation period, even though the absolute number of responses received was identical. This indicates that the document was significantly improved after the first annotation period, and thus fewer comments had to be submitted. It is notable that over 50% of the comments from both annotation periods were fully accepted, while an additional 34.7% and 20% of comments were partially accepted. This demonstrates the importance of the annotation process and stakeholder involvement in the development of a quality guideline, which led to a significant improvement of the document. The numbers during the second annotation period might have been even higher if more resources had allowed for the processing of the 50 remaining comments. The result of the processing of the comments was the development of a secondary version of the quality guideline.

The final step was to organise four expert group meetings with the aim of clarifying those aspects of EOD that had remained unclear. Prior to the meetings, the most up-to-date version of the quality guideline was distributed, which meant that the later meetings benefited from the work of previous ones. Two meetings were held after the first annotation period. Four participants attended the first meeting, and seven participants attended the second one [414]. Another two meetings were organized after the second annotation period had commenced and comments had been processed. The third meeting was attended by four experts, and the fourth one by eight [415].

Once these expert group meetings had been conducted, the *Quality Guideline for Offshore Explosive Ordnance Disposal* was completed. The German version was published in 2019 [416] and the English version was released in 2020 [23].

Appendix 2: Version 1 of the EOD RA Model

FIGURE A2: Version 1 of the EOD RA model.

Appendix 3: Minutes of the 1st EOD Risk Workshop

Date: 06.09.2021

Time: 14:00-18:00

Place: GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Düsternbrooker Weg 20, 24105 Kiel

Moderator: Torsten Frey (GEOMAR)

Minutes: Svenja Ehlers (GEOMAR)

TABLE A2: Workshop 1 participants

Name	Abbreviation	Institution
Lisbeth van der Burght	LB	360survey
Alexander Bach	AB	MELUND
Christian Andersen	CA	Ingenieurgesellschaft Geibelhöfe
Frank Seubring	FS	Heinrich Hirdes EOD Services GmbH
Ingo Schories	IS	GEKA mbh
Paul Müller	PM	Fraunhofer ICT
Ryan Prophet	RP	SafeLane Global Limited
Sonja Krawczyk	SK	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bau und Liegenschaften - Leitstelle für Kampfmittelräumung
Uwe Wichert	UW	MELUND

The 1st EOD RA workshop was conducted on September 6, 2021. It was attended by nine experts (see Table A2). Seven of them held a certificate of competence per § 20 SprengG or a similar certificate issued internationally or by the military. Of the other experts, one was invited due to their expertise in EOD risk management and the other due to their expertise in explosive materials. Before the workshop, version 1 of the EOD RA model was distributed to the experts (see Appendix 2). The workshop was opened by an introductory presentation by the author (part 1). Next, experts were split into three groups and were asked to identify both irrelevant and missing factors and comment on the relationships between the factors as displayed in version 1 of the model (part 2). Observations during the group work were noted by the moderator and minute taker. Subsequently, groups presented their findings to all participants (part 3). Minutes of the workshop are shown in Table A3. Each comment is provided with a note by the author. When a comment was accepted, the note explains how the model was adapted. When rejected, the note argues why. The voting results of the workshop are shown in Appendix 4. Factor names in *italics* are identical to the names in the release version of RUMMs. Factor names in single quotation marks were renamed, remodelled, or do not appear in the release version. Finally, experts were invited to vote both on the normalisation of factors to model outputs and on the weightings that should be used during risk calculations (part 4).

TABLE A3: Workshop 1 comments

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 1: Comments after introduction by TF		
FS	Risk-mitigating factors (e.g., LoUs during EOD) are not included in the model. The additional measures are used to reduce the consequences.	Partially accepted: LoUs were introduced for the factors <i>Current Velocity</i> , <i>Significant Wave Height</i> , and <i>Water Depth</i> (see 5.10.1). These have an effect on the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> and thus on the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> .
SK	It would be helpful to have a definition of the risk receptor.	Accepted: The EOD personnel and equipment at the EOD site were defined as the risk receptor (see 5.5).
Part 2: Work session observations (Group 1 - RP, UW, LB)		
RP	Additional factors that might be considered are ‘Burial angle’, ‘Total burial depth’, and ‘Migration status’.	Rejected: For information on the rationale for omitting factors, see 5.8.
TF	The factor <i>Burial State</i> should not go to values of up to 100%. It should be corrected to a lower maximum value (to ensure that the process <i>UXO identification</i> is possible).	Partially accepted: For both model layouts, a value of up to 100% is permissible. Users are informed that high values for the <i>Burial State</i> are considered inappropriate for the confirmed layout (see 5.7.25).
LB	The risk can occur a second time when the dredging or lifting phase cannot be executed immediately. It is possible that objects are uncovered and identified but cannot be cleared immediately.	Rejected: The focus of this dissertation is an RA for conducting the key processes (see 3.2.2) in the immediate future (see 4.2.2). If this is not possible and later clearance is necessary, the RA needs to be repeated immediately before the key processes take place.
TF	‘Reaction speed’ could be a describing factor.	Rejected: The focus of this dissertation is an RA for conducting the key processes in the immediate future.
RP	Sometimes fishing activities have moved UXO objects to other places and were not found when the team got back to the originally detected site.	Rejected: The focus of this dissertation is an RA for conducting the key processes in the immediate future.
UW	There are roughly 40 different types of Schießwolle, which can influence the ‘Charge size’.	Accepted: Experts are asked to follow a conservative approach by assuming the explosive material with the greatest value for <i>Charge Mass</i> if the <i>Main Charge Type</i> is not known for certain (see 5.7.18).

Participant	Comment	Note
UW	When it is unknown whether an object is fused or not, it needs to be assumed that the object is fused. During clearance, the worst-case scenario must be expected.	Accepted: Experts are asked to follow a conservative approach by assuming an object to be fused, if not certainly known (see 5.7.24).
Part 2: Work session observations (Group 2 - PM, AB, FS)		
FS	When an EOD expert is in the planning phase, they do not start to measure the ‘Rate of corrosion’.	Accepted: For the planning layout, a number of literature-based <i>Corrosion Rate</i> values are provided (see 5.7.15). The factor is not included in the confirmed layout.
AB	Maybe the factor ‘Rate of corrosion’ can be changed to ‘State of corrosion’.	Partially accepted: A factor <i>Condition of Casing</i> was introduced. In the planning layout, this factor is a child of the <i>Corrosion Rate</i> (see 5.7.16).
PM	How much time exists until the problem needs to be solved?	Rejected: The focus of this dissertation is an RA for conducting the key processes in the immediate future.
FS	The <i>UXO Type</i> should be double-checked with the historic information.	Rejected: This is not part of the RA itself but needs to happen before populating the confirmed layout with data.
PM	‘Impact sensitivity rate of change (charge)’ and ‘Impact sensitivity rate of change (detonator)’ are not going to be measured when EOD is already planned.	Accepted: These factors were excluded due to the fact that no sufficient data are available that would allow calculating such a rate of change for neither charge (see 5.7.19) nor detonator (see 5.7.24). Alternative approaches were implemented in RUMMs.
FS	There is no time for additional experiments or samples during an EOD process.	Accepted: For this reason, RUMMs was split into the planning layout and the confirmed layout.
Part 2: Work session observations (Group 3 - SK, CA, IS)		
CA	The <i>Original Casing Thickness</i> is related to the ‘Charge size’ (now <i>Charge Mass</i>).	Rejected: This might be true, but there is no correlation between these factors, which made it impossible to implement in RUMMs.
SK	The <i>Burial State</i> is related to the ‘Rate of corrosion’.	Partially accepted: A distinction between <i>Time Buried</i> and <i>Time Unburied</i> was made. Both have an impact on the <i>Corrosion Rate</i> (see 5.7.15).

Participant	Comment	Note
SK	Exemplary model runs (filling the model with existing examples) would be helpful to understand the thresholds for the factors.	Accepted: Such exemplary runs were performed in the MCS after RUMMs was finalised (see 6.2). However, the thresholds were identified by analysing the EOD dataset (see, e.g., 5.7.4).
Part 3: Work session outcomes (Group 1 - RP, UW, LB)		
Group 1	'Rate of Corrosion' affects 'Casing condition', 'Condition of ignition chain', and charge.	Partially accepted: The <i>Corrosion Rate</i> affects the <i>Condition of Casing</i> and the <i>Fuse Corrosion State</i> but not immediately the charge.
Group 1	<i>Time Unburied</i> is a vague and flexible factor that might vary. Sediment types and storms as migration factors influence the corrosion as well.	Rejected: The statement is true, but the assumptions in RUMMs are explained in detail in 5.7.8.
TF	It would be possible to assume that UXO is buried in the North Sea and unburied in the Baltic Sea.	Rejected: During the workshop, this was considered an oversimplification.
Group 1	'Suggested EOD method' should link back to the desktop study with historical and physical data.	Rejected: This factor was deleted as RUMMs cannot determine the 'Suggested EOD method' automatically. Instead, this is a matter of interpretation, based on RUMMs' outputs.
Part 3: Work session outcomes (Group 2 - PM, AB, FS)		
Group 2	The consequences of an event are related to the insurance of the risk receptor.	Rejected: RUMMs is meant to determine the immediate consequences to the EOD personnel and equipment on location (see 4.2.2).
Group 2	Before the UXO type is determined, <i>UXO identification</i> should be shown as a first step, which would be a cross-link to phase I. This helps answer the question: How reliable is my identification?	Partially accepted: This is not part of the RA itself but needs to happen before populating the confirmed layout with data. The description of RUMMs in 5.7 mentions which process needs to be executed to obtain which piece of information.
TF	Does it make sense to introduce the concept of uncertainty? The higher the uncertainty, the higher the risk.	Rejected: Although the concept of uncertainty is relevant to RA, this is outside the scope of the dissertation. Instead, users of the EOD RA model are asked to enter values that lead to a conservative assessment (see multiple subsections of 5.7).
Group 2	The <i>Significant Wave Height</i> is not too important.	Rejected: The relevance of the individual factors was determined through voting (part 4 of the workshop, see Appendix 4).

Participant	Comment	Note
Group 2	The final endpoint value ‘Risk of an undesired detonation’ should be eliminated. For better transparency, the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> and <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> should be provided as endpoint values.	Accepted: Participants universally agreed that providing the two values is of greater interest to EOD decision-makers.
Part 3: Work session outcomes (Group 3 - SK, CA, IS)		
Group 3	One important question is whether munition has been dumped or used. From personal experience, most of the munition is without detonators. Fuse corrosion (e.g., when the fuse has fallen off) influences the detonation probability. Unfused objects are not very dangerous.	Partially accepted: Assessing the ratio of fused to unfused objects was out of scope. When no fuse is present or when it is fully corroded, the value 0 is entered for the <i>Fuse Corrosion State</i> , which means that the factor does not contribute to the calculated risk.
Group 3	There are numerous <i>Original Impact Sensitivity</i> values for TNT. Which one is the correct one? A range for this factor may be more appropriate than a value.	Rejected: Subsection 5.7.19 discusses the availability of values in detail. To avoid the use of a range, users are asked to enter the highest <i>Original Impact Sensitivity</i> to allow for a conservative assessment.
RP	Every time the UXO object drops by an atmosphere (i.e., The pressure increases by the amount of atmospheric pressure), the sensitivity doubles.	Rejected: This could not be confirmed in the literature.
Group 3	The greatest danger originates from the fuse, not the charge.	Partially accepted: The relevance of the individual factors was determined through voting (part 4 of the workshop, see Appendix 4).
Group 3	A factor ‘Construction Time’ could be a fuse-related factor: WWI fuses are less dangerous than WWII fuses (at least for chemical munition).	Rejected: There are too many different <i>Fuse Types</i> to implement this in a reliable way.
Group 3	‘UXO weight’ and ‘UXO size’ are related to the ‘EOD level of difficulty’, e.g., due to additional measures that must be taken for clearance or due to the number of charges required to perform <i>In situ destruction</i> .	Accepted: The model was changed accordingly.
Part 4: After the group work was discussed, polls were conducted		

Appendix 4: Poll Results of the 1st EOD RA Workshop

During the 1st EOD RA workshop, participants were presented with two types of polls (see Appendix 3). They were asked how each of the factors contributes to the model outputs (i.e., which of the four normalisation types to apply; see 5.9.4) and how strongly to weight each factor’s contribution (on a scale from 1 to 5; see 5.9.5) to the model outputs. Table A4 shows the results of these polls. It is subdivided into five parts, one for each model output. Note that at this point, during the development of RUMMs, the model featured five model outputs. Each line in the table presents one factor and the percentage of answers for each of the four normalisation types, as well as the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (s) of the poll for the weighting.

In Table A4, factor names in italics are identical to the names in the release version of RUMMs. Factor names that are not shown in italics were renamed or remodelled.

- ‘Current impact sensitivity (charge)’ became *Current Impact Sensitivity*. Its values were used for *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* instead.
- ‘Condition of the ignition chain’ became *Fuse Corrosion State*.
- ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’ became *Fuse Properties*.
- ‘Suggested EOD method’ was deleted. Its inputs were redirected to *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.
- ‘Charge size’ became *Charge Mass*. Its values were used for *Shock Factor* instead.
- ‘EOD level of difficulty’ became *Complexity of the EOD Operation*.
- ‘Momentary current speed’ became *Current Velocity*.
- ‘UXO size (longest dimension)’ became *UXO Longest Dimension*.
- ‘Risk of an undesired detonation’ was deleted.

Green numbers indicate that this value was accepted for the model. For the normalisation, this was done if at least 50% of votes favoured the same type. For the weighting, values were accepted if $s < 1.5$. Red values indicate that no expert consensus was reached. Such factors were revisited during the 2nd EOD RA workshops. If a line does not contain any values that are highlighted in green and red, this means either that the model output was deleted or that the connection between the two factors was not implemented in the release version of RUMMs. The poll results are documented in greater detail in the supplementary data [296].

TABLE A4: Poll results of the 1st EOD RA workshop

Factor	Normalisation Types (%)				Weighting	
	Linear	Exponential	Root	Incremental	\bar{x}	s
How does the factor contribute to the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> ?						
Current impact sensitivity (charge)	0	44	11	44	2.125	0.83
Condition of the ignition chain	11	22	56	11	4.875	0.35
Current impact sensitivity (detonator)	11	33	56	0	4.750	0.46
Suggested EOD method	11	11	33	44	2.750	1.39
How does the factor contribute to the <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> ?						
<i>Main Charge Type</i>	11	22	11	56	2.375	0.92
Charge size	44	33	22	0	3.500	1.85
<i>Water Depth</i>	33	0	33	33	3.125	1.64
How does the factor contribute to the ‘EOD level of difficulty’?						
<i>Burial State</i>	11	11	22	56	3.375	1.41
Momentary current speed	33	22	11	33	3.250	1.58
<i>Significant Wave Height</i>	38	25	0	38	2.500*	1.51
<i>Water Depth</i>	22	11	11	56	3.250	1.49
How does the factor contribute to the ‘Suggested EOD method’?						
Current impact sensitivity (charge)	50	13	13	25	2.750	1.28
Condition of the ignition chain	22	33	44	0	4.125	0.83
Current impact sensitivity (detonator)	22	44	33	0	4.000	1.07
<i>UXO Mass</i>	22	11	0	67	2.875	0.83
UXO size (longest dimension)	22	11	11	56	3.000	0.93
<i>Visual Range Under Water</i>	11	22	67	0	4.250	1.39
How does the factor contribute to the ‘Risk of an undesired detonation’?						
<i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>	67	0	33	0	4.000	1.41
<i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>	67	11	11	11	3.750	1.28

* The confidence interval from the result of the 2nd EOD RA workshops was smaller than the one from the results of the 1st EOD RA workshop. Therefore, this value was implemented in the release version of RUMMs despite $s \geq 1.5$.

Appendix 5: Version 2 of the EOD RA Model

FIGURE A3: Version 2 of the EOD RA model (planning layout).

FIGURE A4: Version 2 of the EOD RA model (confirmed layout).

Appendix 6: Minutes of the 2nd EOD Risk Workshops - Group A

Date: 21.10.2021

Time: 09:00-12:00

Place: Online Meeting via Cisco WebEx

Moderator: Torsten Frey (GEOMAR)

Minutes: Svenja Ehlers (GEOMAR)

TABLE A5: Workshop 2a participants

Name	Abbreviation	Institution
Alexander Bach	AB	MELUND
Christian Andersen	CA	Ingenieurgesellschaft Geibelhöfe
Paul Müller	PM	Fraunhofer ICT

The 2nd EOD RA workshop (group A) was conducted on October 21, 2021. It was attended by three experts (see Table A5). Before the workshop, version 2 of both layouts of the EOD RA model were distributed to the experts (see Appendix 5). The workshop was opened by an introductory presentation by the author (part 1). Subsequently, each of the factors that were up for discussion was debated by the participants. Arguments on how to handle them for normalisation (part 2) and weighting (part 3) were exchanged. Minutes of the workshop are shown in Table A6. Each comment is provided with a note by the author. When a comment was accepted, the note explains how the model was adapted. When rejected, the note argues why. Factor names in italics are identical to the names in the release version of RUMMs. Factor names in single quotation marks were renamed, remodelled, or do not appear in the release version. Next, experts were asked to vote on the normalisations and weightings of the discussed factors, in a similar fashion to 1st EOD RA workshop. The voting results of the workshop are shown in Appendix 8. Finally, the matters of LoUs and threshold values were explained to the experts and discussed afterwards (part 4, see 5.10).

TABLE A6: Workshop 2a comments

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 1: Comment after the introduction by TF		
AB	The Belgian DISARM project tries to measure the corrosion of different metals in the laboratory.	Partially accepted: The author followed this project. However, by the time the release version of RUMMs was completed, no results had been published.
Part 2: Normalisation types - General		
AB & CA	Calculating exponential or logarithmic increments makes the model too complicated.	Accepted: Only linear increments were implemented in RUMMs (see 5.9.4).
Part 2: Normalisation types - ‘Current impact sensitivity (charge)’ to <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
PM	Initial suggestion is exponential. The higher the ‘Current impact sensitivity (charge)’, the higher the effect on <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> . On the other hand, impact sensitivity levels are defined according to regulations.	Accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs first converts the <i>Current Impact Sensitivity</i> into the <i>Current Impact Sensitivity Classification</i> (see 5.7.19) which it then normalises in increments (see 5.9.4).
AB	If standardised levels are available, the normalisation type should be incremental, as this implementation in the model can then be justified by the regulations.	Accepted: See the previous note.
CA	Levels can be refined at a later stage if necessary.	Accepted: See the previous note.
TF	The number of increments should be adapted from the regulation.	Accepted: See the previous note.
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> to <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
CA	It is challenging to express this with a continuous curve. Tendency towards incremental function as equipment is used under specific working conditions in certain value ranges, e.g., certain <i>Current Velocity</i> LoUs for ROVs.	Accepted: An LoU value for <i>Current Velocity</i> was introduced (see 5.7.26).
TF	Values for <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> range from 1 to 10. Equipment will not be rated with regard to risk. Increments may be plausible.	Accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> via an incremental function (see 5.9.4).

Participant	Comment	Note
AB	Increments would make sense because equipment on site will not be changed when a situation becomes slightly more complex, but when conditions change more dramatically.	Accepted: See the previous note.
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Charge Mass</i> to <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
CA	Linear, because energy is released linearly to mass.	Rejected: See the notes below.
AB	There is military regulation for safety distances for ships at the surface (<i>Safety distance</i> = $20 * \sqrt{ChargeMass}$). There is also a more accurate way to calculate sound pressure at different distances.	Rejected: No safety distances are calculated in RUMMs. No sound pressure is calculated in RUMMs (see 5.7.21).
PM	Pressure waves are calculated by using $\sqrt[3]{n}$. It depends on <i>Charge Mass</i> and the distance of the vessel. The greater the <i>Charge Mass</i> , the higher the pressure and, thus, the higher the consequences.	Partially accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs first calculates a <i>Shock Factor</i> from the <i>Charge Mass</i> and other parameters (see 5.7.21) which it then normalises via a logarithmic function (see 5.9.4).
TF	Using a logarithmic function with $\sqrt[3]{n}$ means that <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> increases more strongly in the lower value range than in the higher value range.	Partially accepted: See the previous note.
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Water Depth</i> to <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
PM	The greater the distance, the lower the pressure and effects. Maximum pressure depends on <i>Charge Mass</i> and distance. Thus, a linear function with a negative slope is recommended.	Accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Water Depth</i> as an inverted linear function (see 5.9.4).
CA & PM	Water pressure changes with depth, but the formula refers to the distance at the same depth.	Rejected: This comment was later corrected. The pressure wave of the detonation only decreases minimally at a <i>Water Depth</i> of thousands of meters.
TF	In this case, the formula would be applicable to the AUV or diver near the object but not to the ship at the water surface.	Rejected: See the previous note.

Participant	Comment	Note
AB	Mines have different deployment depths for the formation of an ideal gas bubble. The deeper a blast, the smaller the effect at the surface. This is, of course, different for divers or AUVs. The safety distance formula for blasting of the German Bundeswehr applies only from 6 m <i>Water Depth</i> . For 0 m to 6 m, onshore distances are calculated.	Partially accepted: See note above. RUMMs is valid for a <i>Water Depth</i> from 2 m to 71 m. <i>Shock Factor</i> is always calculated for the shortest distance. No safety distances are calculated in RUMMs.
Part 2: Normalisation types - ‘Condition of the ignition chain (corrosion)’ to <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
CA	At the beginning, corrosion has a strong effect, but less so at later stages. A root function is suggested.	Rejected: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Fuse Corrosion State</i> as an inverted exponential function (see 5.9.4).
AB	There are cartridges where a bit of corrosion is less dangerous than later, when the firing chain is completely gone (a logarithmic function would be appropriate). The function depends on the fuse type (magnetic, mechanical, electrical, chemical, etc.). For a mechanical fuse, initial corrosion has more influence than later corrosion (a root function would be appropriate).	Partially accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Fuse Corrosion State</i> as an inverted exponential function (see 5.9.4).
AB	For certain ammunition, the fuse is only armed under certain conditions (e.g., pressures). If the fuse is not armed, corrosion almost does not matter.	Partially accepted: The factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> with the property ‘Fuse Armed’ (see 5.7.24) was introduced to account for this point. Nevertheless, RUMMs assesses the corrosion state of unarmed fuses.
AB	Increments are not recommended because experts may assess them very differently. Maybe categories of detonator systems can be developed with the help of the Explosive Ordnance Disposal Service.	Partially accepted: The factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> (see 5.7.24) was introduced due to this comment. It was, however, generated via a literature review. The factor <i>Fuse Corrosion State</i> is automatically calculated from the <i>Condition of Casing</i> .
CA	Some categorisation is possible, e.g., spring-loaded fuses.	Accepted: The factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> with the property ‘Fuse Armed’ (see 5.7.24) was introduced due to this comment.
AB	Military uses different categories from civilian EOD experts. Include them in the discussion.	Rejected: The factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> was generated via a literature review.

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 2: Normalisation types - ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’ to <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
CA & PM	All detonators are sensitive. It is more relevant whether one is present or not. Assessing ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’ will not improve the RA very much.	Accepted: The factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> (see 5.7.24) was introduced instead of ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’.
PM	In dump sites, the probability that UXO is not fused or primed is higher than in other areas (i.e., it is a yes-or-no decision). A detonator type list might be useful. Categories of detonators might be useful.	Partially accepted: RUMMs assesses the factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> (see 5.7.24) via a list of eight properties, each of which is implemented as a yes-or-no decision.
PM	Booster charge and detonator should be considered together because the ignition chain consists of both.	Rejected: The assessment of the booster is not included in the factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> (see 5.7.24). It is included in the factor <i>Charge Mass</i> (see 5.7.18). Other properties of the booster are not assessed.
CA	I would separate the assessment of the detonator from the booster. For some UXO a booster is present and the fuse is not.	Partially accepted: See the previous note.
CA	It is important to assess whether UXO was fired (i.e., used). It is safe if it was not fired.	Rejected: This type of assessment is the task of the technical supervisor for EOD (see 3.2.4).
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Significant Wave Height</i> to <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
AB	Equipment-dependant LoUs exist. <i>Significant Wave Height</i> is relevant when submerging and recovering equipment and UXO. It is less relevant during underwater work.	Partially accepted: An LoU for <i>Significant Wave Height</i> was introduced in RUMMs (see 5.7.28). However, to decrease model complexity, the factor is assessed independently of whether the process <i>recovery</i> is performed.
CA & PM	It is recommended to distinguish between planning and actually handling the UXO. During planning, <i>Significant Wave Height</i> is important for LoUs. During UXO handling, work becomes more difficult for divers as currents increase.	Partially accepted: RUMMs normalises <i>Significant Wave Height</i> in increments in the planning layout but linearly in the confirmed layout (see 5.9.4).
AB	During planning, it is important to choose the right equipment. The factor is irrelevant, except in shallow water, where waves have a greater impact.	Partially accepted: In RUMMs, the factor is a parent of the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> and not of the other model outputs (see 5.7.28). Nevertheless, it remains in the model.

Participant	Comment	Note
<i>Part 3: Weighting - Charge Mass to Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
AB	<i>Charge Mass</i> has a considerable influence on <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> , therefore rather strong weighting is required.	Accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Charge Mass</i> considerably stronger than <i>Water Depth</i> (see 5.9.5).
AB	For divers, it probably does not matter whether 2 kg or 200 kg detonate. For them, changes at the lower value spectrum of the <i>Charge Mass</i> are relevant.	Accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises the <i>Shock Factor</i> via a logarithmic function (see 5.9.4).
AB	Flora and fauna should be disregarded for the time being because this is much more complicated for a model.	Accepted: The personnel and equipment at the EOD site are the risk receptors of RUMMs (see 5.5).
<i>Part 3: Weighting - Water Depth to Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
CA	Relevant for a ship at the surface but irrelevant for an ROV or a diver. Therefore, medium weighting is suggested.	Rejected: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Water Depth</i> lower than any other factor (see 5.9.5). The factor is assessed independently of the used equipment to avoid adding model complexity and since ROVs and divers will be impacted differently depending on their position in the water.
AB	A weight of 3.125 (which was the result of the poll during the 1 st EOD RA workshop) is rather high. <i>Charge Mass</i> should be weighted higher than <i>Water Depth</i> .	Accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Charge Mass</i> considerably stronger than <i>Water Depth</i> (see 5.9.5).
<i>Part 3: Weighting - ‘Momentary current speed’ to Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
AB	The difficulty increases with the ‘Momentary Current Speed’. Hence, the factor always has a significant influence on <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> .	Partially accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Current Velocity</i> with 3.333, which is an unexceptional value when compared to other factors (see 5.9.5).
<i>Part 3: Weighting - Significant Wave Height to Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
AB	Must have a weak weighting since risk is already reduced by the LoU at a certain value.	Accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Significant Wave Height</i> with 2.500, which is the lowest weight for parents of the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> (see 5.9.5).

Participant	Comment	Note
<i>Part 4: LoU for Visual Range Under Water</i>		
AB	<i>UXO longest dimension</i> is relevant, because if one can see the whole object, EOD becomes easier.	Accepted: Based on this comment, the upper boundary of the value range of <i>Visual Range Under Water</i> was designed to depend on the <i>UXO longest dimension</i> instead of an LoU.

Appendix 7: Minutes of the 2nd EOD Risk Workshops - Group B

Date: 26.10.2021

Time: 09:00-12:00

Place: Online Meeting via Cisco WebEx

Moderator: Torsten Frey (GEOMAR)

Minutes: Svenja Ehlers (GEOMAR)

TABLE A7: Workshop 2b participants

Name	Abbreviation	Institution
Sonja Krawczyk	SK	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bau und Liegenschaften - Leitstelle für Kampfmittelräumung
Laura Wachter	LW	Bertrandt Ingenieurbüro Köln

The 2nd EOD RA workshop (group B) was conducted on October 26, 2021. It was attended by three experts (see Table A7). Before the workshop, version 2 of both layouts of the EOD RA model were distributed to the experts (see Appendix 5). All materials that were used during the workshop were identical to those that had been discussed during the workshop with group A. This ensured that the basis for discussion was identical for both groups. The workshop was opened by an introductory presentation by the author (part 1). Subsequently, each of the factors that were up for discussion was debated by the participants. Arguments on how to handle them for normalisation (part 2) and weighting (part 3) were exchanged. Minutes of the workshop are shown in Table A8. Each comment is provided with a note by the author. When a comment was accepted, the note explains how the model was adapted. When rejected, the note argues why. Factor names in italics are identical to the names in the release version of RUMMs. Factor names in single quotation marks were renamed, remodelled, or do not appear in the release version. Next, experts were asked to vote on the normalisations and weightings of the discussed factors, in a similar fashion to 1st EOD RA workshop. The voting results of the workshop are shown in Appendix 8. Finally, the matters of LoUs and threshold values were explained to the experts and discussed afterwards (part 4, see 5.10).

TABLE A8: Workshop 2b comments

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 1: Comment after the introduction by TF		
SK	Could factors on which experts cannot agree be left out? This way, the other factors will be weighted more heavily.	Rejected: Even though it is true that low-weighted factors impact the weight of other factors, factors were only deleted or changed when explicitly suggested by experts (e.g., ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’ was replaced by <i>Fuse Properties</i>) or when it was not reasonable to implement them in RUMMs (see 5.8).
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation to Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
SK & LW	An incremental function for the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> would make sense. It cannot be quantified continuously. While other factors are scientific quantities, <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> is more of a subjective assessment and depends on people’s experience.	Partially accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> in increments (see 5.9.4). When used as a model output, <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> is provided with the first decimal position to maintain greater nuance for the comparison of results.
LW	It would be nice to integrate the experience of the personnel into the model (e.g., the number of performed EOD operations).	Rejected: This was considered too complex for RUMMs.
TF	The model should assess the number of work steps needed. Each additional step increases <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> and, thus, the risk. It is risky to perform <i>underwater transfer</i> and <i>in situ destruction</i> because then the UXO object has to be handled twice. Each additional work step should be avoided.	Rejected: This was planned during model development but turned out to be too complex for RUMMs.
SK	It would be possible to categorise risk receptors for the model. After all, the environment, beachgoers, offshore wind, etc. are also important for the decision of handling.	Rejected: Even though this is correct, the personnel and equipment at the EOD site are the risk receptors of RUMMs (see 5.5). The model can be adapted to address other risk receptors in the future (see 6.5.1).

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Water Depth</i> to <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
SK	<i>Water Depth</i> does not matter if the risk receptor is under water.	Rejected: The factor is assessed independently of the used equipment to avoid adding model complexity, and since ROVs and divers will also be impacted differently depending on their position in the water.
LW	Depending on <i>Water Depth</i> gas bubbles develop differently. The deeper the detonation, the less it impacts objects at the water surface.	Accepted: Based on this discussion and the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs normalises <i>Water Depth</i> as an inverted linear function (see 5.9.4).
LW	The positioning of the ship is also relevant, which is influenced by <i>Water Depth</i> and geology.	Partially accepted: This notion is reflected by using <i>Water Depth</i> as a parent factor for the <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> . The horizontal offset is not considered in the calculation.
SK	The change in underwater pressure when lifting an object could trigger its explosion.	Rejected: Implementing this would have required calculating different values for the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> . This was considered too complex for RUMMs.
Part 2: Normalisation types - 'Current impact sensitivity (detonator)' to <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
LW	Use a decision tree (e.g., fault tree analysis) instead of 'Current impact sensitivity (detonator)'.	Partially accepted: RUMMs assesses the factor <i>Fuse Properties</i> (see 5.7.24) via a list of eight properties, each of which is implemented as a yes-or-no decision.
Part 2: Normalisation types - <i>Significant Wave Height</i> to <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>		
SK	<i>Significant Wave Height</i> restricts work when a threshold value is surpassed. Check for threshold values on worker safety, technical boundaries, and manoeuvrability during construction work in the literature.	Accepted: RUMMs' threshold values originate from a review of existing termination criteria (see, e.g., 3.4.4).
SK	One would generally not be surprised by the wave height. One plans with it and if the positioning of the ship is not possible due to wave height, the operation is not even started.	Accepted: The planning layout enables the user to perform RA a long time before the key processes are performed.

Participant	Comment	Note
Part 3: Weighting - <i>Water Depth</i> to <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i>		
LW	<i>Water Depth</i> is irrelevant for divers.	Accepted: Based on the poll results (see Appendix 8) RUMMs weights <i>Water Depth</i> lower than any other factor (see 5.9.5). Nevertheless, it must be mentioned that ROVs and divers will also be impacted differently, depending on their position in the water.
Part 4: Threshold value for <i>Charge Mass</i>		
SK	Existing reports on cleared UXO in the German Sea could be reviewed to understand which <i>UXO Types</i> are prevalent and, thus, what typical <i>Charge Mass</i> values are.	Partially accepted: The mentioned reports could not be used for this assessment. However, SeaTerra's EOD dataset was used to understand the distribution of objects and their properties and determine a threshold value (see 2.2.7 and 5.7.18).
LW	Outliers could be excluded from this dataset.	Accepted: This was done for the factor <i>UXO Mass</i> (see 5.7.4).

Appendix 8: Poll results of the 2nd EOD Risk Workshops - Both Groups

During the 2nd EOD RA workshops, participants were presented with two types of polls (see Appendices 6 and 7). They were asked how each of the factors for which no consensus was reached during the previous workshop contributes to the model outputs (i.e., which of the four normalisation types to apply, see 5.9.4). Experts could only vote for normalisation types that were still considered relevant after the 1st EOD RA workshop. Experts were also asked how strongly to weight each factor's contribution (on a scale from 1 to 5, see 5.9.5) to the model outputs, for which the standard deviation had been too large after the previous poll. Table A9 shows the results of these polls. It is subdivided into three parts, one for each model output. Each line in the table presents one factor and the percentage of answers for each of the offered normalisation types, as well as the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (s) of the weighting. The bottommost two lines contain factors that were not included in the previous workshop.

Factor names in italics are identical to the names in the release version of RUMMs. Factor names that are not shown in italics were renamed or remodelled.

- ‘Current impact sensitivity (charge)’ became *Current Impact Sensitivity*. Its values were used for *Current Impact Sensitivity Classification* instead.
- ‘Condition of the ignition chain (corrosion)’ became *Fuse Corrosion State*.
- ‘Current impact sensitivity (detonator)’ became *Fuse Properties*.
- ‘Momentary current speed’ became *Current Velocity*.
- ‘Sedimentation rate’ became *Sediment Accumulation Rate*. Its values were ignored since it is connected to *Complexity of the EOD Operation* via *Burial State*.
- Values of *Charge Mass* were used for *Shock Factor* instead.

Cells without numbers indicate that these normalisation types were not offered or that no question regarding weighting was asked, because this had already been clarified during the 1st EOD RA workshop. Green numbers indicate that this value was accepted for the model. For the normalisation, this was done if at least 50% of votes favoured the same type. For the weighting, values were accepted if $s < 1.5$. If a line does not contain any values that are highlighted in green and red, this means either that a poll result from the 1st EOD RA workshop was implemented instead or that the connection between the two factors was not implemented in the release version of RUMMs. The poll results are documented in greater detail in the supplementary data [297]. Note that the weights in the supplementary data differ from the information used throughout this dissertation. This is due to the correction of an error that was identified after the submission of this dissertation. The effects of this correction on the subsequent work presented here can be neglected.

TABLE A9: Poll results of the 2nd EOD RA workshops

Factor	Normalisation Types (%)				Weighting	
	Linear	Exponential	Root	Incremental	\bar{x}	s
How does the factor contribute to the <i>Probability of an Undesired Detonation</i> ?						
Current impact sensitivity (charge)		20		80		
<i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i>			0	100		
How does the factor contribute to the <i>Consequence of an Undesired Detonation</i> ?						
<i>Charge Mass</i>	20	20	60		3.667	0.55
<i>Water Depth</i>	40*		40	20	1.333	0.55
How does the factor contribute to the <i>Complexity of the EOD Operation</i> ?						
Condition of the ignition chain (corrosion)		60	40			
Current impact sensitivity (detonator)		50 [†]	50			
Momentary current speed	50 [‡]			50	3.333	1.00
<i>Significant Wave Height</i>	50			50 [§]	1.500	1.30
<i>Condition of Casing</i>	0	60	0	40	3.167	0.84
Sedimentation rate	60	40	0	0	2.333	1.30

* A linear normalisation was implemented because the incremental normalisation that was proposed featured linear increments. Hence, a linear function (types 1 and 4) was preferred by experts over a root function (type 3).

[†] Due to the tie, the preferred type (exponential) of the 1st EOD RA workshop was implemented.

[‡] Due to the tie, the author decided to implement a linear normalisation since the factor is measured continuously.

[§] Due to the tie, the author decided to implement an incremental normalisation since the factor is commonly expressed as a sea state, which is given in increments.

^{||} This value was ignored. See footnote in Table A4.

Appendix 9: Detailed Input and Output of the Sensitivity Analysis

To execute a sensitivity analysis of RUMMs, it was necessary to define base cases for the three selected scenarios (step 1), change the input variables (i) (step 2), calculate the sensitivity coefficient (SC) from the changes in the output variables (i), and determine the average SC of the three predefined scenarios (step 4). For more information on this process, see 6.1. Appendix 9 contains much background information on this matter.

Table A10 provides rationales for the base case values in the most likely scenario (step 1). It lists the names of the risk factors that act as i , the base case values and their units, and whether i was used for the sensitivity in the planning layout (plan), the confirmed layout (conf), or both.

All other tables in Appendix 9 present the results of the sensitivity analysis. The values shown here were rounded to the second decimal place. The change in base case values was always a decrease or increase by 50% (step 2). Table A11 documents the change in the output variables (o) and the SC for the most likely scenario of the planning layout (step 3). Next, Tables A12 and A13 show the same information for the low-risk and high-risk scenarios, respectively. Finally, Table A14 presents the outcome of averaging SC over all three scenarios (step 4). This is the same information that is shown in Figures 6.1 and 6.2 in the form of a table. Subsequently, Tables A15 to A18 show the corresponding information for the sensitivity analysis of the confirmed model. The detailed numerical results of the local sensitivity analysis are also disaggregated in the supplementary data [356].

TABLE A10: Rationales for base cases of the sensitivity analysis for the most likely scenario

Risk Factor	Base Case	Unit	Layout	Rationale for the Base Case
Burial State	50	%	Conf	Centre of value range
Charge Mass	10	kg	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 2.6)
Condition of Casing	2	-	Conf	Centre of value range
Current Velocity	0.05	m s ⁻¹	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 3.6)
Fuse Corrosion State	50	%	Conf	Centre of value range
Fuse Properties	4	-	Both	Centre of value range
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	10	N m	Both	Fallback value if <i>Charge Type</i> is unknown
Original Casing Thickness	10.0	mm	Plan	Best guess by the author [*]
Corrosion Rate - Buried	0.05	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	Centre of value range
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	0.42	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	Centre of value range
Relative Effectiveness	1.00	-	Both	Fallback value if <i>Charge Type</i> is unknown (non-maritime)
Sediment Accumulation Rate	0.2	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	A central value of the value range [†]
Significant Wave Height	0.2	m	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 3.7) [‡]
Time Sunk	74	years	Plan	Best guess by the author [§]
UXO Longest Dimension	950	mm	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 2.5)
UXO Mass	25	kg	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 2.2)
UXO Shortest Dimension	40	mm	Plan	Design decision by the author
Visual Range Under Water	0.8	m	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 3.12)
Water Depth	42.5	m	Both	In bin with highest count (see Figure 3.10)

^{*} As described in 5.7.14, no real-world data were available. A search in a UXO database [310] revealed that the value at the centre of the factor value range would be too large and that the value shown here is common for WWII UXO.

[†] The exact centre would be 0.0 mm a⁻¹, since the North Sea's value range is -50.0 mm a⁻¹ to 50.0 mm a⁻¹. As this would not lead to a burial of UXO, the value 0.0 mm a⁻¹ was selected. It is the lower value range boundary of SAR in the Baltic Sea. Thus, it was considered appropriate for the most likely scenario.

[‡] This value is the central value of the sea state measurements' bin with the highest count (sea state 1 with a range from 0.0 m to 0.3 m). Note that the real-world data describe the absolute wave height, while this factor is called *Significant Wave Height*. Since the value for the most likely scenario was derived from a bin with a value range, it is still considered appropriate and not overestimated.

[§] This corresponds to a *Year Sunk* assumption of 1949, the last year in which UXO dumping took place in the study area. It was necessary to set this value so a 50% change in the value took place during step 2 of the sensitivity analysis (see 6.1.1). The centre of the value range would have been 92 years, which would correspond to a *Year Sunk* assumption of 1931. No significant dumping was reported for that year.

^{||} Defining this value was necessary so object burial would be simulated under the selected SAR. The centre of the bin with the highest count would have been 150 mm.

TABLE A11: Sensitivity analysis for the most likely scenario of the planning layout

<i>i</i>			<i>o</i> (Decrease)			δo (%) (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>o</i> (Increase)			δo (%) (Increase)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)			
	Base Case	Unit	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All
Charge Mass	10	kg	5.74	3.55	4.32		-15.53		-4.58	-0.31		-0.09	5.74	4.47	4.32		6.26		1.85		0.13			0.04
Current Velocity	0.05	m s ⁻¹	5.74	4.21	4.31	0.00		-0.35	-0.11	0.00		-0.01	0.00	5.74	4.21	4.34	0.00		0.35	0.11	0.00		0.01	0.00
Fuse Properties	4	-	5.06	4.21	4.12	-11.82		-4.74	-6.19	-0.24		-0.09	-0.12	6.26	4.21	4.66	9.07		7.90	6.04	0.18		0.16	0.12
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	10	Nm	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
Original Casing Thickness	10.0	mm	4.10	4.21	3.50	-28.54		-19.11	-17.27	-0.57		-0.38	-0.35	5.12	4.21	3.95	-10.80		-8.69	-6.98	-0.22		-0.17	-0.14
Corrosion Rate - Buried	0.05	mm a ⁻¹	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	0.42	mm a ⁻¹	4.76	4.21	3.42	-17.12		-20.86	-13.20	-0.34		-0.42	-0.26	6.30	4.21	4.55	9.77		5.22	5.51	0.20		0.10	0.11
Relative Effectiveness	1.00	-	5.74	3.55	4.32		-15.53		-4.58	-0.31		-0.09	5.74	4.47	4.32		6.26		1.85		0.13			0.04
Sediment Accumulation Rate	0.2	mm a ⁻¹	5.74	4.21	4.14	0.00		-4.26	-1.29	0.00		-0.09	-0.03	5.74	4.21	4.51	0.00		4.26	1.29	0.00		0.09	0.03
Significant Wave Height	0.2	m	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
Time Sunk	74	years	4.76	4.21	3.24	-17.12		-25.13	-14.50	-0.34		-0.50	-0.29	6.30	4.21	4.73	9.77		9.48	6.80	0.20		0.19	0.14
UXO Longest Dimension	950	mm	5.74	4.21	4.16	0.00		-3.79	-1.15	0.00		-0.08	-0.02	5.74	4.21	4.40	0.00		1.90	0.57	0.00		0.04	0.01
UXO Mass	25	kg	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	5.74	4.21	4.32	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
UXO Shortest Dimension	40	mm	5.74	4.21	4.69	0.00		8.53	2.58	0.00		0.17	0.05	5.74	4.21	4.23	0.00		-2.13	-0.65	0.00		-0.04	-0.01
Visual Range Under Water	0.8	m	5.74	4.21	4.54	0.00		4.97	1.51	0.00		0.10	0.03	5.74	4.21	4.16	0.00		-3.82	-1.16	0.00		-0.08	-0.02
Water Depth	42.5	m	5.74	4.94	4.06	0.00	17.31	-6.16	3.24	0.00	0.35	-0.12	0.06	5.74	3.48	4.59	0.00	-17.31	6.16	-3.24	0.00	-0.35	0.12	-0.06

TABLE A12: Sensitivity analysis for the low risk scenario of the planning layout

<i>i</i>	Base Case	Unit	<i>o</i> (Decrease)			δo (%) (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>o</i> (Increase)				δo (%) (Increase)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)			
			<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All
Charge Mass	1	kg												2.50	1.00	1.72		0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Current Velocity	0.02	m s ⁻¹												2.50	1.00	1.73	0.00		0.35	0.12	0.00		0.01	0.00	
Fuse Properties	2	-												2.87	1.00	1.81	14.72		4.95	8.68	0.29		0.10	0.17	
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	50	Nm	3.57	1.00	2.17	42.76			26.16	29.10	0.86		0.52	0.58											
Original Casing Thickness	200.0	mm	2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00			0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00											
Corrosion Rate - Buried	0.02	mm a ⁻¹												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	0.02	mm a ⁻¹												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
Relative Effectiveness	0.50	-												2.50	1.00	1.72		0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sediment Accumulation Rate	0.1	mm a ⁻¹												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
Significant Wave Height	0.1	m												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
Time Sunk	74	years												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
UXO Longest Dimension	1000	mm												2.50	1.00	1.80	0.00		4.76	1.57	0.00		0.10	0.03	
UXO Mass	1	kg												2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
UXO Shortest Dimension	1000	mm	2.50	1.00	1.72	0.00			0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00											
Visual Range Under Water	2.0	m	2.69	1.00	2.06	7.59			19.74	10.14	0.15		0.39	0.20											
Water Depth	71.0	m	2.50	2.22	1.28	0.00	121.68	-25.77	14.81	0.00	2.43	-0.52	0.30												

TABLE A13: Sensitivity analysis for the high risk scenario of the planning layout

<i>i</i>			<i>o</i> (Decrease)			δo (%) (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>o</i> (Increase)			δo (%) (Increase)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)				
	Base Case	Unit	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	
Charge Mass	350	kg	8.46	8.83	8.87		-11.39		-4.16		-0.23		-0.08												
Current Velocity	1.50	m s ⁻¹	8.46	9.97	8.41	0.00		-5.13	-1.67	0.00		-0.10	-0.03												
Fuse Properties	8	-	7.50	9.97	8.05	-11.35		-9.24	-6.52	-0.23		-0.18	-0.13												
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	1	N m												8.46	9.97	8.87	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	
Original Casing Thickness	3.0	mm												7.90	9.97	8.64	-6.63		-2.54	-2.88	-0.13		-0.05	-0.06	
Corrosion Rate - Buried	0.10	mm a ⁻¹	7.47	9.97	8.27	-11.71		-6.78	-5.83	-0.23		-0.14	-0.12												
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	0.83	mm a ⁻¹	8.46	9.97	8.87	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00												
Relative Effectiveness	1.66	-	8.46	8.83	8.87		-11.39		-4.16		-0.23		-0.08												
Sediment Accumulation Rate	13.0	mm a ⁻¹	6.26	9.97	7.82	-26.00		-11.85	-11.91	-0.52		-0.24	-0.24												
Significant Wave Height	3.0	m	8.46	9.97	8.53	0.00		-3.85	-1.25	0.00		-0.08	-0.03												
Time Sunk	109	years	7.47	9.97	8.27	-11.71		-6.78	-5.83	-0.23		-0.14	-0.12												
UXO Longest Dimension	3000	mm	8.46	9.97	8.46	0.00		-4.62	-1.50	0.00		-0.09	-0.03												
UXO Mass	1300	kg	8.46	9.97	8.47	0.00		-4.43	-1.44	0.00		-0.09	-0.03												
UXO Shortest Dimension	50	mm												6.26	9.97	7.82	-26.00		-11.85	-11.91	-0.52		-0.24	-0.24	
Visual Range Under Water	0.1	m												8.46	9.97	8.81	0.00		-0.66	-0.21	0.00		-0.01	0.00	
Water Depth	2.0	m												8.46	9.93	8.87	0.00	-0.34	0.00	-0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	

TABLE A14: Sensitivity analysis over all scenarios of the planning layout

<i>i</i>	<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)			
	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All
Risk Factor								
Charge Mass		-0.27		-0.09		0.06		0.02
Current Velocity	0.00		-0.05	-0.02	0.00		0.01	0.00
Fuse Properties	-0.23		-0.14	-0.13	0.48		0.13	0.15
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	0.43		0.26	0.29	0.00		0.00	0.00
Original Casing Thickness	-0.29		-0.19	-0.17	-0.17		-0.11	-0.10
Corrosion Rate - Buried	-0.12		-0.07	-0.06	0.00		0.00	0.00
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	-0.17		-0.21	-0.13	0.10		0.05	0.06
Relative Effectiveness		-0.27		-0.09		0.06		0.02
Sediment Accumulation Rate	-0.26		-0.16	-0.13	0.00		0.04	0.01
Significant Wave Height	0.00		-0.04	-0.01	0.00		0.00	0.00
Time Sunk	-0.29		-0.32	-0.20	0.10		0.09	0.07
UXO Longest Dimension	0.00		-0.08	-0.03	0.00		0.07	0.02
UXO Mass	0.00		-0.04	-0.01	0.00		0.00	0.00
UXO Shortest Dimension	0.00		0.09	0.03	-0.26		-0.14	-0.13
Visual Range Under Water	0.08		0.25	0.12	0.00		-0.04	-0.01
Water Depth	0.00	1.39	-0.32	0.18	0.00	-0.18	0.06	-0.03

TABLE A15: Sensitivity analysis for the most likely scenario of the confirmed layout

<i>i</i>			<i>o</i> (Decrease)			δo (%) (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>o</i> (Increase)			δo (%) (Increase)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)			
	Base Case	Unit	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All
Burial State	50	%	5.51	4.21	4.12	0.00	-4.29	-1.31	0.00	-0.09	-0.03	5.51	4.21	4.58	0.00	6.43	1.97	0.00	0.13	0.04				
Charge Mass	10	kg	5.51	3.55	4.30		-15.53	-4.66		-0.31	-0.09	5.51	4.47	4.30		6.26	1.88		0.13	0.04				
Condition of Casing	2	-	5.51	4.21	4.40	0.00		2.41	0.74	0.00	0.05	0.01	5.51	4.21	4.13	0.00	-4.02	-1.23	0.00	-0.08	-0.02			
Current Velocity	0.05	ms ⁻¹	5.51	4.21	4.28	0.00		-0.35	-0.11	0.00	-0.01	0.00	5.51	4.21	4.31	0.00	0.35	0.11	0.00	0.01	0.00			
Fuse Corrosion State	50	%	6.14	4.21	4.49	11.37		4.42	5.83	0.23	0.09	0.12	4.84	4.21	3.98	-12.16	-7.37	-7.04	-0.24	-0.15	-0.14			
Fuse Properties	4	-	4.83	4.21	4.09	-12.31		-4.76	-6.30	-0.25	-0.10	-0.13	6.03	4.21	4.64	9.44	7.94	6.15	0.19	0.16	0.12			
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	10	Nm	5.51	4.21	4.30	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.51	4.21	4.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00			
Relative Effectiveness	1.00	-	5.51	3.55	4.30		-15.53	-4.66		-0.31	-0.09	5.51	4.47	4.30		6.26	1.88		0.13	0.04				
Significant Wave Height	0.2	m	5.51	4.21	4.28	0.00		-0.53	-0.16	0.00	-0.01	0.00	5.51	4.21	4.32	0.00	0.53	0.16	0.00	0.01	0.00			
UXO Longest Dimension	950	mm	5.51	4.21	4.14	0.00		-3.81	-1.17	0.00	-0.08	-0.02	5.51	4.21	4.38	0.00	1.91	0.58	0.00	0.04	0.01			
UXO Mass	25	kg	5.51	4.21	4.30	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.51	4.21	4.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00			
Visual Range Under Water	0.8	m	5.51	4.21	4.51	0.00		5.00	1.53	0.00	0.10	0.03	5.51	4.21	4.13	0.00	-3.84	-1.18	0.00	-0.08	-0.02			
Water Depth	42.5	m	5.51	4.94	4.03	0.00	17.31	-6.19	3.30	0.00	0.35	-0.12	0.07	5.51	3.48	4.57	0.00	-17.31	6.19	-3.30	0.00	-0.35	0.12	-0.07

TABLE A16: Sensitivity analysis for the low risk scenario of the confirmed layout

i			o (Decrease)				δo (%) (Decrease)				SC (Decrease)				o (Increase)				δo (%) (Increase)				SC (Increase)			
	Base Case	Unit	P	C	E		P	C	E	All	P	C	E	All	P	C	E		P	C	E	All	P	C	E	All
Burial State	1	%												2.50	1.00	1.74	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	
Charge Mass	1	kg												2.50	1.00	1.74		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00
Condition of Casing	4	-	3.57	1.00	2.61	42.76			49.69	36.90	0.86		0.99	0.74												
Current Velocity	0.02	m s^{-1}												2.50	1.00	1.75	0.00		0.35	0.12	0.00			0.01	0.00	
Fuse Corrosion State	100	%	3.58	1.00	2.50	43.04			43.64	35.03	0.86		0.87	0.70												
Fuse Properties	2	-												2.87	1.00	1.83	14.72		4.90	8.65	0.29			0.10	0.17	
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	50	Nm	3.57	1.00	2.19	42.76			25.86	28.99	0.86		0.52	0.58												
Relative Effectiveness	0.50	-												2.50	1.00	1.74		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00
Significant Wave Height	0.1	m												2.50	1.00	1.75	0.00		0.65	0.22	0.00			0.01	0.00	
UXO Longest Dimension	20	mm												2.50	1.00	1.74	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00			0.00	0.00	
UXO Mass	1	kg												2.50	1.00	1.74	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00			0.00	0.00	
Visual Range Under Water	2.0	m	2.69	1.00	2.08	7.59			19.51	10.10	0.15		0.39	0.20												
Water Depth	71.0	m	2.50	2.22	1.30	0.00	121.68	-25.47	14.75	0.00	2.43	-0.51	0.29													

TABLE A17: Sensitivity analysis for the high risk scenario of the confirmed layout

<i>i</i>			<i>o</i> (Decrease)			δo (%) (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>o</i> (Increase)			δo (%) (Increase)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)					
	Base Case	Unit	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All		
Burial State	100	%	9.38	9.86	8.34	0.00		-5.23	-1.64	0.00		-0.10	-0.03													
Charge Mass	350	kg	9.38	8.73	8.80			-11.51	-4.05			-0.23	-0.08													
Condition of Casing	2	-												9.38	9.86	8.63	0.00			-1.96	-0.62	0.00			-0.04	-0.01
Current Velocity	1.50	m s ⁻¹	9.38	9.86	8.35	0.00		-5.17	-1.62	0.00		-0.10	-0.03													
Fuse Corrosion State	2	%												9.29	9.86	8.80	-1.03			-0.01	-0.34	-0.02			0.00	-0.01
Fuse Properties	8	-	8.23	9.86	7.98	-12.25			-9.30	-7.02	-0.24		-0.19	-0.14												
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	1	N m												9.38	9.86	8.80	0.00			0.00	0.00	0.00			0.00	0.00
Relative Effectiveness	1.66	-	9.38	8.73	8.80			-11.51	-4.05			-0.23	-0.08													
Significant Wave Height	3.0	m	9.38	9.86	8.46	0.00			-3.88	-1.22	0.00		-0.08	-0.02												
UXO Longest Dimension	3000	mm	9.38	9.86	8.39	0.00			-4.65	-1.46	0.00		-0.09	-0.03												
UXO Mass	1300	kg	9.38	9.86	8.41	0.00			-4.46	-1.40	0.00		-0.09	-0.03												
Visual Range Under Water	0.1	m												9.38	9.86	8.74	0.00			-0.66	-0.21	0.00			-0.01	0.00
Water Depth	2.0	m												9.38	9.93	8.80	0.00	0.70	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.01	0.00		0.00	0.00

TABLE A18: Sensitivity analysis over all scenarios of the confirmed layout

<i>i</i>	<i>SC</i> (Decrease)				<i>SC</i> (Increase)			
	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All	<i>P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>	All
Risk Factor								
Burial State	0.00		-0.10	-0.03	0.00		0.06	0.02
Charge Mass		-0.27		-0.09		0.06		0.02
Condition of Casing	0.43		0.52	0.38	0.00		-0.06	-0.02
Current Velocity	0.00		-0.06	-0.02	0.00		0.01	0.00
Fuse Corrosion State	0.54		0.48	0.41	-0.13		-0.07	-0.07
Fuse Properties	-0.25		-0.14	-0.13	0.24		0.13	0.15
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	0.43		0.26	0.29	0.00		0.00	0.00
Relative Effectiveness		-0.27		-0.09		0.06		0.02
Significant Wave Height	0.00		-0.04	-0.01	0.00			
UXO Longest Dimension	0.00		-0.08	-0.03	0.00		0.02	0.01
UXO Mass	0.00		-0.04	-0.01	0.00		0.00	0.00
Visual Range Under Water	0.08		0.25	0.12	0.00		-0.04	-0.01
Water Depth	0.00	1.39	-0.32	0.18	0.00	-0.17	0.06	-0.03

Appendix 10: Detailed Input into the Monte Carlo Simulation

During the execution of the MCS, a uniform distribution set and a realistic distribution set were designed. The former explored the full potential of RUMMs by distributing input data over the full value range of each model input. The purpose of the latter was to get a more representative impression of the EOD scenarios that users will encounter more frequently in reality. This appendix presents the realistic distribution set in greater detail than what was described in 6.2.1. For the uniform distribution set, a more detailed description was deemed unnecessary since all model inputs were uniformly distributed throughout their value range.

Table A19 presents the complex situation for the realistic distribution set. In the first column, it lists the names of the model inputs in alphabetical order. Next, it indicates the selected distribution and provides a rationale for this selection. For five model inputs, the uniform distribution was considered the most realistic option. This was done when the existing literature indicates that, in reality, the full value range is populated and no data were available that suggested otherwise. For the other thirteen, a normal distribution, for which the PDF is distributed around a mean (\bar{x}), was selected. If real-world data were available, as was the case for several UXO factors and numerous environmental factors, these data were used to derive \bar{x} and produce a reasonably realistic normal distribution. For other factors for which no data analysis had been possible throughout this dissertation, \bar{x} was defined to be the central value of their value ranges in RUMMs. Accordingly, if available, Table A19 presents \bar{x} and the rationale for its definition. It furthermore presents a standard deviation (s), which was always defined in such a way that $\bar{x} \pm 3 * s$ would approximate the upper or lower end of the factor's value range, whichever is closer. Note that this set of distributions could produce unrealistic factor combinations, such as an object with a large *UXO Mass* but a small *UXO Longest Dimension*, since data for each risk factor were distributed individually.

The eighth column of Table A19 informs about the model layout, for which the respective model input was used during MCS. 'Plan' indicates the planning layout, and 'conf' the confirmed layout. For some model inputs that were available in the planning layout, it was possible to produce values from a uniform distribution of *Latitude* and *Longitude* of the EOD location in the study area. The last column states for which model inputs this is the case.

TABLE A19: Detailed input into the realistic distribution set of the MCS

Risk Factor	Distribution	Rationale for the Distribution	\bar{x}	Rationale for \bar{x}	s	Unit	Layout	Location
Burial State	Uniform	Literature indicates full value range	-	-	-	%	Conf	-
Charge Mass	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 2.6)	109	Mean of EOD dataset [107]	$36.\bar{3}$	kg	Both	No
Condition of Casing	Uniform	Literature indicates full value range	-	-	-	-	Conf	-
Corrosion Rate - Buried	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	0.05	Centre of value range (see Table 5.4)	$0.01\bar{6}$	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	Yes
Corrosion Rate - Unburied	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	0.42	Centre of value range (see Table 5.4)	0.138	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	Yes
Current Velocity	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 3.6)	0.21	Mean of modelled data [244, 245, 246]	0.07	ms ⁻¹	Both	Yes
Fuse Corrosion State	Uniform	Literature indicates full value range	-	-	-	-	Conf	-
Fuse Properties	Uniform	Literature indicates full value range	-	-	-	-	Both	-
Impact Sensitivity Base Value	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	10	Fallback value if <i>Charge Type</i> is unknown (see Table 5.8)	$3.\bar{3}$	N m	Both	No
Original Casing Thickness	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	10	Best guess by the author (see Table A10)	$3.\bar{3}$	mm	Plan	No

Model Input	Distribution	Rationale for the Distribution	\bar{x}	Rationale for \bar{x}	s	Unit	Layout	Location
Relative Effectiveness	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	1.00	Fallback value if <i>Charge Type</i> is unknown (non-maritime) (see Table 5.10)	$0.1\bar{6}$	-	Both	No
Sediment Accumulation Rate	Normal	Central values are more plausible than extreme ones	3.5	Central value in North Sea; in Baltic Sea value range (see 5.7.8)	$1.1\bar{6}$	mm a ⁻¹	Plan	Yes
UXO Longest Dimension	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 2.5)	898	Mean of EOD dataset [107]	$292.\bar{6}$	mm	Both	No
UXO Mass	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 2.2)	203	Mean of EOD dataset [107]	$67.\bar{6}$	kg	Both	No
Visual Range Under Water	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 3.12)	3.4	Mean of MUDAB data [255]	$1.1\bar{3}$	m	Both	Yes
Water Depth	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 3.10)	27	Mean of GEBCO data [257]	9	m	Both	Yes
Wind Speed	Normal	Suggested by real-world data (see Figure 3.9)	7.1	Mean of MUDAB data [255]	1.3	m s ⁻¹	Both	Yes
Year Sunk	Uniform	Literature indicates full value range	-	-	-	-	Plan	-

Bibliographic Information

Bibliographic Description:

Frey, Torsten. *A New Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded Underwater Military Munitions*. Dissertation. Leipzig University. Leipzig, 2024. XXII + 347 pp., 416 references, 39 tables, 49 figures, 10 appendices (incl. 19 add. tables, 4 add. figures). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14620239.

Presentation:

This study addresses the need for improved risk assessment (RA) during explosive ordnance disposal (EOD) at sea by highlighting the environmental and operational complexities of handling unexploded ordnance (UXO) in the marine environment. It discusses the increasing demand for offshore EOD due to the construction of offshore wind parks and initiatives proactively addressing UXO dump sites. Conducting EOD work professionally and diligently to prevent accidents and environmental contamination will, hence, continue to be of paramount importance. In an effort to understand the RA tools that are available to EOD experts, this work reviews ten RA methods and identifies a methodological gap, thereby revealing the need for a new EOD RA method. Consequently, it introduces a novel method named the Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded underwater Military Munitions (RUMMs). This model is based on a directed graph and considers properties and aspects of the UXO, the environment, and the EOD procedure. RUMMs, which can be used during early EOD planning states or immediately before UXO handling, calculates the probability of an undesired detonation, the consequence of an undesired detonation, and the complexity of the EOD operation. The model is extensively explored by means of local sensitivity analysis and Monte Carlo simulation to demonstrate its reliability. Subsequently, RUMMs is tested with twenty EOD operations, which yield plausible model outputs that are in line with expectations and real-world decisions. The model's consistent and reproducible results, unaffected by fatigue or time pressure, add a new layer of reliability to EOD decision-making.

Declaration of Academic Integrity

I hereby declare that I have composed this dissertation myself and without inadmissible outside help, in particular without the help of a doctoral consultant. I have used no other sources and aids than those stated. I have indicated all text passages that are incorporated, verbatim or in substance, from published or unpublished writings. I have indicated all data or information that is based on oral communication. All material or services provided by other persons are indicated as such. This dissertation or parts thereof have neither been submitted in Germany nor elsewhere for the purposes of obtaining a doctorate or any other degree.

Curriculum Vitae

Torsten Frey

Curriculum Vitae

+49 (431) 600 2599

✉ tfrey@geomar.de

in torsten-frey-39526072

id 0000-0003-0834-1718

® Torsten-Frey

Ⓞ tX68m4sAAAAJ

Education

- 2017–2024 **Doctor rerum politicarum**, *Leipzig University, Faculty of Economics and Management Science*
Thesis: A New Risk Assessment Model for Unexploded Underwater Military Munitions
- 2014–2015 **Master of Arts**, *Tel Aviv University, Porter School of Environmental Studies*
Final Project: Taxing Vehicles and Fuels: An Overview of Common Policies and Their Real-World Effects
- 2008–2012 **Bachelor of Arts**, *Hochschule Furtwangen University, Business School*
Thesis: Development of PE International's Country-specific Strategy Towards Lead Generation in China

Experience

Employment

- since 2019 **Scientific Researcher**, *GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, DeepSea Monitoring Group*
Researching Unexploded Ordnance in the Sea and Coordinating Research Projects
- Project: BorDEX (Development and construction of a mobile demonstrator for the thermal disposal of explosives from coastal dumped munitions)
 - Acquisition support (Volume: EUR 5,029,000)
 - Decision-making documentation
 - Investigation of operational conditions for a munitions treatment facility at sea
 - Work package lead and GEOMAR principal investigator
 - Project: ValidITy (Validation of Intelligent Terrain and Feature Recognition Methods for Hydrographic Data)
 - Acquisition lead (Volume: EUR 500,000)
 - Project: CONMAR (CONcepts for conventional MARine Munition Remediation in the German North and Baltic Sea)
 - Acquisition support (GEOMAR Volume: EUR 3,194,000)
 - Development of a multi-criteria analysis for the prioritisation of munition piles
 - Support of the German immediate action programme for munitions in the sea
 - Work package lead
 - Project: ProBaNNt (Professional intelligent munitions assessment using 3D reconstructions and Bayesian Neural Networks)
 - Acquisition lead (Volume: EUR 1,600,000)
 - Development of a risk assessment model for explosive ordnance disposal
 - Conceptualisation and testing of chat-bot for expert-driven UXO identification
 - Project coordination
 - Project: BASTA (Boost Applied munition detection through Smart data inTegration and AI workflows)
 - Acquisition support (Volume: EUR 1,200,000)
 - Development of a UXO annotation workflow for MBES point clouds
 - Definition of data quality factors for UXO detection
 - Project administration

- Other Activities:
 - Participation in research cruises
 - Historical Research at the military archive in Freiburg
 - Presentations targeted at politicians and the general public
 - Organisation and execution of stakeholder events

2016–2020 **Scientific Researcher**, *Leipzig University, Chair for Environmental Engineering and Environmental Management*

Researching Unexploded Ordnance in the Sea and Teaching

- Project: RoBEMM (Robotic underwater salvage and disposal process including technology for dismantling ammunition in the sea)
 - Identification and description of quality management requirements for explosive ordnance disposal
 - Project administration
- Teaching
 - Corporate Environmental Management (Bachelor in Economics and Management Science)
 - Integration Module (Joint International Master's Programme in Sustainable Development)

2012–2014 **Technical Product Manager**, *thinkstep*, Leinfelden-Echterdingen

Corporate Sustainability Software Support and Development Coordination

- Product Owner
 - Set up of two software development teams (virtual software infrastructure and business service integration)
- Technical Customer Support Specialist
 - Technical support for users of GaBi software
 - Monitoring and analysis of customer support performance indicators
 - Restructuring of customer support processes

Self-Employed

since 2024 **Juror for Ideas Contest**, *armasuisse*

- Ideas competition for the clearance of unexploded ordnance from Swiss lakes

2019–2020 **Report Editor**, *Ministry for Energy Transition, Agriculture, Environment, Nature and Digitalization of Schleswig-Holstein*

- Coordination and editing of the HELCOM report on 'Warfare Materials in the Baltic'

2014–2015 **Software Tester**, *thinkstep*

- Structured testing of corporate sustainability software in SCRUM team

Expert Groups

since 2022 **Member**, *DGG*, Working Group Explosive Ordnance Disposal

2021–2022 **Invited Expert**, *Federal Agency for Nature Conservation*, Working Group for legal and technical nature conservation requirements for the clearance and disposal of munitions in the North Sea and Baltic Sea

since 2019 **Permanent Guest**, *HELCOM EG SUBMERGED*

2019-2021 **Active Member**, *NATO STO*, AVT 330: Impact of munitions and explosives of concern (MEC) on maritime safety, security and sustainable remediation

since 2017 **Active Member**, *ITVA Technical Committee C7 'Explosive Ordnance Disposal'*

2017-2018 **Active Member**, *NATO STO*, ET 180: Sea Dumped Munitions and Environmental Risk

Honorary Activity

since 2023 **Treasurer**, *greenXchange e.V.*

- Organising exchange programs for young leaders in sustainability from Israel and Germany
- Founding member (since 2020)

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Chapters

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